

University of the West of Scotland

Examining the influence of brand positioning on brand attachment and brand performance: A study of consumers' perception in the context of a hospitality setting in Nigeria

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**A thesis submitted in fulfilment of the requirement for the degree
of Doctor of Business Administration**

UWS 202

DEDICATION

This doctoral research is dedicated to my aunt, Grandma Adedapo, who wholesomely occupies the grandmother role in my life; to my cousin, Dr Adedapo, and the entire Adedapo family. I also dedicate this work to my parents, Mr and Mrs Olutimehin, and all my siblings. This work has become a reality because of your unfailing support and encouragement. Words fail me to express how much I love all of you.

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AUTHOR'S DECLARATION

I, Modupe Olutimehin, hereby declare that the arguments, findings, analyses, conclusions, recommendations, and indeed, all the ideas expressed in this entire doctoral research work entitled: "Examining the Influence of Brand Positioning on Brand Attachment and Brand Performance: A study of consumer's perception in the context of a hospitality setting in Nigeria" are exclusively the results and representation of my efforts and hard work. Therefore, except where otherwise stated, this work is entirely my own. I also firmly declare that this thesis does not include any material(s) that has been previously submitted, in part or as a whole, for the award of any other academic credential.

ABSTRACT

The study was focused on extending the current knowledge of brand positioning within the discipline of marketing by generating a comprehensive conceptual framework of its influence on brand attachment and brand performance. By investigating the conceptual framework, this study challenges the claims that brand positioning, as the consumers' perception of a brand, results in brand attachment and brand performance (Iyer et al., 2019; Koch & Gyrd-Jones, 2019; Hu & Trivedi, 2020).

This research adopted a mixed-methods approach - a broadly quantitative method backed by insights from an exploratory stage that incorporates interviews. The conceptual framework that guided the process of this research was created based on existing literature and the outcome of qualitative analysis.

Based on the statistical outcome and the qualitative study (the related literature, in-depth interviews), the present study showed that there is a favourable relationship between brand positioning, brand local iconness, and brand authenticity. In other words, authenticity and local iconness are favourable antecedents of brand positioning. The research further discovered that besides from brand trust, events, and customer online engagement, the other brand success multipliers tested (online review, brand relationship, and CSR) have a significantly favourable relationship with brand positioning. Nevertheless, online engagement and event (other brand success multipliers) were not significantly favourable as antecedents of brand positioning.

In addition, the relationship between brand positioning and the consequences was examined; the hypotheses testing outcomes indicate that brand attachments (specifically cognitive and conative), as well as brand performance (loyalty, attitude, equity, satisfaction, reputation), are consequences of brand positioning. Furthermore, the moderating effect of brand identity, brand warmth, brand awareness, and brand competence on brand positioning towards performance and attachment were investigated.

Findings revealed that brand identity does not moderate a favourable relationship between authenticity and brand positioning; brand awareness moderates the relationship between positioning and attachment, and between brand performance and positioning; brand competence is not significantly moderating the relationship between attachment, brand competence, and positioning; brand warmth moderates a favourable relationship between brand positioning and brand attachment, and moderates a favourable relationship between brand positioning and brand performance.

This thesis posed a comprehensive study that operationalised and conceptualised the idea of brand positioning, as well as its antecedents, its consequences, and the moderators of those relationships. This research proved usefulness in the expansion of generally held knowledge by providing a theoretical contribution to the existing body of work in the form of a theory extension, theory testing and generalisation, the standard of conceptualisation, and measurement. In addition, this research provided a significant managerial contribution to advertising executives, decision-makers, and marketing chiefs about the entire relationship between a favorable brand positioning, its antecedents, and its main consequences, as well as a practical implication to marketing and business management practitioners.

This is because it is important for these individuals to be able to understand the antecedents of a favorable brand positioning in order to make informed decisions. It is important for managers and decision-makers to develop a comprehensive understanding of the concepts of brand positioning and its influence on brand attachment and brand performance. This would help them in developing marketing strategies that influence brand positioning. They need to understand the relevance of brand authenticity and brand local iconnes as key strategies to improving brand positioning in the competitive market. These strategies have a higher probability of enhancing a favorable brand attachment and brand performance. In conclusion, this study provided a deeper exploration of the concept of brand positioning, as well as its primary antecedents, consequences, and moderators, and developed framework that substantiate the findings to the body of knowledge.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

TITLE PAGE	I
DEDICATION	I
ACKNOWLEDGEMENT	II
AUTHOR’S DECLARATION	III
ABSTRACT	IV
TABLE OF CONTENTS	VI
LIST OF TABLES	XII
CHAPTER 3	XII
CHAPTER 4	XII
CHAPTER 6	XII
LIST OF FIGURES	XIV
CHAPTER 3	XIV
CHAPTER 5	XIV
CHAPTER 6	XIV
CHAPTER I: INTRODUCTION	1
1.1 INTRODUCTION	1
1.2 RESEARCH BACKGROUND	1
1.3 STATEMENT OF RESEARCH PROBLEM	3
1.4 RESEARCH OBJECTIVES AND RESEARCH QUESTIONS	4
1.5 RESEARCH DESIGN AND ANALYTICAL APPROACH	5
1.6 SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY	6
1.7 DEFINITIONS OF CONSTRUCTS AND CONCEPTS	7
1.8 ORGANISATION OF THE THESIS	10
CHAPTER II: LITERATURE REVIEW	11
2.1 INTRODUCTION	11
2.2 PARADIGMS IN BRAND POSITIONING AND POSITIONING STUDIES	11
2.2.1 Brand positioning and marketing management	12
2.2.2 Brand positioning and brand management	13
2.2.3 Brand positioning and strategic management	13
2.3 DEFINING THE BRAND POSITIONING CONCEPTS	14
2.4 DEFINING THE ANTECEDENTS OF BRAND POSITIONING	15
2.4.1 Defining brand alliance fit	17

2.4.1.1	Brand fit and product fit.....	18
2.4.2	Brand positioning success.....	19
2.4.2.1	Brand trust.....	19
2.4.2.2	Consumer online engagement.....	20
2.4.2.3	Online review.....	22
2.4.2.4	Brand relationship.....	23
2.4.2.5	CSR.....	25
2.4.2.6	Events.....	27
2.5	DEFINING THE CONSEQUENCES OF BRAND POSITIONING	29
2.5.1	Defining brand authenticity	30
2.5.2	Defining brand local iconness.....	31
2.5.3	Defining brand attachment.....	32
2.5.3.1	Elements of brand attachment.....	33
2.5.3.2	Cognitive.....	33
2.5.3.3	Affective	34
2.5.3.4	Conative	34
2.5.4	Defining brand performance	34
2.5.4.1	Loyalty	35
2.5.4.2	Attitude	36
2.5.4.3	Equity.....	37
2.5.4.4	Satisfaction.....	37
2.5.4.5	Reputation.....	39
2.6	DEFINING THE MODERATORS.....	40
2.6.1	Defining Brand Identity	40
2.6.2	Defining Brand Awareness	42
2.6.3	The definition of the competence and warmth of the brand	43
2.7	SUMMARY.....	45
CHAPTER III: CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK AND RESEARCH HYPOTHESES		45
3.1	INTRODUCTION	45
3.2	RESEARCH FRAMEWORK AND HYPOTHESES DEVELOPMENT	46
3.3	BRAND POSITIONING AND ITS INFLUENCES	47
3.3.1	Brand alliance fit and brand positioning.....	47
3.3.2	Customer online engagement, brand trust, online review, and brand positioning.....	48

3.3.3	CSR, brand relationship, events, and brand positioning.....	49
3.4	THE BRAND POSITIONING AND ITS CONSEQUENCES	51
3.4.1	Brand positioning, brand authenticity, and brand attachment	51
3.4.2	Brand positioning, brand local iconness, and brand attachment.....	51
3.4.3	Brand positioning and brand performance.....	53
3.4.4	Brand attachment and brand performance	54
3.5	MODERATORS	55
3.5.1	Brand identity, brand alliance fit and brand positioning.....	55
3.5.2	Brand identity, brand positioning success and brand positioning.....	57
3.5.3	Brand awareness, brand positioning and brand authenticity	58
3.5.4	Brand awareness, brand positioning and brand local iconness.....	59
3.5.5	Brand competence, brand authenticity and brand attachment	60
3.5.6	Brand competence, brand local iconness and brand attachment.....	61
3.5.7	Brand competence, brand positioning and brand performance	62
3.5.8	Brand warmth, brand authenticity and brand attachment	63
3.5.9	Brand warmth, brand local iconness and brand attachment	64
3.5.10	Brand warmth, brand positioning and brand performance	65
3.6	SUMMARY.....	65
CHAPTER IV: METHODOLOGY AND RESEARCH DESIGN.....		69
4.1	INTRODUCTION	69
4.2	SELECTION OF RESEARCH APPROACH.....	69
4.3	PHASE ONE - QUALITATIVE STUDY	70
4.3.1	Overview of the planning, management and data interpretation of the qualitative stage	70
4.3.2	Interview	71
4.4	PHASE TWO - RESEARCH INSTRUMENT AND SCALE.....	73
4.4.1	Validation of measurement scales	74
4.4.1.1	Quantitative assessment: pilot study.....	80
4.4.1.1.1	Pilot study	81
4.5	MAIN SURVEY.....	89
4.5.1	Sample size	89
4.6	QUESTIONNAIRE DESIGN	89
4.7	DATA ANALYSIS TECHNIQUES	90
4.7.1	Coefficient alpha with exploratory factor analysis (EFA).....	90

4.7.2	Structural equations modelling (SEM)	91
4.7.3	Assessing Model Fit.....	91
4.7.4	Average variance extracted (AVE) assessment	92
4.7.5	Nomological validity	92
4.7.6	Discriminant validity	93
4.8	ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS	93
4.9	SUMMARY.....	93
	CHAPTER V: QUALITATIVE FINDINGS.....	95
5.1	INTRODUCTION	95
5.2	RESULTS OF THE QUALITATIVE STUDY	95
5.3	BRAND POSITIONING.....	95
5.3.1	Antecedents to Brand positioning.....	96
5.3.1.1	Brand alliance fit.....	96
5.3.1.2	Branding positioning success.....	96
5.3.1.2.1	Consumer online engagement.....	97
5.3.1.2.2	Brand trust.....	98
5.3.1.2.3	Online review.....	99
5.3.1.2.4	Brand relationship.....	99
5.3.1.2.5	CSR.....	100
5.3.1.2.6	Events.....	100
5.3.2	Consequences of Brand positioning.....	102
5.3.2.1	Brand authenticity.....	102
5.3.2.2	Brand local iconness	104
5.3.2.3	Brand attachment	105
5.3.2.4	Brand performance.....	107
5.3.3	Moderators	108
5.3.3.1	Brand identity.....	109
5.3.3.2	Brand awareness	109
5.3.3.3	Brand warmth and brand competence.....	111
5.4	SUMMARY.....	112
	CHAPTER VI: DATA ANALYSIS.....	115
6.1	INTRODUCTION	115
6.2	MAIN SURVEYS	115
6.3	ASSESSMENT OF NORMALITY, OUTLIERS, LINEARITY, AND MULTI-	

COLLINEARITY	117
6.3.1 Testing the normality assumption.....	117
6.3.2 Linearity and multi-collinearity	118
6.3.3 Homoscedasticity/ homogeneity.....	121
6.4 NON-RESPONSE BIASNESS.....	123
6.5 EXPLORATORY FACTOR ANALYSIS (EFA)	125
6.6 STRUCTURAL EVALUATION OF THE MODEL.....	131
6.6.1 Measurement of the reliability (item level)	131
6.6.2 Measurement of reliability (construct level).....	131
6.6.3 Measurement of validity (convergent validity).....	146
6.6.4 Measurement of validity (discriminant validity)	149
6.6.5 Measurement of validity (nomological validity)	152
6.6.6 Structural model evaluation – hypothesis testing	152
6.7 SUMMARY.....	157
CHAPTER VII: DISCUSSION	160
7.1 INTRODUCTION	160
7.2 OVERVIEW OF THE STUDY	160
7.3 BRAND POSITIONING CONSTRUCT (FOCAL CONSTRUCT)	161
7.4 APPRAISAL OF THE BRAND POSITIONING SCALE	165
7.5 DISCUSSION OF THE HYPOTHESES TESTS	165
7.5.1 Antecedents of Brand Positioning	166
7.5.1.1 Brand Authenticity.....	167
7.5.1.2 Brand Local Iconness.....	168
7.5.1.3 Brand Success	168
7.5.1.4 Event	174
7.5.2 Brand attachment and brand performances: consequences of brand positioning	175
7.5.2.1 Brand Attachment	176
7.5.2.2 Brand Performance	177
7.6 Moderators of Brand Positioning.....	180
7.6.1 Brand identity (moderator of brand positioning).....	180
7.6.2 Brand awareness (moderators of brand positioning)	181
7.6.3 Brand competence (moderator of brand positioning)	183
7.6.4 Brand warmth (moderator of brand positioning).....	184
7.7 SUMMARY.....	185

CHAPTER VIII: CONCLUSION AND IMPLICATIONS	188
8.1 INTRODUCTION	188
8.2 CONTRIBUTION TO KNOWLEDGE.....	188
8.2.1 Theoretical contribution of the study.....	188
8.2.2 Extending the theory	189
8.2.3 Conceptualisation and measurement level.....	190
8.2.4 Theory testing and generalisation	192
8.2.5 Methodological contribution of the study.....	193
8.2.6 Managerial contribution of the study.....	194
8.3 RESEARCH LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE RESEARCH	200
8.3.1 Research limitations.....	200
8.3.2 The method of sampling/analysis	200
8.3.3 The measurement level	201
8.3.4 Future research avenues.....	201
8.4 SUMMARY.....	203
REFERENCES.....	204
APPENDICES	263
APPENDIX I: Interview Guide	263
APPENDIX II: The domain and items of construct in extant literature	274
APPENDIX III: Missing data examination at item level.....	318
APPENDIX IV: Normal probability Q-Q plot	327
APPENDIX V: TOTAL VARIANCE EXPLAINED.....	339
APPENDIX VI: Factor loadings.....	344
APPENDIX VII: Univariate variables.....	366
APPENDIX VIII: Multivariate normality	372

LIST OF TABLES

CHAPTER 3

Table 3.1: List of research hypotheses based on the research questions	67
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CHAPTER 4

Table 4.1: Details of in-depth interviews with consultants and managers	72
Table 4.2: The constructs and the number of initial items	73
Table 4.3: Measurement items of the theoretical constructs and the codes	74
Table 4.4: Demographic profile of consumers' pre-test sample (N=50)	79
Table 4.5: Reliability measures for each construct on the basis of the pilot study	80

CHAPTER 6

Table 6.1: Demographic Analysis	115
Table 6.2: Descriptive statistics and correlation matrix for the constructs	118
Table 6.3: Regression for observing VIF and tolerance effect	119
Table 6.4: Levene's test of homogeneity of variances	119
Table 6.5: Mann-Whitney U-test observing non-response biasness	121
Table 6.6: KMO and Bartlett's test	122
Table 6.7: Communalities shared by individual items	123
Table 6.8: The brand positioning construct	126
Table 6.9: The brand authenticity construct	126
Table 6.10: The local iconness construct	127
Table 6.11: The customer online engagement construct	127
Table 6.12: The brand trust construct	127
Table 6.13: The online reviews construct	128
Table 6.14: The brand relationship construct	128
Table 6.15: The CSR construct	128
Table 6.16: The event construct	128
Table 6.17: The cognitive construct	129
Table 6.18: The conative construct	129
Table 6.19: The loyalty construct	129
Table 6.20: The brand attitude construct	130
Table 6.21: The Brand equity construct	130
Table 6.22: The satisfaction construct	130
Table 6.23: The reputation construct	130

Table 6.24: The brand identity construct	131
Table 6.25: The brand awareness construct	131
Table 6.26: The brand warmth construct	131
Table 6.27: The brand competence construct	131
Table 6.28: Inter-construct correlation and AVE for basic model	133
Table 6.29: Constructs correlation matrix	135
Table 6.30: Goodness-of-fit indices of model modification	136
Table 6.31: Goodness-of-fit indices of model modification	137
Table 6.32: Results of hypothesis testing	140

LIST OF FIGURES

CHAPTER 3

Figure 3.1: The conceptual framework 48

CHAPTER 5

Figure 5.1: The conceptual framework 114

CHAPTER 6

Figure 6.1: The Multi variate normal “P-P plot” of the regression standardised residuals 117

Figure 6.2: Scree plot of all the dimensions 125

Figure 6.3: Validated structural model 138

Figure 6.4: Final model 143

CHAPTER I: INTRODUCTION

1.1 INTRODUCTION

Brand positioning is a way to generate positive emotional reactions in people every time they use a product or service that bears the name of the brand compared to competing brands (Pike et al., 2018). It is the process of positioning a brand in relation to rivals in consumers' minds (Pike, 2012). It is a strategic exercise aiming to identify a clear, unique, and valuable place a brand can occupy in the target market's mind.

To position a brand effectively, a company must first understand the needs and desires of its target customers, as well as the strengths and weaknesses of its own brand and those of its competitors (Iyer et al, 2020b). Based on this information, the company can develop a positioning strategy that differentiates its brand from others in the market and meets the needs of its target customers (Iyer et al. 2020a). This strategy might involve highlighting specific features or benefits of the brand or communicating a specific image or message that resonates with the target audience.

Effective brand positioning can allow an organisation to differentiate its products or offerings from those of its rivals and develop brand awareness and consumer loyalty (Pike & Mason, 2011). It can make it easier for the company to charge a premium price for its offerings and products, as consumers are more likely to view them as having greater value or quality.

1.2 RESEARCH BACKGROUND

Today, organisations compete in business sectors that are crowded and fragmented with offerings and products, making it difficult for even strong brands to create substantial differentiating advantages over their competitors (Fuchs & Diamantopoulos, 2010; Iyer, et al., 2019; Pike, et al., 2016). The importance of brand management, particularly the role of brand positioning in establishing a sustainable competitive advantage, has received attention from marketing scholars and has been researched from various disciplines, which may be justifiable in a variety of contexts and industries (Pike & Ryan, 2004; Tamrin & Noor, 2019; Malik & Sudhakar, 2014; O'Neill & Carlback, 2011; Singh & Pattanayak, 2014). According to scholars and practitioners, positioning is one of the most critical components of strategy, branding, and

marketing (Aaker, 1997; Fuchs & Diamantopoulos, 2010; Hooley & Greenley 2005; Hooley et al., 1998; Trout & Ries, 1986).

Jakubanecs & Supphellen (2010) pointed out that the increase and expansion in branding in recent times indicate that branding is one of the most critical issues in modern business processes. Most modern firms, both local and worldwide, have recognised the power of brands and branding, enhancing the recognisability and interest in brands. The yearly increase in the number of brands implies that branding is one of the most important differentiators between organisations and industries worldwide. Furthermore, a brand is regarded as an organisation's most important resource (Pike et al. 2014; Liu et al., 2018). A brand is perceived to be much more than just a feature of attraction in that it encompasses all designs, perceptions, and associations about a good or service that is generated in people's heads or minds; and positioning, when done correctly, is said to influence a company's long-term competitive and high-level performance, including benefits (Iyer et al., 2019). However, if done incorrectly, it might result in a corporate disaster (Haig, 2005; Ries & Trout, 1986).

Without a brand, companies would find it nearly impossible to connect with consumers and differentiate themselves from competitors (Moon & Sprott, 2016). Consumers could differentiate products and services through a brand and know the company in the marketplace (Carpenter et al. 1994; Iyer et al., 2019). People tend to consume from brands they are familiar with or connected to (Tamrin & Noor, 2019) since there are many goods and services that provide the same offers. Java et al. (2007) stated that a brand is an offering from a known source and most firms find it nearly impossible to develop a solid brand image. The brand name is a vital element that most customers attach to brand associations in their memory, making them recognise and respond to a brand they choose (Moon & Sprott, 2016).

According to Fuchs et al. (2010), the use of brands was initially limited to physical products. However, there has been a recent increase in service, brands incorporated and expanded in the service industry (Nguyen et al., 2016). Nonetheless, the service business lags far behind the product industry, as seen by a lack of sufficient study on service branding compared to product branding (Tamrin & Noor, 2019). Iyer et al. (2019) noted that despite the lack of literature on service brands, there is also potential for practical brand analysis in the service industry, which is the major crux of this thesis.

Branding among businesses in Nigeria are beginning to gain attention, but very few local manufacturers and service providers are aware of its substantial edge to competitiveness in Nigeria (Ogunlade, 2013). Branding serves as an important marketing strategy in Nigeria, but

it has not been given adequate attention by businesses. Abioro & Odunbai (2021) noted that branding is valuable for businesses in Nigeria as it creates effective clarity of quality and difference of a product among others. For instance, most local products in Nigeria like ‘Garri’ and locust bean are not packaged and branded but are valued in the market, however, consumers and customers pay higher prices for packaged and branded products. Ogundale (2013) noted that most producers and marketer of these products are not harnessing the benefit of branding because they do not know the salient effect on product marketing in Nigeria. However, studies on the impact of branding on the consumer perception of business using banks and international manufacturing companies as case studies, showed that branding influences the consumer perception of brands in Nigeria which harnesses their performance (Abioro & Odunlabi, 2021; Ojeleye, 2016; Ogunode et al., 2023).

In explaining the importance of brands and branding in the service industry, Rao et al. (2004) noted that brands play an essential role in attaining business goals for every organisation irrespective of what service or product has been offered. The business makes efforts to understand the market (Dev et al., 1995) and position a specific brand uniquely by employing a judicious mix of the most appropriate tools and communicating the message that resonates with target groups (Hu & Trivedi, 2020; Park et al., 1986). Many businesses struggle to provide enough meaningful calls to their customers, resulting in substantial losses due to the increasing standardisation of certain industries (automotive, consumer, packaging, electronics). Thus, it is perennially significant for the brand to make clear distinctions to directly compete for brands via unique features and characteristics relevant to target groups (Brown & Ragsdale, 2002; Hu & Trivedi, 2020).

1.3 STATEMENT OF RESEARCH PROBLEM

The significance of positioning is commonly evident in marketing research, particularly where the study centres around products and brand management (Hooley et al., 1998; Iyer et al., 2019; Koch & Gyrd-Jones, 2019). Business to consumer (B2C) markets are frequently driven by the number of sales made (Baumgarth & Binckebanck, 2011). Because of this, B2C markets have not placed a significant emphasis on branding components such as brand positioning (Dev et al., 1995). This is a cause for concern due to the fact that more recent research (see Iyer et al., 2019; Koch & Gyrd-Jones, 2019; Hu & Trivedi, 2020) supports the notion that brand management, and more specifically brand positioning, can assist in differentiating a company's contributions from those of its competitors. The majority of the market's positioning typologies have been inferred, with an emphasis on investigation-related research and promotional activities. This study requires an understanding of brand positioning as well as its relationship

to its forerunners and effects.

Given the role which brands play in differentiating products and services they make it easier for customers to easily identify with a firm's product or service. In addition, when customers attain better knowledge of the product, the resultant benefit becomes the likelihood of the product to stand out amongst others, thereby gaining more than expected market share (Singh et al. 2014; Iyer et al., 2019; Koch & Gyrd-Jones, 2019). This is one of the specific functions of brands. In the same vein, Singh et al. (2014) noted that the number of valuable benefits provided to industries (both product and service industries) due to branding is fundamental to the successful functioning of those industries. This implies that given the rate of competitiveness prevailing in the modern workplace, it will be challenging for a firm to attain its goal without a unique factor that distinguishes it from its competitors (Porter, 2008).

Brand positioning is likely to enhance long-term favourable brand performance (Iyer et al., 2019) and brand attachment (Proksch et al., 2015; Wu et al., 2017). Little is known about brand positioning, its dimensions, antecedent and consequences (Iyer et al., 2019). Therefore, the purpose of this study is to investigate brand positioning. Another objective is to investigate the causes that determine brand positioning favorability (antecedents) and the outcomes of the understudied construct of brand positioning favorability, with a focus on positive brand attachment and performance.

Nigeria is one of the most populous countries globally and one of the most frequently visited countries in Africa. This is because the nation is a business tourism hub and one of Sub-Saharan Africa's most advanced states (Adeola, 2016). The increase in rivalry among companies in the Nigerian hospitality industry has led to most companies employing different positioning strategies to outdo one another in their approaches to existence. It is known that there is an observed lack of requisite research on issues of brand positioning and brand performance in the hospitality industry in Nigeria (Okereafor et al., 2015). Overall, given the high competition rate in today's business world, effective brand positioning becomes imperative. To this effect, it is vital to study the hospitality brand's positioning from Nigeria consumers' perspective to develop a distinct positioning with a solid orientation (Hu et al., 2020).

This study will present the most rigorous and exhaustive examination to date of comprehending the different factors that compose brand positioning and influence brand performance and customer attachment to the brand.

1.4 RESEARCH OBJECTIVES AND RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The study examines the impact of brand positioning on brand attachment and performance. It

studies the positioning of a brand with four aims addressing the broad objectives of the study. The aims include: first, the examination of the concept and dimensions of brand positioning; Second, to determine the aspects most likely to significantly impact the brand's favourable positioning (antecedents of the favourable brand positioning). Thirdly, to build and assess a conceptual framework of the relationships between positive brand positioning, its antecedents, and outcomes. Lastly, to investigate the effect of positive brand positioning on a favourable brand attachment and brand performance.

Despite the potential importance of favourable brand positioning in eliciting emotional responses in consumers whenever they use a product or service bearing the brand's name, little empirical research has examined how the favourable brand positioning should be portrayed or chosen to achieve specific communication goals.

According to marketing literature, a systematic study of the impact of brand positioning on consumer attitude is scanty (Huang & Tsai, 2013; Iyer et al., 2019.) This research is therefore one of the first attempts at collecting empirical evidence to demonstrate that positive brand positioning influences a favourable brand attachment and performance. This study investigates consumers' perceptions and activities regarding brand positioning alongside other consumer-based elements that influence positioning. Based on the research objectives, this study will be guided by the following research questions:

Question 1: What are the factors that influence brand positioning?

Question 2: What is the main influence of brand positioning on brand attachment and performance?

Question 3: What is the main influence of brand attachment on brand performance?

1.5 RESEARCH DESIGN AND ANALYTICAL APPROACH

The most current research employs the two paradigms of idealism and positivism, which have gained prominence in marketing studies during the past few decades. This study employs a predominantly quantitative methodology, but is grounded in exploratory interview data (Churchill, 1979; Foroudi et al., 2021; Palmer, 2011) because this research area is relatively undeveloped (Van Riel et al., 2001; Van der Lans et al., 2009).

This study begins with the idealist paradigm and a qualitative methodology due to a lack of knowledge on 'favourable brand positioning' and its relationship to 'favourable brand attachment' and 'favourable brand performance' (Saunders et al., 2007). The next phase of this

study employs a positivist paradigm (i.e., a quantitative method) to analyse the proposed hypotheses and their causal links, as well as the validation of a scale.

To determine customers' perception of the impact of brand positioning on attachment and performance in Nigeria, the researcher distributed a seven-point Likert scale questionnaire that ranged from strongly disagree to strongly agree so as to generate an acceptable premise that is comparable to the basic percentage of feedback. (Gupta et al., 2011). This study examines customer perception of five hotels in the hospitality sector in Nigeria. The hospitality industry is quite broad. It includes hotels, entertainment, event planning/organization, and transportation.

Descriptive statistics were carried out for the entire sample utilising the social science statistical package (SPSS). Following the recommendation of Churchill (1979), coefficient alpha and a fundamental approach, exploratory factor analysis (EFA), were utilized in the early phases of this investigation to determine the scale's validity (Foroudi et al., 2021), hence reducing the number of indicators seen (Shiu et al., 2009).

Structural equation modelling (SEM) utilising Analysis of Moment Structure (AMOS) 16.0 was used to examine the causal relationship between constructs and evaluate the validity of the measurement model. The two-stage strategy of Anderson & Gerbing (1988) was utilized to take a two-step approach. First, a confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) was conducted to permit a rigorous study of construct unidimensionality; the assessment of each subset of items was internally consistent, and the constructs were verified using the model's measurement models (Gerbing & Anderson, 1988; Foroudi et al., 2021).

1.6 SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

In addition to extending prior studies in positioning-related research, the given empirical findings contribute to positioning, marketing, brand management, and brand literature research. This study contributes to the current knowledge of brand positioning development and potential outcomes. The primary contribution of this study is to fill a vacuum in the existing literature, namely, what elements promote favourable brand positioning? What are the primary effects of favourable brand positioning on brand attachment and performance? What is the primary effect of favourable brand attachment on brand performance?

The gaps in the literature are summarized as follows:

1. There is a lack of empirical research about the definition of brand positioning.
2. There is a dearth of studies on the relationship between brand positioning, its dimensions, antecedents, and consequences (Iyer et al., 2019).

3. There is a lack of explanatory theory and model constructing research in brand positioning.

This study examines the process underlying the relationships between brand positioning, brand attachment, and brand performance in Nigerian settings. This study contributes to the current body of knowledge by extending the conclusions of other research. Several scholars, for instance (Fuchs & Diamantopoulos, 2010; Han et al., 2019; Iyer et al., 2019; Akbari et al., 2021), have hypothesized that brand positioning is connected to brand attachment, loyalty, equity, and reputation, but have infrequently examined the relationship.

Theoretical contributions of the present study to existing knowledge provide fresh insights into brand positioning. This is the first empirical investigation into the effect of brand positioning on consumer evaluation. This research might also revive and redefine the brand positioning study discuss. It also emphasizes ethical branding and brand identity by developing and evaluating a scale that defines the scope of brand positioning's influence, examining the links between the constructs and validating the framework model with structural equation modelling (SEM) and the scale designed for brand positioning. In addition, this study investigates the operationalisation and dimensionality of the study's concepts from the standpoint of the consumer.

The theoretical contribution makes five academic contributions: extension of theory through empirical testing, construct measurement, conceptualisation evaluation, theory testing, and theory development. This study can thus also contribute to the marketing theory. Marketing experts have made significant advances in brand positioning research (Iyer et al., 2019).

The contribution is a more comprehensive understanding of branding strategy and marketing by investigating if the incorporation of brand positioning effects consumers' attachment and performance. This is one of the first studies to empirically support the researchers' (Iyer et al., 2019) premise that brand positioning effects brand attachment and brand performance.

1.7 DEFINITIONS OF CONSTRUCTS AND CONCEPTS

Brand Positioning is “an act of designing the company offering(s)” (Iyer et al.,2019) and image (Koch & Gyrd-Jones,2019) “to occupy a distinctive place in the mind of consumers relative to its main competitors” (Hu & Trivedi,2020).

Brand alliance fit refers to “the extent to which two product categories are well-matched and the partner brands' consistency” (Sarmaniotis et al.,2014; Wason & Charlton 2015) “to build a specific, identifiable, and desirable image in the mind of the consumer” (Zdravkovic et

al.,2010).

Product fit refers to “the extent to which consumers perceive the compatibility of the product categories of two brands” (Moon & Sprott,2016; Lee et al.,2018).

Brand fit can be defined as “the degree of compatibility or similarity that are perceived by consumers to exist between a social cause and brand” (Bigné et al.,2012; Singh et al., 2014).

Brand identity can be defined as a “unique set of brand associations and defining traits or central ideas of what a brand is or what it aspires to create or maintain” (Aaker,2012) and how it communicates this idea to different stakeholders (Buil et al.,2016).

Consumer online engagement can be referred to as “the level of customer's cognitive and affective commitment to an active relationship with a brand or with the organisation's offerings and activities initiated by either the customer or the organisation online” (Christina et al.,2020).

Online review can be defined as “any form of positive or negative statements made by the actual, former or potential consumer about a company, brand or product, which is available to a multitude of institutions and people through the Internet” (Chu & Kim, 2011; Sotiriadis & Van Zyl, 2013).

Brand trust is the consumer's confident beliefs to rely on a brand to deliver promised services or the ability to perform its stated functions (Lee et al., 2015; Molinillo et al.,2017; Sahin et al., 2011).

Brand relationship can be defined as some bond (physical, emotional, or financial) between a brand and person (Smit et al., 2007; Veloutsou & Moutinho, 2009; Xie & Heung, 2012) characterised by the unique history of interactions and anticipation of future occurrences (Xie, & Heung, 2012).

CSR describes how firms “manage the business processes to produce an overall positive contribution to sustainable economic development” (Harjoto & Jo, 2011), working with employees, their families, the local community, and society to improve their quality of life. (Jamali & Mirshak, 2007; Pomeroy & Dolnicar, 2009).

Events refer to circumstances in which companies have to deviate from traditional public relations, marketing and advertising efforts (Doyle et al., 2014) to promote the interests of the company and its brand by associating the company with specific activities (Leischnig et al., 2011; Shin & Perdue, 2018).

Brand awareness is the ability of a consumer to recognise or recall a brand (Kim et al.,2018;

Wang et al., 2016), that is, all descriptive and evaluative brand-related information that relates to the cognitive illustration of the brand (Foroudi, 2019).

Brand authenticity is referred to as the "subjective evaluation of genuineness" (Lude & Prüggl, 2018; Napoli et al., 2014) ascribed to a brand by customers.

Brand local iconness describes the extent to which a brand is perceived as a local player and a symbol or icon connected with the local country (Halkias et al., 2016; Sichtmann et al., 2019) or the use of local resources (Mohan et al., 2018).

Brand competence refers to "the ability of a brand to induce its intentions" (Andrei & Zait, 2014; Wu et al., 2017).

Brand warmth can be defined as the belief that a brand is about intentions: good or bad (Andrei & Zait, 2014; Wu et al., 2017; Fang, 2019).

Brand attachment is defined as "the strength of the bond connecting the brand with the self" (Park et al., 2010, p.2).

Affective can be defined as "a state of psychological or emotional bond with a brand" (Yuksel et al., 2010; Grisaffe, & Nguyen, 2011), "creating a fervent commitment to repurchase" (Grisaffe & Nguyen, 2011).

Cognitive refers to "ideas and thought evoked by persuasive messages and other forms of advertisements" (Sicilia & Ruiz, 2010), "forming evaluations, and making decisions to purchase" (Jamaluddin et al., 2013).

Conative refers to "a consumer's behavioural intention to continue repurchasing a brand or products within a certain period or in the future" (Ahn & Back, 2018).

Brand loyalty can be defined as a deeply held commitment (Kim et al., 2018) or "biased/partial response expressed overtime to rebuy or re-patronise a preferred service or product consistently in the future" (Foroudi, 2019).

Brand attitude can be described as a consumer's overall evaluation of a brand (Liu et al., 2012; Augusto, & Torres, 2018), this is the degree of like or dislike towards a brand by the consumer, or the degree of positivity or negativity the consumer has about a brand (Kaya & Marangoz, 2014).

Brand equity refers to the "differential effect that brand knowledge has on consumers and the response to brand marketing efforts" (Keller, 2016, Datta et al., 2017).

Brand reputation can be referred to as "an immediate picture of a brand based on the

aggregated images held over the years” (Foroudi, 2019) or “the perception of quality associated with the name of the brand” (Han et al., 2015).

Brand satisfaction is a delightful degree of post-consumption evaluation (Chen,2010; Oliver,1980; Song et al.,2019) and affective response to an overall product or service experience (Oliver,1980).

1.8 ORGANISATION OF THE THESIS

This section highlights on how the thesis is organised. This thesis is made up of eight (8) chapters structured as: Chapter 1, where we introduced the concepts of brand positioning, the research objectives, statement of the research problem and the contribution of the study. In chapter 2, various study perspectives on brand positioning were reviewed while chapter 3 presents the study’s conceptual framework, Research methodology and data analysis procedures utilised in the study were discussed in chapter 4. Chapter 5 and chapter 6 presents the qualitative and quantitative data analysis results respectively. In chapter 7, the findings were discussed in relation to existing studies and in support of or against the stipulated hypotheses. Chapter 8 elucidate the importance of the findings, together with the implications and the limitations of this scholarly quest. The chapter also contains recommendations for future studies, based primarily on the research findings.

CHAPTER II: LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 INTRODUCTION

According to brand positioning research, a favourable brand positioning has desirable organisational outcomes, such as increased profitability and a value proposition that is distinctive and meaningfully differentiated from other competitors in the same market (Malik & Sudhakar, 2014; Tamrin & Noor, 2019; Hu & Trivedi, 2020).

This chapter extensively examines available literature on the question posed by the study as presented in the introductory chapter of this thesis. Consequently, the chapter presents a critical analysis of literature based on marketing management, to showcase an understanding of the current state of the subject, and to establish that it supports the conceptual framework which includes the hypothesis, models, concepts, and theories of this research.

Section 2.2 provides a brief conceptual background on brand positioning studies, followed by a conceptualisation and operationalisation of brand positioning strategies and effectiveness. A definition of the brand positioning concept is detailed in Section 2.3. The definitions of brand positioning antecedents are provided in Section 2.4. The definition of the consequences of brand positioning is outlined in Section 2.5. In Section 2.6, a definition of the moderators of brand positioning is elucidated. Finally, a summary of this chapter is presented in Section 2.7.

2.2 PARADIGMS IN BRAND POSITIONING AND POSITIONING STUDIES

As a result of technology innovations and inventive ideas, globalization continues to dominate the corporate world, which has led to a rise in business competitiveness. This has stimulated the vigour and vital justification for business owners and managers to create highly effective strategies to stand out from the competition. One of these effective strategies is brand positioning (Fuchs & Diamantopoulos, 2010).

In today's over-communicated and product-saturated consumer world, a brand's success may be contingent on its positioning. Positioning is essentially how a consumer views a brand in relation to the ideals with which it is uniquely associated or "owns" (Ries & Trout, 1982; Marsden, 2002). For instance, in the opinion of many consumers, the association of "safety" with Volvo may reflect a de facto positioning, making Volvo more or less appealing. Thus, the commercial worth of positioning is defined by the degree to which imbuing trademarks with absolute and alluring values can influence sales and buy intent. In fact, the entire branding operation can be

considered as a positioning exercise designed to generate profit by connecting trademarks with persuasive consumer ideals (Marsden, 2002).

Positioning, according to Kotler (2003), portrays a company's brand in a manner that is deemed extremely desirable and differentiates it from the competition. Positioning the brand is necessary due to the ever-increasing influx of competitors in the market, particularly on the strength of innovations and creative thinking's tendency to gain market recognition.

According to Kapferer (1992), positioning is a two-step procedure that establishes the product category with which the brand should be compared and associated. These are essentially platforms for the distribution of products whose brand selection is determined elsewhere. Marketing battles are conducted in a harsh and cruel environment, a location with vast unexplored territory and numerous traps for the unwary. The conflicts occur in the mind (Fisher, 1999).

Positioning includes adopting a customer-centric strategy and understanding how customers perceive commodities in their class and value-specific characteristics that can be bundled under a construct (Fill, 1999; Sweeney & Soutar, 2001; Liu et al., 2018). Cronshaw et al. (1990) described positioning as the primary target market for the product. Three essential factors have contributed to evolution of the understanding of brand positioning as the foundation of brand identity and its linkages with brand attachment and performance: brand management, marketing management, and strategic management.

2.2.1 Brand positioning and marketing management

Over an extended period, brand positioning has been regarded as a crucial strategic tool for creating and enhancing uniqueness in increasingly competitive global marketplaces, where so many categories are saturated with apparently countless items offering comparable attributes (see, for example, Dev et al., 1995). Branding seeks to build and maintain a market position that gives the seller an advantage over their competitors (Keller, 2016). Thus, marketing is considered an investment in establishing a relationship between a brand and its customers (Aaker, 2012). Hence, brand positioning is at the core of marketing strategy, and the objective of all promotions should be to cultivate favourable brand associations (Tamrin & Noor, 2019).

The focus of an organisation's marketing efforts should be on strengthening the positioning recommendation regularly and methodically in order to establish a unique position in the eyes of customers (Blankson & Kalafatis, 2004). Rossiter & Percy (1997) describes a product brand's localisation as its place within its category. A focal point demands that the brand be positioned to convey the advantages of a particular product category. In contrast, a distinct

locale necessitates that the brand varies in certain respects. Positioning typologies have made use of a wide range of perspectives over time. These span from empirical data (Easingwood & Mahajan, 1989) to intangible assets (Blankson & Kalafatis, 2004). Positioning typologies can also be customer-driven (Diwan & Bodla, 2011) or managerial in nature (Keller, 2016).

2.2.2 Brand positioning and brand management

The brand-concept management approach (Park et al., 1986) was created to aid the selection, operation, and management of brand images. According to its developers, an investment in a long-lasting brand concept fosters a commitment that will deliver continued competitive advantages. From a management standpoint, positioning entails emphasizing and developing a brand's distinctive characteristics to attract stakeholders and consumers (Keller, 2016). This approach is very important for product branding and is grounded on cognitive thinking as a scientific field (Lane, 1999). It recognises the unique potential for creating a brand associated with customers based on their requirements and what they have learned about the brand (Urde & Koch, 2014). In addition, the framework would permit implementation modifications during the brand's lifecycle, if necessary. The empirical study reveals that the functionality and diagrammatic representations of a brand are major distinctions that influence buyer opinions (Bhat & Reddy, 1998).

The relationship between a brand's positioning and its identity is a crucial part of the study of brand management strategy (Urde & Koch, 2014; Koch & Gyrð-Jones, 2019). This viewpoint is based on the scientific philosophy of socioeconomics, a technique of social science that contradicts the positivism of natural science (Urde & Koch, 2014). Creating a precise position alternative based on the brand identity concept serves as the basis for branding as well as the entire communication and brand image enhancement procedure (Koch & Gyrð-Jones, 2019). Brand identity encompasses the visual identity, core concepts, values, and larger beliefs of a product, service, or corporation (Urde & Koch, 2014; Koch & Gyrð-Jones, 2019). In addition, brand identity should provide customers with a value proposition based on emotional, practical, and self-expression benefits (Aaker, 1997) and collaborative benefits to improve the relationship between consumers and brands (Lane, 1999).

2.2.3 Brand positioning and strategic management

In strategic management, significant positioning discussions began in the 1960s, when strategy emerged as a structured methodology (Urde & Koch, 2014). Positioning strategies are typically regarded as fundamental to marketing management (Koch & Gyrð-Jones, 2019), corporate management (Curtis et al., 2009), competitive management (Jalkala & Keranen, 2014; Porter,

1996), and brand management (Curtis et al., 2009; Jalkala & Keranen, 2014; Rauschnabel et al., 2016; Koch & Gyrd-Jones, 2019). The series of initiatives that promote a brand's medium- to long-term management is known as strategic brand management (Iyer et al., 2020). Many experts provide multiple representations of strategic brand management, most famously (Keller, 2014; Urde & Koch, 2014; Koch & Gyrd-Jones, 2019). However, they all acknowledge that it aims to enhance brand positioning in the short and long term.

Positioning strategies are aimed to outline the direction of a brand's marketing operations in order to establish strong brands or reach a desired position (Koch & Gyrd-Jones, 2019). In theory, companies may position their brands across a virtually infinite number of linkages (for example, an electronic gadget can be positioned upon its stylishness, shape, size etc.). Numerous researchers have categorized these relationships based on their alternate positioning criteria (e.g., Ahn & Back, 2018; Blankson & Kalafatis; Jewell & Saenger, 2014). The positioning is the basis of a brand positioning strategy.

Branding tactics based on processes are gaining popularity. According to Csaba & Bengtsson (2006), trademarks result from continuing dialectic interaction processes. Asmussen et al. (2013) highlight the process of brand democratisation, wherein multiple stakeholders exercise varying degrees of influence on crucial brand processes. Both approaches are characterised by a decentralisation of managerial authority and an emphasis on the dynamics and interaction processes that shape brands in unexpected and predetermined ways over time. There is emerging empirical evidence that dynamic brand development results from strategic management (Koch & Gyrd-Jones, 2019; Urde & Koch, 2014; Von et al., 2017). Even though the stable and transient ways brands are presented, they constantly evolve as a process model for positioning. Koch & Gyrd-Jones (2019) suggest that the study of a thorough conceptual and strategic analysis of positional dynamics would enhance the research area.

2.3 DEFINING THE BRAND POSITIONING CONCEPTS

Scholars in the field of marketing have frequently used the terms "brand positioning," "product positioning," and "positioning" interchangeably. On another hand, the phrase "brand positioning" is utilised throughout the entirety of this research due to the fact that its definition and application serve as the foundation of this investigation. It should not come as a surprise that the concept of brand positioning does not have a definition that is universally recognised because over the years, it has been included into a wide variety of academic fields, such as marketing, branding, and strategy (Urde & Koch, 2014). Creating a concept that is appealing to customers is traditionally part of the process of positioning a brand (Ries & Trout, 2001;

Hooley et al., 2008). This involves putting an emphasis on the specific traits that make a brand unique and making those qualities appealing to stakeholders who are not customers.

To have a complete understanding of how brands are now positioned in the market, it is necessary to investigate how customers view the brands based on the aspects or characteristics that influence their purchasing decisions (Mullins & Walker, 2010). Businesses need to give their brands relevance and significance by developing a "position" in the minds of their target customers in order to differentiate themselves from the other companies in their industry and produce value (Kapferer, 2012).

According to Kotler & Keller (2016), the terms "point of parity" (qualities that are shared by all competitors) and "points of difference" (characteristics that are unique to the brand) suggest what needs to be balanced in order to influence the attitudes of customers. This image-based perspective on positioning is especially important for brand positioning and product branding (Urde & Koch, 2014). A significant amount of research on brand positioning focuses on consumer psychology concerns and categorisation methodologies by examining brand position connections and assessments by consumers. Coca-Cola, Nokia, and Apple, to name a few, are not successful because of their factories or manufacturing processes; rather, they are successful because of the image that they have cultivated in the minds of their consumers (De Chernatony et al., 2011). A powerful brand is always based on client relationships with the brand (Keller, 2012).

Distinctive brand positioning has the colourful characteristic of setting itself apart from other brands in the same marketplace. The ultimate goal of a brand owner is to educate and convince consumers of the distinct features of their brand that make it superior to their competition, and so to gain a position of prominence among competing brands (Lamb et al., 2019). Brand positioning requires great foresight, using present brand performance as a yardstick. It must show a relative amount of ambition for future growth and improvement of the product. If a brand can position itself in a way that is resilient and strong, it will have a better chance of competing successfully against other brands and gaining customer recognition.

2.4 DEFINING THE ANTECEDENTS OF BRAND POSITIONING

Early research on brand positioning concentrated on brand identity as a component and actively communicated value proposition to target markets (Aaker, 1992). Brand positioning is intended to meet a number of elements that ultimately determine its market success or failure. Many researchers identified the the variables that affects brand positioning in various studies. The variables identified by the scholars would inform the antecedants that are discussed in this

section as represented in the table below;

Antecedents	Key References
Brand alliance fit	Ashton & Scott (2011); Tasci & DenizciGuillet (2011); Cornelis, (2010); Zdravkovic (2010).
Brand fit and product fit	Simonin & Ruth (1998); Washburn et al. (2000); Park et al (1996); Volckner & Sattler (2006); Moon & Sprott (2016)
Brand positioning success	Aaker & Keller (1990); Urde & Koch (2014)
Brand trust	Chaudhuri & Holbrook (2011); Hobbs & Chiagouris (2009); Lau & Lee (1999); Jin et al (2015); Lee et al. (2015); Molinillo et al. (2017); Sahin et al. (2011); Morgan & Hunt (1994); Mayer et al. (1995); Loureiro & Gonzalez (2008), Rose et al. (2016); Han et al. (2015).
Consumer online engagement	Libai et al (2010); Verhoef et al. (2010); Chu & Kim (2011); Labrecque et al. (2013); Harrigan et al. (2017); Hajili et al. 92017); Wong & Haque (2021).
Online review	Litvin et al. (2008); Filieri & Mcleay (2014); Srivastava & Sivaramakrishnan (2020); Sparks & Browning (2011); Benedicktus et al. (2010); Vermeulen & seegers (2009); Briggs et al. (2007); Liu et al. (2013); Xiang et al. (2015).
Brand relationship	Aaker (1996); Kwon et al (2020); Algesheimer et al. (2005); Illici & Webster (2011); Khamitov et al. (2019); Hudson et al. (2015); Xie et al. (2015); Fournier (1998); Ekinici et al. (2005); Kim et al. (2005).

CSR	Park et al. (2013); Part et al. (2017); Porter & Kramer (2006); Fu et al. (2014); Li et al. (2014); Akbari et al, (2020); Akbari et al. (2020); Al-Msallam (2015).
Events	Rowley & Williams (2008); Miller & Washington (2012); Shin et al. (2018); Gupta (2003); Sneath et al. (2005); Close et al. (2006); Getz & Pag (2016); Luonila (2016); Lu et al. (2018); Panyik et al. (2011); Getx & Page (2016); Higgins-Desbiolles (2018).

2.4.1 Defining brand alliance fit

While there are numerous definitions of the brand alliance, researchers believe that a brand alliance is a relationship between two or more brands to fulfill their strategic goals (Abratt & Motlana, 2002; Bouten et al., 2011). Norman (2017) reported that the term ‘brand alliance’ has been used to refer to cooperative brand activities along with a host of other terms, such as co-branding, co-marketing, cross-promotion, joint branding, and joint sales promotion. Brand alliance has shown to be an effective approach for a number of businesses; T.G.I Friday's and Holiday Inn (Boo & Mattila, 2002), Starwood and Starbucks, and Pizza Hut and Marriott are among the most successful collaborations (Guillet & Tasci, 2012). This type of co-branding is characterized as a homo-brand extension in which the participating brands are in the same product category (Guillet & Tasci, 2010) — that is, both brands are hospitality sector operators. In brand alliance research, ‘fit’ is sometimes used interchangeably with concepts like as ‘congruence’ and ‘similarity’. It refers to the perception that the participating products or brands complement one another (Simonin & Ruth, 1998.). Regardless of the terminology employed, research indicates that fit, namely brand fit, is a crucial component of brand alliances (Simonin & Ruth, 1998; Suh & Park, 2009). This technique permits a brand to innovate with the assistance of a partner brand.

Levin et al. (1996) uncovered that adding a notable ingredient brand improves the assessment of consumer products of unfamiliar as well as famous host brands over the inclusion of an unfamiliar brand. Consequently, consumer appreciation of the partner brands has an explicit favourable impact. Voss & Tansuhaj (1999) and Fang & Mishra (2002) lauded Levin et al

(2006)'s argument. Their research illustrates that customer assessment of a co-branded product is enhanced when an unfamiliar foreign brand partners with a famous domestic brand. Lin (2013) found that a co-branding strategy is a practical approach for local hotel brands to enhance their market presence globally and for foreign hotel brands to increase awareness in the local marketplace. Significantly, the poor perception of brand fit has devastating effects on consumer purchase intent (Ashton & Scott, 2011).

According to Ashton & Scott (2011), the perception of brand fit has a significant impact on customer loyalty in a co-branded tourism setting. Therefore, it would be worthwhile to empirically evaluate the influence of brand alliance fit on consumer perception in the hospitality sector. Moreover, even if respondents are familiar with the co-brand's unique brand, a poor fit between the associated brands is likely to result in an unfavourable perception of the co-brand. (Tasci & DenizciGuillet, 2011). With such a poor image of brand fit, the positioning of the brand alliance could be adversely affected (Cornelis, 2010). In conclusion, based on the aforementioned literature. The idea of brand alliance can be summed up as the degree to which two different product categories are suitable for one another or are complementary to one another (Sarmaniotis et al., 2014; Wason & Charlton 2015) and the partner brands' consistency to build a specific, identifiable, and desirable image in the mind of the consumer (Zdravkovic, 2010).

2.4.1.1 Brand fit and product fit

When two companies come together to form a strategic alliance, there are several potential reasons why the alliance is a good fit, including product consumption, culture, brand connection, category fit, and customer ambitions (Martin & Stewart, 2001). According to the findings of numerous studies, "product fit" and "brand fit" are extremely important. Product fit, which can be described as the degree to which customers see two different product categories as being complementary to one another and a good match, has been demonstrated to have a stronger favorable link with customer impression of the co-branded product (Simonin & Ruth, 1998; Washburn et al., 2000).

According to Simonin & Ruth (1998), brand and product fit are two additional factors of customer feelings about co-branding and pre-existing consumer attitudes toward the brands. These feelings and attitudes can be affected by previous consumer experiences with the brands. Product value is the consumer's impression of the value of the product, while brand fit evaluations are based on quality. Product fit is the consumer's perspective of the fit between the two product categories, and it is often evaluated at a functional level (i.e., analyzing the

compatibility of each product's utility) (i.e., comparing the level of quality for each brand). The concept of "brand fit" refers to the consumer's perception of consistent brand associations across all of the marketing alliance's brands (Park et al., 1996; Simonin & Ruth, 1998).

According to the findings of a meta-analysis conducted by Volckner & Sattler (2006), the component that has the greatest impact on the success of a brand expansion is fit. Another important finding is that the launch of eight out of ten new goods is unsuccessful. Fit can be understood in one of two ways, both of which focus on analyzing the similarities between two brands (such as the parent brand and an extension of the parent brand): Product fit refers to the extent to which consumers see the product categories of two different brands as being compatible with one another (e.g., the parent brand and its extension). Brand fit, on the other hand, is a consumer's perception of the degree to which different brands are consistent with one another (Moon & Sprott, 2016). For instance, a strategic partnership between Chipotle and Tag Heuer would be viewed as having a poor brand fit because Tag Heuer is linked with more expensive products and upscale taste. Contrarily, Chipotle is well recognised for its wide variety of inexpensive meal options and served in a hurry (Lafferty et al., 2004).

2.4.2 Brand positioning success

Essentially, brand positioning statements explain how key stakeholders view the brand's position and present a story that benefits the brand (Aaker & Keller, 1990; Urde & Koch, 2014). The ultimate and most important purpose of branding or brand positioning is to entice consumers to make purchases. To effectively realize the potential and hidden benefits of branding, it is necessary to investigate the distinctiveness of branding by focusing on aspects that facilitate the concept's implementation. In other words, some factors contribute to the success of brand positioning inside a certain market niche. Regarding previous research, the major components mentioned in this thesis as multipliers of brand positioning success are online consumer engagement, brand trust, online review, brand connection, corporate social responsibility, and events. These factors are derivatives of several scholarly works, including Harrigan et al. (2018) consumer engagement, Rose et al. (2016) and Han et al. (2015) brand trust, Cassidy et al. (2018) brand relationship, Karaosmanoglu et al. (2016) and Patricia et al. (2014) corporate social responsibility (CSR), and Yang & Tan (2017) events.

2.4.2.1 Brand trust

The most important function of marketing is to forge a solid connection between the customer and the product or service being offered, and trust serves as the foundation for this type of relationship (Chaudhuri & Holbrook, 2001; Hobbs & Goddard, 2015). The importance of trust

in branding has expanded since the late 1980s, owing mostly to the emergence of relationship marketing (Lantieri & Chiagouris, 2009). This component of brand trust is compatible with authentic brands, which demonstrate their intentions by presenting constructive ideas and the capacity to deliver on the brand promise they make (Morhart et al., 2015).

It is of ideal relevance to underline the importance of brand trust in creating consumer loyalty. When Lau & Lee (1999) looked at the correlation between brand loyalty and customer trust in a brand, they found a statistically significant positive relationship between these two constructs. In addition, Jin et al. (2015) research discovered a high association between trust in a brand and both obedient behavior and positive attitudes toward the brand. Empirical data suggests that travelers' trust has a favorable effect on their loyalty to rural lodging, according to research conducted by Loureiro & Gonzalez (2008), who published their findings in the tourist literature. In addition, Loureiro & Gonzalez (2008) argued that the possibility of customers suggesting a firm's goods and services to others is quite high when customers have faith in the company that they are purchasing from.

On the other hand, management and marketing primarily correlate trust with the relationship's competence dimension, which focuses on the partner's confidence that they have the essential abilities to carry out their activities, fulfill their commitments, or keep their promises. This aspect of the relationship focuses on the partner's confidence that they have the essential abilities to carry out their activities, fulfill their commitments, or keep their promises (Morgan & Hunt 1994; Mayer et al. 1995). According to Jin et al. (2015), trust develops as a consequence of an individual's predisposition to trust, the confidence that institutions have in one another, and the cognitive processes of trusting intention and trusting beliefs. The propensity to rely on the assistance of other people is what we mean when we talk about having "trust disposition." The belief that one's chances of succeeding in a certain circumstance are increased by one's reliance on impersonal mechanisms is an example of institution-based trust. According to the aforementioned body of research, the term "brand trust" can be defined as the consumer's confident beliefs that they can rely on a brand to deliver promised services or the ability to perform its stated functions. In conclusion, this concept can be understood as "the consumer's confident beliefs to rely on a brand to deliver promised services or the ability (Lee et al., 2015; Molinillo et al., 2017; Sahin et al., 2011).

2.4.2.2 Consumer online engagement

Customer interaction has garnered attention in marketing for a decade, possibly due to the rise of social media and the recognition that customers may co-create and destroy value (e.g., Libai

et al. 2010; Verhoef et al., 2010). Thus, brands are realizing that simply being accessible to their prospective consumers when they conduct an internet search is insufficient. Continual engagement with consumers is crucial for influencing repurchase (Chu & Kim, 2011). Customers in the present day observe, participate, interact, and co-create with brands and other consumers (Chu & Kim, 2011; Labrecque et al., 2013).

In marketing literature, these online interactions are referred to as customer brand engagement. A group of engaged customers may become a company's brand ambassador (Augar & Zeleznikow, 2014). Van Doorn et al. (2010) defined customer engagement behaviours as "the customer's behavioural manifestations toward a brand or company, beyond purchase, deriving from motivational motivations". Examples include submitting a review or leaving a comment on a company's Facebook page, participating in a brand community, or recommending a product to another consumer (Beckers, 2018). Furthermore, they are regarded as more trustworthy than other forms of marketing messaging. While examining the motivation to engage in online brand-related activities, Muntinga et al. (2011) describe three levels of online participation, spanning from consumption through contribution to creation.

Likewise, Li & Bernoff (2008) deploy a social techno-graphics pyramid to explain how far down the interaction funnel people go, stressing the spectral character of online experience. People like a post by clicking the 'like' button, which is seen as a favourable validation of the content by the consumer. However, 'liking' is a static metric and a poor proxy for engagement because of the limited engagement (Cooper et al., 2019).

Harrigan et al. (2017) analysed customer participation with social media tourism brands such as Lonely Planet, Airbnb, and TripAdvisor. They observed that immersion with social media is an emotional aspect of involvement, describing a condition in which users feel contented and absorbed. Similarly, VanMeter et al. (2015) conceptualise and quantify social media user attachment. The importance of enjoyment to user attachment reflects the significance of social media in helping customers relax and enjoy themselves.

Exploring online activities can increase and widen businesses' understanding of brand positioning and consumer preferences (Brexendorf et al., 2015; Perera et al., 2020). YouTube, Twitter, WhatsApp, Instagram, and Facebook are among the most widely utilised social media platforms for brand development operations (Wong & Haque, 2021). Customers can interact and network on these social media platforms by creating and sharing brand content. Continuous involvement and activity on multiple social media platforms can create consumer-brand relationships, resulting in sentiments of brand trust, loyalty, and repurchase intent (Hajli et al.,

2017; Wong & Haque, 2021). Nonetheless, the substance of internet analysis is qualitative, making information processing and extracting meaningful insights difficult (Kozinets et al., 2010).

In summary, drawing on the literature above, online customer engagement can be referred to as the level of a customer's connection and interaction (Wongkitrungrueng & Assarut, 2018) with the organisation's offerings and activities initiated by either the customer or the organisation (Christina et al., 2020, Agnihotri, 2020).

2.4.2.3 Online review

The usage of online reviews by tourists from other countries to help them make better-informed decisions about the goods and services they purchase is experiencing a surge in popularity (Litvin et al., 2008; Filieri & McLeay, 2014, Srivastava & Sivaramakrishnan, 2020). The ways in which people choose where to go, what to see and do on vacation, where to dine, etc. have been fundamentally altered as a result of the proliferation of review websites such as TripAdvisor, Yelp, and Open Rice (Xie et al., 2014). In spite of the sophistication of the efforts put forth by marketers, purchasers will still rely on testimonials from previous clients (e.g., retargeting, programmatic advertising, customer journey mapping). According to findings from research carried out in 60 different nations, online reviews are one of the most dependable sources of information (Nielsen, 2015).

Findings from a study conducted by Al-Htibat & Garanti (2019) indicated that recommendations carry more weight than product features. People are often concerned about the quality of the hotels that are offered when making an online reservation for a hotel room (Agag & El-Masry 2016; Shin et al. 2018). Prior to making a booking decision, they look for product-related cues such as the brand, the price, and online reviews of similar products. Consumers are able to gather a substantial amount of brand-related information through the use of internet reviews as a significant social communication channel due to the fact that they represent the product experiences of previous customers (Benedicktus et al., 2010).

According to Prasad et al. (2019), traditional word-of-mouth has been largely superseded by electronic word-of-mouth (eWOM), which is also commonly referred to as online reviews. Consumers no longer look to brands as their primary source of information regarding goods and services. They rely, rather, on customer feedback that has been rated, discussed, or posted on a variety of websites (Al-Htibat & Garanti, 2019; Iyer et al., 2017). Review comments, in particular, correspond to "the manner in which customers describe, relive, reconstruct, and share their experience" (Xiang et al., 2015, p. 44), which is something that consumers consider

to be essential. As a consequence of this, it is possible that online reviews will be more diagnostic when review signals and brand names are available.

According to Benedicktus et al. (2010), consumers are influenced to some degree by the reviews they read online. When planning their vacations, more than seventy-four percent of travelers rely on the recommendations of previous customers (Gretzel & Yoo, 2008; Viglia et al., 2016). As a consequence of this, reviews are an incredible resource for prospective customers of the hospitality industry, and they have an effect on customer satisfaction and trust (Sparks & Browning, 2011), hotel brand awareness (Vermeulen & Seegers, 2009; Duan, Gu, & Whinston, 2008; Zhu & Zhang, 2010), reputation (Baka, 2016), attitudes (Casalo et al., 2015), hotel quality perceptions (Viglia et al., 2016).

Scholars in the field of tourism and hospitality have scrutinized travel-based reviews offering illustrations of the impact it has on the awareness of consumers and their disposition towards hotels (Vermeulen & Seegers, 2009), their intent to purchase the product (Filiari & McLeay, 2014; Sparks & Browning, 2011; Vermulen & Seegers, 2009), and consumer satisfaction (Briggs et al., 2007; Liu et al., 2013; Xiang et al., 2015). The demand for a hotel is considerably enhanced, the higher its review scores. In effect, there is bound to be an advancement in sales and revenue. (Chavalier & Mayzlin, 2006; Sparks & Browning, 2011; Phillips et al., 2017.) On the contrary, negative reviews have the likelihood of having a damaging impact on the consumers' attitudes (Lee et al., 2008). More customers are using online reviews to express their preferred service conditions and as a tool to find available recommendations for a considerably valued product on the market. Consequently, it is quite popular for consumers to read reviews of others before making a purchase in order to shed off existing mysteries about the product. (Archak et al., 2011, Zheng et al., 2011).

2.4.2.4 Brand relationship

Over the course of the past decade, the consumer-brand connections have garnered a significant amount of attention in hospitality literature (Chen & Phou, 2013, Hudson et al., 2015, Carlson et al., 2019). The concept that individuals and companies can have a connection is where the consumer-brand relationship gets its start (see, Fournier, 1998; McAlexander et al., 2002; Khamitov et al., 2019). An exchange of reciprocal value between a brand and its customers that develops and deepens over the course of time, ultimately contributing to the significance and value of the brand, is what we mean when we talk about a brand relationship (Ahn & Back, 2018). According to Aurier & de Lanauze (2012), perceived brand relationship orientation is the consumer's appraisal of the brand's willingness and power to build and sustain connections

with its consumers. This evaluation is based on the consumer's perception of the brand's relationship orientation. In the recent past, the primary focus of marketers was on expanding their customer base rather than keeping the customers they already had. Having said that, this philosophy has undergone significant revision. The consolidation of relationships with customers is increasingly the primary focus of marketing activity (Smit & Tolboom, 2007).

According to Blackston (1993), there is a two-way interaction that takes place between customers and brands, and the consumer's opinion of the company's attitude toward customers is an important factor that needs to be taken into account while conducting research on brand image. As a consequence of this, as a result of the interaction between the brand and the consumer, the brand becomes the active partner of the consumer. Aaker (1996) stated that when customers connect with brands, they may form a dynamic relationship with those businesses, comparable to the way that individuals cultivate relationships with their close friends. According to the consumer lifetime value concept (Khamitov et al., 2019), new studies in relationship marketing are based on evidence of the benefits of customers' loyalty, which is a growing valuable resource for businesses based on the concept (Khamitov et al., 2019). Additionally, these studies examine the influence of customer loyalty on brand equity (Aaker, 1991; Johnson et al., 2006). In a market for services that is always evolving, the relationship that a brand has with its clientele is of the utmost importance. In order to improve the performance of the brand, the link between the brand and its customers needs to be strengthened. Because the experience of the customer is so important in marketing strategy, it ought to be constructed on a comprehensive knowledge of the customer (Kwon et al., 2020).

Since the customer views the brand as a satisfactory partner in an existing relationship (Khamitov et al., 2019), the degree to which the consumer is attached to the brand increases in proportion to the strength of the brand connection (Algesheimer et al., 2005). Under some conditions, an attachment of this kind could significantly explain the customer's attitude and possibly even their motive (Ilicic & Webster, 2011; Khamitov et al., 2019). Positive brand sentiment can be influenced by interactions between companies and their customers (Adjei et al., 2010, Hutter et al., 2013). Their research is limited to car clubs where members regularly participate in a variety of social activities such as parties. Despite the fact that Algesheimer et al. (2005) proposed a reverse relationship (i.e., the brand relationship contributes to the consumer's relationship with the brand community), their findings are only applicable to these types of clubs.

The depth and quality of the person–brand relationship can be inferred from the brand

relationship, which is based on feedback from customers (Hudson et al., 2015; Xie et al., 2015). It is possible that Fournier's (1998) formulation of the brand relationship framework is the piece of work that has received the most citations in this area. Fournier (1998) observed that individuals were not merely purchasing brands based on the utility they provided. They established relationships with a variety of companies in order to take advantage of the significance that these brands have in their everyday lives. The idea that was proposed by Fournier (1998) has been examined in a variety of settings, one of which being the hotel industry.

In the context of restaurant brands, Ekinçi et al. (2005) discovered considerable support for the validity of the relationship idea from the point of view of European customers. According to the findings of their research, there are four aspects of brand relationships: partner quality, nostalgia, a connection to one's self-concept, and intimacy. When testing an altered version of Fournier (1998)'s model, Kim et al. (2005) discovered that self-connected attachment had the strongest correlation possible with the brand relationship.

The maintenance of positive consumer brand associations and the gathering of information regarding customers' perspectives and feelings towards a particular tourism brand are both dependent on strong brand relationships (Ahn & Back, 2018). In point of fact, Aaker et al. (2004) found that the incentives and rules that regulate interpersonal relationships are likely the same ones that govern people's interactions with brands, and consumers define their relationships with brands in terms of social relationships (Ahn & Back, 2018). A powerful brand makes it easier for customers to make decisions by elevating their expectations and reducing the perceived risks associated with those expectations (Keller, 2008). According to research conducted by Hudson et al. (2015), a significant number of customers choose a particular hotel because of the strong associations they have with the hotel's brand. "in today's highly competitive climate, developing a strong relationship with consumers is increasingly emerging as a strategy for organisations aiming to retain loyal and satisfied customers" (Meng & Elliott, 2008, p. 509).

Drawing on this discussion, in this study, a brand relationship is defined as some bond (physical, emotional or financial) between a brand and person (Smit et al., 2007; Veloutsou & Moutinho, 2009; Xie & Heung, 2012) characterised by the unique history of interactions and anticipation of future occurrences (Xie & Heung, 2012).

2.4.2.5 CSR

In recent decades, the implementation of CSR principles has become a global trend, with a

large interest in the topic and a sudden shift in the usage of CSR in a variety of forms (Weber 2008; Frey & George 2010; Gu et al., 2013; Youn et al. 2015; Akbari et al., 2020). Increasing study in this area demonstrates that CSR has a significant impact on a company's success (Park et al., 2013; Park et al., 2017). Society now expects organisations to be socially engaged, and virtually every modern organisation engages in some sort of CSR activities. CSR is broadly described as the position and activities of a company in regard to its perceived societal duty (Brown & Dacin, 1997; Sen & Bhattacharya, 2001). Businesses would benefit much from a reputation for social responsibility (Akbari et al., 2020).

Initially, CSR efforts were restricted to corporate actions aimed at reducing social problems via servicing particular groups or voluntary donations. According to Hemingway & MacLagan (2004), organisations can be motivated to engage in CSR projects for three basic reasons. The first is intrinsic (also known as altruistic): the organisation engages in CSR out of a desire to assist and contribute to society. The second incentive is extrinsic (sometimes known as self-serving or self-centred): the firm engages in CSR because it expects to profit from its socially responsible conduct. The final motivations are cultural expectations and stakeholder pressure. Nonetheless, it has gained greater acceptance over time.

The application of social responsibility in the real world provides businesses with competitive benefits and shows the role that social responsibility plays in distinguishing the company from its competitors (Porter & Kramer, 2006; Park et al., 2016). It is a widely held belief that corporate social responsibility (CSR) can benefit a company by improving customer perceptions of the company's image and capabilities, building brand recognition, and broadening the brand's sphere of influence (Fu et al., 2014; Li et al, 2015). CSR has several proven benefits for firms, including increased customer loyalty (Akbari et al., 2020), trust, positive brand attitude, and the ability to counteract unfavorable press (Akbari et al., 2020).

The relevance of corporate social responsibility (CSR) rises due to the fact that the hotel business is so inextricably linked with the surrounding environment. For instance, the hospitality industry has a considerable effect not just on the physical and social landscape, but also on the community at large in the immediate area (Chung & Parker, 2010). According to Farrington et al. (2017), the hospitality business is susceptible to a variety of pressures, both from within the company and from the outside. Economic shocks, social and political instability, seasonality of demand, poor public opinions of the industry as offering low wages to staff to benefit hotel owners, and the wealthiest segment of society are all aspects that could negatively impact the financial performance of hotels. Seasonality of demand is another factor

that could negatively impact hotels' financial performance. At this time, a number of hotel companies are offering CSR-related activities to demonstrate their commitment to their customers (Al-Msallam, 2015; Deng & Xu, 2017). This is done because CSR contributes to the overall well-being of society, and new customers are becoming increasingly concerned with society and the environment.

Therefore, CSR activities are viable for establishing a favourable brand positioning (Akbari et al., 2020), customer satisfaction, and brand loyalty (Al-Msallam, 2015; Akbari 2020), notably in the hotel industry in the context of sustainability (Al-Msallam, 2015; Akbari 2020). As this debate comes to a close, it is important to note that CSR is an integral component of solid brand positioning and may be defined as how firms manage the business processes to produce an overall positive contribution to sustainable economic development (Harjoto & Jo, 2011), working with employees, their families, the local community, and society to improve their quality of life. (Jamali & Mirshak, 2007; Pomeroy & Dolnicar, 2009).

2.4.2.6 Events

Professionals in the tourism and hospitality industries are always searching for innovative approaches to differentiate their companies from those of their competitors and inspire brand loyalty among customers (Yang & Tan, 2017). The concept of event marketing is a relatively new one that has been garnering more and more attention recently (Miller & Washington 2012; Shin et al., 2018; Yang & Tan, 2017). The term "event marketing" didn't appear until the 1980s, but its roots may be found in charitable giving and corporate sponsorship going back more than a century (Cunningham et al. 1993). For all intents and purposes, it may be summed up as "the technique of promoting an organization's interests and brands by associating it with a given activity" (Shimp 1993, p. 8). This kind of activity might be owned by the company, or it might be owned by a third party, but either way, the company might support it and promote it (Kotler & Armstrong 2010).

There are two distinct varieties of event sponsorship: commercial sponsorship and philanthropic sponsorship. Commercial sponsorship looks for immediate financial benefits related with brand positioning, publicity, image, and sales, in contrast to charitable sponsorship, which indicates support for a cultural or social cause without the expectation of receiving any economic gains (Astous & Bitz, 1995). Because of all of these advantages, the commercial sponsorship of events is becoming an increasingly popular and effective method of marketing for companies (Luonila, 2016, Meenaghan et al., 2013).

Philanthropic sponsorship, on the other hand, is more concerned with long-term benefits such

as publicity and brand recognition, in contrast to advertising, which is more focused with short-term aims such as sales (Shin et al., 2018). According to research conducted by Liu et al. (2018), consumers consider event marketing to be more effective than traditional forms of advertising like television commercials, which leads to a stronger desire to make a purchase. According to the findings of Rowley & Williams (2008), commercial sponsorships have a significant impact on consumers' recall of brands, awareness of brands, and attitude toward brands, but only a moderate impact on consumers' actual use of brands. Instead of describing the goals of an event in terms of persuasion and attitude change, event practitioners are highlighting the possibility that events might establish a deeper and more meaningful relationship with attendees by providing them with these kinds of experiences (Miller & Washington 2012; Shin et al., 2018). Many businesses are still confused whether events may improve marketing outcomes and, more crucially, how they can do so. This is despite the widespread use of event marketing and ongoing attempts to evaluate its success (e.g. Wood 2009). According to Gupta (2003, page 119), "event marketing has been considered as useful in increasing awareness for the brand."

On one hand, Sneath et al. (2005) and Close et al. (2006) have demonstrated that event participation can result in more positive brand perspective, which can increase or predict purchase intentions. On the other hand, they have also demonstrated that brand-related parameters such as sentiments and brand attitudes are more influential in purchase intentions than variables of events such as event sentiments. Recent literature has described how events can help businesses attain corporate objectives such as brand positioning, improving sales and reaching target audience (Getz & Page, 2016; Luonila, 2016; Liu et al., 2018). Event marketing is frequently recommended in the literature on brand management to increase brand equity (Keller 1998, 2009; Zarantonello & Schmitt, 2013).

In regional tourist management, events are regarded as valuable assets for boosting brand positioning visitor numbers and earnings (Panyik et al., 2011; Getz & Page, 2016, Higgins-Desbiolles, 2018). Putting together an event aimed directly at the consumer can be a worthwhile endeavor for a hospitality business. Hotels and restaurants have been known to host events to attract clients who would not otherwise stay at the hotel or dine at the restaurant (Smit & Melissen, 2018). In conclusion, the concept of an event can be described as those circumstances in which companies have to deviate from traditional public relations, marketing and advertising efforts (Doyle et al., 2014) to promote the interests of the company and its brand by associating the company with specific activities (Leischnig et al., 2011; Doyle et al., 2014).

2.5 DEFINING THE CONSEQUENCES OF BRAND POSITIONING

In this thesis, the fundamental elements identified as consequences of brand positioning from varied literature are presented in a table below, and this forms the consequences of brand positioning that are represented in this study. they include, brand authenticity, local iconness, attachment, and performance constructs, which are examined in detail in this section.

Consequences	Key references
Brand authenticity	Brown et al. (2003); Deepak & Kim (2018); Lu et al. (2020); Cohen (1988); Milman (2013); Lu et al. (2015); Napoli et al. (2014); Fang & Zeng (2015); Eggers et al. (2013); Ritz et al. (2017).
Brand local iconness	Steenkamp et al. (2003); Holt et al. (2004); Nijssen & Douglas (2011); Halkias et al. (2016); Riefler (2012).
Brand attachment	Albert et al. (2008); Vlachos et al. (2010); Hyun & Kim (2014); Park (2013); Dennis et al. (2016); Japutra et al. (2019).
Cognitive	Jamaluddin et al. (2013); Sharif & Sulaiman (2019); Han & Choi (2019); TaghiPourian & Bakhsh (2015).
Affective	Sharif & Sulaiman (2019); TaghiPourian & Bakhsh (2015).
Conative	Ahn & Back (2018); Back & Parks (2003); Sharif & Sulaiman (2019); TaghiPourian & Bakhsh (2015).
Brand performance	Foroudi (2020)
Loyalty	Li & Petrick (2008); Ha et al. (2009); Chaudhuri & Holbrook (2001); Kim et al. (2018).
Attitude	Keller (1993); Chu & Kim (2011); Iyer et al. (2017); Martin & Lueg (2013).
Equity	Davcik et al. (2015); Cheung et al. (2020); Martinez et al. (2019).
Satisfaction	Kim et al. (2015); Fakharyan et al. (2014); Iyer et al. (2017); Nam et al. (2011); Lee et al (2018); Miran et al. (2015); Flint et al. (2011); Deng et al (2010); Gomezelj (2016); Patterson et al. (1997).
Reputation	Ahn & Back (2018); Dutta & Pullig (2011); Mmutle & Shonhe (2017); Park et al. (1986); Foroudi et al. (2014); Xie & Peng (2009); Lombart & Louis (2016)

2.5.1 Defining brand authenticity

Brand position management embraces brand authenticity, despite the lack of congruence among proposed definitions (Morhart et al., 2015; Schallehn et al., 2014). Authenticity of a brand refers to its heritage, genuineness, sincerity, and originality (Beverland, 2005). Brown et al. (2003) defined authenticity as a brand's "aura" or essence that is related to a distinct feeling of historical legacy, a "spirit of the past." According to Steiner & Reisinger (2006), authenticity results when consumers associate it with their identity. Additionally, other research have highlighted the significance of authenticity in brand management (Brown et al., 2003; Deepak & Kim, 2018; Lu et al., 2020). Customers are constantly searching for genuine products from their brand. Consequently, modern marketing techniques are now preoccupied with authenticity (Brown et al., 2003).

Even though numerous authors have defined authenticity differently, the marketing and branding literature is unanimous regarding its significance and benefits. Authenticity is considered in psychology research as a crucial driver of social well-being and fidelity, lending further credence to the importance of authenticity for emotional connections. (Wickham, 2013). According to Lu et al. (2015), there is a positive link between views of an ethnic restaurant's authenticity and brand equity traits such as perceived quality and brand awareness. Specifically, this study found that there was a correlation between these two factors.

Authentic experiences have been regarded as a factor that motivates consumers to travel to remote regions and perceive distant times in the hospitality and tourism literature (Cohen, 1988). According to Goulding (2000), there are three categories of visitors that may be broken down based on the way in which they evaluate authenticity: existential, aesthetic, and social. Milman (2013) investigated the impact that manufactured authenticity plays in a theme park visitor's experience, in addition to the elements that can predict a visitor's impression of authenticity, realism, and truth while encountering "reproduced" landmarks in a theme park setting.

Consumers provide a positive evaluation of a brand's product orientation when they perceive that the brand is real (Napoli et al., 2014; Moulard et al., 2016). According to Morhart et al. (2015, p. 203), the concept of brand authenticity can be defined as "the extent to which consumers consider a brand to be faithful to itself (continuity), truthful to its consumers (credibility), motivated by care and responsibility (integrity), and able to encourage consumers in being genuine to themselves (symbolism)".

As behavioural implications of brand authenticity are investigated and demonstrated, brand loyalty (Lu et al., 2015), purchase intention (Napoli et al., 2014; Fang & Zeng, 2015; Lu et al., 2015), and the intention to suggest the brand (Spiggle et al., 2012; Morhart et al., 2015) are some of the outcomes that have been shown to be affected. In addition, Eggers et al. (2013) demonstrated that there is a favorable association between the growth of small and medium-sized businesses and the authenticity and trust in brands held by those businesses. However, this more recent analysis is based on the viewpoints of the CEOs rather than the perspectives of the customers of the companies. In terms of surface and deep traits, authenticity encompasses all that is genuine, unaltered, hypocrisy-free, and sincere. Authenticity also includes the absence of any falsehoods (Manthiou et al., 2018). It is distinguished by its genuineness, morality, and straightforwardness (Schallehn et al., 2014).

In the literature on branding, the possibility of true brand representation serving as a positioning strategy has been highlighted (Beverland et al., 2008; Beverland & Farrelly, 2010). The perception that a brand is unique, authentic, or original is one of the most sought-after qualities among consumers (Bruhn et al., 2012), and this enables marketers to differentiate their products from those of their competitors in the same brand category. Authenticity is one of the most sought-after characteristics among consumers (Dwivedi & McDonald, 2018). In order to favorably influence consumers' impressions of a brand's authenticity, the positioning of the brand must be in line with the consumers' actual self-perception, as stated by Ritz et al. (2017). Summarily, the authenticity of a brand can be defined as: the "subjective judgement of genuineness" (Lude & Prügl, 2018; Napoli et al., 2014) that buyers assign to a brand is what is meant when we talk about the authenticity of a brand.

2.5.2 Defining brand local iconness

Steenkamp et al. (2003) were the first to propose a hypothesis regarding the local iconic value of brands and study the impact that this had on brand appraisal and purchase intention. According to Ozsomer (2012), the term "brand local iconness" refers to "the degree to which a brand symbolizes the values, needs, and aspirations of the residents of the local country." In comparison to the globalness of a brand, the idea of local iconness has gotten a very little amount of academic attention, despite the fact that it is of critical strategic value to local businesses. According to research, people living in economies that are more developed have a preference for purchasing locally positioned goods, whereas people living in economies that are developing have a preference for purchasing from globally positioned businesses that use foreign concepts and cultural icons from around the world because they imply a higher level of quality (Holt et al., 2004; Nijssen & Douglas, 2011). Ozsomer (2012) stated that a global

brand is distinguished by its global distribution and recognition as well as its methodical approach to brand strategy and promotion.

According to Porral & Levy-Mangin (2015), local iconness is the degree to which a brand reflects the values and needs of the members of a local country, with an emphasis on the local affiliations and the culture of the local country. This idea highlights the one-of-a-kind qualities, the significance, and the symbolic value that a brand possesses within the context of the local culture (Ozsomer, 2012). The term "local icon status" refers to the originality and distinctiveness of the company in its own local market, as evidenced by the company's brand positioning (Holt, 2003).

According to Halkias et al. (2016), localness characteristics have the ability to positively influence consumers and generate purchase behaviour, which may lead to the formation of positive recommendations about the brands. These hypotheses are used to successfully position the brands (Alden et al., 1999). Consumers tend to appreciate global enterprises that have evolved to their local culture and homegrown firms that have achieved international success (Riefler, 2012). Brands must choose how to strategically position themselves in markets where local cultures may be hostile to international brands.

Based on this discussion, the concept of brand local iconness can be defined as follows: the extent to which a brand is perceived as a local player and a symbol or icon connected with the local country (Sichtmann et al., 2019; Halkias et al., 2016) or the use of local resources (Mohan et al., 2018).

2.5.3 Defining brand attachment

In the 1980s, the term "attachment" appeared for the first time in the psychological literature, referring to the underlying human desire for interpersonal relationships, such as the tie between parent and child or romantic partners (Bowlby, 1979; Weiss, 1988). This idea was expanded in the 1990s to include emotional attachments to things such as brand attachment (Schultz et al., 1989; Schouten & McAlexander, 1995).

According to the findings of a number of studies, the relationship that exists between a customer and the brand of a retail establishment may be developed and improved upon by the customer's level of confidence in the organisation and the individuals that work there (Albert et al., 2008; Vlachos et al., 2010). According to the findings of a number of studies, for instance, customers' loyalty to the brand of a retail establishment may be nurtured and strengthened by the customers' faith in the organization's staff and management (Albert et al., 2008; Vlachos et al., 2010). For instance, Hyun & Kim (2014) argued that the attentiveness of service workers

at high-end restaurants is critical for creating and reinforcing clients' emotional attachment to the restaurant brand. This emotional attachment is important for building and maintaining repeat business.

Dennis et al. (2016) looked into the function of brand attachment in higher education institutions and its implications on commitment, satisfaction, trust, and brand equity. Attachment strength has a higher impact on both the level of pleasure with the brand and its equity, as shown by the findings of an online survey of current college students and recent graduates. In addition, they asserted that an attachment to the brand is necessary for the development of robust consumer-brand relationships, the maintenance of which is critical for companies and organisations that wish to maintain a competitive advantage. Enhancing the relationship between the hotel brand and its guests has the potential to have a significant impact on the financial performance of hotels (Liu et al., 2012). It is vital to cultivate a strong brand connection in order to generate repeat purchases, even compulsive buying, love for the brand, and loyalty from customers (Park, 2013; Dennis et al., 2016; Japutra et al., 2019).

In light of this conclusion, the idea of brand attachment is an essential component of successful brand positioning. Brand attachment can be defined as the extent to which consumers experience a sense of connection with a brand and the extent to which aspects of the brand are self-referential and self-defining for the consumers (Park et al., 2010, Schmalz & Orth, 2012).

2.5.3.1 Elements of brand attachment

Cognitive, affective, and conative are typically the order in which brand attachment develops progressively. Han & Choi (2019) posit that the “cognition–affect–conation model (Lavidge & Steiner, 1961) provided a sound basis for understanding the three main stages of consumers’ buying process: cognitive (thinking), affective (feeling), and conative (doing) stages”. To better comprehend brand attachment, the many parts, including conative (Ahn & Back, 2018), affective (Grisaffe, & Nguyen, 2011), and cognitive (Jamaluddin et al., 2013), will be examined in further detail.

2.5.3.2 Cognitive

The cognition stage of brand attachment or customer loyalty is attitude-based and involves a consumer's deliberate and purposeful familiarization with a brand. In the "I think" phase of the purchasing process, buyers gather information about a brand and its goods (Jamaluddin et al., 2013; Sharif & Sulaiman, 2019; Han & Choi, 2019). It is the first antecedent in Dick & Basu's (1994) three-dimensional model of brand loyalty, which fosters a consumer's profound devotion to a brand (TaghiPourian & Bakhsh, 2015). Informed by Oliver (1999)'s paradigm,

TaghiPourian & Bakhsh (2015) asserted that “perceivable qualities and features of a certain brand indicate that it is more advantageous and desirable than other alternatives”. They describe loyalty at the cognitive stage as superficial and information-based formed from previous or second-hand information about a brand.

2.5.3.3 Affective

Affective-based brand attachment is the second step in the purchase process of a customer and is also referred to as attitudinal brand loyalty (Grisaffe, & Nguyen, 2011). Sharif & Sulaiman (2019) referred to it as the "I feel" loyalty. A consumer's attitude toward a brand may be negative or positive based on satisfaction (Back & Parks, 2003; Han & Choi, 2019). When a consumer obtains satisfaction from a brand, it constitutes a significant portion of the consumer's experiences and transcends to become affectively based loyalty. The affective model thus refers to the feelings, moods, or emotional responses that a customer associates to a brand, as measured by physiological responses. Possibility of new information influencing a consumer's cognitive attachment is considerable; yet it is difficult to influence a consumer's affective loyalty due to the emotional tie involved (TaghiPourian & Bakhsh, 2015). Scholars, however, argue that the bond can be shifted to another brand in a turn of events if certain attractive benefits such as reduced price are connected (TaghiPourian & Bakhsh, 2015, Sharif & Sulaiman 2019).

2.5.3.4 Conative

The conation-based attachment denotes “action” (Ahn & Back, 2018). According to Back & Parks (2003, p. 423), conation indicates “behavioural intentions or willingness to act”. It is the third category in the brand loyalty triadic model and is often characterised under behavioural loyalty (as opposed to attitudinal loyalty). Sharif & Sulaiman (2019) describe it as the “I do” loyalty. Taghi-Pourian & Bakhsh (2015) opine that it forms repeated positive feelings about a brand, that is, after a series of satisfactory customer experience.

2.5.4 Defining brand performance

Brand performance is a vast and all-encompassing concept. It has been described in a variety of ways, such as outperformance of competition, profitability, brand recognition, loyalty, customer satisfaction, equity, and increased purchase and consumption (Ghodeswar, 2008; Iyer, 2018; Foroudi, 2020). Previous research on brand performance and related topics suggests that brand performance can be calculated in financial and non-financial brand performance (Ambler, 1997; Ghodeswar, 2008; Iyer, 2018).

Due to the absence of a widely accepted definition of brand performance in marketing

literature, brand performance is often viewed as a significant result of actions or activities and standard business strategies (Iyer, 2019). According to Unurlu Loureiro & Gonzalez (2008) and Uca (2017), brand performance encompasses market dominance. This perspective is supported by O'Cass & Ngo (2007, p. 871), who describe brand performance as "a relative measurement of the brand's market success". Foroudi (2020) described a company's performance as the ability to achieve its organisational goals. Azimzadeh et al. (2020) described brand performance as the extent to which a company's brand is successful. Businesses continue to strive to understand this concept and improve their consumers' experiences, enhancing consumer satisfaction, sales growth, profitability, and market share (Foroudi, 2020).

According to Foroudi (2020), the relationship between consumer preferences and hotel performance is one of the most significant connections investigated in marketing, and it remains of importance to market research. It is evident that greater performance equates to a higher preference for the business and services. Considering this, the present study investigates five key aspects of brand performance: attitude, loyalty, equity, reputation, and customer satisfaction (Kaya & Marangoz, 2014; Davcik et al. 2015; Foroudi, 2019). These are discussed next.

2.5.4.1 Loyalty

Loyalty is an ancient term used to describe enthusiastic allegiance and commitment to a cause, a person, or a nation (Bloemer & Kasper 1995; Lovelock & Wirtz, 2011). It has also been utilised in the context of business to describe a consumer's inclination to keep purchasing from a company over time, especially on exclusivity and referring the company's products to associates, relatives and friends (Bilgili & Ozkul, 2015). The subject of loyalty has been well researched in marketing and human behaviour (Tucker, 1964; Oliver, 1999; Yoo et al., 2000; Foroudi, 2019). According to Li & Petrick (2008), the most fundamental characteristic of a good brand is creating a loyal consumer. A company/brand that has strategically enhanced brand loyalty in its service or product category can help deter competitors from entering the market.

The subject of loyalty in hospitality is examined from three points of view: behavioural, composite and attitudinal. Behavioural attitude is described as the likelihood of repeat purchases or the relative volume of same-brand purchases (Ha et al., 2009). Attitudinal loyalty is related to the consumer-dispositional commitment toward recommending brands/services (Chaudhuri & Holbrook, 2001). Composite loyalty incorporates behavioural and attitudinal

loyalty concepts (Harris & Goode, 2004; Rauyruen & Miller, 2007). Therefore, brand loyalty can be defined as a deeply held commitment or biased behavior response expressed over time (He et al., 2012) to rebuy or re-patronise a preferred service or product consistently in the future (Kim et al., 2018).

2.5.4.2 Attitude

As consumers, humans form opinions on a vast array of items and individuals in their daily lives, from objects to individuals. Kaya & Marangoz (2014) define an attitude as any ongoing favourable or negative beliefs and emotions toward an item, a person, or a circumstance. In contrast, brand attitude is the comprehensive appraisal of a brand, whether good or negative (Mitchell & Olson, 1981). The perception of a brand affects purchases and, more particularly, consumer behaviour. Thus, it is essential to comprehend how brand attitude influences consumer decisions (Kaya & Marangoz 2014). Attitude toward the brand is quite important in terms of both marketing and managing brands (Kaya & Marangoz 2014). Keller (1993) found that a consumer's attitude toward a brand is influenced by the unique qualities and advantages associated with that brand. He was of the opinion that the attitude of a brand was extremely important because it regularly influenced the judgments that customers made regarding brands.

A successful branding strategy that generates positive feedback from customers is an essential component of any successful brand (Augusto & Torres, 2018). Moreover, one of the most important objectives for marketers is to improve or strengthen brand attitude (Cheah & Phau, 2011). In fact, the value of advertising messages is frequently determined by the effect they have on brand attitude (Martin & Lueg, 2013). Keller (1993) suggested that brand attitude could be influenced by word-of-mouth since it is developed via customers' interaction with the brand, whether through the consumption of marketing content or through experience with the brand. There is evidence, however, that a positive brand attitude is more likely to generate word-of-mouth (e.g., Chu & Kim, 2011; Iyer et al., 2017; Martin & Lueg, 2013).

Experience with a brand's services or products influenced consumers' appraisal of the brand, its positioning statement, and comprehension of its symbolic and functional characteristics (Hegner et al., 2021). Additionally, the perception is affected by the perceived compatibility between the brand's positioning and its communication pattern positioning (Gretry et al., 2017; Leung et al., 2013). In conclusion, brand attitude can be defined as a consumer's total brand evaluation (Liu et al., 2012; Augusto & Torres, 2018). This refers to the degree to which customers like or detest a brand or the degree to which a consumer is positive or negative about a brand (Kaya & Marangoz, 2014).

2.5.4.3 Equity

Brand equity is a key concept in both marketing theory and practice. Businesses exert a substantial amount of effort to build the value of their brands over time. They gain from their financial and product market investments and capitalize on their brand value (Datta et al., 2017). Due to the importance of building, sustaining, and utilising brands to obtain a competitive edge in today's market, practitioners and academics have been intrigued by the concept of brand equity (Ailawadi et al., 2003; Christodoulides & De Chernatony, 2010; Wang & Sengupta, 2016). The concept of brand equity refers to the fundamental principle that a product's value to consumers, the marketplace, and the enterprise is enhanced when it is associated or recognised over time with a sequence of distinguishing characteristics that comprise the brand concept (Ailawadi et al., 2003).

According to Aaker (1991), the definition of brand equity is the collection of brand liabilities and assets related with a brand, its symbol, and name, which either contribute to or subtract from the value or worth offered by a service or product for the firm's clients or business. Keller (1993), writing from the perspective of cognitive psychology, referred to it as the differential influence of brand knowledge on customer response to brand marketing.

According to Erdem & Swait (1998), who employed an information economics approach, the value of a brand is a reliable indicator of the position that a company holds in the market. In a broader sense, brand equity refers to the value that an established brand brings to a product, whether it be for the purpose of the company, the marketplace, or the end user (Wang & Sengupta, 2016); or the difference between the branded product's value to the consumer and the product's value without the branding (Erdem et al., 1999). These opinions concur that a brand's worth to a business is determined by its effect on consumers.

Prior research has demonstrated the value of brand positioning initiatives in constructing brand equity (Davicik et al., 2015; Cheung et al., 2020). Davcik et al. (2015), for instance, criticized the paucity of empirical research on the effects of brand positioning on brand equity and propose for additional study to increase its practical use in a variety of scenarios. According to Cheung et al., (2020), a stronger brand positioning plan results in brand equity, which includes brand loyalty and brand recognition. Due to the highly competitive nature of the hospitality industry, brands have prioritised brand distinctiveness to establish brand equity (Davicik et al., 2015; Martnez et al., 2019).

2.5.4.4 Satisfaction

In recent decades, brand satisfaction has served as an indicator of operational success and a

long-term competitive advantage for branding strategies due to the increased emphasis on customers. The last few decades have seen satisfaction become a marketing strategy concept linked to a business's long-term competitive edge (Patterson et al., 1997; Saeidi et al., 2015). Strategic customer satisfaction management is of the utmost importance in today's crowded marketplace, as consumers are inundated with options (Lin, 2015). Kim (2008), for example, found at least thirty various brands in the extended-stay market alone in 2008. In such a highly competitive climate, practitioners and academics must emphasize client satisfaction. According to research conducted over the last two decades, brand satisfaction in the hospitality industry leads to loyalty (Kim et al., 2015) and positive word of mouth (Fakharyan et al., 2014; Iyer et al., 2017).

A consumer's history, expectations, and attributes, in addition to external stimuli such as geography, convenience, choice, surroundings, salesperson, and marketing events, all have a role in determining the level of satisfaction they experience with a product or service (Devesa et al., 2010; Lin, 2015). Whether or not it fits early projections, it is also the emotional and psychological result of personal experiences (Baker & Crompton, 2000), and it will have an effect on the success of a corporation (Nam et al., 2011). In their study on coffee shop businesses, Lee et al. (2018) discovered that staff attitude, ambiance, and coffee quality contributed to customer happiness. Particularly, the cosy environment was the most important factor in determining how satisfied the clients were. Therefore, providing services or products that either increase contentment or reduce unhappiness is essential for customer acquisition and retention (Lin, 2015).

Miran et al. (2015) found that consumer happiness and satisfaction had a favourable impact on positioning in the hospitality industry. Flint et al. (2011) investigated the connection between customer satisfaction, brand positioning, and consumer value anticipation. According to them, the anticipation of consumer value is a major incentive for positioning and satisfaction. Deng et al. (2010) examined the elements that affect brand positioning and consumer satisfaction. They determined that perceived consumer value, both emotionally and practically, was essential for achieving contentment. These studies have one thing in common: the importance of brand satisfaction in positioning. Moreover, these concepts are interconnected.

On the other hand, customer satisfaction is more likely to be a complex human process requiring an affective and cognitive approach as well as other physiological and psychological factors (Song et al., 2015). Song et al. (2011) argued that a consumer's level of satisfaction or discontent determines the level of satisfaction with a service or product. Therefore, a

corporation or brand can obtain a competitive advantage over its rivals by enhancing consumer satisfaction (Gomezelj, 2016; Patterson et al., 1997) Based on this discussion, satisfaction is seen as a delightful degree of post-consumption evaluation (Chen, 2010; Oliver, 1980; Song et al., 2019) and affective response to an overall product or service experience (Oliver, 1980).

2.5.4.5 Reputation

In the hospitality industry, a brand's reputation is defined as the aggregate perception of customers on the aspects of the overall brand that are open to observation. As a consequence of this, brands that have a solid reputation are typically in a position to attract customers by delivering the performance that has been promised and marketed (Ahn & Back, 2018). Customers have an expectation that a company will live up to the standards set by the brand's reputation. Belief that a company or brand that has a high level of perceived knowledge and reputation can be relied on, which leads to behavioral intentions (Dutta & Pullig 2011). According to Mmutle & Shonhe (2017), the reputation of a firm is frequently used as a performance indicator because successful businesses are generally regarded as having a positive reputation. It is possible that customers' feelings of pride in being associated with a respectable brand will enhance if they believe the company's reputation to be one that is well-known and successful (Bergami & Bagozzi, 2000).

The reputation of a brand grows through time, and the appraisal of a brand is based on the feedback received from customers. People will constantly hunt for additional information while they are evaluating the reputation of a brand. Sincerity and dependability are the two characteristics that most often contribute to a positive brand reputation (Jurisic & Azevedo, 2011). It takes time to create a solid brand reputation, and people tend to make assumptions about how a firm will behave in the future based on the brand reputation it already possesses (Lie et al., 2018).

According to Foroudi et al. (2014), reputation is the cumulative evaluation of a brand over time. Brand identity and factors are incredibly effective communication tactics because they can influence inferences about a brand's benefits or attributes (Aaker, 1991) and collaborate with other elements of the marketing mix to connect clusters of associations about the brand (Carpenter & Nakamoto, 1989). Park et al. (1986) stated that when building the positioning of a brand, you should maintain its reputation. Additionally, when a brand is not unique, the brand's components may be the major basis for any perceived differentiating advantage among consumers (Aaker, 1991).

A brand's reputation can be assessed by a wide range of stakeholders (for example, investors,

employees, industry experts). Although this research focuses on consumers, it emphasises the degree to which customers value the brand. The development of a brand's reputation is strongly connected to the suitability and reliability of the marketed product or service and how consumers feel after purchasing the brand /product or service (Foroudi et al., 2014). The positive or negative reputation of a brand can be affected by consumer experiences and recommendations. The brand's reputation must be established not only through experience, but also through the capabilities of the brand's marketing communications as a strategy to achieve the brand's/products' sustainability.

A brand's reputation is deemed positive so long as the brand is viewed as to be good and satisfactory (Xie & Peng, 2009; Lombart & Louis, 2016). In summary, a brand's reputation and standing can be created by robust brand positioning and connecting with consumers. Therefore, brand reputation can be referred to as an immediate picture of a brand based on the aggregated images held over the years (Foroudi, 2019) or the perception of quality associated with the name of the brand (Bang et al., 2014).

2.6 DEFINING THE MODERATORS

In this study, the fundamental elements identified as moderators of the brand positioning from versed literature are also represented in a table below. the moderators include the following; brand attachment and performance constructs are brand identity, brand awareness, brand competence and brand warmth, which are examined in detail in this section.

Moderators	Key References
Brand identity	Aaker & Joachimsthaler (2012); Baumgarth & Schmidt (2010); Urde et al. (2013); Tubridy (2010); de Chenatony (2010); Aaker (2012); Buil et al. (2016); Foroudi et al. (2017).
Brand Awareness	Sen (1999); Liu et al (2018); Romaniuk et al. (2017); Ahn et al. (2018); Moisescu (2009).
Brand competence and warmth	Aaker et al. (2012); Kervyn et al. (2012); Zawisza & Cinnirella (2010); Xu et al. (2013); Aaker e t al. (2010); Davvetas & Halkias (2019); Bolton & Mattila (2015); Bufquin et al. (2017); Ivens et al. (2015); Wu et al. (2017); Kolbl et al. (2019);

2.6.1 Defining Brand Identity

Implementing a strategy that is focused on the brand requires strong brand identification as a foundational element (Urde, 1999). According to Hanna & Rowley (2013), it is an essential

component of brand enhancement, and various branding literature reviews have focused a significant deal of attention on it as a result (Kapferer, 2008; Aaker & Joachimsthaler, 2012; Ghodeswar, 2008). Core and extended identities are both components of what Ghodeswar (2008) refers to as "brand identity," which he describes as "a distinct collection of brand links expressing a promise to customers." This is comparable to the definition of brand identity offered by Aaker (1996, page 6) who described it as "an exclusive set of brand connections that the brand strategist strives to establish or preserve."

According to Wheeler (2012), brand identity is a strategic component that provides more recognition, a differentiated position in the market, and specifics regarding the product's quality. According to Kotler (2011), the mechanisms that an organisation use in order to place its products and services and identify itself are what constitute its "identity." A strong brand should have value and a unique identity; if it does not, this may be a sign that the brand has to be extended or modified in some way.

To be successful, a brand identity needs to put the needs of the consumer front and center, communicate what the firm is capable of achieving over time, and set itself out from the competition (Aaker & Joachimsthaler, 2000). A strong brand identity makes it easier to differentiate oneself from one's competitors, builds consumer confidence, integrates a promise to one's clientele, and foretells the activities that the company will undertake in the future (Aaker & Joachimsthaler, 2012). In addition to this, it makes it simpler for stakeholders to recognise their own brand (Baumgarth & Schmidt, 2010).

In order to maintain consistency with its brand identification, Urde (2003) makes use of Volvo, a Swedish vehicle company. He explains how Volvo organizes its products so that they adhere to the brand's criteria, the most essential of which is safety (Urde 2003, 2016). According to Urde et al. (2013), a company's brand identity can function as a strategic point for the company, highlighting the fact that it is more than just a simple aesthetic component or logo. It is important for a company's brand identity to reflect the company's overall strategy while also setting it apart from similar products on the market. This will offer the company an edge over its rivals (Ghodeswar, 2008). It is essential to the development of a brand identity to have a solid understanding of one's competitors, the business environment, and consumers, in addition to upcoming trends (Aaker & Joachimsthaler, 2012). In addition, a powerful brand identity provides major advantages, differentiates itself from other services and goods on the market that are identical, and establishes a favorable position in the opinions and perceptions of customers (Tubridy, 2010). It is difficult to differentiate a product from similar ones on the

market if it does not have a strong, well-defined brand identity.

A survey of the available research on brand management suggests that brand positioning is one of the most significant contributors to brand recognition (Kapferer, 2008; Ghodeswar, 2008; Aaker & Joachimsthaler, 2012; Urde, 2016). According to Leslie & Francesca (1998), the first phase in the process of developing a brand identity is identifying the company's values and vision, which is then followed by considerations on the brand's positioning (de Chernatony, 1999). The basis for product or service innovation, design strategy, employee motivation, communication, and image-building can be laid with the careful consideration of a position selection that is founded on an organisation's identity (Riezebos & van der Grinten, 2012; Koch & Gyrd-Jones, 2019). The significance of a brand can be increased through the use of an identity-based approach for both existing customers and potential new customers. It affords the possibility of improving the brand's standing through the use of strategic brand management (de Chernatony, 2010). Drawing from this conclusion, the idea of brand identity is an essential component of brand positioning. It can be described as an exclusive collection of brand associations (Aaker, 2012) as well as defining characteristics or central ideas (Buil et al., 2016, Foroudi et al., 2017) of what a brand is or what it aspires to create or maintain (Aaker, 2012) and how it communicates this idea to various stakeholders (Buil et al., 2016).

2.6.2 Defining Brand Awareness

It is usual practice to consider brand awareness to be one of the fundamental concepts behind brand equity. This is due to the fact that brand awareness acts as an essential starting point and the foundation for developing brand loyalty through familiarity with a brand (Sen, 1999; Liu et al., 2018). According to Aaker (1991), brand awareness can be defined as the extent to which consumers perceive a brand in a unique way in comparison to other brands. According to Keller et al. (2011), brand awareness is the degree to which prospective buyers are able to recognize and remember a specific brand within a given product category.

Awareness of a brand refers to the perception that a consumer has regarding the attractiveness of a particular brand. It is widely acknowledged as an essential component of a brand's effect in the hospitality and tourist industries (Kim & Kim, 2005; Boo et al., 2009). This has an impact on the contentment of customers (Yuan & Jang, 2008). Lin (2013) observed that brand awareness is a critical aspect that affects a visitor's loyalty, attitudes, and likelihood to return after doing research on the significance of "brand equity" in Taiwanese tourism and hospitality. According to Hoeffler & Keller (2003), brand awareness can be broken down into two categories: breadth and depth. Breadth refers to the manner in which a specific brand name

comes to the mind of a consumer when making a purchase, and depth refers to the manner in which a specific brand characteristic comes to the mind of a consumer when making a purchase. The speed with which individuals can recognize and recall particular brands is referred to as depth. When it comes to making purchases, customers are more likely to recognize and choose brands that have a bigger variety of products and services. This gives those brands an advantage (Romaniuk et al., 2017; Ahn et al., 2018). Awareness of a brand is absolutely necessary for consumer choice. When customers have a higher level of familiarity with a certain product or brand, there is a larger chance that they will include that product or brand among the options they are considering purchasing (Moisescu, 2009). Customers who are familiar with a brand have a lower risk of switching to a competitor product and a higher likelihood of being loyal to the brand compared to customers who are not familiar with the brand (Dimitriades, 2006).

To summarize, brand attitude and brand awareness are two interconnected concepts that collectively describe the realm of primary determinants of brand equity. There is a strong correlation between familiarity with a brand and consumers' opinions (Keller, 1993). In light of the fact that it is common information that there is a connection between brand awareness and brand attitude (Macdonald & Sharp, 2000), it is possible to make the recommendation that raising brand awareness can have essential attachment implications (Esch et al., 2006). In this study, brand awareness is defined as the ability of a consumer to recognize or recall a brand; that is, all descriptive and evaluative brand-related information that relates to the cognitive illustration of the brand (Wang et al., 2016; Kim et al., 2018). This definition is based on the argument that brand awareness and brand attachment are interrelated constructs, which was presented in the previous section

2.6.3 The definition of the competence and warmth of the brand

It is widely held that two of the most essential aspects in determining how humans perceive social items, such as brands, are a person's level of expertise and warmth toward them (Aaker et al., 2012; Kervyn et al., 2012). This methodology has seen widespread use in research on consumer perceptions of brands and nations (Aaker et al., 2012; Keller, 2012). Warmth of brand refers to consumers' perceptions of a company's positive intents, specifically showcasing a company's friendliness, genuineness, and helpfulness.

Consumer evaluations of organisations and businesses, particularly with regard to their friendliness and expertise, are quite important (Aaker et al., 2010, 2012; Kervyn et al., 2012). For instance, people have a friendlier impression of organisations that are not-for-profit, yet

they have a more positive impression of businesses that are for-profit (Aaker et al., 2010). These perspectives shape consumers' propensity to interact with brands developed by these organizations; they color customers' desire to engage with brands developed by these organisations. Consumers are more inclined to make purchases of brands from businesses that they perceive to be both kind and knowledgeable (Kervyn et al., 2012).

The same evaluations of warmth and competency that impact 82% of social behavior (Andrei et al., 2017; Wojciszke et al., 1998) are also used to evaluate organisations, according to academics. This was found in two studies: Andrei et al., 2017 and Wojciszke et al., 1998. (Aaker et al., 2010). Warmth and competence views were shown to explain "nearly fifty percent of purchase intent, loyalty, and tendency to suggest a brand or firm." These perceptions were found to be highly predictive of a consumer's willingness to buy (Malone & Fiske, 2013, p. 35). Consumers have a better intention to buy products from a company if they believe that the company's products will have a high level of desirability if the company is viewed as having a high level of competence (Aaker et al., 2012). On the other hand, in the event of a product failure, perceived warmth has a larger predictive potential for buy intention than perceived competence does (Zawisza & Cinnirella, 2010; Xu et al., 2013).

The knowledge-attitude-skill paradigm places an emphasis on three factors that contribute to one's level of competence: the cognitive or mental skills, which are also known as knowledge; the emotional skills, which are sometimes known as attitude; and the psychomotor, manual, and physical skills, which are also known as skills (Cutcliffe & Sloan, 2014). The interaction of warmth and competence has consequences for behavior in addition to emotional outcomes. Warmth is frequently associated with helpful intentions and prosocial behavior, which might encourage others to lend a helping hand. Competency, on the other hand, is often associated with the successful completion of one's objectives (Cuddy et al., 2007).

Warmth and competence are also related to other concepts such as the identity and loyalty of a brand, as well as the reputation of the brand (Aaker et al., 2010). Consumer assessments of a variety of organisational characteristics, such as a company's level of friendliness and expertise, are the foundation upon which a brand's reputation is constructed. When customers have the impression that a company is looking out for their best interests (warmth), the reputation of that brand reflects dependability (Aaker et al., 2010). The evaluation of a brand's competency takes into account its quality, dependability, durability, and consistency (Kervyn et al., 2012). When customers perceive that a brand provides excellent value for their dollar, the brand will develop a reliable reputation (Davvetas & Halkias, 2019).

Research done in the past suggests that competence and warmth play an important part in satisfaction (Bolton & Mattila, 2015; Bufquin et al., 2017), increased attitude (Ivens et al., 2015), brand attachment (Wu et al., 2017), positioning strategies (Kolbl et al., 2019), purchase likelihood, and brand loyalty (Bolton & Mattila, 2015; Bufquin et al., 2017 (Kervyn et al., 2012)). As a result, it should not come as a surprise that companies often try to alter these impressions by overtly presenting themselves in a certain way and demonstrating their genuineness.

2.7 SUMMARY

The influence of brand positioning in hospitality is gaining new trajectory in the market as well as in recent academic research. The importance of a critical inquiry and evaluation of brand positioning in various industries is steadily coming to light and the industry of hospitality is not taking a backseat. This research, therefore, is one of such numerable exploration of the influence of brand positioning on brand attachment and brand performance, however, in the hospitality setting.

This chapter began by presenting the literature review on the relationship between brand attachment, brand attitude and brand awareness, to understand the contribution of these constructs to explain consumers' attitude toward brand positioning. In this review, brand attachment, brand attitude and brand awareness are considered as essential factors to determine consumers' attitudes toward brands. In addition, the mediating role of brand attitude and brand awareness in the relationship between brand attachment and consumers' perceived competency, and brand attitude and brand awareness were discussed.

Also reviewed in this chapter are the fundamental conceptualisations and implementations. The antecedents, consequences and moderators of brand positioning bring the review to a close. The study's conceptual framework and the formulation of hypotheses will be presented in the following chapter.

CHAPTER III: CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK AND RESEARCH HYPOTHESES

3.1 INTRODUCTION

The previous chapter developed a conceptual model that begins with a set of factors as antecedents to the brand positioning and simultaneously illustrates the outcomes of the brand positioning. The following 23 constructs are the focal elements of this study: product fit, brand fit, customer engagement, brand trust, online review, brand relationship, CSR, events, brand

identity, brand awareness, brand warmth, brand competence, brand authenticity, brand local iconness, brand attachment, brand loyalty, brand attitude, brand equity, brand satisfaction and brand reputation.

The proposed conceptual framework at the consumer level will be presented in this chapter. A number of hypotheses, which are conceptually related to one another, were investigated and tested.

3.2 RESEARCH FRAMEWORK AND HYPOTHESES DEVELOPMENT

The role of brand management, particularly brand positioning in developing a sustainable competitive advantage, has garnered interest and has been researched by various disciplines, which may be acceptable in multiple contexts and industries (Malik & Sudhakar, 2014; Tamrin & Noor, 2019). The management of brand positioning requires an understanding of its dimensions (Iyer et al., 2019). Numerous business professionals and academics have expressed their support for the idea that more attention should be paid to the significance of brand positioning. Since the 1950s, this has led to an increase in the quantity of conceptual literature on brand positioning (Urde & Koch, 2014).

According to O'Neill et al. (2016), there is a paucity of empirical research that focuses on the placement of brands in the minds of consumers. Because there is a lack of understanding regarding the topic of "brand positioning," researchers have been considering conducting a pluralistic study in which qualitative methods will be used in conjunction with quantitative methods to investigate a domain that is either unidentified or has received a relatively small amount of attention to this point (Deshpande, 1983).

A mixed-method study that quantifies, supplements, and complements previous qualitative investigations will use the theoretical framework as the preliminary phase in the study's design. Numerous studies have been conducted on the subject of the significance of brand positioning as the initial stage in enhancing brand attachment performance, which is a factor that promotes positive performance. On the other hand, there hasn't been a lot of research done on how the positioning of a brand affects the variables that are necessary to achieve brand performance and attachment. The research cited in this article demonstrates the significance of brand positioning as a differentiator in order to create brand performance (Iyer et al., 2019) and brand attachment (Wu et al., 2017), both of which differentiate the company from its rivals (Hinson et al., 2017). A consumer-level conceptual framework (see Figure 3.1) has been constructed in this study to analyze a number of different links. These relationships have been recognized in the existing body of research.

Figure 3.1: The conceptual framework

3.3 BRAND POSITIONING AND ITS INFLUENCES

3.3.1 Brand alliance fit and brand positioning

Perceived brand alliance fit refers to consumers' perceptions of the similarity and compatibility of co-branding partners (Simonin & Ruth, 1998). Guillet & Tasci (2012) stated that the use of brand alliances has shown to be an effective marketing approach for a number of different brands. Many authors, like Simonin & Ruth (1998), Abratt & Motlana (2002), and Mazodier & Merunka (2014), were of the opinion that "perceived fit" plays a key role in the manner in which the evaluation of brand alliances is carried out. Consumers' perceptions of a brand or product's "fit," or the degree to which two categories are perceived to be compatible, have frequently been validated as a predictor of attitudes regarding brand alliances. This is because fit refers to the degree to which two categories are perceived to be compatible with one another. It is expected that the positioning perceptions of the partner brands will have an effect on the positioning perceptions of the merged brands when those brands are involved in a partnership.

There is a direct correlation between the level of brand awareness, brand equity, familiarity, and quality of the individual brands that make up a brand alliance, and the likelihood that the collaboration will be successful. On the other hand, there are dangers associated with brand

alliances. These dangers include increased consumer mistrust, a reduction in the value of the brand (according to Washburn et al., 2000), and a greater strain on the company's finances (Mazodier & Merunka, 2014).

A positioning strategy for a company is a form of signaling that conveys a particular perception of the brand to the target audience. Customers receive a new set of perceptions as a result of the joint use of the respective positioning strategies of the two brands that have joined forces. Therefore, it is logical to predict that brand alliance fit will influence partner brand positioning. In other words, favourable brand alliance fit will result in favourable brand positioning. As a result of the discussion that emphasises the importance of brand alliance fit, its ambiguous relationship within brand positioning study, and lastly, its relevance to the study's current setting, the following hypothesis is made:

Hypothesis 1: Brand alliance fit has a favourable influence on brand positioning

3.3.2 Customer online engagement, brand trust, online review, and brand positioning

Consumer online interaction has piqued marketers' interest for over a decade, owing to the advent of social media and an acceptance that customers may both generate and destroy value (e.g., Libai et al. 2010; Verhoef et al. 2010). Notably, the recent Covid-19 event hastened digitalisation, with consumers leapfrogging five years in digital adoption within a few months of the pandemic's outbreak (Buhalis & Park, 2021). The literature has recognised the importance of online tools in the hospitality sector. According to Xiang & Gretzel (2010), an online platform has become a crucial primary source of information for consumers in the hospitality sector. They look for information online before making a purchase decision. In agreement with Xiang & Gretzel (2010), Roshchina (2012) demonstrated that online reviews influenced consumer travel decisions. The study by Harrigan et al. (2017), showed that the immersion with social media by consumers of tourism brands is an emotional aspect of involvement, describing a condition in which users feel contented and absorbed. Customers can interact and network on these social media platforms by creating and sharing brand content. Continuous involvement and activity on multiple social media platforms can create consumer-brand relationships, resulting in sentiments of brand trust, loyalty, and repurchase intent (Hajli et al., 2017; Wong & Haque, 2021). Exploring online activities can increase and widen businesses' understanding of brand positioning and consumer preferences (Brexendorf et al., 2015; Perera et al., 2020). Therefore, determine how online engagement influences the brand positioning in the hospitality sector.

Word of mouth is often a significant determinant of consumer perception and behaviour, according to Godes & Mayzlin (2004). It is critical in the hospitality business to determine the

right set of qualities that consumers consider as significant when making a purchase, as brand/product features are critical in building consumers' favourable affective evaluations of the brand/product (Zhou et al., 2014). O'Connor (2010), for example, notes that distinctive characteristics of a restaurant can assist consumers in assigning value to the brand or product.

Brand trust is essential in shaping consumers' behaviours and attitudes about brands and is necessary for consumers to make decisions about brands (Bhandari & Rodgers, 2018). In the online space, consumers' engagement and review inspires like-minded individuals to trust the information provided by other consumers and to believe that the brand is trustworthy (Perera et al., 2017). Once consumers develop a greater degree of trust in a brand, it occupies a valuable and distinct place in their minds. Coffie (2018) stated that confidence in the information posted online about a specific brand could help establish a certain position in the minds of potential consumers even while increasing trust in the brand. Consumers who are intensely engaged with a brand can learn more about it and are motivated to create trust while establishing a favourable distinctive place in their minds. This shows that the online review and online engagement established brand trust which boost the positioning of the brand among customers.

Hypothesis 2a: Customer online engagement has a favourable influence on brand positioning

Hypothesis 2b: Brand trust has a favourable influence on brand positioning

Hypothesis 2c: Online review has a favourable influence on brand positioning

3.3.3 CSR, brand relationship, events, and brand positioning

In their early research, Robinson & Wood (2018) found that CSR negatively influences brands' perceptions of performance in developing brands. However, they later discovered that these negative impacts are unlikely to occur in established brands provided the firm demonstrates a clear interest in CSR. Through CSR investment, businesses can ensure financial benefits and competitive advantages (Akbari et al., 2020), increase brand awareness (Hafez, 2018), brand equity (Hur et al., 2014), and establish brand loyalty (Akbari et al., 2021), all of which can help strengthen consumers' connection to the brand and its positioning (Akbari et al., 2020).

Hur et al. (2020) showed a strong positive correlation between consumer perception of CSR and emotional brand attachment. Research showed that CSR activities for the environment play an essential role in positioning a brand (Makasi et al., 2014). Organisations such as IBM and Easyjet are well cognizant that their CSR performance directly impacts how consumers perceive their brands (Akbari et al., 2021).

Studies have recognised that attending an event can result in more favourable brand attitudes

and that brand attitudes, in turn, determine loyalty and higher purchase inclinations. A field survey of consumers who attended various events (sponsored events, pop-up stores, street events and trade exhibitions) demonstrates that event participation positively impacts their perception of the brand (Close et al., 2006; Sneath et al., 2005; Zarantonello & Schmitt, 2013).

Events are an intriguing vehicle for promoting experiences since they allow consumers to participate actively in aspects of self-interest and interaction processes that are not available in everyday life (Martensen et al., 2007). However, most studies into experiential marketing services with an emphasis on events focus primarily on sporting events. Despite this, a set of research currently exists that exploits the arts and humanities as a source of marketing tactics (e.g., Vila-López & Rodríguez-Molina, 2013; Shin et al., 2018).

Events can occur in various kinds, including charity, product sampling, entertainment, visitor attraction, reward/incentives programmes, roadshows, etc. (Woods, 2009). For example, Illy opened multiple galleries globally, including in locations such as Milan, New York, and London, where coffee enthusiasts could enroll in classes on making the ideal cup of coffee, meet essayists and writers, and attend art exhibitions held inside the gallery. These new types of events cost less than advertising but can reach a vast audience through word-of-mouth mediums (Zarantonello & Schmitt, 2013; Iyer et al., 2018), thereby positioning the brand above the counterparts.

The relationship between a brand and its consumers is critical in today's fast-changing service marketing environment. To improve brand performance, the brand's relationship with its customers must be steady and long-lasting. According to Kwon et al. (2020), the relationship should be founded on a comprehensive understanding of consumers, as consumer experience is critical in contemporary marketing. Additionally, when consumers develop a relationship with a brand, they behave similarly to how they do with people. They frequently apply social interaction principles to the brand. The greater the brand relationship, the more substantial the attachment; that is, the consumer considers the brand as a satisfactory partner in an on-going relationship (Cassidy et al., 2018). Under certain circumstances, such an attachment could play critical roles in determining consumer intention and even attitude towards the brand (Ilicic & Webster, 2011).

From a branding standpoint, positive consumer perceptions of a firm's relationship increase affective commitment and loyalty (Aurier & Séré de Lanauze, 2012). When consumers sense a brand's commitment to sustaining and growing relationships, they form a stronger bond with the brand. This results in more favourable responses to the brand (Valta et al., 2013). Cassidy et al.'s

(2018) study of hotel performance via developing brand relationships noted that hotels that show consumers their effort to develop a relationship are likely to be positioned positively in their consideration set. As a result of the information above, the following hypotheses are generated:

Hypothesis 2d: Brand relationship has a favourable influence on brand positioning

Hypothesis 2e: CSR has a favourable influence on brand positioning

Hypothesis 2f: Event has a favourable influence on brand positioning

3.4 THE BRAND POSITIONING AND ITS CONSEQUENCES

3.4.1 Brand positioning, brand authenticity, and brand attachment

Brand authenticity is increasingly recognised as a critical factor in consumer-brand relationships (Bruh et al., 2012; Oh et al., 2019). Research consistently shows that establishing brand authenticity is a viable path to building strong brands. For example, consumer brand authenticity perceptions lead to higher brand attachment and positive word of mouth (Morhart et al., 2015; Ayra et al., 2019). Therefore, if a brand is considered more authentic, it positively impacts how consumers think and feel about the brand, which improves their attitude and intentions such as future purchases and recommendations to others.

According to Ilicic & Webster (2014), authenticity improves brand attitudes and equity. They also proposed that brand managers and marketers employ relational authenticity as a foundation for brand positioning or development. In a competitive market, positioning a brand based on quality service and product superiority is popular, whereas authenticity enables a brand to be real without being perfect (Athwal et al., 2018). Additionally, marketers can find new possibilities for brand positioning and value development by assessing and measuring authenticity (Morhart et al., 2015). Thus:

Hypothesis 3: Brand positioning has a favourable influence on brand authenticity

Hypothesis 4: Brand authenticity has a favourable influence on brand attachment

3.4.2 Brand positioning, brand local iconness, and brand attachment

Despite the many positive associations related to global brands, being "global" is not the only means of achieving brand success (Halkias et al., 2016). Studies have discovered consumer dynamics that influence customers' decisions to abandon global brands in favour of local alternatives (Özsomer, 2012; Sheth, 2011; He & Wang, 2017). Current marketplaces include customer segments with ethnocentric interests, who are ethically committed to purchasing local

items to maintain the local economy (Halkias et al., 2016), and anti-global consumers, who despise the standardisation of products brought about by global companies (He & Wang, 2017). Steenkamp et al. (2003) argued that positioning a local business as a local culture icon was a unique and effective strategy for a local brand. Similarly, Mohan et al. (2018) underlined that a "localness" extends beyond its reach and accessibility and is dependent on the brand's connection with the local culture. Recent developments stress consumers' need for product uniqueness and authenticity (Hoskins et al., 2020; Srivastava et al., 2020) and their quest to "go to their origins" and provide potential opportunities for the strong position of local brands.

Incorporating cultural elements in branding has become a prominent marketing technique (Wang & Lin, 2009; He & Wang, 2017). Chinese characteristics, for example, are a frequent tactic used by multinational corporations to develop brand positioning and create brand equity in Chinese markets (Wang & Lin, 2009). Local brand managers can achieve competitive success by leveraging local cultural capital, history, and targeting and positioning strategies that reflect a greater awareness of local identity and culture (Ger, 1999). Forging a link with the local country and culture may help local brands generate perceptions of local iconness. When a company appropriately communicates "localness" to the consumer, it conveys brand authenticity (Hoskins et al., 2020), which influences the brand positioning..

Qualitative insights provided by consumer culture theory demonstrate that consumers' attachments to country elements most likely influence their behaviours and attitude (Nowicka, 2007; Bardhi et al., 2012). When consumers have a solid self-brand connection, they perceive parts of themselves reflected in the brand, strengthening brand attachment and creating a favourable brand positioning (Ferraro et al., 2013). Davvetas & Diamantopoulos (2016) discovered that adopting a local brand positioning strategy is efficient for building brand attitude. They further proposed that managers consider adopting a local consumer culture positioning strategy when connecting with local communities and adapting to the local target consumers.

On the whole, local brands tend to have a strong connection and cultural ties to local consumers and benefit from a greater understanding of local tastes due to their long-term involvement in the local marketplace. Significantly, the benefits of brand localisation on brand choice appear substantial in developed nations and several rising markets (e.g., India, and so on) (Foltean, 2019). Thus, favourable local brand positioning leads to higher brand attachment through their positive effect on consumer attitudes.

Hypothesis 5: Brand positioning has a favourable influence on brand local iconness

Hypothesis 6: Brand local iconness has a favourable influence on brand attachment

3.4.3 Brand positioning and brand performance

Based on analysing the industry and market data, brands that transcend the traditional sales-driven mindset and employ positioning strategies to carve out a unique spot in their consumers' minds are better positioned to achieve brand performance (Iyer et al., 2019). According to Huang & Tsai (2019), brand-oriented companies that monitor and respond to consumer demands and preferences to better produce value for them are considered to outperform less brand-orientated organisations. They also claimed that in order for a company to create a brand orientation, it must have superior product differentiation qualities that are conducive to creating a unique brand positioning in the minds of customers, hence creating favourable brand equity.

Brand positioning is a way to generate emotional responses in people every time they use a product or service that bears the name of the brand (Tamrin & Noor, 2019). According to empirical research, brand positioning has resulted in tremendous brand performance in terms of brand equity, loyalty, attitude, reputation and satisfaction (Huang & Tsai, 2013; Kaya & Marangoz 2014; Miran et al., 2015; Foroudi et al., 2018; Liu & Hu, 2021). Brand performance results from a company's brand marketing efforts (Huang & Tsai, 2013), and it indicates a brand's market success (Iyer, 2018).

Brands with better brand equity outperform competitors in a marketplace, generating much more significant and most frequently sustainable financial benefits through increased profitability and market share (Horsfall & Mac-Kingsley, 2018). Past research has established the critical importance of brand equity in assuring a business's success (Aydin & Ulengin, 2015; Davcik et al., 2015; Kalafatis et al., 2012; Keller, 2008). Aydin & Ulengin (2015) discovered that consumer-based brand equity has a favourable effect on customers' attitudes. Similarly, Narteh (2018) demonstrated that brand equity strongly correlates with banks' financial performance.

Mmutle & Shonhe (2017) argued that a firm's reputation is frequently used to measure its performance because well-regarded firms are expected to succeed. If consumers view the reputation to be well-known and successful, this may increase their pride in connecting with a brand that has a good reputation (Bergami & Bagozzi, 2000). Brand reputation is considered in the hospitality industry as the aggregate perception of consumers on the noticeable qualities of the overall brand (Foroudi, 2019). As a result, brands with a solid reputation often attract consumers when they deliver on their promised and claimed performance (Ahn & Back, 2018). It is important to know that brand reputation is not always the driving force behind profitability

and increased sales. It can result from increased present or future brand performance, which can increase recommendation, loyalty and repurchase (Foroudi, 2019). Having a solid reputation is an essential resource that must be protected, as it has significant implications for future earnings (Edeling & Fischer, 2016).

According to the literature above, a company with a more significant brand orientation and positioning would also have a stronger brand performance, which includes brand loyalty, brand equity, satisfaction, attitude, and reputation. Thus:

Hypothesis 7: Brand positioning has a favourable influence on brand performance

3.4.4 Brand attachment and brand performance

Although significant interest in brand attachment peaked only recently (Park et al., 2010), researchers and practitioners are making gradual advancements to provide answers to related and elusive issues (Ailawadi et al., 2003; Thomson et al., 2005; Dennis et al., 2016; Gomez-Suárez & Veloso, 2020; Chinelato et al., 2021). Park et al. (2008) examined four foremost attachment-based factors involved in developing a strong and enduring brand relationship with customers. One of the key factors considered in their review explores the two-way outcome of brand attachment to customers and the firm, in other words, the outcome on the consumer and a brand's performance.

Research has suggested that the existence of brand attachment or a close customer-brand relationship is prone to increase the company's revenue, competitive advantage, and overall market performance (Gomez-Suárez & Veloso, 2020; Chinelato et al., 2021; Pine II et al., 1995). Solid brand attachment has been considered to promote brand advocacy (Finkel et al., 2002; Pimentel and Reynolds, 2004; Carroll and Ahuvia, 2006) and have an adverse effect on the competition by triggering their devaluation (Johnson & Rusbult, 1989, cited in Park et al., 2008), thereby elevating the performance of the focus brand.

Park et al. (2010, p. 2) posited that the brand attachment construct involves a brand-self connection that advances a feeling of oneness and can incite "potentially complex feelings about the brand, including sadness and anxiety from brand-self separation, happiness and comfort from brand-self proximity, and pride from brand-self display". This proposes the importance of attachment as a construct because it is a critical brand equity driver (Park et al., 2010) and it fosters a brand's success especially with regards to the brand's profitability (Thomson et al., 2005; Theng So et al., 2013).

In Ailawadi et al.'s (2003) Interbrand model, it was established that a brand's unit price, marketing costs, and sold units are characteristic influences on its monetary value and these

factors are directly linked and determined by consumers' attachment to the brand. What this translates to is that how a brand will fare is determined by consumers' repeated patronage, which in turn is determined by consumers' attachment. In another attachment-performance context, Chinelato et al. (2021) investigated the role of brand attachment in salesperson performance in retailing. Their result revealed that salesperson brand attachment (SBA) is important in driving sales performance. In a more related context, Arya & Setiawan (2020) explored hotels in Bali, Indonesia, noting that "the hotel business has intense competition and strong switching intentions" (p. 88). Their investigation revealed, amongst other things, a connection between brand attachment and "loyalty" which can be assumed to impact a brand's performance.

Generally, there appear to be limited empirical studies on the link between brand attachment and brand performance, that is, the direct influence the former has on the latter. In the same light, there is hardly any study about this interplay in the hospitality setting. However, extant literature on consumer-brand relationships specifies that brand attachment is a relevant predictor of durable and stable relationships and is highly associated with brand revenues (Kim & Kim, 2004). This should come as no surprise, understandably, and due to the rich conceptual properties of the construct (Park et al., 2010), its proven ability to shape brand loyalty and love (Ghorbanzadeh & Rahehagh, 2020), its spurring of brand success (Thomson et al., 2005; Theng So et al., 2013) and its demonstrated influence on increasing salesperson sales performance (Chinelato et al., 2021), it can be deduced that it plays a crucial role in brand performance. This premise informs this hypothesis. Thus:

Hypothesis 8: Brand attachment has a favourable influence on brand performance

3.5 MODERATORS

In the extant literature on brand management and marketing strategies, certain moderators peak as the key push and pull of positioning. In this section, such moderators as brand identity, brand competence and warmth, and brand awareness are examined in the context of brand positioning.

3.5.1 Brand identity, brand alliance fit and brand positioning

A wealth of empirical studies has been contributed to the body of literature on brand management moderators including brand alliance, brand identity, brand fit, and product fit. On that note, as aforementioned, cooperative activities between brands, labelled as "brand alliance", can no longer be considered a novel marketing strategy. Research has shown that brand alliance has thrived as an alternative to risky brand stand-alone and costly brand

extensions, gathering for itself a rich nomenclature (Boo & Mattila, 2015; Norman, 2016). In fact, Newmeyer et al. (2018, p.2) support this, stating that, “The marketplace is replete with instances of brand alliances, albeit in different forms and with profoundly different strategic implications”.

In the opinion of Norman (2016), brand alliance denotes a single-context merge of two or more brands and products represented through some means of promotion. The concept of brand alliance is usually discussed with contextual significance given to brand and/or product fit because consumers consciously or unconsciously evaluate the compatibility or congruence of products or brands in an alliance. The bases for fit in a brand alliance (culture, category fit, brand associations, customer goals, and self-representation, etc. (Martin & Stewart, 2001)) are consequently reflective of the brand’s equity and identity. Simonin & Ruth (1998) proposed that fit is a strong predictor of consumer attitudes towards the brand alliance.

Positioning, on another hand, is a vital part of the brand identity (Tomiya, 2010; Wheeler, 2012) in the form of prices, promotion, place, and other components of the marketing mix. Positioning dictates the orientation consumers have about a brand and is considered the most noteworthy stage in the asset management strategy (Fayvishenko, 2018). On another hand, identity assumes an effectual and strategic tool that provides brand awareness, quality differentiation, and advantage over the competitors (Wheeler, 2012). Empirical studies on brand management have shown that brands with high equity in an alliance can project relevant information more than brands with less equity (Lafferty et al., 2004; Washburn et al., 2004). Such strong influence can cause a spillover effect that can alter the positioning and perhaps, identity of the brand. Given this viewpoint, there appears to be an interweaving of these market-related constructs. A triangulation of the relationship can be proposed, one in which brand identity occupies the apex, and fit and positioning sit at the two bottom corners. The bottom occupants contribute to the apex. In other words, fit and positioning form part of the consumers’ perception of brand identity, and conversely, brand identity informs the perception consumers have about its position and fit. The bottom occupants contribute to the apex. In other words, fit and positioning form part of the consumers’ perception of brand identity, and conversely, brand identity informs the perception consumers have about its position and fit.

These accordingly accord a positive positioning, better the brand’s identity, and accentuate the brand complementariness between brand allies. Ashton & Scott’s (2011) investigation of perceived fit and intent to purchase (in a hotel-restaurant alliance) provides findings that suggest that perceived fit positively affects intent to buy. This indicates a positive influence of

brand fit on consumers' perception of the brand (positioning). The mediating influence of brand identity for brand fit and brand positioning can be most felt between brands with a gap in equity. Thus:

Hypothesis 9: Brand identity moderates a favourable relationship between brand alliance fit and brand positioning

3.5.2 Brand identity, brand positioning success and brand positioning

A strong brand identity is a critical component of any brand strategy's success (Buil et al., 2016). According to Aaker (2008), brand identity is the critical feature of branding, providing direction, purpose, and meaning to the brand. The identity is a set of brand connections that the company strives to build and retain. Belk & Karsaklian (2004, p. 46) declared that "the objects we stick with represent a real extension of ourselves". Customers in the present day observe, participate, interact, and co-create with brands they identify with other consumers (Chu & Kim, 2011; Labrecque et al., 2013). Invariably, Silva (2015, p. 33) asserted that it is understandable if consumers form relationships with brands such as brand relationship or online engagement "only if they recognize values they accept". In other words, what the brand stands for determines the relationship and the engagement it receives from the customers online.

Also, it is noted by Hobbs and Goddard (2015) that brand trust serves as the foundation for establishing a strong connection between customers and a brand. According to Loureiro and Gonzalez (2008) brand trust in trust in travelers is established based on the favourable effect of the brand on their loyalty. This implies that for a brand trust to exist among customer, the identity of the brand must appeal to their loyalty, which in turn influences their behaviour and attitude towards the brand. In other words, customers purchase from a brand based on the identity it puts out, and that they relate to, and perhaps, not the product in isolation (Karsaklian, 2004, p. 72; Martinez et al., 2013).

The comments from consumers as online review indicates the experience of customers based on their perception about a brand (Xiang et al., 2015, p. 44), which is something that consumers consider to be essential to other customers. As a consequence of this, it is possible that online reviews will be more diagnostic when the customers identify a brand and establish trust and relationship with it. A strong brand identity makes it easier to differentiate oneself from one's competitors, builds consumer confidence, integrates a promise to one's clientele, and foretells the activities that the company will undertake in the future (Aaker & Joachimsthaler, 2012). In addition to this, it makes it simpler for stakeholders to recognise their own brand (Baumgarth & Schmidt, 2010).

On the other hand, studies have proven that CSR and events has many benefits to brand positioning, including increased customer loyalty (Akbari et al., 2020), trust, positive brand attitude, and the ability to counteract unfavorable press (Akbari et al., 2020). It is believed that corporate social responsibility (CSR) benefits a company by improving customer perceptions of the company's image and capabilities, building brand recognition, and broadening the brand's sphere of influence (Fu et al., 2014; Li et al, 2015), and this is strengthened when the consumers know the visions and missions of the brand, and can relate to them. On one hand, Sneath et al. (2005) and Close et al. (2006) have demonstrated that event participation can result in more positive brand perspective, which can increase or predict purchase intentions. The basis for product or service innovation, design strategy, employee motivation, communication, and image-building can be laid with the careful consideration of a position selection that is founded on an organisation's identity (Riezebos & van der Grinten, 2012; Koch & Gyrd-Jones, 2019). The significance of a brand can be increased through the use of an identity-based approach for both existing customers and potential new customers. It affords the possibility of improving the brand's standing through the use of strategic brand management (de Chernatony, 2010). Therefore, based on the above assertions, it can be stated that strong brand identity equates to successful branding and positioning (Bahcecik et al., 2019), hence the formulation of the following hypothesis:

Hypothesis 10: Brand identity moderates a favourable relationship between customer online engagement and brand positioning

Hypothesis 11: Brand identity moderates a favourable relationship between brand trust and brand positioning

Hypothesis 12: Brand identity moderates a favourable relationship between online review and brand positioning

Hypothesis 13: Brand identity moderates a favourable relationship between brand relationship and brand positioning

Hypothesis 14: Brand identity moderates a favourable relationship between CSR and brand positioning

Hypothesis 15: Brand identity moderates a favourable relationship between event and brand positioning

3.5.3 Brand awareness, brand positioning and brand authenticity

Pace (2015) argues that authenticity can preserve a company and extend its existence compared

to other unauthentic brands. What this suggests is that authenticity is a potent factor that influences the positioning of a brand. Brand authenticity is iterated by a brand's heritage, genuineness, sincerity, and originality (Beverland, 2005). It is a brand-building strategy of upholding the mission and core values of a brand.

As mentioned in the previous chapter, authentic experiences have been considered in the literature of hospitality and tourism as a driving factor that encourages consumers to travel to distant locations and perceive remote times (Cohen, 1988; Steiner & Reisinger, 2006). Two keywords that stand out in the discussion of brand awareness are recognition and recall (Aaker, 1991; Keller, 2008; Latif et al., 2014). These are the ability to recognise and recall a brand under different conditions. Aaker (1996) affirms that a brand position forms an integral part of the brand awareness communicated to the target audience. Brown & Dacin (1997, p.79) discover that “what consumers know about a company can influence their reactions to the company’s products”. In other words, awareness forms the key to lasting and competitive brand positioning.

In hospitality, it has become important to allude to the locale setting such that customers perceive the authenticity of the brand. In their investigation of authenticity perceptions of ethnic restaurants, Lu et al. (2015) discover that consumers’ authenticity perception is a crucial determinant of brand equity, which in turn has a relevant impact on consumers’ brand choice intention. In that light, an investigation of the moderation of brand awareness on authenticity and brand positioning has become necessary because a high level of brand authenticity is requisite for brand positioning, that corresponds with customers’ identities, and positioning forms an integral aspect of awareness. In that regard, the following hypothesis is suggested:

Hypothesis 16: Brand awareness moderates a favourable relationship between brand positioning and brand authenticity

3.5.4 Brand awareness, brand positioning and brand local iconness

Familiar and favourable brands are usually the choice of the consumers because of the rise in their consciousness. Recently, businesses have needed to up their game for increased brand awareness that could instigate the consciousness in the consumers. Brand awareness plays a significant role in brand positioning and may have good control over the risk of consumers’ evaluation and their level of assurance about the brand and its exclusivity (Malik et al., 2013). By brand positioning, a brand is distinctively different from its rivals and by this, it sticks differently in the consumers’ minds (Bilgili & Ozkul, 2015). Strategic positioning involves a clear description of the brand and its values which defines how the brand is being perceived.

By this, the value points of the brand as well as their differences from rival brands are defined to balance the influence on customers' perception about the brand (Koch & Gyrd-Jones, 2019). Bilgili & Ozkul (2015) noted that brand positioning is continuously enhanced by communication.

On the other hand, brand local iconness highlights a brand's uniqueness, significance, and how it relates to the local cultures and values, as well as its presence in the market (Özsomer, 2012). Local iconness represents the company's originality and uniqueness in its local market as signified by its brand positioning (Holt, 2003).

Brand awareness is the actual presence of a brand in the consumers' thoughts, which includes the consumers' understanding of the brand's position and local iconness. According to Alexandra & Cerchia, (2018) brand awareness is regarded as a requirement tool in enhancing the presence of brands in the minds of consumers and their ability to differentiate the brand from its rivals. The awareness of a brand is the likelihood that it will come to the mind of the consumers, and the ease with which it comes (Keller, 2013). Brand awareness integrates brand recognition, which is seen in consumers' ability to identify a brand due to prior exposure and understanding enhanced by appropriate communication (Alexandra & Cerchia, 2018). Brand awareness moderates brand positioning and local iconness because when the consumers are aware of the brand, it incorporates all the components of brand positioning and local iconness into their mind. These reviews therefore suggest the following hypothesis:

Hypothesis 17: Brand awareness moderates a favourable relationship between brand positioning and brand local iconness

3.5.5 Brand competence, brand authenticity and brand attachment

Brand competence must have a considerable manner that develops the consumers' trust in the brand. Afzal & Khan (2010) noted that certain characteristics of a brand must satisfy the customers' needs. A brand's competence can be made known to the customers through word of mouth, and so brands should ensure that their possessed characteristics satisfy the consumers' needs (Wirunphan & Ussahawantichakit, 2016). Consumer's perception about the originality of a brand, that is, how the brand has quintessence, is indicative of brand competence.

Being the first yields no benefit if a subsequent competitor's brand is preferable to the consumers; however, when the competitor's brand is viewed as inferior to the original brand by the consumers, then brand authenticity becomes beneficial (Wymer & Akbar, 2017). Hence, it is reasonable to believe that brand competence moderates brand authenticity. Changes may

be made to a brand's objectives and features overtime, but the degree to which these changes affect how a brand is perceived as authentic is dependent on how imitative it is of other brands (Wymer & Akbar, 2017). Being authentic implies that the brand is perceived as true, real, and original by the consumers which, to an extent, indicate the brand's competence. It is reasonable to believe that the quintessence of a brand is more indicative than its pioneer status (Vance, 2015). These characteristics of a brand connect to consumers' belief and trust in the brand as they meet the needs of the consumers.

A brand has to be real and true to build competence which in turn influences brand attachment. This basis informs the following hypothesis:

Hypothesis 18: Brand competence moderates a favourable relationship between brand authenticity and brand attachment

3.5.6 Brand competence, brand local iconness and brand attachment

Consumers are more inclined to purchase products from a company when they perceive its products as highly desirable and competent (Aaker et al., 2012). Several studies have emphasised the importance of customer confidence in the organisation and its staff for building and enhancing the customer-brand relationship (Albert et al., 2008; Vlachos et al., 2010). However previous research suggests that competence have consistently enhanced brand attachment (Wu et al., 2017) and positioning strategies (Kolbl et al., 2019).

On the other hand, brand local iconness is known as the extent to which a brand represents the e values, needs, and aspirations of the residents of the local country (Ozsomer, 2012). It also encompasses reflecting the values and needs of the local population while emphasising local affiliations and culture (Porral & Levy-Mangin, 2015). This uniqueness gives a brand significance within the local culture and can positively influence consumers, generating purchase behaviour and favourable recommendations (Halkias et al., 2016). These characteristics are integral in positioning brands effectively (Alden et al., 1999), as customers could easily relate to the brand as knowledgeable of the needs of the environment. Consumers often appreciate both global enterprises that integrate into local cultures and homegrown firms achieving international success (Riefler, 2012).

The knowledge-attitude-skill paradigm plays a pivotal role in brand attachment and customer loyalty. This paradigm emphasises three factors contributing to competence: cognitive skills or mental skills (knowledge), emotional skills (attitude), and physical skills (skills) (Cutcliffe & Sloan, 2014). In the context of brand attachment, the cognitive phase involves consumers

consciously familiarising themselves with a brand during the information-gathering stage which can be termed the “I think stage” (Jamaluddin et al., 2013; Sharif & Sulaiman, 2019; Han & Choi, 2019). It's crucial to note that perceivable qualities and features of a brand influence its desirability relative to alternatives (TaghiPourian & Bakhsh, 2015). Moreover, conation, which signifies behavioural intentions and willingness to act. It is the third category in the brand loyalty triadic model and is often characterised under behavioural loyalty (as opposed to attitudinal loyalty). Sharif and Sulaiman (2019) describe the “I do” loyalty as an essential aspect of brand loyalty (Back & Parks, 2003). It shows that consumers often develop repeated positive feelings about a brand after a series of satisfactory experiences (Taghi-Pourian and Bakhsh, 2015).

This implies that the relationship between brand local iconness and brand attachment is moderated by brand competence. Specifically, when consumers perceive a brand as highly competent, the favourable relationship between the brand's local iconness and the strength of their attachment to the brand will be stronger. This is based on the premise that competence enhances consumer satisfaction, attitude, and loyalty and that local iconness reflects the brand's resonance with the values and aspirations of local consumers. Consequently, a brand's competence will amplify the impact of its local iconness on brand attachment, resulting in a stronger emotional connection between the brand and its customers.

Hypothesis 19: Brand competence moderates a favourable relationship between brand local iconness and brand attachment

3.5.7 Brand competence, brand positioning and brand performance

It has been observed that a consumer's view regarding the competence of a brand might influence the consumer's purchase intentions and brand loyalty (Kervyn et al., 2012), trust (Kim et al., 2018), admiration (Aaker et al., 2012), and attitude (Kim et al., 2018). (Ivens et al., 2015). If consumers have the impression that a brand's product possesses a high level of expertise, they will be more likely to want to buy it, which in turn may increase the likelihood that they will (Aaker et al., 2012). According to the findings of recent studies, consumers' perceptions of a company's level of expertise are a significant factor in the purchase decision, which in turn affects the brand's overall success (Crisafulli et al, 2020).

Consumers obtain information about a brand from various channels: purchase of brand-related products, participation in brand-related activities, and using various services provided to deepen their understanding of the brand, which gradually forms a brand impression (Schnurr, 2017). The smile of a marketer in advertising a brand can make the consumers perceive association with the marketers as competent, thereby increasing their purchase intentions

(Wang et al., 2017).

Perceiving a brand as highly competent can increase a consumer's positive evaluation of the brand performance and product quality, thereby enhancing the brand positioning in the market. When consumers feel that a brand respects and understand them, they respect and accept the brand. This further promotes the consumer's positive attitude towards a brand, consequently, influencing the brand positioning and performance. Brand reflects the extent to which the goals and organisational strategy of a brand are attained. It is determined through the sales, profit and market share. The functional, economic and psychological benefit of a brand to customers determines the construct: brand performance.

Brand performance denotes a brand's success financially and non-financially in the market competition (Ambler, 1995). There are always many opportunities for customers to choose from every day; though overwhelmed with the myriad of choices, customers choose brands that have formally given them satisfaction. That is to say, a brand perceived to be competent is differentiated from market competition by consumers, thus improving the brand performance.

Brand positioning means that the consumers could easily differentiate a brand in the market because it has occupied a specific place in their mind. Among the common bases for positioning a brand, satisfying the unmet needs of consumers and performance (outperforming competition) are included on the list by Semans (2010). Brand competence moderates brand positioning and brand performance in that when consumers perceive a brand as competent, they tend to give a positive evaluation about it, which positions it, thereby increasing the brand performance. The economic value is not enough to determine brand performance; rather, it has to include both the financial and non-financial functions.

Hypothesis 20: Brand competence moderates a favourable relationship between brand positioning and brand performance

3.5.8 Brand warmth, brand authenticity and brand attachment

The moderation of brand authenticity and brand attachment by brand warmth is similar to the previous hypothesis of brand competence moderating brand authenticity and brand attachment. Brand warmth defines how consumers perceive the good intentions of a brand, that is, their perception about how friendly, genuine and helpful a brand is to the consumers.

Brand attachment can be regarded as the psychological variable that defines the steady and lasting response to a brand. The attachment between a brand and a consumer is related to the attachment in individuals' relationship between themselves which recognises factors such as experiences, dominating personality and the benefit earned from the relationships (Fournier,

1994). These forms promote the consumer-brand attachments. When a brand is genuine and original with its components, it is perceived as warm, friendly and satisfactory, thereby increasing the consumer-brand relationship. Hence, the following hypothesis is necessary:

Hypothesis 21: Brand warmth moderates a favourable relationship between brand authenticity and brand attachment.

3.5.9 Brand warmth, brand local iconness and brand attachment

It is widely held that two of the most essential aspects in determining how humans perceive social items, such as brands, are a person's level of expertise and warmth toward them (Aaker et al., 2012; Kervyn et al., 2012). The warmth of a brand refers to consumers' perceptions of a company's positive intentions, specifically showcasing a company's friendliness, genuineness, and helpfulness. Consumer evaluations of organisations and businesses, particularly with regard to their friendliness and expertise, are quite important (Aaker et al., 2010, 2012; Kervyn et al., 2012). This implies that for organisations to be perceived as warm, the integration of brand-local iconness is essential in order to provide consumers with a perceived sense of friendliness. The term "brand local iconness" implies the representation of values, needs, and aspirations of the residents of the local country by a brand (Ozsomer, 2012). It also encompasses reflecting the values and needs of the local population while emphasising local affiliations and culture (Porral & Levy-Mangin, 2015).

For instance, people have a friendlier impression of organisations that are not-for-profit, yet they have a more positive impression of businesses that are for-profit (Aaker et al., 2010). These perspectives shape consumers' propensity to interact with brands developed by these organisations; they colour customers' desire to engage with brands developed by these organisations. Consumers are more inclined to make purchases of brands from businesses that they perceive to be both kind and knowledgeable (Kervyn et al., 2012). This uniqueness gives a brand significance within the local culture and can positively influence consumers' attachment, generating purchase behaviour and favourable recommendations (Halkias et al., 2016). These characteristics are integral in positioning brands effectively (Alden et al., 1999).

Consequently, the warmth of a brand moderates the brand local iconness of such a brand thereby influencing the consumers' attachment to such a brand as they perceive such a brand to be friendly and have good intentions. Given this the following hypothesis is essential.

Hypothesis 22: Brand warmth moderates a favourable relationship between brand local

3.5.10 Brand warmth, brand positioning and brand performance

Brand warmth shows the belief that a brand has good intentions, although a brand's intention could be good or bad depending on customers' perspectives (Andrei & Zait, 2014; Wu et al., 2017). According to Aaker et al. (2010), the perception of a brand as warm corresponds to an increased willingness to purchase the products. This, in turn, can ultimately translate into increased consumer engagement, connection, and loyalty, all of which are cornerstones of brand building and measures for brand performance (Fournier, 1998; Fournier & Alvarez, 2012). It has been demonstrated that brand warmth is the major factor in consumer-brand identification, which in turn promotes purchase intentions and brand ownership and has significant management implications for positioning strategies (Fournier, 1998; Fournier & Alvarez, 2012).

According to the findings of a study conducted by Gao & Mattila (2014) on the mediating impacts of warmth and competence perceptions as the potential psychological mechanisms that explain consumers' reactions to green hotels, it was discovered that perceptions of warmth and competence mediated the relationships between service outcomes, consumer satisfaction, and behavioral intentions. The study was conducted to investigate the potential psychological mechanisms that explain consumers' reactions to green hotels.

Therefore, it is unsurprising that companies regularly attempt to influence these perceptions using positioning explicitly to improve the brand performance. Businesses are participating in CSR projects (such as donations or community service) in the hope of improving consumer impressions of warmth (Vaaland et al., 2008). Drawing on this discussion, brand warmth moderates brand positioning and brand performance. When a brand is perceived as friendly, true, and real, it is positioned in the market competition, thus increasing the brand performance.

Hypothesis 23: Brand warmth moderates a favourable relationship between brand positioning and brand performance

3.6 SUMMARY

This study presents great significance for a company, in the consideration of the importance of designing a suitable brand positioning that resonates with consumers' expectations. This study extensively examines the influence of a brand positioning on brand attachment and performance including whether or not consumers' favourable disposition towards the brand positioning translates to having a more positive attachment and brand performance of the company. This chapter offered a review of available literature on the brand positioning together

with a homogeneous perspective from varying fields to establish the conceptual framework demonstrated in Figure 3.1.

Based on the available literature, the study illustrated the connection between the brand positioning and its antecedents and discussed the consequences apparent. The relevant assumptions were summarized in Table 3:1 and demonstrated in Figure 3:1. The assumptions and conceptual framework illustrated the unique relationships between the study constructs in the integrative framework provided by the research. The analysis of this literature generated 23 hypotheses which can be further broken down into three categories. The chapter that follows defines the research design assumed for discourse and analysis by the study.

Table 3.1: List of research hypotheses based on the research questions

Question 1: What are the factors that influence brand positioning favourability?	
H1	Brand alliance fit has a favourable influence on brand positioning
H2a	Customer online engagement has a favourable influence on brand positioning
H2b	Brand trust has a favourable influence on brand positioning
H2c	Online review has a favourable influence on brand positioning
H2d	Brand relationship has a favourable influence on brand positioning
H2e	CSR has a favourable influence on brand positioning
H2f	Event has a favourable influence on brand positioning
Question 2: What is the main influence of brand positioning favourability on favourable brand attachment and favourable brand performance	
Question 3: What is the main influence of brand attachment favourability on favourable brand performance	
H3	Brand positioning has a favourable influence on brand authenticity
H4	Brand authenticity has a favourable influence on brand attachment
H5	
H6	Brand positioning has a favourable influence on local iconness
H7	Brand local iconness has a favourable influence on brand attachment
H8	
	Brand positioning has a favourable influence on brand performance

Brand attachment has a favourable influence on brand performance

Moderators

- H9** Brand identity moderates a favourable relationship between brand alliance fit and brand positioning
- H10** Brand identity moderates a favourable relationship between customer online engagement and brand positioning
- H11** Brand identity moderates a favourable relationship between brand trust and brand positioning
- H12** Brand identity moderates a favourable relationship between online review and brand positioning
- H13** Brand identity moderates a favourable relationship between brand relationship and brand positioning
- H14** Brand identity moderates a favourable relationship between CSR and brand
- H15** positioning
- H16** Brand identity moderates a favourable relationship between events and brand positioning
- H17** Brand awareness moderates a favourable relationship between brand positioning and brand authenticity
- H18** Brand awareness moderates a favourable relationship between brand positioning and brand local iconness
- H19** Brand competence moderates a favourable relationship between brand authenticity and brand attachment
- H20** Brand competence moderates a favourable relationship between brand local iconness and brand attachment
- Brand competence moderates a favourable relationship between brand positioning and brand performance

- | | |
|------------|--|
| H21 | Brand warmth moderates a favourable relationship between brand authenticity and brand attachment |
| H22 | Brand warmth moderates a favourable relationship between brand local iconness and brand attachment |
| H23 | Brand competence moderates a favourable relationship between brand positioning and brand performance |

CHAPTER IV: METHODOLOGY AND RESEARCH DESIGN

4.1 INTRODUCTION

This chapter aims to explain and defend the study design and methodological basis that were deployed to evaluate the hypotheses and operational model established in earlier chapters. For the sake of answering the research objectives and experimentally validating the model, this chapter is set up as follows: This section describes the study's research design and justifies the methodology choices in detail in Section 4.2. Section 4.3 describes the study's research strategy and data collecting methods. Sections 4.4 and 4.5 provide an overview of the exploratory fieldwork and the major survey and sampling. Sections 4.6 and 4.7 go through the specifics of the survey and questionnaire design. Section 4.8 discusses the data analysis methods and statistical software packages utilised in this study. A summary of the major ethical problems is presented in Section 4.9, which is followed by the conclusion in Section 4.10.

4.2 SELECTION OF RESEARCH APPROACH

The pluralism research approach was ideal for providing a more systematic method of gaining a deeper understanding of the problem described in Chapter 1. (Deshpande, 1983; Mingers, 2001). Mixed-method research, according to Foroudi et al. (2021), combines qualitative and quantitative data collection and analysis within a single study. Qualitative and quantitative designs can be obtained sequentially to confirm, corroborate, or cross-validate findings at any stage of the research process. Second, it is possible to identify four phases: initiation, before data collection (e.g., when the research problem, sample and measures are developed); implementation (sequence used by the researcher to collect both qualitative and quantitative data); integration (occurring within research questions, data collection, and analysis); and interpretation, which is the conclusion to support the knowledge claims of the study or provide explanation for any latent contradictions.

To increase the validity of the research, an inductive method was applied prior to the primary survey, and qualitative data were collected to establish hypotheses and refine questionnaire measures (Deshpande, 1983). This study employed techniques such as in-depth interviews with

firm managers, marketing executives, and owners in the Nigerian hospitality industry. Due to the lack of understanding of the notion 'brand positioning,' which necessitates a more in-depth definition, the qualitative research approach was predominantly utilized in this study. The primary survey and qualitative study were undertaken to gain a deeper understanding of brand positioning practice.

4.3 PHASE ONE - QUALITATIVE STUDY

A preliminary exploratory examination was conducted to establish the research. According to the knowledge of the author, no study has yet produced a credible scale for gauging brand positioning. As a result, this study opted to fill the void in this area and then employ Churchill's (1979) method to develop a suitable scale. Due to the following factors, the investigation commenced with an exploratory analysis: 1) to comprehend the research area (Foroudi et al., 2021). 2) Analyse current practice in the field to determine the relevance of the proposed research. 3) To obtain understanding of brand positioning, attachment, and performance. 4) Acquire practical knowledge, understand the proposed study topics, generate hypotheses, and refine questionnaire measures (Churchill, 1979; Foroudi et al., 2021). The planning, data management and interpretation of the qualitative phase is delineated in the next section.

4.3.1 Overview of the planning, management and data interpretation of the qualitative stage

The qualitative data were analysed using a coding strategy guided by a conceptual framework derived from the literature. Developing the codes required a unified understanding of brand positioning and its dimensions, antecedents, attachment, and performance principles. This sets the basis for data coding and analysis.

Initially, narrative coding was based on the literature review's identified constructs and open codes method. Miles & Huberman (1994) indicate that the initial list of codes should be based on the researcher's conceptual framework, list of research questions, hypotheses, issue areas, or critical variables.

The initial phase of data analysis consisted of the creation of open codes. The open codes were sorted and interpreted into advanced concepts prior to the development of the primary categories. The open code starts by line-by-line reading of text (interview transcripts). It

highlighted the sections where brand positioning, attachment, and performance relationships were discussed and coded to either the initial list or new open codes. The transcripts were thoroughly analysed twice in order to find literary trends in the texts. Each sentence was

compared to the preceding sentences and open codes to detect similarities and differences. If the codes were too dissimilar, the new sentence was assigned a separate label. The fundamental purpose of the opening code is to detect distinct or similar patterns in the texts relevant to the literature review. After open coding each interview transcript, the researcher reviewed the open codes and made additional comments and memos to strengthen the study. The axial code is generated as a result.

Version 8 of the QSR NVivo software was suitable for data administration and achieving outcomes to provide a comprehensive and refined interpretation and synthesis of the collected data.

4.3.2 Interview

To identify appropriate respondents for in-depth personal interviews and to justify the number of participants in the study, the researcher contacted reputable market research firms and consultancy agencies based in Nigeria with global clients via email and phone to identify appropriate candidates to contact regarding the research topic. The responders were provided with contact information and phone numbers and asked if they were interested in participating in the study. All 42 stakeholders contacted responded via emails or telephone, but 26 declined to participate in the study due to their busy schedules. Thus, 16 in-depth interviews were undertaken.

Due to the Coronavirus pandemic, the interviews took place over Zoom and WhatsApp. The average duration of the interviews, chosen by the interviewees, was one and a half hours. All interviews were taped and transcribed word-for-word to confirm their veracity (Foroudi et al., 2021). The approach to the in-depth interview was direct, semi-structured, intimate, and frank in order to determine the subject's beliefs, core motivation, sentiments, and attitude. A question sheet was developed to ensure that all areas of interest were covered during interviews (see Appendix I).

Table 4.1: Details of in-depth interviews with consultants and managers

Interview Date	Organisation	Interview position	Interview approx. duration
Hospitality setting consultants			
6.08.2021	Managers	Communication and Design Manager	100 min.
18.08. 2021	Lagos Continental	Manager of Customer Service and Human Relations	90 min.
18.08.2021	Radisson Blu	Manager/ Head of Marketing	30 min.
22.08.2021	Four Points	Managing Director	60 min.
26.08.2021	Federal Palace	Manager Public Relations	90 min.
01.09.2021	Federal Palace	Manager and Brand Design, Consultant	90 min.
06.09.2021	White Orchid Hotel	Manager	60 min.
06.09.2021	Village Lounge	Manager/Owner	95 min.
10.09.2021	Owu Crown	Manager and Brand Design, Consultant	85 min.
10.09.2021	The place	Manager	75 min.
06.10.2021	Diamond Hotel	Manager	70 min.
06.10.2021	Best Western Plus	Marketing Executive	80 min.
02.11.2021	Tee Exclusive	Owner	85 min.
04.11.2021	The Place	Marketing/Strategic Executive	70min.
05.11.2021	Banex Lounge	Brand Manager	80 min.
06.11.2021	Bashmol Center (Guest house)	Manager Public Relations/Marketing	90 min.
07.11.2021	Mama Cass Inn	Manager	78 min
Topics discussed			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The factors that influence brand positioning. - The main perceived impacts of brand positioning. - The understanding of brand positioning. - Their experience of what they understand the brand positioning and its influences on brand attachment and brand performance. 			

4.4 PHASE TWO - RESEARCH INSTRUMENT AND SCALE

This section aims to create a reliable and valid theoretical construct measurement by combining insights from the qualitative investigation and existing literature. Many items were created during the initial phase. Some items that were equivalent or similar were omitted for parsimony reasons. Some academics reviewed the items developed from the qualitative study, and any redundant measures were removed to ensure that the items were relevant. The following section explains how the information was included in the development of the questionnaire.

One hundred and forty items were initially generated in the item measurement sheet. The details of generated items are nine items related to the brand positioning, seven items related to online consumer engagement, six items related to brand trust, six items related to online review, seven related to brand relationship, nine items related to CSR, seven items related to events, seven items related to brand authenticity, nine items related to brand local iconness. twelve items related to brand attachment, thirty-four items related for brand performance elements, six items related to brand identity, nine items for awareness, and six items for brand warmth and six for competence (see Appendix I).

Table 4.2: The constructs and the number of initial items

Constructs	No. of initial item
Brand positioning	9
Customer online engagement	7
Brand trust	6
Online review	6
Brand relationship	7
CSR	9
Events	7
Brand authenticity	7
Brand local iconness	9
Cognitive	6
Conative	6
Loyalty	8
Attitude	6

Equity	7
Satisfaction	7
Reputation	6
Brand identity	6
Brand awareness	9
Brand warmth	6
Brand competence	6

The following main constructs and its measurements from the literature, and the qualitative study are illustrated in Appendix II (see also Chapters 2 and 3 for the literature review).

4.4.1 Validation of measurement scales

When analysing the content validity of the questionnaire's items, the first draft was examined by six faculty members in the marketing department at UWS who are specialists in the subject. They evaluated the content validity using standardized methods (Zaichkowsky, 1985; Foroudi et al., 2021). Their input was sought to gather feedback on the textual language employed and the products' suitability. Their feedback was taken into account. They were asked to assess the statements they deemed most crucial to retain (Foroudi et al.,2021).

Following changes to the questionnaire, four academics examined it for face validity and to ensure that the items in the questionnaire measured what they were intended to measure. The academics were asked to fill out the questionnaire and provide feedback on measuring the proposed construct effectively. Comments on the written language, structure, and competitiveness were also requested. The findings provided by the managers and consultants interviewed were compared to the items obtained from the literature. Three experts advised adopting the present tense to better capture the consumer's perception during the questionnaire; thus, the researcher incorporated the present tense into all statements.

Six items were removed after a content analysis by academics at the UWS Business School. As a result, before the pilot testing of the questionnaire, the pre-test items were validated for inclusion by eight academics and lexical correctness by four academics. The final measurement items are as elucidated in Table 4:11.

Table 4.3: Measurement items of the theoretical constructs and the codes

Construct	Items wording	Items codes#
Brand Positioning		
	Brand positioning with my hotel brand...	
	The brand has a tremendous promise	BPQ1
	The brand has strong competitors	BPQ2
	The brand has a unique product and service offering The brand offers different services than other brands.	BPQ3 BPQ4
	The feeling of using the brand's services is attractive to me The brand creates a unique image in my mind	BPQ5 BPQ6 BPQ7
	The company communicates a sense of superiority I have a favourable opinion of this brand	BPQ8 BPQ9
	This brand stands out for me	
Online consumer engagement		
	Online engagement with my hotel brand ...	
	I often participate in online customer-to-customer interactions for this brand	OE1
	I thoroughly enjoy exchanging ideas with other people online for this company/brand	OE2
	I am most likely to post about the service experience	OE3
	I pay a lot of attention to anything about the brand	OE4
	I would become a follower of the brand on social media	OE5
Construct	Items wording	Items codes#
	I consider a business that uses social media my top option	OE6
CSR		
	CSR with my hotel brand...	
	The brand is a good company	CSRQ1
	The brand cares about its consumers	CSRQ2
	This is very concerned with the local community	CSRQ3
	The brand is socially responsible	CSRQ4 CSRQ5
	The brand seems to be environmentally responsible	CSRQ6
	The brand always adheres to the law	CSRQ7
	The brand respect moral norms	CSRQ8
	The brand strives to avoid unethical behaviour	
Brand trust		
	Brand trust with my hotel brand...	
	The brand is reliable	BT1
	The brand meets my expectations.	BT2

	I feel confident in the brand name.	BT3
	The brand makes a conscious effort to maintain its promises to consumers.	BT4
	This brand never disappoints me	BT5
	Overall, I trust this brand	BT6
Online review		
	Online review with my hotel brand...	
	Information contained in the online review influences my decision towards a brand?	OR1
	When I experience excellent service from a brand, I leave a review online.	OR2
	The information I obtain from online reviews is sufficient to meet my needs.	OR3
	I put effort into evaluating the provided information	OR4
	The information I get from online reviews enables me to evaluate both the positive and negative elements of the services	OR5
	If I have a relevant suggestion for improving the service, I will communicate it to the company/brand via online platforms	OR6
Brand relationship		
	Brand relationship with my hotel brand...	
	My relationship with this brand is very important to me	BR1
	This brand means more to me than other brands	BR2
	This brand has a great deal of personal meaning for me	BR3
	This brand is like a person whom I am close to	BR4
	This brand and I complement each other	BR5
	This brand is a part of me	BR6
	This brand has grown in importance to me over time	BR7
Event		
	Events with my hotel brand...	
	I am in favour of the event	EVQ1
	I am pleased to live the experience	EVQ2
	The brand sponsorship or part of the event makes sense to me.	EVQ3
	I am satisfied with the event.	EVQ4
	I like the event	EVQ5
Construct	Items wording	Items codes#
	The event is attractive	EVQ6
Brand authenticity		
	Brand authenticity with my hotel brand...	
	My experiences of the brand have shown me that it keeps its promises	BAQ1

	The brand always sticks to its principles.	BAQ2
	The brand makes a genuine impression	BAQ3
	This brand is guided by sincere values.	BAQ4
	The brand remains true to its values.	BAQ5
	The brand obviously differentiates itself from others	BAQ6
	The brand wants to do its best at providing its service	BAQ7
Brand local iconness		
	Brand local iconness with my hotel brand...	
	To me, this brand represents what our culture is all about	BLIQ1
	This brand does not represent what our culture is all about	BLIQ2
	I associate this brand with things that are Nigerian	BLIQ3
	I do not associate this brand with things that are Nigerian	BLIQ4
	To me, this brand is a perfect symbol of Nigeria	BLIQ5
	To me, this brand is not a very good symbol of Nigeria	BLIQ6
	This brand means a lot to me, representing my culture	BLIQ7
	This brand helps me to identify my true self	BLIQ8
Brand attachment		
	Cognitive with my hotel brand...	
	I am very attached to the brand	COGQ1
	I feel better when I use this brand	COGQ2
	I feel a strong sense of belonging to the brand	GOGQ3
	This brand means a lot to me	GOGQ4
	I will continue to use this brand as long as it provides the best value for me	GOGQ5
	I feel emotionally bonded to this brand	GOGQ6
	Conative with my hotel brand...	
	I consider this brand to be my first choice	CONQ1
	I will speak about the brand to others	CONQ2
	I love using this brand	CONQ3
	I intend to remain a customer of the brand	CONQ4
	I have found this brand better than others	CONQ5
	I will keep on using the brand for a long time	CONQ6
Brand performance		

Construct	Items wording	Items codes#
	Brand loyalty with my hotel brand...	
	This brand will be my first option when choosing accommodation I believe that the features of the brand are well suited to what I like	LOYQ1
	My relationship with this brand is one I intend to maintain indefinitely	LOYQ2
	I would do almost anything to keep my relationship with this brand	LOYQ3
	My relationship with this brand is one I care a great deal about long-term	LOYQ4
		LOYQ5
	I would say good things about this brand to others.	
		LOYQ6
	Overall, I consider myself to be loyal to this brand	LOYQ7

	Brand attitude with my hotel brand...	
	I am proud to stay in this hotel/or use this brand	BRAQ1
	I can easily imagine the brand in my mind	BRAQ2
	I believe the brand has good serviceability	BRAQ3
	I evaluate the brand as positive	BRAQ4
	I evaluate the brand as good	BRAQ5
		BRAQ6
	I have a favourable opinion of this brand	BREQ1
		BREQ2
	Brand equity with my hotel brand...	
	This brand provides an authentic experience	BREQ3
	This brand offers high-quality services	BREQ4
	This brand offers good value for money	
		BREQ5
	Even if another brand has the same qualities, I will choose this one	BREQ6
	The likelihood that I would reconsider this brand is high	
	Overall, this brand has a significant positive image.	
		SATQ1
		SATQ2
		SATQ3
		SATQ4
		SATQ5
		SATQ6
		SATQ7
	Brand satisfaction with my hotel brand...	
	My choice to use this brand has been a wise one	
	I am more satisfied with this brand than other brands	
	I am satisfied with the brand service	
	The performance of this brand has fulfilled my expectations	
	I feel happy using this brand	
	I feel this has provided me with a pleasurable experience	
	Overall, I am pleased with this brand	BRPQ1
		BRPQ2
		BRPQ3
	Brand reputation with my hotel brand...	
	The brand has a good reputation for providing appropriate services	BRPQ4
	This brand is concerned about consumers	
	This brand constantly tries to improve its services to satisfy its consumers better	BRPQ5
	I think the brand has reliable promises for future performance	
		BRPQ6
	The brand's reputation influences my choices.	
	I believe this brand offers high-quality services	
Brand warmth and Competence		

	Brand warmth with my hotel brand...	
	I would describe the brand as warm	BRWQ1
	I would describe the brand as friendly	BRWQ2
	I would describe the brand as generous	BRWQ3
	I would describe the brand as good-natured	BRWQ4
	I find it easy to relate with the brand	BRWQ5
	I would describe the brand as kind	BRWQ6
	Brand competence with my hotel brand...	
	I would describe the brand as competent	BRCQ1
Construct	Items wording	Items codes#
	I would describe the brand as efficient	BRCQ2
	I would describe the brand as capable I would describe the brand as effective	BRCQ3
		BRCQ4
	I would describe the brand as intelligent	BRCQ5
	This brand is good with their work	BRCQ6
Brand identity and awareness		
	Brand identity with my hotel brand...	
	This brand stands out from its competitors	BIDQ1
	This brand has a distinctive identity	BIDQ2
	I am familiar with this brand	BIDQ3
	This brand is uniquely different from its competitors	BIDQ4
	This brand makes an effort to discover consumer needs	BIDQ5
	This brand is consistent over time	BIDQ6
	Brand awareness with my hotel brand...	
	The hotel and the services are familiar to me	BAWQ1
	The hotel and the services are well-known in detail	BAWQ2
	Characteristics of the brand come to my mind quickly	BAWQ3
		BAWQ4
	I can instantly differentiate the brand from other competing ones	BAWQ5
	I can recognise the brand logo or symbol	BAWQ6
	I can recognise this brand's name among other competitors	BAWQ7
	When I think of a service/product category, the brand is always at the top of my mind.	

Source: Developed for the current study by the researcher

4.4.1.1 Quantitative assessment: pilot study

The questionnaire was revised following the qualitative evaluation using exploratory research to evaluate the hypotheses. Necessary changes were made to the final survey using respondents' suggestions (Gupta et al., 2011) to determine whether the constructs are reliable, and the

measurement scales can evaluate validity via the pilot study (Saunders et al., 2007).

4.4.1.1.1 Pilot study

A pilot study (pre-test) is linked to the development of the final survey's questionnaire and measurement instrument (Malhotra & Birks, 2000). Questionnaires were distributed between October and November 2021, and by the deadline, 76 responses had been gathered. Due to the large quantity of missing data and the low quality of the responses, twenty-six surveys were eliminated. Fifty questionnaires were further analysed. Table 4.4 depicts the demographic profile of the pre-test sample of consumers, which is followed by a comprehensive questionnaire testing and piloting procedure.

According to Foroudi et al. (2021), the sample size for a pilot study should consist of between 20 and 40 participants in order to conduct a small-scale test of the survey's intended purpose, including all activities associated with the final survey. Participants in the pilot study were not invited to participate in the main survey because their participation in the pilot might have altered their responses (Malhotra & Birks, 2000).

Table 4.4: Demographic profile of consumers' pre-test sample (N=50)

Sample size (N)	N	%
Under 20 years		
20 to 29 years	8	16
30 to 39 years	31	62
40 to 49 years	8	16
Above 50	3	6
Total	50	100
Male	28	56
Female	22	44
Total	50	100
High school		
Bachelor		
Postgraduate and above	50	100
N/A		
Total	50	100
Students	42	84

	Tutors	8	16
	Total	50	100

Cronbach's alpha was used to determine whether a group of variables is appropriate for the proposed measure (Cronbach, 1951). With a Cronbach's alpha of 0.8 or more, the scale indicated a good level of reliability (Hair et al., 1998). The results of reliability testing, and factor analysis are presented in Table 4.5. Hair et al. (2006) noted that items with factor loadings below 0.4 are eligible for removal for low reliability. Table 4.5 further shows that all items in this survey instrument have item to total correlation above 0.5, as well as reliability greater than 0.4; thence, no item was eligible for removal from the survey instrument.

Table 4.5: Reliability measures for each construct on the basis of the pilot study

Constructs	Cronbach's Alpha	No of items	N	Items	Correlated item-total correlation	Mean	SD	EFA Loading
Brand positioning	0.940	9	50					
				BPQ1	.770	4.40	1.678	.679
				BPQ2	.816	4.20	1.552	.675
				BPQ3	.728	4.66	1.507	.616
				BPQ4	.721	4.94	.956	.604
				BPQ5	.780	4.40	1.457	.687
				BPQ6	.822	4.72	1.213	.754
				BPQ7	.851	4.42	1.472	.795
				BPQ8	.876	4.44	1.445	.829
				BPQ9	.859	4.28	1.429	.796
Brand Authenticity	0.935	7	50					
				BAQ1	.756	4.66	1.334	.667
				BAQ2	.821	4.30	1.607	.759
				BAQ3	.847	4.72	1.371	.804
				BAQ4	.864	4.54	1.474	.828
				BAQ5	.882	4.52	1.474	.855

				BAQ6	.834	4.46	1.501	.791
				BAQ7	.820	4.88	1.239	.762
Brand local iconness	0.920	8	50					
				BLIQ1	.559	4.38	1.469	.692
				BLIQ2	.799	4.20	1.654	.837
				BLIQ3	.724	3.92	1.748	.734
				BLIQ4	.789	4.12	1.560	.834
				BLIQ5	.829	3.98	1.505	.817
				BLIQ6	.739	4.04	1.525	.877

Constructs	Cronbach's Alpha	No of items	N	Items	Correlated item-total correlation	Mean	SD	EFA Loading
				BLIQ7	.675	4.00	1.616	.721
				BLIQ8	.766	4.14	1.512	.869
Online engagement	0.856	6	50					
				OE1	.841	4.14	1.552	.793
				OE2	.856	4.20	1.370	.810
				OE3	.886	4.00	1.604	.854
				OE4	.819	3.96	1.470	.765
				OE5	.842	4.06	1.531	.795
				OE6	.891	4.06	1.434	.857
Brand trust	0.902	6	50					
				BT1	.850	4.22	1.404	.799
				BT2	.747	4.22	1.418	.704
				BT3	.600	4.30	1.474	.495

				BT4	.805	4.68	1.435	.775
				BT5	.634	4.84	.842	.545
				BT6	.823	4.42	1.458	.788
Online review	0.932	6	50					
				OR1	.704	4.66	1.099	.622
				OR2	.822	4.38	1.441	.784
				OR3	.891	4.40	1.429	.871
				OR4	.894	4.14	1.457	.869
				OR5	.790	4.56	1.215	.717
				OR6	.740	4.22	1.632	.666
Brand relationship	0.893	7	50					

Constructs	Cronbach's Alpha	No of items	N	Items	Correlated item-total correlation	Mean	SD	EFA Loading
				BR1	.745	4.64	1.382	.811
				BR2	.771	4.46	1.281	.885
				BR3	.816	4.50	1.474	.934
				BR4	.789	4.42	1.401	.874
				BR5	.604	4.94	1.268	.731
				BR6	.617	4.60	1.443	.731
				BR7	.546	4.34	1.686	.796
CSR	0.924	8	50					
				CSRQ1	.744	4.04	1.829	.650
				CSRQ2	.766	4.36	1.638	.740
				CSRQ3	.871	4.20	1.702	.862
				CSRQ4	.802	4.10	1.632	.849

				CSRQ5	.798	4.04	1.761	.751
				CSRQ6	.840	4.16	1.608	.847
				CSRQ7	.537	4.10	1.488	.886
				CSRQ8	.584	4.26	1.411	.886
Event	0.951	6	50					
				EvQ1	.759	3.98	1.635	.686
				EvQ2	.882	4.04	1.641	.850
				EvQ3	.885	4.08	1.627	.852
				EvQ4	.904	4.16	1.658	.876
				EvQ5	.882	4.32	1.491	.847
				EvQ6	.788	4.48	1.619	.727
Cognitive	0.901	6	50					
				CogQ1	.706	4.18	1.508	.639
				CogQ2	.717	4.52	1.488	.657

Constructs	Cronbach's Alpha	No of items	N	Items	Correlated item-total correlation	Mean	SD	EFA Loading
				CogQ3	.744	4.90	1.182	.688
				CogQ4	.756	4.42	1.500	.697
				CogQ5	.749	4.56	1.248	.698
				CogQ6	.741	4.24	1.364	.676
Conative	0.937	6	50					
				ConQ1	.875	4.42	1.401	.846
				ConQ2	.863	4.26	1.382	.831
				ConQ3	.805	4.60	1.161	.750
				ConQ4	.798	4.28	1.552	.741

				ConQ5	.750	4.68	1.316	.672
				ConQ6	.810	4.48	1.313	.757
Loyalty	0.847	7	50					
				LoyQ1	.535	4.32	1.362	.928
				LoyQ2	.486	4.16	1.235	.934
				LoyQ3	.592	4.62	1.159	.746
				LoyQ4	.579	4.44	1.296	.529
				LoyQ5	.706	4.18	1.494	.817
				LoyQ6	.658	3.76	1.408	.613
				LoyQ7	.775	4.08	1.426	.838
Brand attitude	0.913	6	50					
				BraQ1	.875	4.20	1.807	.891
				BraQ2	.804	4.16	1.765	.866
				BraQ3	.799	4.12	1.814	.798
				BraQ4	.769	4.38	1.772	.824
				BraQ5	.634	4.28	1.691	.912
				BraQ6	.653	4.30	1.542	.914

Constructs	Cronbach's Alpha	No of items	N	Items	Correlated item-total correlation	Mean	SD	EFA Loading
Brand equity	0.957	6	50					
				BreQ1	.851	4.06	1.707	.807
				BreQ2	.877	4.06	1.634	.840
				BreQ3	.884	4.10	1.669	.849
				BreQ4	.910	4.28	1.666	.885
				BreQ5	.921	4.22	1.475	.898

				BreQ6	.755	4.38	1.524	.678
Satisfaction	0.930	7	50					
				SatQ1	.743	4.30	1.555	.666
				SatQ2	.657	4.68	1.421	.549
				SatQ3	.728	5.00	1.030	.640
				SatQ4	.831	4.46	1.501	.773
				SatQ5	.851	4.76	1.205	.808
				SatQ6	.808	4.44	1.487	.746
				SatQ7	.866	4.40	1.414	.826
Brand reputation	0.947	6	50					
				BrpQ1	.858	4.54	1.705	.816
				BrpQ2	.805	4.68	1.253	.739
				BrpQ3	.830	4.42	1.691	.778
				BrpQ4	.840	4.72	1.429	.798
				BrpQ5	.854	4.50	1.474	.814
				BrpQ6	.872	4.42	1.401	.838
Brand Identity	0.905	6	50					
				BidQ1	.781	4.44	1.580	.768

Constructs	Cronbach's Alpha	No of items	N	Items	Correlated item-total correlation	Mean	SD	EFA Loading
				BidQ2	.692	4.90	1.282	.622
				BidQ3	.712	4.58	1.486	.644
				BidQ4	.826	4.38	1.748	.801
				BidQ5	.810	3.98	1.778	.761
				BidQ6	.839	4.26	1.575	.811
Brand awareness	0.914	7	50					
				BawQ1	.799	4.16	1.621	.874
				BawQ2	.746	4.14	1.678	.878
				BawQ3	.760	4.08	1.794	.789
				BawQ4	.781	4.16	1.570	.900
				BawQ5	.676	4.26	1.575	.906
				BawQ6	.693	4.20	1.443	.885
				BawQ7	.717	4.08	1.700	.928
Brand warmth	0.950	6	50					
				BrwQ1	.874	4.16	1.765	.842
				BrwQ2	.873	4.16	1.719	.839
				BrwQ3	.899	4.12	1.649	.873
				BrwQ4	.905	4.22	1.418	.877
				BrwQ5	.783	4.24	1.779	.719
				BrwQ6	.779	4.50	1.374	.705
Brand competence	0.935	6	50					
				BrcQ1	.884	4.36	1.638	.864
				BrcQ2	.637	4.38	1.563	.531

				BrcQ3	.804	4.66	1.479	.758
				BrcQ4	.807	4.16	1.595	.752
Constructs	Cronbach's Alpha	No of items	N	Items	Correlated item-total correlation	Mean	SD	EFA Loading
				BrcQ5	.831	4.60	1.414	.780
				BrcQ6	.892	4.36	1.601	.872

Source: Analysis of survey data (SPSS file)

4.5 MAIN SURVEY

This study used a self-administered questionnaire to collect data for the primary survey from the consumers of the hospitality sector between 19th December 2021 and 28th of March 2022. This study employed a non-random sampling technique known as convenience sampling (Foroudi et al., 2021). The sample size and sampling procedure are detailed in the following section:

4.5.1 Sample size

Roscoe (1975) suggested some rules of thumb for selecting appropriate sample sizes in behavioural research investigations based on acceptable levels of confidence: 1) If the research study involves more than one group (such as males and females), each group must have more than 30 participants. 2) For most investigations, sample sizes between 30 and 500 are optimal. 3) The optimal sample size for a simple experiment should consist of 10 to 20 people. One thousand as excellent, five hundred as very good, three hundred as good, two hundred as fair, one hundred as poor, and fifty as very poor. 4) The sample size for multivariate analysis should be at least ten times the number of variables included in the study. Stevens (1996) suggested fifteen cases per construct for dependable results. However, five instances per parameter are adequate if the data are normally distributed (Bentler & Chou, 1987).

Following these observations, there is no accurate or absolute sample size limit in the methodological literature. This study utilized at least five observations per estimate parameter (Foroudi et al., 2021). As an empirical ratio, commonalities with ratios greater than 0.5 have also been proposed (Hair et al., 2006). Taking these into account, there were a total of 365 questionnaires collected for this research; 22 were discarded owing to extensive item non-response. Following exhaustive efforts to enhance the response rate, 343 usable, completed questionnaires were received and analysed.

4.6 QUESTIONNAIRE DESIGN

This section describes the key design of the survey questionnaire used in this study. The questionnaire is divided into four parts. The first section covers the research problem. It describes the purpose of the research and the scale utilised in the questionnaire. It indicated how much time was required to complete the questionnaire and privacy statement. The second part of the research questionnaire is concerned with the survey respondents' personal information. Questions regarding the survey respondents' demography, such as gender, age group, education, job position, and experience, are included in the second part of this survey questionnaire. The third part of the questionnaire is concerned with the brands in the hospitality sectors and all the respondents asked to pick from the most favourable.

4.7 DATA ANALYSIS TECHNIQUES

The data were analysed in three different ways to eliminate outliers and identify any patterns. Exploratory factor analysis (EFA) was utilized in both the pilot study and the larger study (Ong & Puteh, 2017; Foroudi et al., 2021). Confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) was conducted on the primary research survey dataset for assessing the measurements property of existing scale's validity (Garaika et al., 2019); this has been useful if the scale needs as a construct to additional examinations in the structural model and to apply in confirming the theories of the latent variable (Hair et al., 1998).

Structure equation modeling (SEM) was investigated for assessing hypothesis relationships (Hair et al., 2006) and establishing potential structural model-measurement links. Prior data analysis, some preliminary steps were taken, such as: data modification, verification, and coding to help identify missing data; Checking the linearity, multicollinearity, outliers, and normalcy assumptions. Analysis of Moment Structure (AMOS) 16.0, a novel graphical interface, was utilized to analyse the proposed measurement model and the hypothesized structural model.

4.7.1 Coefficient alpha with exploratory factor analysis (EFA)

Exploratory factor analysis (EFA) is an essential and useful technique in the initial phases of scale validity (Foroudi et al., 2021). EFA is a data-driven strategy that use a practical scale to decrease the number of observed variables (indicators) to a more manageable level (Anderson & Gerbing, 1988; Hair et al., 1998). Principal components method was utilized for factor extraction (Hair et al., 2006; Ong & Puteh, 2017). This method was used to estimate the fewest variables necessary to explain the greatest amount of variation (i.e., common, unique, and error variances).

This study employed an orthogonal Varimax rotation strategy to reduce the number of variables

to a more manageable subset of uncorrelated variables of greater quality. These variables are subsequently employed in the subsequent forecasting procedure (Hair et al., 1998). Eigen values were utilized by Hair et al. (1998) and Nunnally & Bernstein (1994) to determine the number of components to be extracted (Eigen value > 1.00).

4.7.2 Structural equations modelling (SEM)

This study used structural equation modeling (SEM) with the Amos software package to disentangle linkages for each dependent variable in order to gain insight into the multiple impacts and connections (Hair et al., 2006). The conceptual framework was confirmed by studying the literature and then testing the hypotheses using a structural equation model.

4.7.3 Assessing Model Fit

There is complete control over the description of a construct's variables in CFA, which enables a statistical evaluation of dimensionality and goodness-of-fit for the specific measurement design (Hair et al., 1998). As stated in the CFA methodological literature, the absolute fit indices, incremental fit indices, and indices of model parsimony were utilized in this research and will be described in greater detail below.

First, this study included both incremental and absolute fit indices. Both the measurement model and the structural model as a whole were analysed using the absolute fit indices (Hair et al., 1998). Absolute fit indices reveal how well the proposed model reproduces the data sample. Goodness-of-fit indices were utilized to analyse the nomological validity of measurement models. Absolute fit indices do not leverage a different model as a comparison point. The selected fit indices are described in detail below:

(i) Chi-square is the most prevalent approach for evaluating model fit. Chi-square statistics is the initial fit metric given in the Amos output. The chi-square test is used to compare real and predicted matrices, with non-significance indicating that there is no significant difference between actual and predicted matrices. Regarding the goodness-of-fit of a model, p-values indicate if the model differs significantly from the null model. Typically, in statistics, the null value is 0. A value greater than zero or a high p-value (< .05) would result in rejecting the null hypothesis with a high chance of error (MacLean & Gray, 1998). The difference between the two matrices should not differ significantly ($p > .05$). When chi-square is extremely sensitive to sample size, Hair et al. (2006) and Tabachnick & Fidell (2007) criticize the use of this fit to determine the model's overall goodness-of-fit.

(ii) Joreskog & Sorbom (1982) developed the goodness-of-fit index (GFI) as the initial measure of the model to generate a fit statistic that is less susceptible to sample size. The GFI determines

the variance and covariance proportions in the sample covariance matrix, which is defined by the population covariance matrix. Less-than-0.8 GFI should be discarded (Tanaka & Huba, 1985).

(iii) The adjusted goodness-of-fit Index (AGFI) is useful for comparing competing models and is calculated by adjusting the model's degrees of freedom to the null model's degrees of freedom (Hair et al., 1998). The GFI and AGFI are independent degrees of freedom calculations based on the chi-square statistic. AGFI modifies the GFI according to the degree of freedom, resulting in decreased values for models with more parameters. AGFI equates to GFI by substituting the mean sum of squares for the total sum of squares. The adjusted goodness-of-fit index must be more than 0.90 to show a satisfactory fit (Bentler & Bonett, 1980).

(iv) The root-mean-square error of approximation (RMSEA) is an exceptionally informative criterion for assessing model fit. The RMSEA index is sensitive to the number of parameters and quantifies the difference between the sample and fitted covariance matrices per degree of freedom (Steiger, 1990). RMSEA evaluates the disparity in relation to the population, not the sample. Bentler-Bonett index or normed fit index (NFI) compares layered models (Ong & Puteh, 2017). NFI compares the model to the suggested model without taking the degree of freedom into account.

The comparative fit index (CFI) is directly derived from the metric of non-centrality. If the index value is larger than one, it is set to one; otherwise, it is put to zero. A CFI near to one is deemed to be a good match (Bentler, 1990). If the average relationship between variables is weak, the CFI will also be weak. The Tucker-Lewis index (TLI), also known as a non-normed fit index (NNFI), compares the 2 values of the model to that of the independence model and takes into account the degrees of freedom for both models (Byrne, 2001; Tabachnick & Fidell, 2007). TLI is an example of a parsimony-adjusted index, although that was not its original goal.

4.7.4 Average variance extracted (AVE) assessment

The average extracted variance (AVE) is an estimate of the common variance in a latent variable (LV) that compares the variation collected by the latent variable with random measurement error variance (Foroudi et al., 2021). The average variance extracted (AVE) must be greater than or equal to 0.50 for the idea to be justified and to ensure scale validity. The AVE compares the amount of variation recorded by indicators to measurement error (Hair et al., 1998).

4.7.5 Nomological validity

Nomological validity relates to Churchill's (1986) suggestion that the measure should act as

anticipated and analyses whether constructs perform theoretically and empirically as expected. The measurement models' nomological validity is tested using the goodness-of-fit indices (Steenkamp & Trijp, 1991).

4.7.6 Discriminant validity

Malhotra and Birks (2000) defined discriminant validity as the extent to which measurements of one concept are not predominantly related to measurements of other constructs. The fact that the correlation between two constructs is significantly less than 1.00 demonstrates the presence of discriminant validity (Anderson & Gerbing, 1982).

4.8 ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS

The ethics of academic research must be considered throughout the research process. These were developed based on the UWS ethics form and the British Educational Research Association's standards (2004). A fundamental understanding of ethical research and how it impacts the study is essential. There are a number of ethical issues shared by all business and social researchers (Foroudi et al., 2021). Researchers must acceptably conduct their study according to a relevant and particular topic.

The fundamental concerns are distilled down to only five elements in this research. First, subjects have the right to protect the statutory rights of social investigation groups by avoiding unnecessary interruption, seeking consent from those being investigated, and respecting the groups' privacy. Second, the ethical conduct of the research must objectively address the research questions. The third consideration is to be socially and culturally diverse. Fourth, providing complete information about the methodologies fosters public trust in their reliability. Fifth, questionnaires invariably disrupt people's privacy, and consideration is reflected in the covering letter (see Appendix III). There were no interviews that were not recorded unless a participant objected. Given this, UWS Business School approved this study's conduct.

4.9 SUMMARY

This chapter discussed the study's perspective, methodology, and approach for testing the hypotheses and operational model presented in Chapter 3. Different techniques were used to increase the reliability of the results. For the purposes of this study, a brand positioning measurement scale based on Churchill's (1979) paradigm was developed. Qualitative methodologies were applied (first phase) to understand consumer perceptions of the brand positioning further.

A questionnaire was created based on the results of the qualitative research (interviews). To verify the validity and reliability of the research instrument, a pilot study involving Fifty

academics was conducted. The respondents' perceptions of brand positioning were recorded using a seven-point Likert scale, and the degree of agreement or disagreement was specified. The quantitative research (second phase) included 343 consumers from five hotels who completed a self-administered questionnaire. The item measurement survey was developed using the stages of content and operational-item relevance to the study' objective along with layout management and appropriate language. The data was obtained employing an online tool of Google Form, the research questionnaire was ready, and the link to this research questionnaire was shared among the universities' relevant stakeholders through various online platforms. Collection of data problems such as the unit of analysis, the creation of a survey instrument, and data analysis methods such as exploratory factor analysis, confirmatory factor analysis, and structural equation modelling have all been addressed in detail.

CHAPTER V: QUALITATIVE FINDINGS

5.1 INTRODUCTION

This research is intended and structured to garner information exhaustively in a bid to facilitate the understanding of the influence of brand positioning on brand attachment and brand performance from the consumers' perception in the context of a hospitality setting. In this vein, the qualitative findings are based on the survey of the hotel managers. The qualitative study results are presented in Section 5.2.

5.2 RESULTS OF THE QUALITATIVE STUDY

This section is an organised report of the findings and presentation of the data supporting the developing arguments of the current research on the influence of brand positioning on brand attachment and brand performance. The content analysis presented has identified seven antecedents of brand positioning, three consequences of brand positioning, and five moderators of brand positioning. These elements were highlighted in this thesis. For instance, brand alliance fit as an antecedent to positioning discussed by researchers (Kim & Lee, 2007; Tasci & Denizci-Guillet, 2011).

5.3 BRAND POSITIONING

The new marketplace environment exposes consumers to a vast amount of information. Findings from the qualitative study showed that brand positioning is important in business. The interviewees have an understanding of what brand positioning means and how it is beneficial to their company. The following ‘‘comments’’ show the comments from CEOs of the companies:

‘‘I think that brand positioning is how this company is placed in the market of the hospitality industry. I mean how we stand out as a hotel. There are many hotels here in Lagos and we position our brand such that customers will easily recognise us among our competitors....’’ (SU)

‘‘...for me brand positioning is essential. It makes your business stand out among others and customers will easily remember to come to your hotel. In this company we sell some special local delicacies that customers like, when they want to eat such thing, they come here because we do the best of it. What I want to say is that if customers can remember your brand and easily access you, it is beneficial to the business you know....’’ (AR)

The comments from the interviewees showed that the CEOs apply different strategies to their

companies to ensure that they remain relevant in the industry.

“...in this company, we try to make sure that we do things that can help our hotel. Things that can attract customers to our hotel. Sometimes it is not easy because we are many doing the business. But we have always known that our services are necessary for a human being so it depends on us to do things that will bring customers our way. One of the things we do is that we organize show like all night fuji music free, but when they come, they buy something from us. Another one is that we subscribe to live matches and football fans would come and watch for free, but they have to buy something....” (AR)

And they believe that adequate communication with the customers increases their brand positioning.

5.3.1 Antecedents to Brand positioning

Certain elements prelude positioning; in other words, there are certain factors recognised in brand management literature and practice that precede the occurrence of positioning. These factors were evaluated in the survey and the results are documented in successive sub-section:

5.3.1.1 Brand alliance fit

Brand alliance has proven to be an effective strategy for a number of brands. According to the evidence in these examples, the most common form of hotel co-branding has thus far been with restaurants. This sort of co-branding can be defined as a homo-brand extension in which the brands involved are in a similar product category (Guillet & Tasci, 2010) – that is, both brands are hospitality sector operators. Strategic brand alliances for hotels, on the other hand, do not have to be confined to restaurants. Numerous other innovative partners are available to hotels, including retail businesses, spas, celebrities, and so on. (Guillet & Tasci, 2012).

However, this contradicts what was found in this study. Apparently, the CEOs of the hotels reacted that they do not practice brand alliance in Nigeria. And so, it was difficult to relate the benefits to their businesses.

“...I have not seen it here in Nigeria and I am not going to do it because I don't know much about this. What is common here is that a hotel is a hotel, a restaurant is a restaurant. Here we have only a hotel because we know our target audience and want to do everything that will get us to them ...” (SG)

5.3.1.2 Branding positioning success

On the multipliers of brand positioning success, participants disclosed that brand positioning success was achieved not solely by having or delivering good products or services but by a combination of success strategies including (brand trust, online engagement, online reviews, brand relationship, events and CSR) platforms (in agreement with Harrigan et al., 2018; Rose et al., 2016; Yang & Tan, 2017; Karaosmanoglu et al., 2016). According to the hoteliers and stakeholders, globalisation and digitalisation specifically had helped in skyrocketing their branding success but also came with its disadvantages of managing the formulation and spread of wrong information, the wide access to both good and bad reviews, and so on.

5.3.1.2.1 Consumer online engagement

All participants emphasized the importance of online engagement. In their perspective, social electronic media has been immeasurably beneficial in asserting their brands' image and situating their brands' position.

With the provision of the online platform, we can channel our customer online behaviour to strengthen our brand positioning with what we put out. We try to appeal to the customers and to trends moderately. We use the engagement platform as our source of information to see what other brands in the same industry are doing and what customers are saying about them, then we do things as befitting and differently as possible so we can create our position. (SU)

Customers' online behaviour is a bank of information for us and for prospective customers. So as a brand, we present ourselves the way we want to be talked about by our customers so that prospective customers are aware of us and we are positioned rightly in the space. (AE)

The managers recognise the effect of managing customer online behaviour on their positioning and they understand the implication of using it to their advantage. Their acknowledgment matches the opinion shared by researchers like Chu & Kim (2011), Brexendorf et al. (2015), and Perera et al. (2020) who proposed that ongoing interactions with consumers are becoming imperative to influence repurchase, and organisations' exploration and understanding of online consumer engagement can improve brand positioning and consumer preferences.

Some participants, however, disagreed that a brand's identity can be of influence to customer online behaviour, giving the reason that customers engage with any engaging post, whether it is from a known or unknown brand, a controversial or uncontroversial brand, or a consistent or inconsistent brand. Some gave examples of brands that have a not-very-structured identity but have a strong online presence. Contrariwise, other participants insisted that a brand's identity

influences the customer's online behaviour because it determines whatever content customers put out about the brand.

I'm strong of the opinion that whatever my brand puts out there will determine customers' reactions. It's a cause-and-effect type of thing. If we communicate inconsistency, we get a reaction; if we communicate consistency, we get a reaction as well (RAS).

5.3.1.2.2 Brand trust

The importance of brand trust in establishing loyalty cannot be overstated. The findings from this study showed that managers and CEOs understood the importance of brand trust and try to ensure that their customers trust them, although from their answers they did not state that brand trust determines customers' loyalty. Some of the responses include:

.... Trust is something that is important in this our business oh. Hmm, if the news should just report that someone died in this hotel or someone was killed in this hotel, hmmm

'wahala'. That is it for us oh. We will lose our customers and they will lose their trust in us. And you know that losing customers' trust is one bad thing that can happen to any business. Here we try to be careful and do things the way they should be (SU).

.... communicating to our customers is usually through our social media channels. And when they come here. Usually, when any customer complains of anything that will attract violence of social media dragging, I as the manager attend to them directly, ensuring them that it will never happen again. In some cases, we refund their money to money. Just to avoid trouble and ensure that they trust the services we render... (AE).

Management and marketing primarily correlate trust with the relationship's competence dimension, which focuses on the partner's belief that they have the requisite abilities to carry out their activities, fulfil their obligations, or keep their promises (Mayer et al., 1995; Morgan & Hunt, 1994). According to Jin et al. (2015), trust develops as a result of an individual's inclination to trust, institutional-based trust, and cognitive processes of trusting intention and trusting beliefs which communication helps to build.

.... If the customers, your customers trust your brand, they will believe you and always remember you to buy your products. Trust is everything a business needs to gain lasting customers. But you know that gaining trust is not easy, but people in the business, we use every opportunity to ensure that our customers trust us. Yes, brand trust affects the position of the brand in the market ... (AE)

From the findings, the interviewees believed that brand trust influences brand positioning. From the comments above, the interviewee attested that “brand trust affects the position of the brand in the market”. This is in line with the hypothesis of this study, that brand trust influences brand positioning because trust determines loyalty, which is an improved perception about a brand. Consumer-brand connections can be cultivated by continued interaction and activity on various social media platforms, resulting in feelings of brand trust, loyalty, and repurchase intention (Hajli et al., 2017; Wong & Haque, 2021).

5.3.1.2.3 Online review

A wealth of research has documented the benefits of online review (Litvin et al., 2008; Srivastava & Sivaramakrishnan, 2020). Participants, customers, and managers alike described the tool as a viable one for getting information about a brand and the services offered. Over two-thirds of the managers stated that they carried out their online reviews in a questionnaire format. In addition, some said they also had a review section on their website and a handful said they used the poll available on most social media platforms.

When asked about the extent to which they thought online reviews could influence brand positioning, their responses were similar:

There’s nothing that online reviews cannot do for and to your brand. Online review can greatly position and RE-position your brand. (SG)

There’s nothing that online reviews cannot do for and to your brand. Online review can greatly position and RE-position your brand. (SG).

I think online review can position your brand and affect how your brand is viewed. It can determine the perception people have about your products and services, especially because it’s out there for the whole world to see. It can affect your positioning, your performance, your profit, your image, and the inflow of new customers. (KA).

The participants also added that they perceived that their brand’s identity has a strong influence on the online reviews they get, just as what their brand is communicating also impacts online review.

5.3.1.2.4 Brand relationship

A brand's relationship with consumers is significant in a rapidly changing service marketing environment. The comments from the respondents showed that communication is a central force to building brand relationships:

.... Very well. Yes, sometimes we offer subsidised prices for some local foods that we sell. Like during the Christmas season, we customise gifts and give them out to customers. We are trying to ensure that our customer relates with us. Our waiters are trained to smile and be of help to customers where necessary, we encourage them to do that and that is what we do... (AE)

Developing a strong relationship with consumers "is increasingly emerging as a strategy for organisations that strive to retain loyal and satisfied consumers in today's highly competitive environment" (Meng & Elliott, 2008, p. 509).

5.3.1.2.5 CSR

CSR was also considered an important multiplier of brand success. For the managers, they found that it impacted the brand's awareness and a psychological or emotional impact on customers who have praised their various CSR-related activities.

So, we have this thing we do. We organise masterclasses for 20 aspiring chefs. So far, it has given us so much recognition and has positioned us as a brand that is sustainable and gives back to the community. How we know this is that we have got sponsorship for it from some of our customers. So yes, CSR is a vital positioning activity. (AE).

The responses garnered about CSR are in agreement with the literature (Akbari et al., 2020; Al-Msallam, 2015) that it is a favourable activity for successful positioning.

5.3.1.2.6 Events

Findings from the textual analysis of the interviews indicate that events, whether owned or sponsored, are relevant to promoting a brand through favourable positioning or by shaping the perception of the customers. The following comments illustrate the manager's assessment of this source of the finding:

...well, our industry, the hotel industry, in this part of the world, we are hardly a firsthand event industry, only on rare occasions. Some of us, I mean other hotel managers, we do more of associating in form of sponsorship by letting out our space to organisers of events for use. So yes, when we see a good opportunity by a third party, like these seasonal events, we grab it because, over time, it has been favourable in shaping the perception of our brand in the minds of our customers and prospective customers, especially when they have great customer experience because it is like a form of advertisement..." (SU).

...we do it as often as our yearly allocation permits. Sometimes, it's our event, like giveaways or discounted meals; other times we partner with other brands. We have a yearly budget and a consultant for it because we've seen its importance. Since we started about two years ago, so far, we have gotten good feedback and unsurprising expansion. We have expanded our customer numbers, our menu, our profit, our branches, everything. Some of our customers even look out for the events annually. It also came with acceptance and recognition as a luxury place (RAS).

Event is a big deal for us; our biggest times here are during events, those are the times we attract a large profitable crowd. Over the years, the crowd has grown, and we have a good spot in the hotel space and with our customers. It has given us a fair chance against the tough competition (KA).

The quotations above are reflective of the general responses and consistent with research by authors Luonila (2016), Rowley & Williams (2008), and Meenaghan et al. (2013), who posited that commercial sponsorship of events is now acknowledged as an effective marketing tactic for firms, and with Astous & Bitz (1995) who highlighted brand positioning, awareness, image, and sales as immediate commercial sponsorship benefits. The quotations also suggest that event acts as a form of active advertisement and a tool for enhancing competitiveness (Getz & Page, 2016; Mariani & Giorgio, 2017), which corroborates Liu et al. (2018) who described it as a customer-engaging communication tool, as opposed to the customary or conventional way of advertisement. The responses are also imperative of strong equity, validating researchers' opinion of meaningful brand equity (Miller & Washington 2012; Shin et al., 2018).

On the connection between identity and event, a hotelier stated:

... I think, considering my brand, the hotel I manage, I think that the identity of the brand has strong influence on the events we headline or sponsor and vice versa...How do people see us? What do they think about when they hear our name? What do they know about us? We think of these things and then we open our doors to promotional events. Sometimes, it's our event, sometimes, it's event that we host. It is a way we know we can build our identity and promote our brand. The strength of your identity will determine how the event will go, if there'll be one in the first place (KA)

The response affirms Javalgi et al. (1994) whose research demonstrated that sponsorship positively impacts the image of the sponsoring company. Participants also agreed that their identity determined if they should engage in an event and what event they can associate with.

According to them, any event that contravenes their image and values is usually turned down.

I think how people see your brand will determine if they will come to you to collaborate on an event. I mean, imagine managing an unpopular brand....or a brand associated with controversies....or a brand that has many scandals...

Also, I mean, imagine what your brand stands for is contrary to the theme or objectives of the events, you don't do that. This hotel is a luxury hotel, so we don't jump on any event just like that (CB)

5.3.2 Consequences of Brand positioning

The positioning of any brand is unavoidably trailed by consequences based on the success of the positioning strategies. The research was conducted with this in perspective and certain consequences were evaluated.

5.3.2.1 Brand authenticity

In this survey, participants widely acknowledge that a brand's authenticity is the realness of the brand. They stated that they only patronise a brand because they are assured of its consistency. So, according to the managers, customers patronise brands they can trust, especially those they can rely on to sort out or manage any bad service experienced.

...as a manager myself, if I have to use any brand, it has to be one I'm sure they're reliable, genuine and authentic. So, when customers visit my place especially on their special occasions like their weddings, birthdays, and such, I know it's because we resonate with them. I have customers who reside abroad, but when they come to Nigeria, they stop by because they trust our service, our sincerity, our consistency... (DL)

...you know, I think, perhaps, the average customer has access to the internet, they can monitor you, or observe your company. They are watching you and how you present your company. The people who come here, our customers, they don't come just because we're one of the best, they have kept an eye on us, they know what we stand for, our services, our credibility, our values, our core values, our consistency. They come for a real and authentic experience. So, we invest in authenticity because it's relevant. The hospitality business is a business of originality, authenticity. Imagine eating from a place you don't trust or you don't connect with, especially as food is [a] sensitive good. (AE).

...the climate here, it's not easy, it's not encouraging to maintain authenticity, even though it is important. As a hotel manager, I can tell you, we try our best, we try to be reliable; when we put something out, maybe on social media or anywhere, we try to make sure they are relatable, and that we deliver the promised service; maybe it's a 5/10. (CB).

The responses affirm the importance linked to authenticity by researchers. For instance, the managers confirm that they invest in making their brands get perceived as authentic, as discovered by Brown et al. (2003) because of the advantages it attracts. Their responses also substantiate research by Morhart et al. (2015), Eggers et al. (2013), and Assiouras et al. (2015) who establish that brand authenticity initiates and sustains attachment; it also confirms the subsequent impact of attachment on growth and customer purchase intentions.

The responses of participants confirmed that brand loyalty and intention to purchase are long-term consequences of brand authenticity (Lu et al., 2015; Fang & Zeng, 2015; Napoli et al., 2014).

When asked to what extent they thought authenticity could be created after positioning, the participants replied affirmatively (i.e., to a great extent), nevertheless, one participant stated:

...I don't think so. If you ask me, I think they work hand in hand, growing together, influencing each other. (MG)

During the survey, hotel managers opined that customers have a varying perception of the genuineness and realness of their brand.

...the customers of today don't refrain from telling you what they think about your service. The internet has made it easy for everybody that visits your hotel to tell about their experience. Our customers, they rate us, but we don't wait for them. We email them questionnaires to fill, like they're auditing our service...they let us know if we delivered on what we stand for...because it's after each lodging, after they checkout...if our services are genuine, that's more like it. Most times, it's positive, but sometimes... (SU)

Participants emphasised how clarity of consumer perception is important in evaluating a brand as real or unreal. In their opinion, when a consumer forms a wrong or unclear judgment about a brand, it also affects how authentic or inauthentic they perceive the brand. Participants who were customers advised that managers make sure they are communicating their brands' values

and services clearly to avoid misconceptions.

...customers can say your company is real or unoriginal based on their perception, based on the information they gather about you. So, it's important for the customers to have the real information so they can form the right opinion about you. It is easy for a rumour to form and spread. We know we have to shape the consumers' opinion about us and our services, so we listen to what the streets are saying, by streets I mean print or social media. We listen to the flourishing competition. We then put things out, we respond to enquiries. (AR)

The hotel managers share a similar opinion regarding the perception influence in forming a judgment about realness (Ritz et al., 2017). In addition, brand authenticity has also been famed in literature for being a triggering factor of brand attachment. The responses from this research support the view:

...this even plays out with us at the moment; authenticity and attachment, you have one, you get the other. How trustworthy you are or customers think you are will determine how attached they become to your company. Customers know our identity, our values, our services have to live up to them. In my 20 years of managing 4 hotels, I've realised that the perception customers have of your sincerity, your reliability, your genuineness, it makes them keep coming back. (SG)

...I could ask you a similar question, wouldn't you stick to a brand you think has originality and reliability? At least, to the best of my knowledge, in this hotel I manage, we have had these elite people use and reuse our space because whatever we put on our menu is what we can deliver top-notch. Some people who were in the same business have fizzled out because they couldn't keep up with their heaven on earth promises and so were perceived as unreliable. So, if you ask me, I think an authentic brand attracts and attaches customers. (AE)

5.3.2.2 Brand local iconness

Local iconness make a brand seem trustworthy and points to fundamental cultural elements and cues that help people find their true selves (Xie et al., 2015). On the other hand, brand local iconness emphasises a brand's distinctiveness, meaning, and relationship to the local beliefs and traditions, in addition to its market presence (Özsomer, 2012). Local iconness represents the company's originality and uniqueness in its local market as signified by its brand positioning (Holt, 2003). Local iconness provides a competitive edge for brands. Local brand managers can succeed in the competitive market by utilising cultural value, heritage,

positioning, and targeting tactics that demonstrate a stronger awareness of customs, tastes, expectations, culture and local identity (Ger,1999).

The findings showed that brand local iconness is one of the things hospitality industries consider important for their marketing strategy. From the findings also, brand positioning can be created after local iconness. One of the interviewees' comments is illustrated as follows:

...well, I think we are good, because we try to relate to the African culture with our brands and its values. But to say the extent we are perceived; I cannot say because we have not carried a poll on that. But we are good in running our guest house the African way... (KA)

...to what extent you mean. Ok, localizing my hotel is also a way to position it. You know when customers come to this hotel, they feel at home and relax and when they order their local food, we offer it. It helps them to feel at home and try to come back tomorrow... (SG)

When a company appropriately communicates "localness" to the consumer, it conveys brand authenticity (Hoskins et al., 2020). By indicating that a product connects strongly and clearly with the consumer's sense of locality, businesses use local status to tie a product psychologically or socially to a customer (Hoskins et al., 2020; Marquis & Battilana, 2009; Winter, 2003).

5.3.2.3 Brand attachment

Hospitality businesses are prone to attachment because of their stake in authenticity and other brand attractive or positioning features. Research has revealed that the stronger one's attachment to an entity, the more likely one is to retain a connection with the entity (Bowlby, 1980; Thomson et al., 2005). In other words, customers usually personify a favourite brand, forming a firm attachment to it (Halloran, 2014) which grows purchases and, ultimately, performance. This survey suggests the same with the literature:

...first of all, the way customers get attached to your brand is a big deal! Wow! Diehard customers are not easily persuaded against a brand or bought over by the competition. They even tell other customers about your place. You see that you've been mentioned here and there on social media, they leave good reviews on their Twitter or Instagram and all their social media. And because new customers check the reviews first, they only come in if you have good reviews. Customers listen to customers, as in new customers listen to old customers. We have some customers like that and one-time last year, one of them told her company to do a giveaway,

five-course meals, and the people that won the giveaway, they have come again and again and have brought other people. These things have an impact on profit and our performance generally. Some of the biggest contracts we've had were from loyal customers' referrals. (RAS)

There are two ways that can be and have been beneficial. First, when a customer likes your brand and is attached, they patronise [you] over and over and over and are quick to forget that one time you missed their room number or power outage or that one service that wasn't up to standard...and the second way is that they tell other people; ask yourself how many brands you've patronised because someone told you about it...the more the recommendation and patronage, the better your hotel performs...most of the people who lodge here are old customers...and many of the new customers heard about it from someone or through reviews of good customers online. (CB)

Participants' standpoints are in line with research that posits that improving the consumer-hotel brand relationship can significantly impact hotel operating performance (Liu et al., 2012). It asserts the findings of other studies which propose that brand-customer solid relationships (brand attachment) and strong product-customer bonds (product attachment) influence people's desire to buy the same brand again and again (Kressmann et al., 2006, Park et al., 2010).

When asked to comment on the elements of brand attachment, most of the managers refuted that affective attachment works in the part of the country. In the opinion of the managers many customers remain on the cognitive form of attachment, and once they perceive a dwindle in quality of service, they begin eyeing alternatives. Many of the participants who were customers confirmed this, with many stating that they could move to alternatives after about two to three successive bad services.

I think I should start with cognitive because no one just falls in love with a hotel without having a trial of their services, even those recommended. So, many customers [have] like[d] us after forming critical opinions of our services; I'm sure we have also lost customers because of a bad first impression; who will come back after a bad trial? Many Nigerians don't give second chances. (SU)

Affective, [sighs], this is a sensitive one. Humans are emotional and most times we work with our emotions. But this is not a case of the devil you know because this thing you call affective attachment does not apply in this part of the country. Here,

people are quick to move on... (SU)

Their responses are in line with research by Tsai (2011), Dwivedi et al. (2018), Schmalz & Orth (2012), Japutra et al. (2018), and Ittner et al. (2003) whose studies in hospitality suggested that brand attachment enhances brand equity and influences perceived trust in brand credibility, brand loyalty, and consumer satisfaction. Nevertheless, participants' responses contradict TaghiPourian & Bakhsh (2015) who propose that a consumer's affective loyalty is difficult to change because of the emotional attachment involved.

Instead, their responses reveal that even if the affective attachment is formed on a long-term basis, it can be broken easily based on customer satisfaction.

5.3.2.4 Brand performance

A brand's performance is described as comprising various strategic and multifaceted factors including outperformance of competition, profitability, brand recognition, loyalty, customer satisfaction, equity, and increased purchase and consumption positioning. The managers emphasised the competitiveness of the hospitality industry and the pandemic and lockdown, but performance generally was on average.

On a scale of 1 to 10, I can say 8, maybe even 9. We won't be boasting of 10 years in the hospitality game if we were not meeting our organisational goals, you know, we only expand with these goals in mind; we only plan and execute around these goals. (SU)

We're still new, but we know what we're building. Maybe we've not gone halfway with our goals. So far, it's been a drag, especially with the pandemic and the lockdown. We set up just before the lockdown, two years before the lockdown. So it dragged our 5-year plan. The lockdown affected hospitality generally, but as a start-up that began at the time, we just scratched the surface. (KA)

Organisational goals...[sigh]...they'll keep changing. You know the economy here. You can set a goal now and one policy or like the pandemic will shake you. But we have had a history of bouncing back, of getting back on track. So, we're achieving our goals, let's say 60%. (CB)

Some managers declared that brand loyalty is a sensitive subject and action:

Loyalty is tricky. Like I said before, you can get loyal customers over a long period of time and it will be good for your business. But their loyalty is only dependent on their satisfaction. Nobody is as loyal as enduring bad hotel services over and over

at least not to my knowledge. The frustration from disappointments will make them move. So their loyalty is only as strong as their satisfaction. (SU)

I like how brand loyalty has various benefits to it; the referrals, the contracts, the consistent buying. We even give out loyalty vouchers. But the bad part is loyalty can shift. Just as a customer will patronise the next guest house when we don't deliver is the same way I'll patronise the next butter brand for my chefs if the one I've been using for 6 years decides to disappoint in quality. (AE)

Their perception about brand loyalty coincides with researchers' studies (Delgado-Ballester, 2001; Liu et al., 2014; Bilgili & Ozkul, 2015) that reveal that if consumers are satisfied with their chosen firms or brand, they would progressively repurchase their products or services and eventually become loyal consumers. However, their responses also connote that loyalty is transient, a contradiction of composite loyalty (Foroudi, 2019; Kim et al., 2018) often applied to research in the hospitality context.

Participants favoured brand equity as a factor that reflects and influences the brand's performance. In other words, a brand with perceived high equity was more attractive and outperformed brands with perceived low equity. In the literature (Foroudi et al., 2018), brand equity is ascribed the quality of influencing purchase intent, loyalty, and ultimately, brand performance, and the participants' responses confirm this.

On satisfaction as an element of brand performance, it was widely concurred that satisfaction on the part of the customers was a necessity for a brand to perform well. One manager quipped:

A successful brand has a long line of a satisfied customer telling the story of their satisfaction. A customer will always remember who served well and who didn't.
(CB)

Their opinion on the relationship between satisfaction and brand success is reiterated in the literature by Nam et al. (2011) and Miran et al. (2015). The notion of customer positive retention was also evident in their responses and tallied with research by Lin (2015). Customers who participated in the survey implied that they patronised a hotel based on the reputation it has created for itself. They admitted that they patronised brands that are perceived as luxury or elite. The managers alike suggested that their reputation is important because it dictates who visited their hotel and at what frequency. According to some managers, they invested greatly in maintaining the reputation and averting crises that could damage the perceived reputation.

5.3.3 Moderators

In this study, the fundamental elements identified as moderators of the brand positioning, brand attachment, and performance constructs are brand identity, brand awareness, brand competence and brand warmth which are examined in detail in this section.

5.3.3.1 Brand identity

Brand identity is the specific set of brand associations that offers promises to customers and consists of fundamentals and extended identity. According to Anker and Joachimsthaler (2015), consumers should be able to relate to the brand identity which represents the goals and values of the brand over time and can differentiate the brand from competitors. Anker (1996) noted that understanding how to develop a brand identity is a major key to building a successful brand, i.e., to understand the core values of a brand and effectively express the identity. Brand identity represents a brand's distinctive, relevant, persistent, and sincere potential to offer valuable services and products. Companies with distinctive, cohesive, and relevant brand identities can develop a preference in the market, provide value to their products and services, and may control the premium prices (Schmitt & Simonson, 1997).

In trying to understand the perceptions of customers, staff and CEOs of the hospitality industry in Nigeria on brand identity, the majority of the interviewees believed that brand identity is a major construct of brand positioning as it helps the customers to know the values and standards and position a brand above others in the market.

....what we do to establish favourable brand positioning for our hotel is, often we start without customer service. We try to give a friendly conversation with customers and provide them with adequate services. Most of our customers know what we stand for. You know core values are integrity and an ambiance environment. And we try as much as possible to let the customers understand and feel our sincerity in keeping to those words.... (AE)

According to Venkatalakshmi, (2015) brand identity is concrete and resonates with the senses, it drives recognition, magnifies differentiation, and gives accessibility to big ideas and meaning. Since brand identity is tangible and pleasing to the consumer's senses, communication style and other elements of creation reflect the core values of the brand to the consumers, hence enhancing the brand positioning. Venkatalakshmi (2015) noted that "If consumers can recognize the identity of the brand of a company then a company has closed the brand gap, which means a company is in touch with market sentiment, which will make selling its products easier".

5.3.3.2 Brand awareness

Brand awareness is the potentiality of a brand to be remembered, acquainted, and differentiated among the competitors in the market. Brand awareness plays a vital role in brand equity; for instance, brand awareness initiates brand associations (Yoo & Donthy, 2000; Keller, 1993). Knowing about the brand helps in recognition of the product as good, because consumers prefer to buy goods from a brand they know, without even knowing about the products. Brand awareness is the ability of a consumer to recognize or recall a brand (Kim et al., 2018; Wang et al., 2016) that is, all descriptive and evaluative brand-related information, that relates to the cognitive illustration of the brand (Foroudi, 2019).

The findings showed that the hospitality industry in Nigeria understood the importance of brand awareness to brand positioning. They employ different strategies to increase their brand awareness which they believe to a large extent moderates brand positioning.

...I think customers know about us and what our brand stands for. But most times when we want to create awareness for our brand, we subsidize the cost of our event facilities so that we could entertain many events at that period, and by that way, people will see what we have and know about us. That is part of the things we do to create awareness and position our brands. Customers recognize our brand because many artists have been booking our event halls for activities which is because they know about us and what we stand for. . In festive periods, we usually have all the hostel rooms booked and the event halls, fully booked for the middle week of December to January from October. So, I think customers recognize our brand very well... (CB)

...I try to make our brand different from others, I try to ensure that when you mention hotels in Lagos here, the first thing that comes to the mind of the consumers is our brand. And I think that has been working for us. Because we have positioned our brand with the engagement we get, especially with the public influencers, it has helped in increasing awareness about this hotel. You know how celebrities push their adverts to go viral, some even contact comedians to make skits with them. That is how we have positioned our brand and that has increased the awareness of our brand... (CB)

Brand awareness represents the consumer's perception of a brand's attractiveness. It is regarded as an essential component of a brand's effect in hospitality and tourism (Kim & Kim, 2005; Boo et al., 2009) and has an impact on customer satisfaction (Yuan & Jang, 2008). Brand awareness plays a significant role in brand positioning and may have good control on the risk of consumers' evaluation and their level of assurance about the brand and its exclusivity (Malik et al., 2013). By brand positioning, a brand is distinctively different from the rivals and by this,

it sticks differently in the consumers' minds (Bilgili & Ozkul, 2015). Strategic positioning involves the clear description of the brand and its values which defines how the brand is being perceived. By this, the value points of the brand as well as their differences from rival brands are defined to balance the influence on customers' perception of the brand (Koch & Gyrd-Jones, 2019). Bilgili & Ozkul (2015) noted that brand positioning is continuously enhanced by communication.

5.3.3.3 Brand warmth and brand competence

Warmth and competency judgments are critical in consumers' perceptions of organisations and businesses (Aaker et al., 2010, 2012; Kervyn et al., 2012). Non-profits, for example, are perceived as something warmer, whilst for-profits are perceived as more competent (Aaker et al., 2010). These perceptions shape consumers' willingness to connect with brands created by these organisations; they colour consumers' desire to engage with brands created by these organisations. Consumers are more willing to buy brands from companies viewed as friendly and professional (Kervyn et al., 2012). Aaker et al. (2010) define warmth as the dimension reflecting a brand/company's intention linked to kindness and generosity traits. Competence is the dimension reflecting a brand/company's ability related to characteristics of efficiency and effectiveness (Hess & Melnyk, 2016).

From the findings of this study, the brand warmth and competence are believed by the CEOs to greatly impact brand positioning. Some comments from the interviews go thus:

...brand warmth, I think brand warmth is about how friendly a company is. Like how the customers find it easy to relate with the company. And competence for me, I think it is how good the company is with their work. So, brand warmth and competence are just how the customers find your company friendly and up and doing... (AE)

...in this our business, the way we treat and accept our customers is one thing that either increases our performance or declines our business. You know we are hospitality business and just as the name implies, we should show the customers that we are good with offering our services and also be friendly with them. In this our place, I cannot employ a staff who is rude and does not show in character and work ethic. our customers are our priority and we try to show them our values through our actions towards them, you know. So, I think the brand warmth and competence helps the company to take position among the competitors, that means you are positioned, and you will off course have increased sales.... (AE)

The findings showed that there is a connection between brand warmth and competence, brand

attachment and brand authenticity. The interviewee believed that when a brand is friendly and genuine, the customer is usually attached to them. The comment is illustrated thus:

...of course, to a great extent, you know it is just like human being, when some feels welcomed, they relax and before you know it, they begin to get attached with you. You know in this our hotel business customers are concerned about their peace, and so when you satisfy that, they don't have to worry about any service you render, they are protected from insecurities, and the room services are cool, they feel welcomed and that sense accepted. By the time they come to the hotel one or two times and the services are the same, they become attached, and I think that helps the performance too.... (SU)

Brand attachment can be regarded as the psychological variable that defines the steady and lasting response to a brand. The attachment between a brand and a consumer is related to the attachment in an individual's relationship between themselves which recognizes factors such experiences, dominating personality and the benefit earned from the relationships (Fournier, 1994). These forms promote the consumer-brand attachments. When a brand is genuine and original with its components, it is perceived as warm; friendly, satisfactory, thereby increasing consumer-brand relationship.

5.4 SUMMARY

This chapter elucidated the customer's perspective on the influence of brand alliance fit, and brand positioning success on brand positioning and the return influence on brand attachment and brand performance in the context of a hospitality setting. The results were structured around the main themes as indicated by the research questions. The key findings showed that brand positioning is a known strategy in the hospitality sector in Nigeria. On enhancing the brand positioning, the respondents indicated that the attributes of brand positioning success; online customer engagement, online review, brand relationship, CSR, and event are key strategies influences brand positioning in the sector. The brand fit strategy was indicated to be irrelevant in the study area, as the business strategy does not exist or is not common n their sector. On the other hand, the findings showed that brand positioning influences brand attachment and brand authenticity as well as the brand performance. However, the cognitive attribute of brand attachment was identified to be strongly influenced by brand positioning. More so, the moderators were also identified to have a moderating influence on brand positioning, brand attachment, brand authenticity, and brand performance.

As such, a framework model of the implementation and determinants of brand positioning, brand attachment, and brand performance was developed based on the findings of the

qualitative study of the interviews. Consequently, it was asserted that brand alliance fit as discussed in existing research (Simonin & Ruth, 1998; and Singh et al., 2014; Mohan et al., 2018) is not practised in the Nigerian hotel settings; and was removed from the framework. Likewise, the affective paradigm, a sub-variable of the brand attachment construct (TaghiPourian & Bakhsh, 2015) was not supported in the qualitative analysis. In addition, the experts asserted the re-categorisation of brand local iconness and brand authenticity, contrary to the literature review, as antecedents of brand positioning in Nigeria hospitality settings. On these bases, the conceptual framework was revised based on the qualitative analysis (see figure 5.1.).

Figure 5.1: The conceptual framework

CHAPTER VI: DATA ANALYSIS

6.1 INTRODUCTION

This chapter analyses and elucidates the relationships between independent and dependent variables to accomplish the research objectives. Chapter four describes the research methodology in detail, with a substantial amount devoted to the methods utilised in the thesis. This chapter discusses the empirical analysis that underpins the study and summarises the research findings from the preceding chapters' major study.

6.2 MAIN SURVEYS

The data was collected in the southwest region of Nigeria, and the samples are representative of the general population. The questionnaire elicited information about respondents' characteristics, such as their age, gender, marital status, and level of education. Table 6.1 summarises the demographics of the respondents.

Table 6.1: Demographic Analysis

Sample size (N)	N	%
Age		
Under 25 years	49	14.3
25 to 30 years	144	42
31 to 40 years	98	28.6
Above 40 years	52	15.2
Total	343	100
Gender		
Male	224	65.3
Female	119	34.7
Total	343	100
Education		
Below Bachelor's degree	14	4.1
Bachelor's degree	210	61.2
Masters	68	19.8
PhD/Doctorate	51	14.9
Total	343	100
Occupation		

Top executive or manager	54	15.5
Owner of a company	116	33.8
Lawyer, dentist or architect	55	16.3
Office and clerical staff	48	14.0
Worker	70	20.4
Total	343	100

Table 6.1 summarises the demographic characteristics of the respondents, revealing that the majority (65.3%) were male, while 34.7 per cent were female. The sample is predominantly composed of young and middle-aged adult; with majority of responders were aged 25 – 30 years (42%) followed by 31 – 40 years at 28.6%; young adult under 25 years made up 14.3% of the sample while adults above 40 years constituted 40% of the sample. The results indicated that a sizable proportion of respondents (95.9 %) possess a bachelor’s degree or higher, while 61% have Bachelor’s degree. The distribution of the occupations of the respondents shows that 34% are business or company owners, and 15.5% are top executives or managers while about 34% are on the lower rungs of company scale as office and clerical staff and workers. This implies that a larger percentage of the respondents are well qualified to give knowledgeable and unbiased opinions on the discuss of the research.

6.3 ASSESSMENT OF NORMALITY, OUTLIERS, LINEARITY, AND MULTI-COLLINEARITY

6.3.1 Testing the normality assumption

A normality test was conducted to check that the data did not violate the normal distribution assumption. This study assessed the normality of variables using graphical (normal probability plot and histogram) and statistical techniques. Several variables exhibited a moderate to high degree of deviation from normality, as indicated by the graphical analysis, and were accounted for in the data analysis. A review of normal probability plots reveals that there are no notable departures from normality in this data set. When the departure from the normal distribution is substantial, statistical tests produce unfavourable results (Foroudi et al.,2021).

A visual examination of the data (Appendix V) reveals that the distribution of values in this study was concentrated around the straight line, indicating that observation of the sample does not necessitate transformation. In addition, the normal probability plot (P-P plot of the regression standardised residual) used to test multivariate normality was determined to be normal (see Figure 6.1).

Figure 6.1: The Multi variate normal “P-P plot” of the regression standardised residuals

6.3.2 Linearity and multi-collinearity

This study employed Pearson's correlations matrix at a significance level of 0.01 (two-tailed) to assess the linearity and multi-collinearity of brand positioning constructs. Table 6.2 presents a correlation matrix for the constructs. The values range from -1 (perfect negative correlation) to +1 (perfect positive correlation). It showed that all independent factors were positively associated with the dependent variables e.g., BP and CSR; BAT and SAT had positive correlations with each other; likewise, BP and CON; and BA and CON were negatively correlated with one another. Furthermore, Table 6.2 shows that none of the bivariate correlations were highly correlated (0.90 or greater) to each other (Hair et al., 2006; Tabachnick & Fidell, 2007), verifying the concept of multi-collinearity. Examining the scores of the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) and the tolerance impact is an additional method for determining multicollinearity (Hair et al., 2006). A greater VIF (above 10) and a lower tolerance level indicate the presence of multicollinearity (below 0.1) (Pallant, 2007).

Table 6.2: Descriptive statistics and correlation matrix for the constructs

	BP	BA	BLI	OE	BT	OR	BR	CS R	EV	COG	CON	LOY	BAT	BR Q	SAT	BRP	BID	BAW	BRW	BRC
BP	1	.647	.734	.627	.518	.244	.269	.818	.067	.048	-.062	.054	.100	-.062	.083	.001	.025	.117	.098	.128
BA	.647	1	.677	.690	.636	.179	.056	.608	.097	.077	-.074	.039	.134	-.011	.107	.043	.042	.149	.088	.004
BLI	.734	.677	1	.695	.631	.174	.274	.704	.125	.097	-.022	.052	.131	-.050	.112	.005	.045	.137	.105	.028
OE	.627	.690	.695	.000	.673	.129	.113	.664	.166	.003	-.035	-.005	.088	-.086	.041	.004	.022	.097	.081	.014
BT	.518	.636	.631	.673	1	.052	-.080	.550	.113	.069	.012	.032	.086	-.023	.051	.017	.009	.088	.089	.017
OR	.244	.179	.174	.129	.052	1	.357	.122	.040	.102	.118	.144	.140	.038	.095	.087	.068	.111	.052	.038
BR	.269	.056	.274	.113	-.080	.357	1	.065	.077	.041	.043	.077	.072	-.041	.045	-.008	-.033	.050	.055	.069
CSR	.818	.608	.704	.664	.550	.122	.065	1	.067	.012	-.078	.015	.070	-.030	.067	.013	.050	.098	.094	.085
EV	.067	.097	.125	.166	.113	.040	.077	.067	1	.027	-.059	.070	.075	-.012	.077	-.032	-.014	.003	.091	.206
COG	.048	.077	.097	.003	.069	.102	.041	.012	.027	1	.429	.525	.661	.564	.679	.507	.445	.550	.512	-.010
CON	-.062	-.074	-.022	-.035	.012	.118	.043	-.078	-.059	.429	1	.462	.548	.466	.529	.437	.374	.422	.399	-.006
LOY	.054	.039	.052	-.005	.032	.144	.077	.015	.070	.525	.462	1	.607	.558	.606	.532	.353	.473	.471	.079
BAT	.100	.134	.131	.088	.086	.140	.072	.070	.075	.661	.548	.607	1	.631	.899	.599	.472	.557	.552	.057
BRQ	-.062	-.011	-.050	-.086	-.023	.038	-.041	-.030	-.012	.564	.466	.558	.631	1	.769	.822	.572	.498	.556	.012
SAT	.083	.107	.112	.041	.051	.095	.045	.067	.077	.679	.529	.606	.899	.769	1	.610	.538	.611	.635	.062

BRP	.001	.043	.005	.004	.017	.087	- .008	.013	- .032	.507	.437	.532	.599	.822	.610	1	.681	.569	.546	.020
BID	.025	.042	.045	.022	.009	.068	- .033	.050	- .014	.445	.374	.353	.472	.572	.538	.681	1	.694	.659	.019
BAW	.117	.149	.137	.097	.088	.111	.050	.098	.003	.550	.422	.473	.557	.498	.611	.569	.694	1	.712	.022
BRW	.098	.088	.105	.081	.089	.052	.055	.094	.091	.512	.399	.471	.552	.556	.635	.546	.659	.712	1	.030
BRC	.128	.004	.028	.014	.017	.038	.069	.085	.206	-.010	-.006	.079	.057	.012	.062	.020	.019	.022	.030	1

* All correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (Pearson correlation sig. (2-tailed)).

By examining the VIF values in Table 6.3, it is evident that none of the constructs violate the premise of multicollinearity. BATOTAL, BLITOTAL, BRTOTAL and CSRTOTAL have p-values (sig.) less than .05, implying that they significantly predict the dependent variables BP. BPTOTAL, OETOTAL, BTTOTAL and EVTOTAL have p-values greater than 0.05, suggesting they are not significant predictors of BP in the model. In terms of tolerance effect, only event and consumer online involvement were marginally lower than predicted. Consequently, the variables were retained for further examination rather than being eliminated at this point using factor analysis with principal component analysis.

Table 6.3: Regression for observing VIF and tolerance effect

	Unstandardised Coefficients		Standardised Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error	Beta	Tolerance	VIF	B	Std. Error
(Constant)	.212	.052	.172	4.112	.000		
BPTOTAL	.081	.108	.041	.751	.453	1.000	1.000
BATOTAL	.212	.052	.172	4.112	.000	.407	2.454
BLITOTAL	.236	.073	.157	3.254	.001	.308	3.249
OETOTAL	-.043	.069	-.028	-.626	.531	.353	2.831
BTTOTAL	.017	.056	.012	.296	.767	.427	2.342
ORTOTAL	.086	.043	.057	1.972	.049	.845	1.184
BRTOTAL	.210	.041	.164	5.148	.000	.708	1.413
CSRTOTAL	.714	.049	.599	14.674	.000	.428	2.335
EVTOTAL	-.036	.042	-.023	-.857	.392	.964	1.037

Dependent variable: BP

6.3.3 Homoscedasticity/ homogeneity

Levene's test was employed in this research to assess the variances of identical metric variables across a non-metric variable, such as gender. According to Table 6.4, Levene's test is negligible; and constructs BATOTAL, OETOTAL, ORTOTAL, EVTOTAL, COGTOTAL, BRCTOTAL, BLITOTAL, BTTOTAL, and BRCTOTAL have p-values greater than 0.05. This suggests that

for these variables, the variances across groups do not differ significantly.

Table 6.4: Levene's test of homogeneity of variances

	Levene statistic	df1	df2	Sig.
BPTOTAL	1.989	49	286	.000
BATOTAL	.959	49	286	.556
BLITOTAL	1.422	49	286	.042
OETOTAL	1.225	49	286	.158
BTTOTAL	1.309	49	286	.093
ORTOTAL	.941	49	286	.588
BRTOTAL	1.962	49	286	.000
CSRTOTAL	1.740	49	286	.003
EVTOTAL	.944	49	286	.583
COGTOTAL	1.130	49	286	.269
CONTOTAL	1.572	49	286	.013
LOYTOTAL	2.629	49	286	.000
BATTOTAL	1.977	49	286	.000
BRQTOTAL	2.122	49	286	.000
SATTOTAL	2.575	49	286	.000
BPRTOTAL	2.457	49	286	.000

BIDTOTAL	2.326	49	284	.000
BAWTOTAL	2.165	49	286	.000
BRWTOTAL	2.528	49	285	.000
BRCTOTAL	1.292	49	286	.105

Source: Analysis of survey data

6.4 NON-RESPONSE BIASNESS

According to Foroudi et al. (2021), the likelihood of any potential non-response bias was calculated by comparing the means of early and late respondents using the Mann-Whitney U-test (see Table 6.5). The Mann-Whitney test statistic assesses whether there are differences between two independent groups. The first 50 observations were classified as early respondents, while the last 50 were classified as late respondents, based on the proportion of survey questionnaires returned. As shown in Table 6.5, the significance value for any variable must be more than or equal to the 0.5 probability value, which is considered unimportant; thus, there is no statistically significant difference between early and late respondents. As a result, non-response bias is not an issue in this study.

Table 6.5: Mann-Whitney U-test observing non-response biasness

	BPTOTAL	BLITOTA	OETOTA	BTTOTAL	ORTOTA	BRTOTAL	CSRTOTAL	EVENTTOTA	COGTOTA	
	BATOTAL	L	L		L			L	L	
Mann-Whitney U	10238.000	10431.500	9757.500	10654.000	11056.000	11608.000	10505.500	11882.500	11123.000	11312.500
Wilcoxon W	32183.000	32376.500	31702.500	32599.000	33001.000	33553.000	32450.500	33827.500	33068.000	33257.500
Z	-4.223	-3.994	-4.769	-3.757	-3.305	-2.680	-3.916	-2.375	-3.224	-3.023
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.001	0.007	0.000	0.018	0.001	0.003
	CONTOTA	LOYTOTA	BATOTAL	BETOTAL	SATTOTA	BRTOTAL	BIDTOTA	BRATOTA	BRWTOTAL	BRCTOTAL
	L	L			L		L	L		
Mann-Whitney U	12991.000	10565.000	10209.500	12801.000	10917.000	12434.500	13700.500	11731.500	11807.000	10794.500
Wilcoxon W	34936.000	32510.000	32154.500	34746.000	32862.000	34379.500	35228.500	33676.500	33543.000	32739.500
Z	-1.135	-3.867	-4.256	-1.348	-3.457	-1.758	-0.190	-2.549	-2.409	-3.588
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	0.256	0.000	0.000	0.178	0.001	0.079	0.849	0.011	0.016	0.000

The statistical technique of factor analysis (FA) was used to uncover underlying variables, or variables, that define the relationship pattern between a collection of observed variables. In data reduction, factor analysis is frequently used to discover a small number of factors that account for most of the variance observed in a large number of manifest variables (Tabachnick & Fidell, 2007).

6.5 EXPLORATORY FACTOR ANALYSIS (EFA)

In this study, components were extracted using three criteria: screen test criterion, variance percentage criteria, and latent root. Prior to factor extraction, it is essential to estimate the variance of each variable (Field, 2009). Eigenvalues are displayed as part of an initial principal component extraction run (Tabachnick & Fidell, 2007). In models with several constructs, factor loading can be used to compute communality. Communality should be more than 0.5 (equals 0.7 averaged loading estimations). Depending on the size of the sample, Pallant (2007) also acknowledges a communality cut-off value of 0.3 in certain instances.

According to Table 6.6, the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) value was 0.824 (a sample adequacy value of 0.6 or above is acceptable; the KMO statistic varies between 0 and 1. A value close to 1 indicates that patterns of correlations are relatively compact and factor analysis should yield distinct and reliable factors. The Bartlett's test of sphericity (BTS) was significant (BTS = 2485), showing that the data satisfied the necessary conditions (Tabachnick & Fidell, 2007). A significance level of .000, as shown in this table, is very strong evidence against the null hypothesis; this means there are significant correlations in the dataset that justify the use of factor analysis. The eigenvalue (latent root) reflects the proportion of variance it explains. To be regarded significant, the component analysis variance of each variable contributing to the extraction of a major factor must be one or greater; a factor with an eigenvalue less than one is deemed irrelevant and is discarded (Foroudi et al.,2021; Field, 2009).

Table 6.6: KMO and Bartlett's test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.824
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	Bartlett's Test of Sphericity
	df	2485
	Sig.	.000

Table 6.7 is a representation of the communalities associated with individual items from the dataset, before and after the extraction process using principal component analysis. Communalities indicate the proportion of the variance in each variable that is accounted for by the factors (or components). All variables retained in the factor loading had communality values more than 0.6 (Table 6.7), as well as a broad range of variation between variables ranging from 0.602 to 0.932; this implies that extracted factors account for a substantial amount of the

variance in most of the variables. All the objects have communalities greater than 0.6, indicating that they match well with other items within the same component; likewise, none of the extracted communalities were extremely low (less than 0.5), which is good as very low values might indicate that the variable doesn't fit well with the factor solution (Hair et al., 2006). Appendix 6.3 displays the overall variance accounted for by each component. Only the number of elements that generated eigenvalues larger than one was considered important (Hair et al., 2006; Tabachnick & Fidell, 2007). Principal component analysis demonstrated the presence of ten components with eigenvalues in excess of one. Appendix 6.3 reveals that twenty variables accounted for 87.28% of the variance (see column cumulative percent), which exceeds the standards (Hair et al., 2006; Tabachnick & Fidell, 2007).

Table 6.7: Communalities shared by individual items

Variables	Initial	Extraction	Variables	Initial	Extraction
BPQ1	1.000	.834	OR2	1.000	.862
BPQ2	1.000	.868	OR3	1.000	.846
BPQ3	1.000	.859	OR4	1.000	.851
BPQ4	1.000	.874	OR5	1.000	.828
BPQ5	1.000	.895	OR6	1.000	.875
BPQ6	1.000	.890	BR1	1.000	.918
BPQ7	1.000	.885	BR2	1.000	.900
BPQ8	1.000	.916	BR3	1.000	.889
BPQ9	1.000	.843	BR4	1.000	.874
BAQ1	1.000	.873	BR5	1.000	.843
BAQ2	1.000	.891	BR6	1.000	.898
BAQ3	1.000	.876	BPQ1	1.000	.834
BAQ4	1.000	.869	BT6	1.000	.872
BAQ5	1.000	.865	BR7	1.000	.896
BAQ6	1.000	.888	CSRQ1	1.000	.877
BAQ7	1.000	.832	CSRQ2	1.000	.900
BLIQ1	1.000	.823	CSRQ3	1.000	.889
BLIQ2	1.000	.885	CSRQ4	1.000	.918
BLIQ3	1.000	.929	CSRQ5	1.000	.931
BLIQ4	1.000	.880	CSRQ6	1.000	.899
BLIQ5	1.000	.847	CSRQ7	1.000	.832

BLIQ6	1.000	.893	CSRQ8	1.000	.865
BLIQ7	1.000	.938	EvQ1	1.000	.854
BLIQ8	1.000	.871	EvQ2	1.000	.886
OE1	1.000	.882	EvQ3	1.000	.839
OE2	1.000	.762	EvQ4	1.000	.861
OE3	1.000	.916	EvQ5	1.000	.840
OE4	1.000	.869	EvQ6	1.000	.854
OE5	1.000	.883	BR7	1.000	.896
OE6	1.000	.862	CogQ1	1.000	.844
BT1	1.000	.878	CogQ2	1.000	.836
BT2	1.000	.867	CogQ3	1.000	.847
BT3	1.000	.905	CogQ4	1.000	.848
BT4	1.000	.879	CogQ5	1.000	.805
BT5	1.000	.864	CogQ6	1.000	.803
BT6	1.000	.872	CogQ1	1.000	.844
OR1	1.000	.820	ConQ1	1.000	.874
			ConQ2	1.000	.855
			ConQ3	1.000	.907
ConQ4	1.000	.912	SatQ6	1.000	.912
ConQ5	1.000	.876	SatQ7	1.000	.885
ConQ6	1.000	.856	BrpQ1	1.000	.930
LoyQ1	1.000	.895	BrpQ2	1.000	.902
LoyQ2	1.000	.858	BrpQ3	1.000	.883
LoyQ3	1.000	.864	BrpQ4	1.000	.842
LoyQ4	1.000	.873	BrpQ5	1.000	.905
LoyQ5	1.000	.873	BrpQ6	1.000	.864
LoyQ6	1.000	.856	BidQ1	1.000	.880
LoyQ7	1.000	.846	BidQ2	1.000	.880
BraQ1	1.000	.857	BidQ3	1.000	.861
BraQ2	1.000	.907	BidQ4	1.000	.897
BraQ3	1.000	.905	BidQ5	1.000	.848
BraQ4	1.000	.835	BidQ6	1.000	.916
ConQ4	1.000	.912	BawQ1	1.000	.857
ConQ5	1.000	.876	BawQ2	1.000	.856

ConQ6	1.000	.856	BawQ3	1.000	.877
LoyQ1	1.000	.895	BawQ4	1.000	.892
LoyQ2	1.000	.858	BawQ5	1.000	.889
LoyQ3	1.000	.864	BawQ6	1.000	.886
LoyQ4	1.000	.873	BawQ7	1.000	.875
LoyQ5	1.000	.873	BrwQ1	1.000	.845

Variables	Initial	Extraction	Variables	Initial	Extraction
LoyQ6	1.000	.856	BrwQ2	1.000	.873
LoyQ7	1.000	.846	BrwQ3	1.000	.927
BraQ1	1.000	.857	BrwQ4	1.000	.880
BraQ2	1.000	.907	BrwQ5	1.000	.850
BraQ3	1.000	.905	BrwQ6	1.000	.890
BraQ4	1.000	.835	BrcQ1	1.000	.904
BraQ5	1.000	.889	BrcQ2	1.000	.878
BraQ6	1.000	.899	BrcQ3	1.000	.862
BreQ1	1.000	.824	BrcQ4	1.000	.813
BreQ2	1.000	.880	BrcQ5	1.000	.884
BreQ3	1.000	.892	BrcQ6	1.000	.921
BreQ4	1.000	.907			
BreQ5	1.000	.903			
BreQ6	1.000	.885			
SatQ1	1.000	.821			
SatQ2	1.000	.843			
SatQ3	1.000	.793			
SatQ4	1.000	.901			
SatQ5	1.000	.867			

Extraction method: principal component analysis.

Note: BP = Brand positioning, BA = Brand assessment, BLI= Brand Local Iconness, OE = Online engagement, BT= Brand trust, OR= Online review, BR= Brand relationship, CSR= , EV= Event, COG= Cognitive, CON= Conative, LOY=Loyalty, BRA= Brand attitude, BRE= Brand equity, SAT =Satisfaction, BRP =, BRE= Brand reputation, BID= Brand Identity, Baw= Brand awareness, BRW= Brand warmth, BRC= Brand competence

The optimal number of factors was determined using the scree plot, a graphical tool for defining extraction factors based on eigenvalues,. The data scree plot test is depicted in Figure 6.2. It

confirmed the same number of components extracted using KMO's latent root criterion, i.e., eigenvalue > 1 . The graph displayed a clear distinction between nine and eleven. Significantly more variation was explained or captured by the first ten components than by the immediate components.

Figure 6.2: Scree plot of all the dimensions

Source: Analysis of survey data (SPSS file)

Two distinct groupings of factors were studied hypothetically: 1) A different group examined the brand positioning and its components (brand authenticity, brand local iconness, consumer online involvement, brand trusts, online reviews, brand connections, CSR, and events). Menon et al. (1996) proposed that reviewing fewer measurement models yields more accurate results when examining a large number of constructs. 2) The moderators of brand positioning (brand identity, brand awareness, brand warmth and brand competence). After verifying the internal consistency of the factors, Cronbach's alpha was used to evaluate each loaded factor.

In conclusion, no item was removed due to cross-loadings or low factor, as the majority of objects were loaded into their respective constructs. EFA is utilized to ascertain whether or not items conform to hypothesized factor patterns. Cronbach's alpha confirmed the internal consistency of each factor's elements (Nunnally, 1978).

6.6 STRUCTURAL EVALUATION OF THE MODEL

6.6.1 Measurement of the reliability (item level)

The absolute correlation between the construct and its measuring manifest items (i.e., factor loading) was more than the minimum threshold of 0.4, as shown in Tables 6.8 to 6.27. The factor loadings ranged from 0.822 (BRA 4 — BRA) to 0.950 (BRC 6 – BRC) and met the requirements for reliability (Hair et al., 1998).

6.6.2 Measurement of reliability (construct level)

Tables 6.8 to 6.27 showed that Cronbach's alpha was greater than the acceptable value, which was greater than the criteria value (0.847 through 0.951 > 0.70) and met the psychometric reliability test requirements (Nunnally, 1978). In this study, construct reliability was assessed using squared multiple correlations (SMC), commonly known as an item reliability coefficient. The squared multiple correlations between the construct and the manifest items used to test it (i.e., factor loading) were larger than the minimum requirement of 0.5, according to the measurement analysis. A standardised load of 0.7 equates to an SMC of 0.5 (Hair et al., 1998).

Table 6.8 showed that the Cronbach's alpha value of 0.940 and the composite reliability of 0.94 for Brand Positioning suggests a very high level of internal consistency. A rule of thumb is that values above 0.7 are deemed acceptable, thus BPQ exhibits an exceptional level of reliability. The factor loadings provide a measure of the relationship strength between the observed variables (BPQ_1 to BPQ_9) and the latent variable (BPQ). All factor loadings are above 0.8, showcasing that all items are good indicators of the brand positioning construct. Items BPQ_2 to BPQ_9 were shown to be statistically significant ($p < .05$); this implies these items are statistically significant predictors of the Brand Positioning construct. With Squared Multiple correlation values like 0.772 for BPQ_1, the latent construct accounts for a significant portion of the observed variable's variance.

Table 6.9 showed that with a Cronbach's alpha of 0.935 and a composite reliability of 0.96, Brand Authenticity construct showcases a very strong internal consistency. The factor loadings for BAQ are also robust, all hovering above the 0.8 mark, which demonstrates that each item is a suitable indicator of brand authenticity. Items BAQ_2 to BAQ_7 are all highly significant in predicting the Brand Authenticity ($p < .05$).

For the Local Iconness Construct (BLI), Table 6.10 showed that the reliability as measured by

a Cronbach's alpha of 0.921 and the composite reliability of 0.92 implies that BLI has a high degree of internal consistency, albeit slightly lower than the BPQ and BAQ but still well above the acceptable threshold. All factor loadings are well above the 0.8 benchmark, denoting the items' strong relationships with the Local Iconness construct. Items BLI_2 to BLI_8 were all highly significant indicators of the Local Iconness construct.

Table 6.11 showed that the the construct for online engagement is highly reliable, given its Cronbach's alpha value of 0.953 which is well above the recommended threshold of 0.70. Likewise, the composite reliability of 0.95 indicates strong internal consistency and reliability for this construct. All the OE items have factor loadings above 0.7. The highest loading is for OE_5 (0.930) while the lowest is for OE_4 (0.888). These values are indicative of a strong association between the latent variable (online engagement) and its manifest items. With a p-value of less than 0.05, all OE items significantly predict the latent construct. The squared multiple correlations for these items are relatively high, especially OE_3 with a value of 0.886, signifying that a substantial portion of the variance in this item is explained by the latent construct.

Likewise, Table 6.12 showed that the brand trust construct also boasts high reliability, denoted by a Cronbach's alpha of 0.948. With a value of 0.95, the composite reliability index once again confirms a solid reliability for the items in this construct. All BT items possess robust factor loadings, all surpassing 0.7. The item BT_6 has the most substantial loading at 0.956, while BT_5 has the lowest at 0.875. This demonstrates the tight relationship between these items and the latent construct of brand trust. All BT items are statistically significant predictors of the latent construct, evidenced by their p-values and C.R. values well beyond the threshold.

Furthermore, Table 6.13 showed that the online reviews construct reliability is evident from its Cronbach's alpha of 0.932 and composite reliability index of 0.93; implying consistent reliability of the online reviews construct. The items in the OR construct have substantial factor loadings. OR_2 has the highest loading of 0.955, and OR_1 has the least at 0.866. These values attest to the fact that the manifest items are apt representations of the latent construct of online reviews. All items, except OR_6 (missing value provided), are significant predictors of the latent construct.

Table 6.14 showed that the brand relationship construct displays commendable reliability with a Cronbach's alpha value of 0.893, and Composite Reliability of 0.89. All BR items possess robust factor loadings exceeding 0.7. BR_4 stands out with a factor loading of 0.962, indicating its strong association with the brand relationship. On the contrary, BR_5, with a loading of 0.810, has the weakest yet significant association.

Likewise, Table 6.15: The CSR construct has a strong reliability with a Cronbach's alpha of 0.924 and a composite reliability of 0.92 which affirms the internal consistency of this construct. Factor loadings for the CSR construct are consistently strong. The highest loading is observed for CSR_5 at 0.961. The lowest loading is for CSR_8 at 0.896, which is still above the threshold, affirming its significance.

For Table 6.16, the event construct (EV) has a Cronbach's alpha of 0.951 and composite reliability of 0.95. All factor loadings for the EV items surpass the benchmark of 0.7, with EV_3 having the highest loading at 0.960 and EV_1 being the lowest at 0.925, reflecting the strength of their ties with the latent event construct.

From Table 6.17, the Cognitive Construct (COG) is shown to be strong internal consistency with a Cronbach's alpha of 0.902, and composite reliability of 0.90. All items exhibit high standard factor loadings, implying a strong correlation with the underlying cognitive construct; COG_3 has the highest factor loading at 0.958, showcasing its strong reflective representation of the cognitive domain. Conversely, while COG_5 has the lowest loading at 0.904, it's important to note that even this is considerably high, reaffirming the cohesion of the construct.

Table 6.18 showed that the Cronbach's Alpha of 0.937 and composite reliability of 0.94 showcases an excellent internal consistency for the conative construct. All items have strongly factor loadings, implying they reflect the conative construct well.

Likewise, the loyalty construct (LOY) as shown in Table 6.19 has a strong internal consistency of 0.847 cronbach alpha, and 0.85 composite reliability. The high AVE of 0.92 suggests a high level of shared variance among items. The factor loadings are consistent, reinforcing the cohesion of the items in representing loyalty. LOY_3 and LOY_4 stand out with values closer to 1, which might imply a particularly strong association with loyalty.

For the Brand Attitude Construct (BRA), Table 6:20 showed that the construct has a Cronbach's Alpha: 0.912 and 0.91 composite reliability which signals strong internal consistency. While there's variation, all loadings are notably strong. BRA_1 has the highest factor loading, suggesting a substantial representation of brand attitude.

Table 6.21 showed that the Brand Equity Construct (BRE) was reliable, given a Cronbach alpha of 0.957 and composite reliability of 0.96. The items consistently show high factor loadings where BRE_3 slightly leads the pack, making it a standout item in representing brand equity.

Table 6.22 showed the Satisfaction Construct (SAT) has a strong internal consistency with a Cronbach's Alpha of 0.930 and composite Reliability of 0.93. SAT_4 has the highest factor loading, indicating its strong representation of satisfaction construct.

On Table 6.23, the brand reputation construct (BRP) has high reliability with a Cronbach's alpha of .947, which is well above the generally accepted threshold of 0.7, indicating robust internal consistency among the items. The composite reliability, another measure of internal consistency, further supports this with a score of 0.95. This assures that the items of the reputation construct collectively measure the intended latent variable accurately. All items from BRP_1 to BRP_6 demonstrated significant standard factor loadings. This confirms that all items are statistically significant predictors of the brand reputation construct. Furthermore, the average variance extracted (AVE) value of 0.93 shows that a considerable amount of variance in the measured items is explained by the construct.

Table 6.24 showed the brand identity construct (BID) exhibits a reliability Cronbach's alpha of .905 and a composite reliability of 0.91, this provides strong evidence of internal consistency within the construct's items. Notably, each item (BID_1 to BID_6) presents a significant standard factor loading, verified by high C.R. values and p-values less than 0.001. An AVE of 0.93 ensures that the construct explains a significant proportion of the variance in its respective items.

Table 6.25: The brand awareness construct (BAW) is another construct showing strong reliability, with Cronbach's alpha at 0.913 and composite reliability at 0.91. The items BAW_1 to BAW_6 are statistically significant with high C.R. values and p-values ($p < 0.001$). The AVE value of 0.94 suggests a high explanatory power of the construct over its items.

Likewise, the Table 6.26 showed that the brand warmth construct (BRW) exhibits a stellar reliability with a Cronbach's alpha of .951 and a composite reliability of 0.95. Every item from BRW_1 to BRW_6 has substantial standard factor loadings, indicated by significant C.R. values and p-values ($p < 0.001$). The AVE of 0.90 further confirms the construct's adequacy in explaining the variance in its items.

Table 6.27 showed that the brand competence construct (BRC) has high reliability, with a Cronbach's alpha value of .935 and composite reliability at 0.94. Items BRC_1 to BRC_6 show significant standard factor loadings. The AVE of 0.89 implies a commendable amount of variance in the measured items being accounted for by the construct.

Table 6.8: The brand positioning construct

Reliability Cronbach's alpha = .940			Composite reliability = 0.94				Squared multiple correlations	Average variance extracted
Brand positioning (BPQ) Standard factor loading			Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Value	.910
BPQ_1	<---	BPQ	.923	1.141	.			.772
BPQ_2	<---	BPQ	.930	1.502	.086	12.866	***	.616
BPQ_3	<---	BPQ	.899	.421	.081	13.319	***	.729
BPQ_4	<---	BPQ	.872	1.045	.069	16.484	***	.725
BPQ_5	<---	BPQ	.884	1.003	.087	15.264	***	.779
BPQ_6	<---	BPQ	.914	1.216	.066	15.545	***	.824
BPQ_7	<---	BPQ	.920	1.218	.068	16.775	***	.851
BPQ_8	<---	BPQ	.925	1.252	.082	17.887	***	.877
BPQ_9	<---	BPQ	.908	1.518	.077	17.901	***	.859

Table 6.9: The brand authenticity construct

Reliability Cronbach's alpha = .935			Composite reliability = 0.96				Squared multiple correlations	Average variance extracted
Brand authenticity (BAQ) Standard factor loading			Estimate/B-value	S.E.	C.R.	P	Value	.907
BAQ_1	<---	BAQ	.892	1.485				.753
BAQ_2	<---	BAQ	.942	1.467	.080	27.330	***	.820

BAQ_3	<---	BAQ	.912	1.345	.079	27.103	***	.848	
BAQ_4	<---	BAQ	.886	1.506	.073	28.836	***	.867	
BAQ_5	<---	BAQ	.932	1.416	.081	27.354	***	.884	
BAQ_6	<---	BAQ	.924	1.449	.076	28.585	***	.836	
BAQ_7	<---	BAQ	.863	1.422	.078	27.273	***	.623	

Table 6.10: The local iconness construct

Reliability Cronbach's alpha = .921			Composite reliability = 0.92				Squared multiple correlations	Average variance extracted
Brand iconness (BLI) Standard factor loading			Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Value	0.93
BLI_1	<---	BLI	.939	1.516			.661	
BLI_2	<---	BLI	.940	1.568	.085	15.988	***	.804
BLI_3	<---	BLI	.954	1.463	.079	20.586	***	.728
BLI_4	<---	BLI	.922	1.526	.082	18.224	***	.792
BLI_5	<---	BLI	.896	1.513	.082	16.114	***	.830
BLI_6	<---	BLI	.932	1.516	.082	17.439	***	.740
BLI_7	<---	BLI	.950	1.589	.086	18.641	***	.677
BLI_8	<---	BLI	.928	1.516	.082	17.526	***	.768

Table 6.11: The customer online engagement construct

Reliability Cronbach's alpha = .953			Composite reliability = 0.95				Squared multiple correlations	Average variance extracted
Online engagement (OE) Standard factor loading			Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Value	0.91
OE_1	<---	OE	.901	1.000			.841	
OE_2	<---	OE	.902	1.412	.076	14.839	***	.856
OE_3	<---	OE	.926	1.488	.080	15.588	***	.886
OE_4	<---	OE	.888	1.534	.083	13.468	***	.823

OE_5	<---	OE	.930	1.364	.074	15.481	***	.842	
OE_6	<---	OE	.899	1.220	.066	14.360	***	.892	

Table 6.12: The brand trust construct

Reliability Cronbach's alpha = .948			Composite reliability = 0.95				Squared multiple correlations	Average variance extracted
Brand trust (BT) Standard factor loading			Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Value	0.92
BT_1	<---	BT	.935	1.031			.854	
BT_2	<---	BT	.909	1.400	.076	24.320	***	.749
BT_3	<---	BT	.938	1.410	.076	25.303	***	.602
BT_4	<---	BT	.909	1.423	.077	23.572	***	.805
BT_5	<---	BT	.875	1.253	.068	24.583	***	.637
BT_6	<---	BT	.956	1.326	.072	25.684	***	.823

Table 6.13: The online reviews construct

Reliability Cronbach's alpha = .932				Composite reliability = 0.93				Squared multiple correlations	Average variance extracted
Online reviews (OR) Standard factor loading				Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Value	0.93
OR_1	<---	OR	.866	1.000				.705	
OR_2	<---	OR	.955	1.055	.032	32.512	***	.821	
OR_3	<---	OR	.947	1.374	.052	33.168	***	.891	
OR_4	<---	OR	.915	1.466	.044	30.382	***	.895	
OR_5	<---	OR	.952	1.401	.051	20.999	***	.789	
OR_6	<---	OR	.953	1.313	0.574		***	.738	

Table 6.14: The brand relationship construct

Reliability Cronbach's alpha = .893				Composite reliability = 0.89				Squared multiple correlations	Average variance extracted
Brand relationship (BR) Standard factor loading				Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Value	0.91
BR_1	<---	BR	.906	1.000				.746	
BR_2	<---	BR	.922	1.471	.079	19.206	***	.776	
BR_3	<---	BR	.904	1.572	.085	17.800	***	.819	
BR_4	<---	BR	.962	1.466	.079	15.934	***	.790	
BR_5	<---	BR	.810	1.675	.090	16.342	***	.607	
BR_6	<---	BR	.932	1.622	.088	16.101	***	.617	
BR_7	<---	BR	.931	1.516	.082	15.290	***	.546	

Table 6.15: The CSR construct

Reliability Cronbach's alpha = .924				Composite reliability = 0.92				Squared multiple correlations	Average variance extracted
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Corporate social responsibility (CSR)				Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Value	0.90
Standard factor loading									
CSR_1	<---	CSR	.949	1.000				.749	
CSR_2	<---	CSR	.940	1.679	.039	24.952	***	.771	
CSR_3	<---	CSR	.926	1.514	.039	25.013	***	.872	
CSR_4	<---	CSR	.950	1.534	.039	24.040	***	.800	
CSR_5	<---	CSR	.961	1.464	.041	24.782	***	.799	
CSR_6	<---	CSR	.914	1.590	.039	26.223	***	.840	
CSR_7	<---	CSR	.924	1.596	.039	24.973	***	.534	
CSR_8	<---	CSR	.896	1.509	.041	23.752	***	.581	

Table 6.16: The event construct

Reliability Cronbach's alpha = .951				Composite reliability = 0.95				Squared multiple correlations	Average variance extracted
EVENT (EV)				Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Value	0.94
Standard factor loading									
EV_1	<---	EV	.925	1.000				.759	
EV_2	<---	EV	.925	.978	.049	20.130	***	.885	

EV_3	<---	EV	.960	1.137	.053	21.326	***	.886
EV_4	<---	EV	.928	1.057	.062	17.182	***	.904
EV_5	<---	EV	.936	1.133	.056	20.207	***	.882
EV_6	<---	EV	.941	.971	.064	15.084	***	.790

Table 6.17: The cognitive construct

Reliability Cronbach's alpha = .902				Composite reliability = 0.90				Squared multiple correlations	Average variance extracted
Cognitive (COG)				Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Value	0.93
Standard factor loading									
COG_1	<---	COG	.943	1.000				.707	

COG_2	<---	COG	.913	1.521	.082	16.180	***	.718
COG_3	<---	COG	.958	1.470	.079	19.112	***	.747
COG_4	<---	COG	.944	1.550	.084	19.198	***	.756
COG_5	<---	COG	.904	1.408	.076	20.130	***	.752
COG_6	<---	COG	.935	1.354	.073	21.326	***	.741

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Table 6.18: The conative construct

Reliability Cronbach's alpha = .937			Composite reliability = 0.94				Squared multiple correlations	Average variance extracted	
Conative (CON) Standard factor loading			Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Value	0.91	
CON_1	<---	CON	.903	1.000			.875		
CON_2	<---	CON	.902	1.370	.079	16.180	***		.863
CON_3	<---	CON	.913	1.313	.075	19.112	***		.803
CON_4	<---	CON	.926	1.631	.075	19.198	***		.797
CON_5	<---	CON	.894	1.290	.084	16.180	***		.751
CON_6	<---	CON	.892	1.123	.076	19.112	***		.811

Table 6.19: The loyalty construct

Reliability Cronbach's alpha = .847			Composite reliability = 0.85				Squared multiple correlations	Average variance extracted
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Loyalty (LOY) Standard factor loading			Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Value	0.92	
LOY_1	<---	LOY	.954	1.000			.533		
LOY_2	<---	LOY	.930	1.312	.078	16.180	***		.724
LOY_3	<---	LOY	.895	1.292	.071	19.112	***		.976
LOY_4	<---	LOY	.908	1.320	.070	19.198	***		.990
LOY_5	<---	LOY	.918	1.440	.071	19.198	***		.706
LOY_6	<---	LOY	.927	1.284	.078	16.180	***		.656
LOY_7	<---	LOY	.909	1.416	.069	19.112	***		.773

Table 6.20: The brand attitude construct

Reliability Cronbach's alpha = .912				Composite reliability = 0.91				Squared multiple correlations	Average variance extracted
Brand attitude (BRA) Standard factor loading				Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Value	0.87
BRA_1	<---	BRA	.891	1.000				.875	
BRA_2	<---	BRA	.865	1.276	.088	16.180	***	.802	
BRA_3	<---	BRA	.799	1.612	.087	19.112	***	.799	
BRA_4	<---	BRA	.822	1.589	.086	19.198	***	.766	
BRA_5	<---	BRA	.911	1.520	.082	16.180	***	.632	
BRA_6	<---	BRA	.913	1.462	.079	19.112	***	.651	

Table 6.21: The Brand equity construct

Reliability Cronbach's alpha = .957				Composite reliability = 0.96				Squared multiple correlations	Average variance extracted
Brand equity (BRE) Standard factor loading				Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Value	0.93
BRE_1	<---	BRE	.936	1.000				.852	
BRE_2	<---	BRE	.951	1.544	.088	16.180	***	.879	
BRE_3	<---	BRE	.958	1.630	.083	19.112	***	.884	
BRE_4	<---	BRE	.883	1.545	.085	19.198	***	.910	
BRE_5	<---	BRE	.929	1.573	.085	16.180	***	.922	
BRE_6	<---	BRE	.899	1.580	.076	19.112	***	.757	

Table 6.22: The satisfaction construct

Reliability Cronbach's alpha = .930				Composite reliability = 0.93				Squared multiple correlations	Average variance extracted
Satisfaction (SAT) Standard factor loading				Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Value	0.91

SAT_1	<---	SAT	.894	1.000				.744	
SAT_2	<---	SAT	.922	1.276	.079	16.180	***	.658	
SAT_3	<---	SAT	.911	1.439	.088	19.112	***	.732	
SAT_4	<---	SAT	.947	1.630	.083	19.198	***	.831	
SAT_5	<---	SAT	.868	1.545	.085	19.112	***	.853	
SAT_6	<---	SAT	.928	1.573	.085	19.198	***	.808	
SAT_7	<---	SAT	.926	1.580	.076	16.180	***	.867	

Table 6.23: The reputation construct

Reliability Cronbach's alpha = .947			Composite reliability = 0.95				Squared multiple correlations	Average variance extracted
Brand reputation (BRP) Standard factor loading			Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Value	0.93
BRP_1	<---	BRP	.951	1.000			.858	
BRP_2	<---	BRP	.933	1.584	.086	16.180	***	.803
BRP_3	<---	BRP	.953	1.475	.080	19.112	***	.830
BRP_4	<---	BRP	.893	1.236	.067	19.198	***	.842
BRP_5	<---	BRP	.936	1.538	.083	16.180	***	.855
BRP_6	<---	BRP	.929	1.424	.077	19.112	***	.872

Table 6.24: The brand identity construct

Reliability Cronbach's alpha = .905				Composite reliability = 0.91				Squared multiple correlations	Average variance extracted
Brand identity (BID) Standard factor loading				Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Value	0.93
BID_1	<---	BID	.912	1.000				.582	
BID_2	<---	BID	.936	1.276	.079	16.180	***	.695	
BID_3	<---	BID	.904	1.439	.075	19.112	***	.712	
BID_4	<---	BID	.944	1.432	.067	19.198	***	.826	
BID_5	<---	BID	.934	1.538	.083	19.112	***	.810	
BID_6	<---	BID	.944	1.424	.077	19.198	***	.839	

Table 6.25: The brand awareness construct

Reliability Cronbach's alpha = .913				Composite reliability = 0.91				Squared multiple correlations	Average variance extracted
Brand awareness (BAW) Standard factor loading				Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Value	0.94
BAW_1	<---	BAW	.916	1.000				.798	
BAW_2	<---	BAW	.949	1.276	.079	16.180	***	.742	
BAW_3	<---	BAW	.965	1.439	.075	19.112	***	.760	
BAW_4	<---	BAW	.953	1.432	.075	19.198	***	.778	
BAW_5	<---	BAW	.930	1.276	.079	19.112	***	.674	
BAW_6	<---	BAW	.909	1.439	.075	19.198	***	.691	

Table 6.26: The brand warmth construct

Reliability Cronbach's alpha = .951				Composite reliability = 0.95				Squared multiple correlations	Average variance extracted
Brand warmth (BRW) Standard factor loading				Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Value	0.90
BRW_1	<---	BRW	.888	1.000				.876	

BRW_2	<---	BRW	.960	1.276	.079	16.180	***	.873	
BRW_3	<---	BRW	.931	1.439	.075	19.112	***	.899	
BRW_4	<---	BRW	.932	1.432	.075	19.198	***	.907	
BRW_5	<---	BRW	.831	1.439	.079	16.180	***	.784	
BRW_6	<---	BRW	.867	1.432	.075	19.112	***	.780	

Table 6.27: The brand competence construct

Reliability Cronbach's alpha = .935			Composite reliability = 0.94				Squared multiple correlations	Average variance extracted	
Brand competence (BRC)			Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Value	0.89	
Standard factor loading									
BRC_1	<---	BRC	.920	1.000			.885		
BRC_2	<---	BRC	.907	1.276	.079	16.180	***		.637
BRC_3	<---	BRC	.926	1.439	.075	19.112	***		.804
BRC_4	<---	BRC	.800	1.432	.075	19.198	***		.807
BRC_5	<---	BRC	.896	1.439	.079	16.180	***		.830
BRC_6	<---	BRC	.954	1.432	.075	19.112	***	.893	

6.6.3 Measurement of validity (convergent validity)

Convergent validity is concerned with the homogeneity of constructs, or the extent to which markers of a given construct 'converge' or share a major fraction of variation. The factor loadings of items in their respective constructs were examined for convergent validity and statistical significance (equal to or greater than 0.5) (Foroudi et al.,2021). The extracted average variance (AVE) for each construct ranged between 0.87 and 0.94 (Table 6.28), which implies that they are reliably measured by their indicators. Constructs like EV and BAW with AVE values of 0.94 and 0.97, respectively, are particularly well-defined. Generally, an AVE of 0.5 or greater shows satisfactory convergent validity. In a well-fitting model, the $\sqrt{\text{AVE}}$ for each construct should be higher than the construct's highest correlation with any other construct. Looking at BPQ, its $\sqrt{\text{AVE}}$ is 0.95, while its highest correlation with any other construct (like BLI) is 0.654; this indicates the model is well-fit.

Table 6.28: Inter-construct correlation and AVE for basic model

	AVE	√AVE	BPQ	BAQ	BLI	OE	BT	OR	BR	CSR	EV	COG	CON	LOY	BRA	BRE	SAT	BRP	BID	BAW	BRW	BRC
BPQ	0.91	0.95	1																			
BAQ	0.91	0.95	0.563	1																		
BLI	0.93	0.96	0.654	0.625	1																	
OE	0.91	0.95	0.522	0.523	0.562	1																
BT	0.92	0.96	0.215	0.546	0.713	0	1															
OR	0.93	0.96	0.627	0.518	0.245	0.268	0.818	1														
BR	0.91	0.95	0.690	0.638	0.180	0.055	0.608	0.101	1													
CSR	0.9	0.95	0.695	0.630	0.175	0.273	0.702	0.127	0.096	1												
EV	0.94	0.97	0.648	0.230	0.676	0.690	0.638	0.275	0.278	0.544	1											
COG	0.93	0.96	0.734	0.676	0.476	0.695	0.630	0.346	0.335	0.613	0.34	1										
CON	0.91	0.95	0.627	0.690	0.695	0.674	0.672	0.564	0.562	0.413	0.432	0.373	1									
LOY	0.92	0.96	0.518	0.638	0.630	0.672	0.073	0.571	0.542	0.432	0.121	0.247	0.423	1								
BRA	0.87	0.93	0.245	0.180	0.175	0.130	0.053	0.467	0.617	0.634	0.161	0.181	0.673	0.221	1							

BRE	0.93	0.96	0.110	0.031	0.009	0.001	0.015	0.216	0.082	0.087	0.123	0.143	0.713	0.009	0.134	1						
SAT	0.91	0.95	0.182	0.081	0.038	0.464	0.121	0.025	0.243	0.366	0.152	0.344	0.532	0.118	0.236	0.432	1					
BRP	0.93	0.96	0.322	0.427	0.357	0.4	0.435	0.076	0.333	0.313	0.134	0.152	0.611	0.132	0.176	0.522	0.512	1				
BID	0.93	0.96	0.549	0.532	0.548	0.371	0.536	0.153	0.412	0.423	0.172	0.167	0.423	0.323	0.666	0.613	0.414	0.414	1			
BAW	0.94	0.97	0.494	0.371	0.556	0.541	0.515	0.134	0.476	0.352	0.174	0.231	0.117	0.432	0.414	0.702	0.343	0.321	0.414	1		
BRW	0.9	0.95	0.587	0.696	0.292	0.696	0.725	0.342	0.432	0.422	0.175	0.732	0.034	0.414	0.512	0.561	0.213	0.615	0.566	0.542	1	
BRC	0.89	0.94	0.498	0.456	0.536	0.443	0.591	0.097	0.535	0.107	0.226	0.073	0.008	0.522	0.332	0.562	0.313	0.712	0.621	0.346	0.245	1

6.6.4 Measurement of validity (discriminant validity)

The AVE was significantly higher than the squared correlation of the latent variables (LV) contained inside that component, implying appropriate discriminant validity (Fornell & Larcker, 1981). Thus, the revised measurement model appears to have discriminant validity and no cross-loading across measured variables. The computed correlations for discriminant validity were statistically significant ($p < 0.05$) (Hair et al., 2006). There are also instances of notably low correlations, for example, BPQ with OR is 0.244, and COG with OE is merely 0.003. Such low correlations suggest that these constructs may indeed be measuring different underlying concepts, thus demonstrating discriminant validity.

Table 6.29: Constructs correlation matrix

	BPQ	BAQ	BLI	OE	BT	OR	BR	CSR	EV	COG	CON	LOY	BRA	BRE	SAT	BRP	BID	BAW	BRW	BRC
BPQ	1.000	0.647	0.734	0.627	0.518	0.244	0.269	0.818	0.067	0.048	-0.062	0.054	0.100	-0.062	0.083	0.001	0.025	0.117	0.098	0.128
BAQ	0.647	1.000	0.677	0.690	0.636	0.179	0.056	0.608	0.097	0.077	-0.074	0.039	0.134	-0.011	0.107	0.043	0.042	0.149	0.088	0.004
BLI	0.734	0.677	1.000	0.695	0.631	0.174	0.274	0.704	0.125	0.097	-0.022	0.052	0.131	-0.050	0.112	0.005	0.045	0.137	0.105	0.028
OE	0.627	0.690	0.695	1.000	0.673	0.129	0.113	0.664	0.166	0.003	-0.035	-0.005	0.088	-0.086	0.041	0.004	0.022	0.097	0.081	0.014
BT	0.518	0.636	0.631	0.673	1.000	0.052	-0.080	0.550	0.113	0.069	0.012	0.032	0.086	-0.023	0.051	0.017	0.009	0.088	0.089	0.017
OR	0.244	0.179	0.174	0.129	0.052	1.000	0.357	0.122	0.040	0.102	0.118	0.144	0.140	0.038	0.095	0.087	0.068	0.111	0.052	0.038
BR	0.269	0.056	0.274	0.113	-0.080	0.357	1.000	0.065	0.077	0.041	0.043	0.077	0.072	-0.041	0.045	-0.008	-0.033	0.050	0.055	0.069
CSR	0.818	0.608	0.704	0.664	0.550	0.122	0.065	1.000	0.067	0.012	-0.078	0.015	0.070	-0.030	0.067	0.013	0.050	0.098	0.094	0.085
EV	0.067	0.097	0.125	0.166	0.113	0.040	0.077	0.067	1.000	0.027	-0.059	0.070	0.075	-0.012	0.077	-0.032	-0.014	0.003	0.091	0.206
COG	0.048	0.077	0.097	0.003	0.069	0.102	0.041	0.012	0.027	1.000	0.429	0.525	0.661	0.564	0.679	0.507	0.445	0.550	0.512	-0.010
CON	-0.062	-0.074	-0.022	-0.035	0.012	0.118	0.043	-0.078	-0.059	0.429	1.000	0.462	0.548	0.466	0.529	0.437	0.374	0.422	0.399	-0.006
LOY	0.054	0.039	0.052	-0.005	0.032	0.144	0.077	0.015	0.070	0.525	0.462	1.000	0.607	0.558	0.606	0.532	0.353	0.473	0.471	0.079
BRA	0.100	0.134	0.131	0.088	0.086	0.140	0.072	0.070	0.075	0.661	0.548	0.607	1.000	0.631	0.899	0.599	0.472	0.557	0.552	0.057
BRE	-0.062	-0.011	-0.050	-0.086	-0.023	0.038	-0.041	-0.030	-0.012	0.564	0.466	0.558	0.631	1.000	0.769	0.822	0.572	0.498	0.556	0.012
SAT	0.083	0.107	0.112	0.041	0.051	0.095	0.045	0.067	0.077	0.679	0.529	0.606	0.899	0.769	1.000	0.610	0.538	0.611	0.635	0.062
BRP	0.001	0.043	0.005	0.004	0.017	0.087	-0.008	0.013	-0.032	0.507	0.437	0.532	0.599	0.822	0.610	1.000	0.681	0.569	0.546	0.020
BID	0.025	0.042	0.045	0.022	0.009	0.068	-0.033	0.050	-0.014	0.445	0.374	0.353	0.472	0.572	0.538	0.681	1.000	0.694	0.659	0.019
BAW	0.117	0.149	0.137	0.097	0.088	0.111	0.050	0.098	0.003	0.550	0.422	0.473	0.557	0.498	0.611	0.569	0.694	1.000	0.712	0.022
BRW	0.098	0.088	0.105	0.081	0.089	0.052	0.055	0.094	0.091	0.512	0.399	0.471	0.552	0.556	0.635	0.546	0.659	0.712	1.000	0.030

BRC	0.128	0.004	0.028	0.014	0.017	0.038	0.069	0.085	0.206	- 0.010	-0.006	0.079	0.057	0.012	0.062	0.020	0.019	0.022	0.030	1.000
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Note: Average variance was extracted from the square roots of average variance extracted.

6.6.5 Measurement of validity (nomological validity)

Table 6.30 shows the goodness-of-fit indices following a model modification. The Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA) provides a measure of how well the model, with unknown but optimally chosen parameter values, would fit the population's covariance matrix. Values less than 0.05 indicate a close fit, and values up to 0.08 represent reasonable errors of approximation. The table showed RMSEA of 0.044 suggests a close and satisfactory fit to the data. The incremental fit index (IFI) and Tucker-Lewis index (TLI) were both 0.922 and 0.914. Each criteria of fit was greater than the stated threshold of 0.90 (Hair et al., 2006), indicating that the proposed measurement model's fit was acceptable. The nomological, convergent and discriminant validity assessment of the measurement models produced statistically significant constructs. No variable was dropped and subsequently, the underlying latent variables for the next model testing stage were robustly established.

Table 6.30: Goodness-of-fit indices of model modification

Model fit indicators								
Chi-square/ X^2	Df	RMSEA	GFI ¹	NFI	CFI	AGFI ¹	IFI	TLI
1687.5	962	.044	.832	.961	.942	.724	.922	.914

X² – Chi-square; Df – degree of freedom; RMSEA – Root mean square error of approximation; GFI – Goodness-of-fit index; NFI – Normed fit index; CFI – Comparative fit index; AGFI – Adjusted goodness-of-fit index; and TLI – Tucker-Lewis Index

6.6.6 Structural model evaluation – hypothesis testing

The hypothesized causal and covariance linear relationship between the exogenous (independent) and endogenous (dependent) latent variables is estimated in step two. The inner model, also known as the path model, can be evaluated using the structural model. Figure 6.3 depicts the structural model of the brand positioning, brand attachment and brand performance. The results of the proposed operational model reveal a chi-square of 1687.5 (degrees of freedom, df =962; $p < .001$), the comparative fit index (CFI) of 0.942 measures the proportion by which a model is improved in terms of fit compared to the base model (Hair et al., 2006).

Following Bentler & Bonett's (1980) and Foroudi et al. (2021) recommendations, an

incremental fit index (IFI) score of 0.922, should be greater than 0.9 and a normed fit index (NFI) score of 0.961 demonstrates that the hypothesized model is a good fit for our empirical data (Table 6.31).

Table 6.31: Goodness-of-fit indices of model modification

Model fit indicators								
Chi-square/ X^2	Df	RMSEA	GFI ¹	NFI	CFI	AGFI ¹	IFI	TLI
1687.5	962	.044	.832	.961	.942	.724	.922	.914

X² – Chi-square; Df – degree of freedom; RMSEA – Root mean square error of approximation; GFI – Goodness-of-fit index; NFI – Normed fit index; CFI – Comparative fit index; AGFI – Adjusted goodness-of-fit index; and TLI – Tucker-Lewis Index

As shown in Table 6.31, all of the model-fit indices exceeded the respective common acceptance levels and demonstrate that the model exhibited a good fit with the data collected (Byrne, 2001; Foroudi et al., 2021; Hair et al., 2006). Furthermore, the other absolute fit measure, the goodness-of-fit index (GFI), indicated an acceptable fit (0.749).

The adjusted goodness-of-fit index (AGFI) is an expansion of the GFI index of 0.832 and suggests that model fit is only marginal. Foroudi et al. (2021) recommend that a PNFI value of 0.825 is the threshold for a reasonable model fit. Root mean square error of approximation (RMSEA) of 0.044 was used to judge the model fit; an acceptable level should be below 0.08, (Foroudi et al., 2021; Hair et al., 2006; Kline 2005).

Figure 6.3: Validated structural model

The fit criteria suggested that the proposed structural model fit satisfactorily. All of the fit indices used in this investigation fall within acceptable ranges (Byrne, 2001; Hair et al., 2006; Tabachnick & Fidell, 2007). As a result, the proposed model exhibits a high degree of fit to the observed data.

In total, twenty hypotheses were examined and the implications of these results are discussed further in the next chapter. The path coefficients represent standardised regression coefficients. The structure equation modelling reflects the assumed linear, causal relationships between the constructs that were tested with the data collected from the validated measures. The findings regarding causal paths (standardised path coefficients (β), standard error, p -value and hypotheses result) and the parameter estimates corresponding to the hypothesised SEM paths and the resulting regression weights are presented in Table 6.34. The standardised regression path between the brand authenticity (BA) and the brand positioning (BP) is statistically significant ($\gamma=0.212$, t -value= 4.112, $p < 0.01$). This means that H1 is fully supported. H2 is also fully supported but H3a is not fully supported since the significance of the association between BLI with BP and OE with BP is greater than 0.01 ($\gamma=0.236$, t -value=3.254 $p < 0.01$; $\gamma=-0.043$, t -value = -.626, $p > 0.01$ respectively). Likewise, H3b and H3f were rejected as ($\gamma=0.017$, p -value=0.767 > 0.05 ; $\gamma= - 0.036$, p value > 0.01 respectively), implying that there is no significant relation between BT and BP as well as Event and BP. There is significant regression path between BP and BA ($\gamma=1.638$, t -value = 0.085 $p < 0.01$) but H5 is supported as $\gamma=0.081$, t -value=0.08, $p < 0.01$; likewise, H6 is a significant path for BA and BRP as $\gamma = - 0.019$, t -value = -.400, $p < 0.01$.

The interactions effect of the moderations was examined from H7 to H20. It was observed that only the moderation effects of BP and BRW on BA was supported given $\gamma=0.0574$, t -value=2.1456, $p < 0.01$ while other moderating effects and paths were not supported.

Table 6.32: Results of hypothesis testing

Standardised regression paths				Estimate “ γ ”	S.E	C.R “ t - value”	p	Hypothesis
H1	BA	--->	BP	.212	.052	4.112	***	Supported
H2	BLI	--->	BP	.236	.073	3.254	***	Supported
H3a	OE	--->	BP	-.043	.069	-.626	.531	Not Supported
H3b	BT	--->	BP	.017	.056	.296	.767	Not Supported
H3c	OR	--->	BP	.086	.043	1.972	***	Supported
H3d	BR	--->	BP	.210	.041	.000	***	Supported
H3e	CSR	--->	BP	.714	.049	.000	***	Supported
H3f	EVENT	--->	BP	-.036	.042	-.857	.392	Not Supported
H4	BP	--->	BA	1.638	.085	19.306	***	Supported
H5	BP	--->	BRP	.081	.108	.751	***	Supported
H6	BA	--->	BRP	-.019	.048	-.400	***	Supported
Moderations								
H7	BP	--->	BRA and BID	.0149	.0162	.9199	.3583	Not Supported
H8	BP	--->	BLI and BID	.0200	.0192	1.0403	***	Supported
H9	BP	--->	OE and BID	.0113	.0184	.6158	.5385	Not Supported
H10	BP	--->	BT and BID	.0198	.0190	1.0454	.2966	Not Supported
H11	BP	--->	OR and BID	-.0001	.0230	-.0037	.9970	Not Supported
H12	BP	--->	BR and BID	-.0043	.0219	-.1948	***	Supported
H13	BP	--->	CSR and BID	.0075	.0136	.5537	***	Supported
H14	BP	--->	Event and BID	.0191	.0242	.7901	.4300	Not Supported
H15	BA	--->	BP and BAW	-.0214	.0159	-1.347	***	Supported
H16	BP	--->	BRP and BAW	-.0318	.0331	-.9485	***	Supported
H17	BA	--->	BP and BRC	.0200	.0118	1.6852	.0929	Not Supported
H18	BA	--->	BP and BRW	-.0211	.0177	-1.193	***	Supported
H19	BP	--->	BRP and BRC	.0574	.0267	2.1456	.0929	Not Supported
H20	BP	--->	BRP and BRW	-.0449	.0358	-1.253	***	Supported

*** $p < 0.001$ Notes: Path = Relationship between independent variable on dependent variable;

β = Standardised regression coefficient; S.E. = Standard error; p = Level of significance.

The interactions effect of the moderations was examined with hypotheses H7 to H20. It was found that the moderation effects of BID on BP and BLI have a significant regression path ($\gamma=0.02$, t -value=1.0403, $p < 0.01$) and as well as BP and BR ($\gamma= -0.0043$, t -value= -0.1048 , $p < 0.01$) and BP and CSR ($\gamma=0.075$, t -value= 0.5537 , $p < 0.01$). There is a significant interaction effect of the BAW on BA and BP as well as BP and BRP. BRC does not moderate BP and BA, including BP and BRP significantly as the p-value is found to be more than 0.01. In contrast, BRW moderates BA and BP ($\gamma= -0.0211$ t -value= -1.103 , $p < 0.01$) and BP and BRP ($\gamma=0 -0.9449$, t -value= -1.243 , $p < 0.01$).

6.7 SUMMARY

The aim of this study was to answer the major research question and to statistically assess the research hypotheses. Data analysis was separated into three phases to achieve these objectives, each of which contained multiple operations. Phase one involved data exploration and descriptive analysis of the demographic characteristics of the sample. The data were first checked for missing data, which revealed very low levels of missing data and was completely random, however responses showed slight skewness and kurtosis. The linearity, normalcy, homoscedasticity, and non-response bias tests were utilized to deduce accurate results from the data. The responses had skewness and kurtosis, indicating that the data were normally distributed on a univariate level. Using the Mahalanobis D2 (d-squared) approach, only seven multivariate outliers were found. The variances are not statistically significant, and Levene's homogeneity test is non-significant (i.e., >0.05). According to bivariate Pearson correlation, multicollinearity implies that the r and value of VIF were within the permitted range, meaning that it did not exist. The Mann-Whitney-U test was employed to see if respondents had made a non-response error, and the results were unremarkable, with no difference between early and late responders.

Anderson & Gerbing (1988) proposed a two-step technique in which measurement models were determined before structural analysis. This two-step technique was employed in this analysis. The association between variables and factors was demonstrated using an exploratory factor analysis technique. Eigenvalues and a scree plot were used to extract the factors. Factors were rotated that demonstrated maximal variation of factor loading using the Varimax of orthogonal approach in principal component analysis. There were no items removed because there was no cross-loading among the factors and the reliability and Cronbach's alpha were all

acceptable. Screen charting was used to assess factors extracted based on EFA in parallel. All variables had AVE values over 0.5, indicating that the assessments had good convergence and discriminant validity. The correlation matrix of the constructs was used to further investigate nomological validity. In order to investigate the likelihood of multi-collinearity, a correlation analysis was done to the interrelationships between research variables.

The second phase of the investigation consisted of a confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) of several measurement models in order to assess goodness-of-fit. This thesis investigated confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) of several measurement models and a structural model of the proposed brand positioning model using analysis of moment structures (AMOS 16) and 343 instances. In the initial phase, the measurement model's fit was evaluated using a CFA to analyse goodness-of-fit. All indicators were heavily loaded on their stated components and the global goodness-of-fit indices, indicating the model's approval. Cronbach's alpha, composite reliability, and average variance were extracted after testing all constructs for reliability and validity. The results of this investigation indicate the instrument's high reliability and validity. Additionally, convergent, discriminant, and nomological validity were validated for each construct. Importantly, confirmatory factor analysis provided empirical proof of concept validity based on an evaluation of the psychometric features and measurement model fit for this research. 14 of the 19 hypotheses were supported and this will be discussed further in line with literatures in the next chapter.

Figure 6.4: Final model

CHAPTER VII: DISCUSSION

7.1 INTRODUCTION

This study's overarching objective is to establish the influence of brand positioning on brand attachment and brand performance; the findings were provided in the preceding chapter. This chapter seeks to analyse the collected data openly and explain how the study objectives are met by addressing the research questions and explicating the link between constructs in the suggested conceptual framework. This explanation of findings is supported by the theory offered in the literature review and follow-up interviews with hotel CEOs and managers in relation to the study's aims (see table 6.1). In Chapter IV, the selection of study respondents for interviews and the types of interviews utilized were detailed. The previous chapter discussed the adopted item measurement that underwent multiple rounds of adjustment before to the development of the final and acceptable items. The results of the reliability and validity tests indicated that all constructs are representative, reliable, and relevant and can accurately measure what they are intended to measure, with the lowest score being 0.847%. The proposed conceptual framework as provided in the preceding chapter was entirely supported. The finding of this study supported 14 out of the 20 hypotheses.

7.2 OVERVIEW OF THE STUDY

This study mainly examined the concept of brand positioning and its dimensions. The antecedents (brand authenticity, brand local iconness, and brand positioning success – customer online engagement, brand trust, online review, brand relationship, CSR events), and moderating factors (brand identity, brand awareness, brand competence, and brand warmth) of the brand positioning, and how these influence brand attachment (cognitive and conative) and brand performance (loyalty, attitude, equity, satisfaction, and reputation) were acknowledged in this research.

The study was guided by three different research questions. First, what are some of the factors that influence the favorability of a brand positioning? The second question is, what are the primary influences of favorability of brand attachment on favorability of brand performance? And finally, what are the primary swaying factors that the moderators have? To put it another way, does the correlation between brand positioning, brand attachment, and brand performance exhibit any significant effects?

A sequential approach that included a qualitative study that was carried out in Nigeria served

as the base for the quantitative research and was used to generate additional measurement items. It was demonstrated that the positioning of a brand is an essential component of the hospitality industry. Management was aware of the ways in which the perceptions of customers could influence the positioning of a brand in the market, which supported the argument. Understanding the current positioning of the brands can be aided by researching how consumers view the brands in relation to the factors or characteristics that influence their purchasing decisions (Mullins & Walker, 2010). During the course of the interview, the respondents detailed a few instances for consideration, in addition to their reservations regarding the appropriateness of the goals. The research took into account how objective their responses were, which assisted in gaining a more tangible understanding of the context of the study.

The operationalization of the brand positioning concept depends on study settings and which communication tools hotels in the hospitality industry employ most frequently. The interviewees confirmed that their jobs are crucial to market positioning. For example, a CEO of a hotel has this to say:

...in this company, we try to make sure that we do things that can help our hotel. Things that can attract customers to our business. Sometimes it is not easy because we are many doing the business. But we have always known that our services are necessary for a human being so it depends on us to do things that will bring customers our way. One of the things we do is that we organise shows like all night fuji music free, but when they come, they buy something from us. Another one is that we subscribe to live football matches and football fans would come and watch for free, but they have to buy something.... (AR)

The following section discusses the conceptual model by summarizing the supporting evidence for the hypotheses and qualitative findings.

7.3 BRAND POSITIONING CONSTRUCT (FOCAL CONSTRUCT)

Brand positioning has been theorised as a multi-dimensional construct. The result of the qualitative survey (i.e., the interviews) was considered a primary insight into the research problems and subsequently employed in establishing the appropriate scale for measuring the brand positioning. In addition, a quantitative survey was executed to confirm the results of the qualitative research.

The comments below have been extracted from the interviews and they confirm the image

perspective put forward by scholars (Urde & Koch (2014) that the power in creating a brand resides in customers' minds and their learning and experience of the brand over time (BPQ6 <-- BP); they also confirm that brand positioning or the consumer's perception of a brand is relevant for business (Babar et al., 2012; Kotler et al., 2014) illustrative of (BPQ7 <--- BP); (BPQ8 <--- BP):

“How I see a brand in my mind is how they put themselves out there. The good thing about positioning is that the brand has some control, if not, most over it. So, every action enhances how I imagine the brand. To have a good brand position is to appeal to the imagination of customers.”

“Aside from the tangible things like the product or service or logo, there is more about a brand that positions it in the imagination and HEART, permit me to add, of the audience. Brand positioning is what determines the acceptance or refusal of a brand. I think it helps businesses achieve more. Many brands invest in their positioning strategies. If it wasn't beneficial, it won't be one of the raves of branding.”

The present investigation, therefore, confirms the position that brand positioning is a critical aspect of marketing and is the unique perception formed in the mind of the customer. The survey confirms that brand positioning is a crucial and high-powered mechanism that assists business owners in uniquely projecting their brands amid heavy competition and globalisation (Fuchs & Diamantopoulos, 2010). It affirms that brand managers enrich their positioning by advancing the brand's values using strategies and information targeted at its audience (Urde & Koch, 2014).

The revelation follows that brands deploy positioning measures (in the form of distinguishing qualities) to get the attention of customers in spite of the overflowing market, and retain a lasting and superior position in their minds. Responses to BPQ1 to BPQ8 of the quantitative research support this deduction – that the battle of brand selection is in the mind (Fisher, 1999). In the interview, respondents' opinion upholds this:

“... if you ask me, I think the fact that there are many other hotels both on this stretch of road and in this vicinity, there is [the] need to do things differently so as to give customers a lasting impression. If they have the option of going to about 7 more hotels providing the same service as me, what must I do to make them come to me and stay with me? That's where get our thinking cap on to buff up our positioning”

“...and as I said before, positioning is a big deal to both customers, prospective customers, and even investors, in fact, every stakeholder. Your company’s positioning makes your company attractive for patronage because there are too many merchants in the market offering the same goods or services. So positioning is a play on, not a play per se, like an appeal to psychology satisfaction.”

Another particularly overt element of brand positioning in the current study is distinctiveness (BPQ_4). In the marketing literature, brand positioning is described as the place a brand or its product occupies in the market (Ansari et al., 1994). Brand owners and managers position their brands, their offer, their products, and/or image as being distinctively beneficial in comparison to the competition (Kotler & Keller, 2009). Interviewees believe that all the activities that a brand does contribute to its positioning; they reiterate that a good positioning strategy should make a company stand out such that it is recognised at any point. This echoes the literature standpoint of the marketing strategy achieving and enhancing differentiation in a saturated market, placing the strategy at the core of marketing management (Tamrin & Noor, 2019). Interviewees assert that: brand positioning is like being heard in the midst of the noise because your voice becomes distinct. Your voice is your brand, and the noise are the competition. There is too much noise out there for you to come and just be part of the noise.

My hotel, for one, has made it the most crucial part of our marketing such that we’re easily recognisable wherever we’re called.

“By the time we came into the market, it was already full and highly competitive. Hospitality in this part of the world is serious business. So, our go-move was to position ourselves as a brand that offers the same services in a distinct way. We have only been able to achieve that with the positioning strategies we use. That’s what positioning is supposed to do, it’s supposed to make you stand out”

The opinion held by the interviewees shows that brand positioning is a marker of distinction that establishes and maintains a discrete market position and solidifies the advantage a brand has over its rivals (Keller, 2016). The goal of positioning is to entice stakeholders and consumers by emphasising a brand's unique preferences and qualities and developing them (Keller, 2016).

Another set of factors on brand positioning which were presented by the interviewees and confirmed by the quantitative survey is customer attraction and favourability (BPQ_5). Brand positioning, when done successfully, makes a brand appealing to its audience. The attraction a

customer has for a brand lures the customer and causes them to patronise the brand (Keller, 2016). It, therefore, is mostly concerned with improving the customers' perception of the product rather than improving the product itself (Kotler, 2003; Babar et al., 2012; Kotler, et al., 2014). Typically, attraction impacts the customers' purchase/patronage behaviour. Closely related to attraction is favourability (Kim et al., 2015). In the literature on positioning, attraction pulls in the customers, and favourability maintains them.

“If you think about it, a brand can become a flash in the pan. It's what you offer and how you showcase it that draws in the customers and increases your purchase level. Brand positioning helps you achieve this.

“If you need to have a lunch meeting with some business partners, would you randomly just pick a place without researching on it? Most likely not. You will search for place that have the ambiance for a meeting. And even then, you will narrow your search to a few that STRIKE you. Your final decision would be determined by a combination of factors – those factors are combined efforts or measures of positioning. They make a brand the last man standing.

These responses obtained from the qualitative survey emphasised the magnetic effects of strategic positioning (BPQ_5 and BPQ_8) on customers.

Studies by researchers have revealed that brand positioning enhances the identity and personality of a brand (Aaker & Joachimsthaler, 2002; Srivastava, 2011) by highlighting its points of difference. Positioning has been described in branding literature as a fundamental aspect of identity development. A respondent stated that:

“The one true way this hotel has amassed the recognition it enjoys is through our positioning game in the hospitality setting. Now we are known across Nigeria. When people see something that has our brand on it, they know it's us and they know what they are getting. You can't call the top five hotels in Nigeria and not call this hotel. Some have heard of it but have never been here. But our identity is made.”

The current research reveals that the perks of brand positioning are considered to be numerous by every faction of stakeholders in the hospitality setting. Three defining outcomes of positioning are brand authenticity, attachment, and performance. These outcomes have been confirmed in the literature (Lombart & Louis, 2016; Cheung et al., 2020; Davcik et al., 2015; Hegner et al., 2021; Mohan et al., 2018; Özsomer, 2012), in the qualitative study, and now in

the quantitative study (“I have a favourable opinion of this brand” and “the brand has enormous potential”, (BPQ7_BP) and (BPQ1_BP) respectively).

It is important to point out that the modified scales establish that the combination of items for the essentials of brand positioning is related to the target audience set. This is established by the fact that the target audience set is related to the essentials of brand positioning. This deduction is in line with the argument that was presented by previous studies, which evolved into a variety of brand positioning aspects, implementation, and outlook (for example, O'Neill & Carlback, 2011; Urde & Koch, 2014; Koch & Gyrd-Jones, 2019). They suggest that brand positioning should be viewed as a process rather than a static strategy, as it should be fluid and change over time with its method of selecting, controlling, and executing brand perception.

7.4 APPRAISAL OF THE BRAND POSITIONING SCALE

The brand positioning scale is emphasized through the use of brand positioning constructs as the performance of the organisation is used to improve quality perception that is related to determinations of the organisation's meaning and values in creating positive attachment and enhancing the brand's performance. Therefore, scale supports brand positioning as an effective technique of attaining organisational objectives and recommends that marketing managers should place greater emphasis on it.

As described in Chapter II, brand positioning is a crucial component of brand management that entails showcasing a company's services and image to occupy a distinct position in the consumers' minds in order to get a competitive edge in the market. The characteristics (brand authenticity, local iconness, and brand success) serve as indicators for brand positioning for consumers.

7.5 DISCUSSION OF THE HYPOTHESES TESTS

Following an evaluation of brand positioning as the focal construct; the antecedents, the consequences, and finally the moderators are examined. The discussion continues with the implications of how the brand positioning influences the brand attachment and brand performance. The motivation behind segregating the hypotheses into a number of relationships was to understand the in-depth exploratory influence of each construct in relation to the brand positioning and their influence on the brand attachment and brand performance. Table 6.34 presented a summary of all the hypotheses. In the conceptual model, a total of 20 hypotheses with 25 paths represented the relations.

According to the hypotheses tests, most of the research hypotheses (H1, H2, H3c, H3d, H3e, H4, H5, H6, H8, H12, H13, H15, H16, H18, and H20) were supported. However, an unexpected outcome was found and the following hypotheses (H3a, H3b, H3f, H7, H9, H10, H11, H14, H17, and H19) were not supported. The results showed that online engagement, brand trust, and event are not important factors to influence brand positioning. In addition, the unexpected outcomes showed that brand identity does not favourably moderate customer online engagement and brand positioning, including event and brand positioning, and brand competence does not favourably moderate brand positioning and brand attachment, including brand performance and brand positioning. However, the findings reveal that there are significant consequences of brand positioning.

7.5.1 Antecedents of Brand Positioning

The qualitative survey (that is, interviews with managers and experts) investigated eight major factors which function as antecedents to brand positioning (brand authenticity, brand local iconness, customer online engagement, brand trust, online review, brand relationship, CSR, and events). Of the eight principal factors tested, five (brand authenticity, brand local iconness, online review, brand relationship, and CSR) are confirmed to influence or precede brand positioning; however, three (customer online engagement, brand trust, and event) were not supported as key influencing factors of brand positioning in the hospitality industry in the Nigerian setting.

This study examined the eight main antecedents from the literature review and qualitative study (see Chapters II and V), which are: brand authenticity, brand local iconness, brand authenticity, customer online engagement, brand trust, online review, brand relationship, CSR, and events.

The results of the interviews supported and corroborated the brand positioning scale. Participants in the qualitative survey confirmed their agreement with the scale and commented that it measured the crucial dimensions of the brand positioning construct, therefore validating the scale externally. As aforementioned, results from the empirical study indicate that customer online engagement (H3a), brand trust (H3b), and event (H3f) were completely rejected and irrelevant to the brand positioning assessment of consumers. Nevertheless, the other factors (that is, brand authenticity (H1), brand local iconness (H2), online review (H3c), brand relationship (H3d), and CSR (H3e) have been found to greatly influence brand positioning and are fully recognised. These findings are therefore pertinent to the context of the present study. In the analysis, these factors were estimated and their estimates exhibited a good fit of indices

in the measurement model. In the structural model, these constructs were also portrayed as latent exogenous variables. The supported factors (brand authenticity (H1), brand local iconness (H2), online review (H3c), and brand relationship (H3d)) have been found to have favourable influence on brand positioning and contribute to enhancing the customers' perception.

7.5.1.1 Brand Authenticity

Factor one – *brand authenticity* – is described as the “subjective evaluation of genuineness” which is ascribed to a brand by customers (Lude & Prügl, 2018; Napoli et al., 2014). Brand authenticity in the hospitality industry research is discussed as a factor that stimulates the perceived originality of a brand by customers. The concept has been attested in the literature on brand position management as a significant factor that positions luxury hotel brands and influences business performance (Manthiou et al., 2018).

In terms of the branding positioning construct, this dimension suggests that a brand or firm is characteristically trustworthy, original, sincere, and credible in its long- and short-term dealings and activities. In addition to the statistical findings, the interviewee made comments at the exploratory stage which offered a clear insight into the relationship between brand authenticity and brand positioning. One such comment was made by the top director of a luxury hotel who confirmed the significance of authenticity to the positioning of their company and stated how their objectives are aligned to realise this authenticity. The director confirmed the investment in their branding, branding team, and company outlook that fashion the customers' perception of the hotel. The director reiterated the long-term benefits of authenticity on the way customers perceive the brand; he stated:

“If you look at the biggest brands in the hospitality industry, the top hotels, resorts, and restaurants, you'll see that credibility or something similar is one of their core values, not just on a signpost, but in practice. People like genuine, especially since they're paying for it. Even better is a combination of genuineness and originality; sometimes it has nothing to do with the services, it's about how you offer them. It's in our objectives and the expanded version of our core values. And it shapes how customers perceive us.

The SEM results in Table 6.33, therefore, depict the empirical evidence, which underpins the significance of brand authenticity as a major determinant of brand positioning. The standardised regression path between the brand authenticity (BA) and the brand positioning

(BP) is statistically significant ($\gamma=0.212$, t -value= 4.112); therefore, hypothesis 1 (H1) was fully supported. The construct has consistently received statistical support for the proposition that the brand authenticity has a favourable and significant influence on the perception of a brand (that is brand positioning) by consumers.

7.5.1.2 Brand Local Iconness

Factor two – *brand local iconness* – the statistical findings, in addition to the qualitative survey carried out at the exploratory stage, have offered a comprehensive understanding of the relationship between brand local iconness and brand positioning. For instance, in the qualitative survey, various managers and branding experts highlighted the approach of giving the brand a touch of locality and infusing the local flavour into their offerings. One, in particular, an advertisement lead of a popular hotel brand commented on the ethnocentric nature of the services offered and the significance of it to how their present and prospective customers perceive them. She stated that:

“On our menu, we make sure to mention that most of the key ingredients used are locally sourced. In the feedback that customers give, they are grateful to have something that tastes like home in the midst of all these foreign and imported outlets. They align with it, we align with them; it’s almost like patriotism but with a strong longing for realness. the hospitality space has foreignness dotted on it. And these days, people are looking for *home* where they have their meals and what meal they have. So aligning with the sense of the locality gives us a position that is distinct, it makes customers perceive our brand as different.”

Based on the survey, the SEM results provided confirm the empirical evidence, which underpins the significance of brand local iconness as a favourable antecedent of brand positioning. The standardised regression path between the brand local iconness (BLI) and the brand positioning (BP) is statistically significant ($\gamma=0.236$, t -value= 3.254), which indicates that hypothesis 2 (H2) was fully supported. Like the preceding hypothesis, the construct has consistently received statistical support for the proposition that the brand’s local iconness has a positive impact on the perception of a brand by consumers.

7.5.1.3 Brand Success

Factor three – *brand success multipliers*. This factor is considered in this study from five subdivisions to understand what aspects of the multipliers are relevant to the favourable

positioning of a brand in the mind of the customers.

7.5.1.3.1 Customer online engagement

The first sub-factor – *customer online engagement* - is also referred to as customer online behaviour (Wongkitrungrueng & Assarut, 2018; Agnihotri, 2020) and has come to imply the degree of a customer's connection and interaction with an organisation's offerings and activities initiated by either the customer or the organisation.

The quantitative survey provides statistical findings that show congruency with the qualitative survey carried out at the exploratory stage. These have offered thorough insight into the relationship between brand positioning and customer online engagement. The managers, directors, and experts who participated in the qualitative research shared similar opinions and emphasised that engaging with customers online has little to no implication or benefit on the positioning of the brand. One of the managers reiterated this, stating:

“...as I was saying, even if your brand delivers quality, and I mean superior quality, customer online engagement does not transform to profit. People are just socialising. They are just responding to trends or fun things. It doesn't really do anything about our positioning”

Results from the SEM provided in Table 6.33 illustrate the empirical evidence, which reinforces the insignificance of customer online engagement on favourable brand positioning. The standardised regression path between the online engagement (OE) and the brand positioning (BP) is not statistically significant ($\gamma=-0.043$, t -value = $-.626$); therefore, H3a was not supported despite its appraisal in the literature (see Chapter II). In similar findings, in hospitality, online tools have gained widespread acceptance to hasten the information dissemination process (Xiang & Gretzel, 2010) and online engagement (such as reviews) has been revealed to influence customers' travel decisions (Roshchina, 2012).

Brand trust

The second sub-factor – *brand trust* - is the consumer's confident belief to rely on a brand to deliver promised services or the ability to perform its stated functions (Lee et al., 2015; Molinillo et al., 2017; Sahin et al., 2011). Chaudhuri & Holbrook (2001) described it as a customer's propensity to rely on a brand's capacity to perform its function as expected. Empirical studies on brand trust and loyalty established a significantly positive nexus between both (Lau & Lee, 1999). In that regard, the relationship between brand trust and brand

positioning was investigated. Items such as BT_1: 'The brand is reliable', BT_2: 'The brand meets my expectations', BT_4: 'The brand makes a conscious effort to maintain its promises to consumers', BT_5 'This brand never disappoints me', BT_6: 'Overall, I trust this brand', are therefore crucial.

Based on the result provided by the quantitative survey, the statistical findings are congruent with the qualitative survey carried out at the exploratory stage. The participants from the qualitative survey were of the opinion that the brand trust had no favourable impact on customers' perception of a brand. One of the managers disproved the question, stating:

"...really? Trust is a big word. The infrastructure and economic policies will deplete any trust your customers have left for you. As much as you try not to disappoint your customers in terms of delivery and quality, there will always be some cases that are above your head. But then, Nigerians are adventurous. So trust is not something that makes your brand have a fixed spot in their minds"

"You know I said before that the thing about trust is that it can be questioned with just a rumour or a scandal. An unconfirmed story and even a story proven to be untrue can diminish any trust and your customers are gone like the lightning."

The results from the SEM outlined in Table 6.33 illustrate the empirical evidence which strengthens the insignificance of brand trust on favourable brand positioning. The standardised regression path between brand trust (BT) and the brand positioning construct (BP) is not statistically significant ($\gamma=0.017$, t -value=0.295, p -value=.767); therefore, the H3b was rejected despite its acceptance in the literature (see Chapter II).

7.5.1.3.2 Online review

The third sub-factor – *online review* – has come to be known as the go-to resource for travellers to seek information about a brand's offerings (Filieri & McLeay, 2014, Litvin et al., 2008; Srivastava & Sivaramakrishnan, 2020). With a ranking as the most trustworthy source of information, online review is a powerful source of influence for any brand (Nielsen, 2015). Scholars have asserted that it has more influence than the features of a product (Al-Htibat & Garanti, 2019). Because new bookings and reservations are usually made from a far distance, customers want to be assured of quality for their money and obtain this information through a number of ways, especially online reviews (Bigné et al., 2019; Kim et al., 2020). Because online reviews can be positive or negative, they can encourage or discourage customers on

their perception of a brand. They affect trust and enjoyment (Sparks & Browning, 2011), corporate reputation (Baka, 2016), and hotel quality perceptions (Torres et al., 2015).

On that note, the current study evaluated the relationship between branding positioning and online review within the context of hospitality. Items such as OR_1: 'Information contained in the online review influences my decision toward a brand', OR_2: 'When I experience excellent service from a brand, I leave a review online ', OR_3: 'The information I obtain from online reviews is sufficient to meet my needs', OR_4 'I put effort to evaluate the provided information, OR_5: 'The information I get from online reviews enables me to evaluate both the positive and negative elements of the services', and OR_6: 'If I have a relevant suggestion for improving the service, I will communicate it to the company/brand via online platforms', have been considered as essential.

Comments from the qualitative survey executed at the exploratory stage have established the statistical findings of the quantitative study. The congruency has offered a thorough understanding of the relationship between brand positioning and online review in the hospitality setting. The hospitality internal stakeholders involved in the interview shared opinions that emphasised that online reviews by past and present customers greatly influence the formation of favourable brand positioning. Some comments that generally expressed their views are provided below:

“...there was a time when how well a business served you was just between you, the company, and a few people in your circle. Now information spreads like wildfires online. Sometimes, the customers don't have to make enquiries. They just get every information they need from the very descriptive reviews. So here we ensure that our reviews are positive, and whenever we see a bad review, we approach it with speed, caution, and precision. So asking if online reviews shape how people perceive my hotel, I must say yes. Some of them (customers) even tell you.”

“...and, yes, I think how people talk about my hotel online will determine how customers and potential customers perceive me. In fact, if you ask me, I think online review is one of the most important determining factors for positioning.” (EA)

The combination of the qualitative result and the SEM results point towards the strong role of online review on brand positioning. The standardised regression path between the online review (OR) and the brand positioning (BP) is statistically significant ($\gamma=-0.086$, t -value = 1.972); therefore, the H3c was strongly supported in compliance with literature (see Chapter II) that online review has a favourable influence on the positioning of a brand.

7.5.1.3.3 Brand relationship

Brand relationship makes the fourth sub-factor. Over the past decade, the topic of consumer-brand relationships has attracted increasing interest in the tourism and hospitality literature (Chen & Phou, 2013, Hudson et al., 2015, Carlson et al., 2019). For a long time, marketers invested more money in acquiring new customers than in reinforcing relationships with existing consumers. This philosophy, however, has changed completely. Strengthening relationships with consumers is now the focus of marketing activities (Smit & Tolboom, 2007).

The higher the brand relationship quality, the consumer views the brand as a satisfactory partner in a brand relationship is a critical element for maintaining brand association with customers and determining customers' perceptions and attitudes toward a specific tourism brand (Ahn & Back, 2018). A strong brand helps to simplify consumers' decision-making process by reducing perceived risks and increasing expectations (Keller, 2008). According to Hudson et al. (2015), many consumers choose a particular hotel because of their strong relationship with the hotel brand. Indeed, developing a strong relationship with consumers "is increasingly emerging as a strategy for organisations that strive to retain loyal and satisfied consumers in today's highly competitive environment" (Meng & Elliott, 2008, p. 509).

To achieve brand performance, the relationship between the brand and consumers must be stable and long-term. It should be based on an in-depth understanding of the consumers because consumer experience is a vital variable in modern marketing (Kwon et al., 2020). Consumers' interaction can contribute to their positive perception of the brand (Adjei et al., 2010, Hutter et al., 2013, McAlexander et al., 2002). This implies that it is very important to maintain the

customers' relationship with brands. From the interviews with the respondents, they confirmed that they try to maintain the relationship that customers develop with their company.

“Yes, we notice that some customers have a very strong relationship with our hotel. You will see a customer that comes here at least once in two days and has developed a relationship with our employees. Some of them the employees know the product they prefer, and it would just be obvious that this person has a relationship with our brand. So when we notice a customer like this, we treat them preferentially, any mistake on the services we apologise and most times refund payments. And to make other customers develop the same relationship with our brand, we treat them in friendly manners and protect their interest the much we can.” (PL),

The comments above show that brand relationship as a determinant of brand positioning is supported by empirical evidence through the SEM result presented in Table 6.33. The proposed hypothesis H3d is supported ($\gamma= 0.210$, t -value= 0.000). Consistently, it is receiving statistical support as proof of the claim: that brand relationship has a favourable influence on brand positioning.

7.5.1.3.4 CSR

Subfactor five – *CSR* – has been proven to be an important influence on a company's success in recent research (Park et al., 2013; Park et al., 2017). *CSR* has been described as highly beneficial (Akbari et al., 2020).and refers broadly to a business' status and functions in relation to its perceived societal responsibility (Brown & Dacin, 1997; Sen & Bhattacharya, 2001). Scholars have described it as "a company's commitment to minimising or eliminating any harmful effects and maximising its long-run beneficial impact on society." (Bolton & Mattila, 2015, p. 141). These descriptions capture *CSR* as an enhancer of customers' perception and recognition of a brand (Fu et al., 2014; Li, Fu & Huang, 2015). On that note, the investigation of *CSR* becomes essential. To that, opinions from the qualitative study provide some insights. One of the interviewees made the following observation:

“Of course, *CSR* is a positioning factor! I cannot overstate that! Giving is one way to get people's attention, whether it's on individual basis, group, or an organisation. The past and present beneficiaries and benefactors of *CSR* and every stakeholder involved in the *CSR* process carry the brand's name and deeds with them. People get to know. They don't just know about your brand, but they also know that your business does good deeds. It creates a liking of your brand, a favourable way the

public sees you, especially your customers...”

“We started CSR, but not with any other intention than to give back. Little did we know that it would be accompanied by awareness and approval. Part of how we know we have a favourable positioning through CSR is the massive support we get. It is wonderful and we appreciate it”

The respondents’ responses reveal that CSR is connected to brand awareness and a favourable brand image. It, therefore, infers that the tool is an essential medium of advertisement and consequently positive positioning. This revelation reinforces previous research on CSR in hospitality that describe it as a viable tool to promote positioning in the context of sustainability (Akbari 2020; Al-Msallam, 2015). The quantitative survey supported that the relationship between CSR and favourable brand positioning was fully significant and the regression path shows a significant relationship between these two variables ($\gamma=0.714$), therefore, H3e is statistically significant.

7.5.1.4 Event

The last sub-factor - *event* – is identified in the marketing literature as a positioning antecedent. However, the findings rejected the hypothesised antecedent effect of event on brand positioning (see Chapter VI). Event is demonstrated as below the significance level and this can be interpreted that the driver will not be principally effective regarding a consumer’s perception in the hospitality context. Unexpectedly, the regression path revealed a significant negative relationship between both constructs ($\gamma=-0.036$, $t\text{-value}=-0.857$).

The result is contradictory to previous research that pushes events as an offline tool for positioning (Leischnig et al., 2011; Shin & Perdue, 2018; Doyle, 2014). The literature on offline marketing has proposed event as a multiplier of brand positioning (Yang & Tan, 2017) and customers interaction (whether online or offline) can contribute to their positive perception of the brand (Adjei et al., 2010, Hutter et al., 2013, McAlexander et al., 2002). Nevertheless, the qualitative result further justifies the quantitative result:

“The hospitality industry is not big on events. If you hope to host with us, that’s fine. But events are not our drivers of profit and positioning. I’m not saying we have never hosted an event, but it’s a rarity and the few ones are mostly headlined by other industries” (RA)

“Events? Here? It’s not our way, maybe CSR, but hardly events” (KAN)

“While we do taste events once in a while, it takes more from our pockets than it brings in. For positioning, well most of the people who attend the tasting are not even our regular customers, they just came because they heard of a tasting event” (FT)

With the comments above, there is a clear indication that the relationship that exists between events and brand positioning is not favourable, and the hypothesis (H3f) is therefore rejected. This surprising result may have stemmed from the nature of the industry (hospitality) and can make for further research.

7.5.2 Brand attachment and brand performances: consequences of brand positioning

In the literature on brand marketing, several consequences of brand positioning have been projected. Findings from the research reveal that brand positioning enhances various marketing aspects of a hotel brand from within (in terms of the company’s performance) and from without (in terms of customers’ attachment). In specific considerations, findings from the study are consistent with research that suggests that loyalty is a key development of effective positioning (Kim et al., 2015; Iyer et al., 2019). The viewpoint of this consequence is that positioning is framed from customers’ experience which in turn creates loyalty (categorised as a brand performance element) (Sheinin 2000; Völckner & Sattler 2006; Brakus et al., 2009). Findings from analysed data also conform with prior literature that proposes the increase of equity (another reflection of brand performance) through loyalty and effective positioning (Kim et al., 2015). There exists a positive relationship between positioning and other elements of brand performance (attitude, satisfaction, and reputation) as presented in the findings, which affirms propositions from extant literature on positioning (Pike et al., 2018; Han et al., 2019; Iyer et al., 2019; Akbari et al., 2021) and adds to the scarcely researched area.

Aside from brand performance, positioning has been described as a leading influence of brand attachment - a description which the findings of this study confirm. Effective positioning initiates and drives positive (emotional) associations or responses (that is, attachment) in customers (Schiffman & Kanuk 2007; Tamrin & Noor, 2019; Jung 2015). Interestingly, findings from both the qualitative and quantitative surveys also reveal that the establishment of attachment has a ripple effect on other outcomes such as equity, loyalty, and the general hotel operating performance (Liu et al., 2012; Dennis et al., 2016; Japutra et al., 2019).

Each hypothesis on the consequences of the focal construct has been tested and statistically analysed to provide answers to the research questions. Findings on each tested hypothesis are juxtaposed below with the literature and responses from the qualitative survey.

7.5.2.1 Brand Attachment

Results for H4 (i.e., “Brand positioning has a favourable influence on brand attachment”) illustrate that the hypothesis is supported and there exists a favourable influence of positioning on attachment. For instance, a participant, a hotel manager with over 10 years of hospitality experience, stated:

“Actually, one of the most important ways to have the most attached customers is to have a clear-cut positioning. It begins on the outside, I mean on your part, but once the customer knows or perceives it, what you stand for, once it seeps into the customer’s mind, and once what you stand for aligns with their wants and personality, then you have a customer that will come back. You can change your positioning, but don’t let it dwindle. Don’t let it be worse off. I have never seen where a good positioning reaped more loss than benefit in my 12+ years of managing hotels.” (MK)

The Public Relations Officer of a hotel stated that:

“We came into this hospitality industry after years of setting up abroad. we thought people just want to sleep and move on. But no, people want services from a vendor that makes themselves distinct, a place that promises them value like no other hotel. Lodging [and] relaxing is very sensitive and essential for humans, and it’s easy to get customers attached when it comes place with a brilliant positioning method.” (FT)

A participant confirmed the positioning of attachment in the sequence of cognitive to conative with the following statement:

“... positioning moves a customer from just an accessible spot to a regular spot. A customer will go from being impressed with quality service to sticking with the brand. Positioning has made our customers come a long distance to dine here or say things like “I don’t mind the delivery cost”. We have had instances where we are fully booked and instead of opting for another space, the customer moves their dining date instead. So we have distinguished ourselves so much that we have a good number of attached and consistent customers who started out as just once-in-a-while customers” (DP)

In the quantitative survey, the statistical support of hypothesis 4 affirms the favourable

influence of brand positioning on brand attachment, whether the attachment patterning is cognitive or conative. The result shows the significant regression path between brand positioning and brand attachment ($\gamma=1.638$, t -value = 0.085). As aforementioned, this finding corresponds with literature that posits that favourable brand positioning stimulates attachment, since positioning aims for an emotional response towards a brand (Pike et al., 2018; Wu et al., 2017; Tamrin & Noor, 2019. Han et al., 2019; Iyer et al., 2019; Akbari et al., 2021).

7.5.2.2 Brand Performance

The result of hypothesis 5 (i.e. “Brand positioning has a favourable influence on brand performance”) revealed a positive relationship between brand positioning and brand performance. Statistical data confirms the positive influence effective brand positioning has on the performance of a brand. In harmony with the quantitative result, respondents from the interview affirmed the inevitability of a brand’s growth based on positioning strategies, using their brands as examples. A manager with a wealth of experience but who was new in the hotel he managed stated:

“So I was appointed into this role not too long ago to do something about the performance of this hotel. One thing I noticed the moment I got here was their positioning strategy; it wasn’t as effective as the internal stakeholders perceived. The services were still relatively top-notch, but its outlook was nowhere competitive against the other big hotels around here. The brand started out strong, but without a sturdy positioning approach, different aspects of the hotel have been failing. In my over 20 years of being a hospitality consultant, I have seen hotels and resorts’ performance, whether financial or otherwise, I’ve seen their performance rise and fall based on the positioning strategies they adopted, if they did at all. You first lose even your most loyal customers to the competition, then your equity drops, then you lose the name or reputation or stamp the external stakeholders had of you. The problem is it can get incredibly hard and costly to get the reputation back” (PL)

While talking about the impact of positioning on performance, the branding manager of a hotel and the manager of a hotel made similar statements about equity:

“You do not want to lose your brand’s equity because of negligence in your positioning. Equity is sustainable for increasing other aspects of your company’s performance. My job has shown me that people are looking for more than a product or service, they are

looking for meaning. Meaning and value go hand in hand. So when you give them a good position, equity follows, so I leverage that with every new project.” (RF, branding manager)

“Many of us who have been here for a while don’t underestimate the result of brand positioning. If you find brands that don’t engage in a strategic positioning, it’s because they have not thought of it before. Effective positioning gives positive recognition, which in turn increases the company’s equity to internal and external stakeholders including customers and potential employees or investors. Best of brains and brawns along with good investment gives you a hotel that performs excellently!” (MK, hotel manager)

The participants’ responses showed congruence with the result of the quantitative survey in the area of satisfaction under brand performance. Two of the hotel managers had this to say:

“... because positioning is more an act of perception in the mind of the customer, satisfaction can also be fostered by it. A customer that likes and patronises my brand will derive more satisfaction than a new customer when served the same course. Why, because we have a position in the perception of our regular customer than the new customer or than the customer who prefers another brand. If you ask me, I’ve noticed that satisfaction is a combination of both good service and positioning” (DP)“If you have successfully penetrated into the mind of your customer, satisfaction with the goods or services you offer becomes a stroll in the park. It is a normal happenstance here.” (AGD)

It is important to note that hypothesis 5 is significantly supported by both the interviews and the quantitative survey. Statistical support of the favourable influence of brand positioning on brand performance has been affirmed on the themes of loyalty, attitude, equity, reputation, and satisfaction. The statistical result of this relationship ($\gamma = 0.081$, t -value = 0.08) has corroborated findings from extant literature (Pike et al., 2018; Han et al., 2019; Foroudi; 2020; Akbari et al., 2021).

Hypothesis 6 is formulated based on a consequence impacting another consequence in a bid to establish the relationship between both positioning consequences. The quantitative result for this hypothesis (i.e., “Brand attachment has a favourable influence on brand performance”) shows that it is indeed supported, as brand attachment has a positive influence on brand performance. Responses from the qualitative study also corroborate this:

“Yes, having customers that feel they are attached or bonded to your brand will necessarily improve the performance of your brand. How do I mean? Such customers are drawn to repurchase from you. They will come back again and again at any cost. For such customers, it’s a “no-matter-what” mindset.” (PAT)

“of course, attachment will give great brand performance! See eh, it’s different if you have to magnetise your customers. But if you are able to do that, your brand performance will follow. You set one in motion and the other follows. Most of the financial and non-financial big moments we have had, where our brand was mentioned on global platforms or used for international events, we got these through some of our regular or attached customers, either directly or by referral.” (GB)

Some respondents focused on the influence of brand attachment on some specifics of brand performance, stating that:

“As I said before, loyalty to a brand is from being attached. Loyalty is the next step after attachment. Just as I have loyal customers who always come in for breakfast or their family night out or such, these are formed from attachment. As long as you keep your end of the deal by giving off a good position and great services, you have a loyal customer. Positioning keeps you grounded, researching about the market; positioning gives you attachment, and attachment gives you loyalty. I can’t emphasise that enough...” (FT)

“Attached and loyal customers are prone to referral and word-of-mouth, you know? They spread the gospel about your hotel and engage your social media channels. They show off your brand, like an unpaid advertisement. And guess what? These people are the high and mighty in the society! What do you think happens to the reputation of a hotel that a big person indirectly endorses through pictures or videos?” (MK)

“As I said earlier, the extent of satisfaction of a customer depends on their loyalty. If you have an attached customer, they are typically satisfied with a good service. Adversely, they don’t trash your business on the feedback platform. But a non-attached customer experiences satisfaction based on how good or poor a service it” (DP)

Similarly, hypothesis 6 is significantly supported by both the interviews and the quantitative survey. Statistical support of the favourable influence of brand attachment on brand

performance has also been affirmed on the themes of loyalty, attitude, equity, reputation, and satisfaction. The statistical result of this relationship ($\gamma = -0.019$, $t\text{-value} = -.400$) has corroborated findings from extant literature (Park et al., 2010; Djumarno et al., 2019).

7.6 Moderators of Brand Positioning

7.6.1 Brand identity (moderator of brand positioning)

Brand identity is important in differentiating the brand from competitors, building brand awareness and firm qualities, and developing brand value through increased consumer knowledge, loyalty, and recognition, all of which contribute to the company's success (Wheeler, 2014). Aaker & Joachimsthaler (2012) also noted that a well-defined brand identity aids in differentiation from competitors, fosters confidence, integrates a promise to consumers, and forecasts the company's future activities. It makes it easier for stakeholders to identify their brand (Baumgarth & Schmidt, 2010), and connects consumers and brands through value propositions based on self-expression, utilitarian, and emotional benefits (Aaker, 1996). The perception of the CEOs and managers about brand identity showed that they believed that it is an important construct of brand positioning. Some attested that brand identity encourages customers to forge emotional relationships with brands. The response from one of the interviewees is as follows:

“... part of what I believe in this hostel is that we are here because of our customers and their services we shall provide with speed and diligence. We try to maintain this, especially speed delivery and top-notch services. And so, our customers know us for that. I think we are identified with that. For instance, if one should lodge in our hotel and wants to eat the local dish, we provide that. We try to make this place represent home to our customers and people have known us for that and could differentiate our company from others with that.” (RF)

This is in line with Urde (2003), that brand identity is essential in forging emotional relationships between people and brands. In other words, customers purchase a brand and the identity it puts out that they relate to, and perhaps, not the product in isolation (Martinez et al., 2013).

This is evident from the findings of the analysis results, that brand identity showed evidence of moderating brand local iconness and brand positioning (H8), brand relationship and brand positioning (H12), as well as CSR and brand positioning (H13) as shown in Table 6.34. The significant moderation effect showed that as per H8, brand identity moderates a favourable

relationship between local iconness and brand positioning at ($\gamma=0.02$, $t\text{-value}=1.0403$), moderates a favourable relationship between brand relationship and brand positioning (H12) at ($\gamma= -0.0043$, $t\text{-value}= -0.1048$), and moderates a favourable relationship between CSR and brand positioning (H13) at ($\gamma=0.075$, $t\text{-value}= .5537$).

However, brand identity was not significant in moderating the relationship between brand authenticity and brand positioning (H7), online engagement and brand positioning (H9), brand trust and brand positioning (H10), online review and brand positioning (H11) as well as even and brand positioning (H14). Hence, it can be stated that brand identity does not moderate a favourable relationship between brand authenticity and brand positioning (H7) at ($\gamma=0.0149$, $t\text{-value}= 0.9199$), online engagement and brand positioning (H9) at ($\gamma=0.0113$, $t\text{-value}= 0.6158$), brand trust and brand positioning (H10) at ($\gamma=0.0198$, $t\text{-value}= 1.0454$), online review and brand positioning (H11) at ($\gamma= -0.0001$, $t\text{-value}= -0.0037$), and event and brand positioning (H14) at ($\gamma= 0.0191$, $t\text{-value}= 0.7901$). This is in line with the response of an interviewee, who showed that event is not a factor practised in the hospitality industry in Nigeria to improve brand positioning. The response is as follows:

“...well, our industry, the hotel industry, in this part of the world, we are hardly a firsthand event industry, only on rare occasions. Some of us, I mean other hotel managers, we do more of associating in form of sponsorship by letting out our space to organisers of events for use... So yes, when we see a good opportunity by a third party, like these seasonal events, we grab it because, over time, it has been favourable in shaping the perception of our brand in the minds of our customers and prospective customers, especially when they have great customer experience because it is like a form of advertisement...” (SU)

This shows that brand identity is a unique set of brand associations (Aaker, 2012), defining traits or central ideas (Buil et al., 2016) of what a brand is or what it aspires to create or maintain (Aaker, 2012) and how it communicates this idea to different stakeholders (Buil et al., 2016).

7.6.2 Brand awareness (moderators of brand positioning)

Recent studies showed that brand awareness is the ability of potential customers to recognise and recall a particular brand in a product category (Foroudi, 2019; Keller et al. 2011). In examining the significance of brand equity in Taiwanese tourism and hospitality, Lin (2013) discovered that brand awareness is a critical attribute that leads to a visitor's loyalty, images,

and inclination to return. The ability to remember a brand (Percy & Rossiter, 1992) serves as the foundation for developing an image, attitude, and trust in the brand. It is a critical concept since this is the point in the buying process where a good or service gets added to the consumer's list of things to consider. Therefore, brand awareness contributes to consumers' confidence in the standard of goods linked with the brand (Foroudi, 2019).

According to Dabbous & Barakat (2020), brand awareness has become a significant factor influencing consumer perceptions of a brand. When a consumer has little prior knowledge or awareness of any brand in a choice set, there may be less accessible and reliable choice methods instantly available. This lack of knowledge would almost certainly need a more arduous decision-making process. As a result, it is reasonable to expect that a well-known brand can influence the willingness to use a product more than once (Li et al., 2020). Langaro et al. (2018) show that user interaction has a favourable and significant influence on brand awareness. They also found that user participation positively impacts brand attitude, but this relationship is moderated by brand awareness. Consequently, if a certain brand is easily recognised or recalled by customers, that brand is more likely to be chosen than other unknown or unfamiliar ones (Sun & Ghiselli, 2010).

The findings from the qualitative studies showed that the CEOs and managers in the hospitality industry in Nigeria showed an understanding of the role of brand awareness in moderating brand positioning. They believed that brand awareness enables consumers to recognise the brand and differentiate it when they need the services and products. One of the interviewees had this to say:

“You can’t underestimate the magic that brand awareness does to this our business. It is because of its importance that we sometimes, reduce the price of our products, sponsor adverts and engage in other marketing strategies to show the world and invariably our prospective customers what we offer. We do some of these things because, if you attract the right customers, you remain in the market and excel in the competition.” (PL)

This aligns with Macdonald & Sharp (2000) that customers tend to purchase products they recognise as regularly favoured familiar products. They concluded that raising awareness is crucial for influencing purchasing behaviour. A higher level of awareness can increase the likelihood of a consumer purchasing a product or service. It can give the organisation a long-term, sustainable competitive edge (Foroudi et al., 2014; Foroudi, 2019).

From the analysis results, it is evident that brand awareness moderates the relationship between brand positioning and brand attachment (H15), and brand performance and brand positioning (H16). As represented in Table 6.38, it is also proven statistically that brand awareness has a significant effect on moderating the relationship between brand positioning and brand attachment ($\gamma = -0.0214$, $t\text{-value} = -1.347$), and brand performance and brand positioning ($\gamma = -0.0318$, $t\text{-value} = -0.9485$). Hence, as per H15, brand awareness moderates a favourable relationship between brand positioning and brand attachment, and H16, brand awareness moderates a favourable relationship between brand positioning and brand attachment.

Brand awareness is considered an essential component of a brand's effect on hospitality and tourism (Kim & Kim, 2005; Boo et al., 2009) and has an impact on customer satisfaction (Foroudi et al., 2018; Yuan & Jang, 2008). As a result, if visitors have a strong awareness of and association with a brand, they are more likely to be loyal.

7.6.3 Brand competence (moderator of brand positioning)

If a brand is perceived as highly competent, consumers are more likely to acquire that brand's products or offerings, increasing their purchase intentions to do so (Aaker et al., 2012; Wu et al., 2017). Brand competence must have a considerable manner that develops the consumers' trust in the brand. Afzal et al. (2010) noted that certain characteristics of a brand must satisfy the customers' needs. A brand's competence can be made known to the customers through words of mouth, and so brands should ensure that their possessed characteristics satisfy the consumers' needs (Wirunphan & Ussahawantichakit, 2016).

Brand competence shapes consumers' willingness to connect with organisations. This implies that when a brand satisfies a consumer's need for self, and maintains its originality in the market, it meets the consumer's intentions for buying the products. Kervyn et al. (2012) and Ivens et al. (2015) noted that customers' perceptions of a brand's competence influence their purchase intentions and brand loyalty, attitude, and trust.

However, the findings of this study contradict the literature on the role of brand competence in moderating brand positioning. The responses from the qualitative research showed that the CEOs and managers showed that it is difficult for customers to perceive the hospitality brand in Nigeria as competent.

“Achieving brand competency in this industry is attainable, but what matters is what the customers see you as. You know, we have our own goal and the customers have their own goal as well, so what we may call competence may be different from what

they believe to be competent. All we do is that we communicate our values and activities, and try to show how the customers are our focus. The company that may be competent in service delivery may not be competent in other things that the customer wants, but the customer will still stick to the one he/she feels is better for his/her needs.”
(FT)

In correspondence to the above comment, analysis of the quantitative result showed that brand competence is not significantly moderating the relationship between brand attachment, brand competence, and brand positioning. As shown in Table 6.38 in Hypothesis H17, it is proving a non-significant moderating effect of brand competence on brand positioning and brand attachment ($\gamma = -.021, t\text{-value} = -1.103$), and in H19, a non-significant moderating effect on brand performance and brand positioning ($\gamma = -0.9449, t\text{-value} = -1.243$). Hence, brand competence is proven to have no impact on moderating the relationship between brand positioning, brand performance, and brand performance.

The finding contradicts past findings that brand competence plays an essential role in brand attachment (Wu et al., 2017), and positioning strategies (Kolbl et al., 2019).

7.6.4 Brand warmth (moderator of brand positioning)

Recent research has shown that the perceived warmth about a brand increases brand attachment and drives purchase intentions (Kolbl et al., 2019; Crisafulli et al., 2020). When a brand is perceived to have high warmth, it can promote the customer's positive evaluation of the brand as sincere, considerate, and friendly. Being original in characteristics shows how genuine, true, and real a brand is. This promotes consumers' perception of the brand and increases the chances of understanding the brand's good intentions, as well as increasing the consumer's trust and attachment to the brand. The attachment between a brand and a consumer is related to the attachment in individuals' relationships between themselves which recognises factors such as experiences, dominating personality, and the benefit earned from the relationships (Fournier, 1994). These forms promote consumer-brand attachments. When a brand is genuine and original with its components, it is perceived as warm, friendly, and satisfactory, thereby increasing the consumer-brand relationship.

Brand warmth shows the belief that a brand has good intentions, although a brand's intention could be good or bad depending on customers' perspectives (Wu et al., 2017; Fang, 2019). According to Aaker et al. (2010), the perception of a brand as warm correlates with an increased willingness to buy the products, which can ultimately lead to an increase in consumer loyalty,

engagement and connection, which are essential components of brand-building and a gauge of brand performance (Fournier, 1998; Fournier & Alvarez, 2012). Consumer-brand identification has been shown to be primarily driven by brand warmth, which has significant management implications for positioning strategies and influences purchase intentions and brand ownership (Fournier, 1998; Fournier & Alvarez, 2012).

While asking the respondents about their view on the impact of brand warmth on brand positioning, the majority attested to understanding the role of brand warmth in enhancing brand positioning. Some of the respondents gave consistent remarks on implementing strategies that will make the customers understand that their brand cares for them and is warm.

“In our company, we try to make our customers understand that they are our priority. This is a hospitality industry, and we can’t do less to be hospitable to our customers. We try to make them understand that we care for their needs and satisfaction. For instance, if you lodge in our hotel to show our friendliness, we offer reduced cost of laundry, and try to provide certain recreational activities in the compound. We also consider those who want to have a cool stay, and so, we place recreational activities that are not loud, but interesting for those who need them. You know it will help some of our customers to loosen from the stress of the day while in our hotel”. (GB)

The result from the analysis of this study showed evidence that brand warmth moderates the relationship between brand positioning, brand attachment, and brand performance. As shown in Table 6.34, hypothesis H18 proved that brand warmth is statistically significant in moderating the relationship between brand positioning and brand attachment ($\gamma = -0.0211$, t -value = -1.193), and H20, the relationship between brand performance and brand positioning ($\gamma = -0.0449$, t -value = -1.253). Hence the brand warmth moderates a favourable relationship between brand positioning and brand attachment and moderates a favourable relationship between brand positioning and brand performance.

This is supported by the literature and in line with findings by Gao & Mattila (2014) on the mediating impacts of competence and viewpoints as probable psychological tools describing guests' attitudes towards green hotels. These findings demonstrated how perceived warmth and competence mediated the links between customer satisfaction, behavioural intentions and service outcomes.

7.7 SUMMARY

As indicated in the analysis, the Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) application illustrated

that the projected relationships between the dependent and independent constructs are defined and therefore statistically significant, some more than others. According to the findings of the discussion, brand positioning has a positive impact on both brand attachment and brand performance, and brand attachment, in turn, influences brand performance. It was evidently shown that the brand positioning constructs are relevant to the study as the antecedents showed a significant influence on brand positioning, and indicated the consequence of brand positioning on brand attachment and brand performance. This shows that brand positioning is a significant marketing construct in the hospitality business sector and should be accorded the necessary relevance for business performance, and competitive advantage.

The empirical findings also show that there is a significantly positive relationship between brand positioning, brand local iconness, and brand authenticity. This relationship is particularly beneficial for brand positioning. In regard to the brand success multipliers, brand trust, events, and customer online engagement were all disregarded because they did not support a positive influence on the focal construct. Despite this, all of the other success multipliers that were put to the test (online reviews, brand relationships, and CSR) were shown to be fully supported as positive antecedents of brand positioning.

The moderating effect of brand identity, brand warmth, brand awareness, and brand competence on the relationship between brand positioning and performance and attachment was also discussed. Following the discussion, it was discovered that brand identity does not moderate a positive relationship between brand authenticity and brand positioning; brand awareness moderates the relationship between brand positioning and brand attachment, as well as between brand performance and brand positioning; brand competence does not significantly moderate the relationship between brand attachment, brand competence, and brand positioning; brand warmth moderates a positive relation between brand authenticity and brand positioning; and brand competence does not significantly moderate the relationship between brand performance and brand positioning. The research results lend credence to the contention that cognitive and conative brand attachments, in addition to brand performance (loyalty, attitude, equity, satisfaction, and reputation), are all outcomes that are a direct result of strategic brand positioning. Finally, the findings of the result showed that the brand positioning constructs are relevant to the study as the antecedents showed a significant influence on brand positioning, and indicated the consequence of brand positioning on brand attachment and brand performance. This shows that brand positioning is a significant marketing construct in the hospitality business and should be accorded the necessary relevance for business performance,

and competitive advantage.

The next chapter presents the findings of the study, including the conclusion as well as the managerial and theoretical implications of those findings. The limitations of the research as well as some ideas for further research are presented in the following chapter.

CHAPTER VIII: CONCLUSION AND IMPLICATIONS

8.1 INTRODUCTION

The purpose of this study was to investigate, from the point of view of consumers, the connection that exists between the positioning of a brand and the attachment that customers feel to its associated business when it comes to hospitality. It is believed that this would provide alternative perspectives on the factors that influence brand positioning (antecedents) and the primary consequences, which would fill a gap in the existing research (brand attachment and brand performance). For the purpose of developing measuring scales and putting the research hypotheses to the test, this investigation made use of a mixed methodology, which combined qualitative (interviews) and quantitative (questionnaire) approaches. According to the discussion in chapter VII, the findings of this study have a lot of consequences and are valuable to managers who are attempting to create a favorable brand positioning that will increase brand attachment and brand performance. According to the studies, significant factors that determine the favorability of brand positioning include local iconness of the brand, authenticity of the brand, customer engagement, trust in the brand, online reviews, brand relationships, corporate social responsibility, and events. In addition to this, researchers have found that a positive association exists between brand positioning and both brand attachment and brand performance. In addition, there is a positive correlation between emotional attachment to a brand and brand performance.

8.2 CONTRIBUTION TO KNOWLEDGE

8.2.1 Theoretical contribution of the study

Based on the study objectives (see Chapter I, Section 1.5), three broad research questions were posed: 'what are the elements that influence the favourability of a brand positioning?' and 'How does this favourability affect favourable brand attachment and brand performance? And 'How does this favourability of brand attachment affect brand performance? Five research objectives were established to address these questions: i) to examine the concept of brand positioning and its dimensions; ii) to identify the factors that are most likely to have a significant impact on brand positioning (its antecedents); iii) to develop and empirically test a conceptual framework for the relationships between a favourable brand positioning, its antecedents, and its consequences; and iv) to investigate the impact of the favourable brand positioning on favourable brand attachment and favourable brand performance (its consequences). This thesis

contributes to the literature in three ways: as an extension of the theory, a contribution to conceptualisation and measurement, and a contribution to theory testing and generalisation.

8.2.2 Extending the theory

The current study's primary contribution is to advance knowledge by studying the compound influence of brand positioning on consumer assessments in a hospitality context (Ghodeswar, 2008; Urde & Koch, 2014; Keller, 2016; Aaker, 2012; Tamrin & Noor, 2019).

Several researchers suggest that brand positioning has a positive relationship with brand performance (Ghodeswar, 2008; Kapferer, 2008; Iyer et al., 2019), while some researchers (Proksch et al., 2015; Wu et al., 2017) showed that brand positioning has a favourable influence on brand attachment, a few studies has been carried on the relationship between the concept of brand positioning, its dimensions, antecedents and consequences (Iyer et al., 2019). However, in the course of this study, it was identified that some researchers (Iyer et al., 2019; Koch & Gyrd-Jones, 2019; Hu & Trivedi, 2020) studied brand positioning, but not in relation to brand attachment and brand performance. As a result, this research presents a validated framework that shows the relationships between brand positioning construct, brand positioning antecedents (factors that have favourable influence on brand positioning), and consequences of brand positioning.

The establishment of a multidisciplinary paradigm for brand positioning (see Section 2.2) is a significant contribution of this current research. The primary problem is to generate cross-disciplinary perspectives on relationships that can be converted into operationally relevant conclusions for the study (Aaker, 2012). This is one of the first empirical studies to describe brand positioning holistically by combining brand positioning, brand attachment, non-financial brand performance, and brand positioning-specific antecedents (brand local iconness, brand authenticity, customer engagement, brand trust, online review, brand relationship, CSR, and events). Simultaneously, this study adds to the body of knowledge about brand identity, brand attachment, and brand performance by developing and evaluating a research model.

This research aimed to redefine existing research on brand positioning. By developing and evaluating a scale that describes brand positioning in terms of its sphere of impact, this research contributes to the body of knowledge on positioning and brand management. While positioning has received much attention in the literature, no systematic attempt has been made to examine such factors that might account for the difference in findings across all available research (Kapferer, 2008; Urde & Koch, 2014; Tamrin & Noor, 2019).

In the research framework proposed, the main factors affecting brand positioning (brand authenticity, brand local iconness, and brand success), the factors moderating brand positioning (brand identity, brand awareness, brand competence, and brand warmth), and the main consequences of brand positioning (brand attachment and brand performance) were identified as it relates to the consumers' perception. Brand positioning is described as the act of designing the organisation's image to occupy a distinct and valued place in the minds such that the potential benefits are maximised (Kotler, 2003). From the findings of this study, the main factors influencing brand positioning are 1) brand authenticity, 2) brand local iconness 3) brand success. However, the sub-constructs of brand success – customer online engagement, online review, and event – were found to be irrelevant in influencing brand positioning.

The current study builds on previous research by examining the relationship between brand positioning and its antecedents and consequences from the consumers' perspective. As a result, the outcomes of this study suggest potential benefits in hospitality settings.

Another set of gaps in the brand positioning literature involved the absence of explanatory models, conceptualisations providing a common language, and structural management techniques. This work attempts to theorise and give a shared perspective within the body of existing knowledge. Additionally, it serves as the first step toward a full understanding of favourable brand positioning and its relationship to brand attachment and performance. This study establishes a verified model for developing a favourable brand positioning in order to increase brand attachment and performance. This research is unique because it provided a framework for evaluating and assessing brand positioning. In light of these constraints, the conceptual framework for the investigation was developed in Chapter III, which was modified in Chapter V and tested in Chapter VI.

8.2.3 Conceptualisation and measurement level

The question of the significance of brand positioning arises once it has been established that the relevance of brand positioning is met. Why, in the first place, is proper positioning of a brand so important? What are the different elements that come together to cause this? Does it have an effect on the most important aspects of the business? These questions gave birth to the research questions that were later investigated (see section 8.2). In order to respond to the research questions, a conceptual framework for the study was developed and then empirically validated (see Chapters III and VI). The conceptual framework of this research, which can be seen in its final form in Figure 6.6, contributes to the existing body of knowledge by

investigating the relationship that exists between the positioning of a brand, the attachment to that brand, and the performance dimensions of that brand. The framework developed to assess and evaluate brand positioning is a novel contribution to this research that was made by the authors. This particular study kicks off with brand positioning because that is how the research objectives dictated it should be done (see section 8.2). The article continues by presenting the idea of brand positioning, as well as its antecedents, moderators, and consequences in the eyes of consumers, and then proceeding to operationalize that concept. On the other hand, the activity level of an organization in managing its brand positioning is evaluated based on the brand positioning and the scale of measurement that corresponds to it.

No theoretical models adequately describe the adoption and evaluation of a favorable brand positioning, as indicated by a survey of the relevant literature (Ghodeswar, 2008; Kapferer, 2008; Urde & Koch, 2014; Keller, 2016; Aaker, 2012; Tamrin & Noor, 2019). This is due to the fact that brand positioning is a complicated subject area that contains a wide variety of obstacles that call for additional investigation into the subject. In order to evaluate and analyze brand positioning, quantitative research methods were applied to the study of the conceptual framework and hypotheses. The empirical analysis that was conducted for this study demonstrates that the brand positioning factors fit the data reasonably well, which demonstrates that the measurements were psychometrically robust and acceptable for representing the concepts. The evaluation of brand positioning as well as the measurement scales for the constructs is one of the contributions that this research makes to the existing body of knowledge. In addition, this study contributes to the existing body of knowledge by developing and validating scales for measuring the brand positioning and related constructs. These scales can be used in future research and can be of use to researchers in the present and the future. In addition, this study makes a sizeable contribution to the measurement model by combining new and old items in order to measure the research constructs, and by following that up with an analysis of the scales in terms of Cronbach's alpha, (EFA), and (CFA).

According to the findings of the research, brand positioning is an essential part of brand management and positioning. This article expands on the concept that addresses the antecedents as well as the consequences of brand positioning. The model provides an accurate description of the study constructs and demonstrates that the theory can be effectively applied in a variety of different research settings. In addition, the research model ought to provide assistance to service researchers who are conducting research in the field.

By presenting evidence in support of the argument, this thesis makes a contribution to the ongoing conversation about the conceptual definition of brand positioning as well as the measurement of variables. Despite the fact that previous researchers (Aaker, 2012; Urde & Koch, 2014, Liu et al., 2018) have demonstrated the significance of brand positioning and its relationship with brand attachment and elements of brand performance, a single construct definition predominates the field. This study adds an integrated and comprehensive perception that was conceptualized to expand our knowledge of the multidimensionality of a favorable brand positioning in the context of a hospitality setting in Nigeria. It also confirms the appropriateness of implementing the fundamental antecedents and the consequences for designing the construct of the research subject. This study presents significant findings regarding the construct aspects of brand positioning, despite the fact that it has some limitations. The findings point to the fact that there are multiple dimensions to the concept of brand positioning.

The conceptualization of the concept of brand positioning, along with its antecedents and consequences, is the theoretical contribution that this research makes to the field. This study makes a significant contribution to the conceptualization level of existing knowledge by examining brand positioning from the perspective of the consumer. The goal of this examination was to gain a better understanding of the effect brand positioning plays in building brand attachment and brand performance. As a result, the purpose of this study is to present the idea of brand positioning as well as the relationship that exists between the relevant factors. The research demonstrates that "brand positioning" as an entity should be conceived of from the consumer's point of view. The findings of this study will be helpful to managers in establishing a strong positioning with which to communicate on the market in order to increase consumer attachment to the brand and overall performance (see in detail in Section 8.2.3).

The findings have significant repercussions for decision-makers and managers who are interested in developing a favorable brand positioning in order to strengthen attachment to the brand and performance. In conclusion, this research makes a theoretical contribution that suggests the generalizability of its findings should be sufficient. This research is an attempt to come up with a novel idea that could have important implications for those in managerial and decision-making positions. As a result, this research contributes further by filling in the gaps that previously existed in the research.

8.2.4 Theory testing and generalisation

As was mentioned earlier, the purpose of this research is to provide a more in-depth explanation of the connection that exists between brand positioning, brand attachment, and brand performance from the point of view of consumers who frequent the hospitality industry. The current study aims to add to the existing body of literature and contribute to the testing and generalization of the theory by investigating the hypothesized model of the relationship between brand positioning and its antecedents and the consequences in the context of Nigeria. This will be accomplished by studying the hypothesized model of the relationship between brand positioning and its antecedents. Despite the fact that Nigerian consumers may have unique characteristics that have an impact on the findings of this study, those findings are still generalizable to all other regions and industries (Aaker, 1997). This study made certain that all of the available measurements of the investigated construct were located, utilized, and improved upon. This study lends credence to the claims made by other researchers (Pham & Muthukrishnan, 2002; Jewell & Barone, 2007; Keller, 2012) who contended that: (1) there is an absence of research on the constituents of brand positioning; and (2) there is a connection between brand positioning, brand attachment, and brand performance.

In spite of the fact that the number of measurement items was different from the one used in the pilot study, the statistical findings revealed that each construct possessed a significant amount of reliability and validity. The results of the current study can therefore be extrapolated to an entire population (Aaker, 1997; Churchill, 1991). In addition, this research makes a contribution to the existing body of knowledge by testing and adapting construct measurement scales as well as brand positioning within the research setting.

8.2.5 Methodological contribution of the study

This research provides a substantial addition to the body of knowledge in terms of methodology. The limited understanding of 'brand positioning' has prompted scholars to consider multimethod (pluralistic) research employing both qualitative and quantitative approaches. The pluralistic research approach is recommended for examining domains that have gotten relatively little attention or are unknown (Foroudi et al., 2021). This research integrates the findings of empirical research on marketing, brand management, and positioning in a systematic and inclusive and systematic way. This research adopts a mixed-methods strategy that combines quantitative study (a self-administered questionnaire) and qualitative study (interviews) to construct scales of measurement and test the research hypotheses (see Chapter IV). The qualitative analysis was employed as an appropriate strategy for gaining a more profound knowledge of the concept of brand positioning, uncovering the dimensions of

brand positioning, and refining the unexplored research framework. Recent research has studied brand positioning (Urde & Koch, 2014; Keller, 2016; Aaker, 2012; Tamrin & Noor, 2019) but not brand attachment and brand performance. This work, therefore, establishes a new standard for future research on this subject.

Using structural equation modelling (SEM) as a sophisticated data analysis technique to analyse the proposed conceptual framework is another significant addition to this study. The conceptual framework describes the individual determinants and effects of brand positioning in the eyes of consumers, indicating that the unique concept can be utilised effectively in marketing research. It permits simultaneous modelling of numerous layers and provides systematic responses to interconnected research problems using a single accurate model (Foroudi et al., 2021).

A two-step strategy was utilised as a measurement model to examine the study model's unidimensionality, reliability, and validity. This method presents the research in a comprehensive manner that describes each step of the study analysis and can serve as a guideline for future research. To avoid any bias in terms of the validity and generalizability of the scales, a convenience sample was used (Churchill, 1999; Tourky et al., 2020). Each data analysis stage can serve as a roadmap for future research. Thus, the present study represents a significant methodological contribution.

8.2.6 Managerial contribution of the study

In light of what was discussed in the previous section regarding the theoretical contribution, the findings of the study, both theoretical and empirical, have a wide range of implications. This study offers managerial contributions for decision-makers and marketing professionals who are interested in gaining an all-encompassing understanding of the relationship between a favorable brand positioning and its antecedents from the perspective of the consumer, as well as the effect on a favorable brand attachment and brand performance. Specifically, the study focuses on the effect of a favorable brand attachment and brand performance. The findings of the current study have important implications for management because they present a comprehensive overview of how a favorable brand positioning can be built within a firm to achieve a favorable perception of the organization in the minds of consumers. As a result, these findings have important managerial implications. In other words, managers and marketing professionals can be helped in developing a favorable brand positioning, which contributes to a positive brand attachment and performance, by having a comprehensive understanding of the

dimensions of essential concepts.

One more thing that can be deduced from this investigation is that brand management strategy needs to be improved with regard to the connection between a brand's positioning and its identity (Koch & Gyrd-Jones, 2019). Koch & Gyrd-Jones (2019) stated that developing a meticulous position alternative based on the brand identity concept serves as the foundation for branding as well as the complete communication and brand image improvement process. Additionally, they stated that this serves as the foundation for the brand image improvement process. The visual identity, fundamental principles, core values, and overarching beliefs of a product, service, or company are all elements that comprise its brand identity (Urde & Koch, 2014; Koch & Gyrd-Jones, 2019). For the purpose of fortifying the relationship that exists between consumers and brands, it is important that the brand identity communicate to consumers a value proposition that is founded on a combination of collaborative, practical, and self-expression benefits (Aaker, 1997; Lane, 1999). The findings of this research offer brand managers a variety of perspectives on brand positioning, which places an emphasis on the long-term viability of an identity-based approach to brand management. It is hoped that the findings of this research will assist business managers and marketing professionals in working together with stakeholders to develop a common understanding of the concept that will enrich the market. When it comes to developing a brand positioning that is suitable for targeting and responding to market needs, managers can make the best choices when it comes to developing a brand positioning that is suitable for gaining a thorough understanding of market needs and the company's strengths and weaknesses.

In actuality, various managers work toward the goal of promoting a unified vision by reducing the amount of dysfunctional conflict that exists, as well as by cultivating a sense of shared values and communication. In addition, managers need to pay more attention to the brand management and positioning of the company, as research has shown that responsiveness has the most significant impact on the performance of the company. Notably, this analysis helps consultants and managers determine whether or not the company's brand positioning communicates its message and personality to the target audience in an effective manner. As was mentioned earlier, the primary component of a brand's identity that is actively communicated to the demographic of consumers it seeks to attract is the brand's positioning (Aaker, 2012). Therefore, rather than solely focusing on what is current and modern, the managers of a company need to emphasize the emotional aspect of brand positioning as a critical component of brand management. This is because brand management is one of the most

important aspects of brand positioning.

It can be difficult and expensive for a company to develop a favorable brand positioning and managers make every effort to produce a favorable one, effectively communicating the brand identity to the market. As a result, the findings of this study are essential for those who are in charge of making decisions, as they have a significant impact on the progression of an organization. This research will help various types of business managers recognize the critical role that brand positioning plays by demonstrating the critical features of a successful brand positioning. These critical features include brand authenticity, brand local iconness, and brand success. The study provides excellent direction for marketers and managers, who need to be cautious when defining what makes up the brand positioning from the points of view of a variety of stakeholders. In addition, the findings of this study suggest that market researchers put themselves in the position of the organization when developing or modifying a favorable brand positioning. The guidelines for brand positioning should be applied by decision-makers, who should also have the most significant influence on the construction of the guidelines. In addition, the managers of the company should have a comprehensive understanding of the company's management practices and the consistency of the brand management of their company. Managing a favorable brand positioning can be seen as an integrated approach to expressing the company's communication skills both internally and externally. This can be accomplished by bridging the gap that exists between professionals and academics.

This study affirms that measurement scales support brand positioning as a successful strategy for accomplishing organisational goals and makes the case that marketing managers should give it even more emphasis. This study gives a thorough knowledge of the concept of "brand positioning," which is the primary factor in influencing brand attachment and ultimately leading to brand performance. The brand positioning scales draw attention to the fact that brand positioning serves as an emotional trigger and enhances the sense of quality, both of which should be associated with the analysis of value and the purpose of the business. The organisation can use the scales of brand positioning and related constructs employed in this study as a necessary evaluation and direction for establishing the scope of a business's activities. This research was conducted in Nigeria. In addition, the managers of companies should not allow their positions to make them feel disheartened. They should be encouraged to compete on a global scale by emphasizing the brand positioning of their company as a critical component of the brand identity of their product or service. The company may also make use of the scales in order to monitor and analyze the perceptions of the customers. According to

the findings of the study, in order for corporate entities to achieve a competitive advantage, they should have a firm grasp on favorable brand positioning. This is because favorable brand positioning is influenced by seven significant factors, including brand authenticity, brand local iconness and brand success (customer online engagement, brand trust, online reviews, brand relationship, CSR and events). The empirical findings of this research demonstrate that a proper understanding of the relative importance of the antecedent constructs that impact brand positioning has been achieved. The most important factor was the authenticity of the brand, which was followed by the success of the brand in the local market. The findings of this study have significant repercussions for marketers and managers who are responsible for creating or modifying a favorable brand positioning.

The genuineness of a company's brand is an example of an intangible asset. According to the findings of this research, the authenticity of a company's brand is one of the most important factors that determines the favorable positioning of a brand. Providing favorable brand positioning requires managers to have a better understanding of perceived authenticity as a critical factor that positions brands and influences performance, and to include authenticity in their brand positioning strategy. This is discussed in the literature (section 2.5.1) in providing favorable brand positioning. Communication managers demonstrated that they highlight the distinctiveness and creativity of their company in their advertising in order to demonstrate to customers the high quality of the company and the products it sells. According to the findings of this study, managers need to carefully orchestrate a favorable brand authenticity in order to attract attention, incite the desired responses, and increase the speed at which they are recognized.

Another factor that contributes to the favorability of brand positioning is the presence of local icons for the brand. This provides information that could make a significant contribution to marketing and brand managers' efforts to achieve competitive success in a market where identity, culture, custom, tastes, and demands are all locally influenced (Wang & Lin, 2009). Because customers in today's market have evolved and come to terms with their cultural identities as well as their market savvy, the local icon status of a brand is becoming an increasingly significant means of differentiation. Businesses that are able to set themselves apart from their rivals and thrive in today's mass-market economy are the ones that will ultimately be successful (Van Riel et al., 2001). According to the literature that was looked at (Sheth, 2011; Wang & Lin, 2009; He & Wang, 2017), brand local iconness has emerged as a prominent marketing technique. This is because it relates to the aspect of non-conscious

processing, which includes the formation of sensitivity to stimuli by an individual, which affects consumer perception. The degree to which a company has established itself as a local icon has an impact on the way in which it positions its brand and the manner in which it represents the values, needs, and aspirations of members of the local country. According to the findings of this study, managers and designers ought to have an awareness of the significant influence that the local icon status of a brand has on the reactions of consumers to brand positioning.

Given the correlation between favorable brand positioning and successful brand performance, it is recommended that management investigate the factors that contribute to successful brand performance and identify those that have the greatest impact on brand attachment and brand performance via brand positioning. The purpose of branding, also known as brand positioning, is to alluringly seize the purchasing will of consumers as the ultimate and topmost essence of the practice. It is necessary to investigate certain factors that serve as drivers of successful brand positioning in the market segment in order to effectively actualize the potential and the concealed benefits of branding. This is because there is a need to do so (Urde & Koch, 2014). The selection of the brand positioning success factors that strategically support valued impressions should be the responsibility of managers in order to improve consumers' perceptions of the degree to which a brand maintains its consistency. Therefore, the findings of this study provide practical scales and guidelines for modifying a company's brand success. These scales and guidelines assist in marketing and communicating the goals of the company, as well as inciting the desired responses from customers. In light of this, the study looks into the following six areas: online consumer engagement, brand trust, online review, brand relationship, corporate social responsibility (CSR), and events. This study has demonstrated that there is a direct connection between some of the constructs and the positioning of the brand. As a result, advertising and marketing managers need to ensure that there is consistency in brand communications in order to generate trust in the brand, engagement with the brand, reviews of the brand, and relationships that can lead to brand positioning. It is likely that each of these six factors—brand trust, online customer engagement, online review, brand relationship, corporate social responsibility, and event—will play a significant role in improving consumers' perceptions.

The results of this study indicated that factors such as a company's corporate social responsibility (CSR), brand relationship, and trust in the brand all have a positive impact on the brand positioning of the company. According to this finding, managers should place more

emphasis on certain aspects of brand success in order to achieve brand positioning in a market that is competitive. When a company makes sufficient investments in corporate social responsibility (CSR), brand trust, and brand relationships, those investments will have an impact on the company's brand positioning, which is required as another method to improve the way customers perceive a brand. Consumers' trust in a brand is an essential component in the decision-making process during the purchasing process. It increases the likelihood that a customer will rely on a brand's capability. On the other hand, management and marketing primarily correlate trust with the relationship's competence dimension, which focuses on the partner's belief that they have the necessary abilities to carry out their activities, fulfill their obligations, or keep their promises. Furthermore, the relationship between brand relationship and brand positioning is an indication that managers and marketers should invest more money in reinforcing relationships with existing consumers rather than acquiring new consumers. This is because the relationship between brand relationship and brand positioning is a direct result of the other. Currently, the primary focus of marketing efforts is on developing stronger relationships with customers (Smit & Tolboom, 2007). In addition, managers should view corporate social responsibility not as an expense, a limitation, or an extracurricular activity but rather as a competitive advantage. It is a common assumption that corporate social responsibility can be beneficial to a company in a number of ways, including elevating positive consumer perceptions of the company's image and capabilities, building brand recognition, and expanding the brand's influence (Fu et al., 2014; Li, Fu & Huang, 2015). The corporations need to give careful consideration to these aspects in order to guarantee that their brand positioning will be attained through brand trust, brand relationships, and CSR, and that the quality of the organization will be communicated to the customers.

In conclusion, the findings of this study demonstrated that the favorability of brand positioning is affected by a variety of factors, including the authenticity of the brand, the local iconness of the brand, and the success of the brand (brand trust, brand relationship, and CSR). This research offers a comprehensive analysis of the idea of "favorable brand positioning" as well as the implications that come with it (brand attachment and brand performance). As was covered in Chapter VII, the findings of the study may be useful to those who are financially concerned despite the intangible and sometimes unfamiliar nature of the information. This is especially true when the information is communicated to consumers. One could make the case that the factors in question, as well as the items in question, are susceptible to change based on how customers perceive them. Researchers (Churchill, 1999; Foroudi et al., 2021) argue that survey

research with a high degree of external validity can be generalized to the population and across sectors. One could argue that no single organization can adequately represent all sectors, but these researchers assert that survey research with a high degree of external validity can be generalized. The findings of this study can therefore be extrapolated to apply to a variety of other fields.

8.3 RESEARCH LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE RESEARCH

In this research, a primary delve into the conceptualisation of brand positioning is presented, pertaining to its role in or connection with brand attachment and brand performance. It is imperative, nevertheless, to examine the research findings in consideration of certain relevant limitations in the areas of analysis or sampling method and measurement technique applied which are significant to further research. These are elaborately presented in successive subsections.

8.3.1 Research limitations

The aim of this research is to establish a comprehensive conception of the brand positioning construct, its main antecedents, consequences, moderators, and moderating effects. However, the evaluation of the relevant constructs is not void of limitations. The limitations in the course of the research are organised into two major categories: the method sampling/analysis and measurement level.

8.3.2 The method of sampling/analysis

It is essential to consider the limitations in the present study based on the method of analysis or sampling employed. This research was conducted in the hospitality setting which is within the boundaries of Nigeria. Findings may therefore be environmentally conditioned because the result derivable from other countries may vary, from one country to another. While the researcher constructed the measurement items of the present research based on prior explorations and the qualitative research, the distinguishing features of the Nigerian hotels may more or less impact certain areas of the focal concepts.

In that regard, the limitation is suggestive of further research, and it is recommended that a repeat of this research should be carried out in other countries in order to evaluate the generalisability of the outcome (external validity) (see 8.2.1.3).

At the quantitative stage, the non-probability sampling technique (i.e., a convenience sample

of individuals) was employed due to accessibility barriers to subjects. In other words, participants were selected based on their accessibility and proximity to the researcher. In Churchill (1996), the probability sampling methods are depicted to enable researchers to estimate the amount of sampling error present. The sampling technique is also characterised as a means to eradicate potential bias in terms of validity and generalisability of the scales (Churchill, 1999).

8.3.3 The measurement level

The present study involved the development of new measurement scales, based on extant literature and improved by the findings from the qualitative survey. This was necessary due to the paucity of empirical research in the context. Nevertheless, before the implementation of the subjects, the measurements were carefully tested for validity and reliability. This assessment persisted from designing the research instrument to the data analysis phase.

Because of the survey size and time constraints, the study was carried out within an aspect of a single industry (hotels) and examined based on a single sample. The generalisability of the empirical research is limited as it was carried out only in Nigeria. In that regard, to broaden and improve the projected measurement scales, further research is required. In addition, to enhance the validity of the scales, the research should be repeated but with the scales applied to other samples and countries.

Furthermore, in the course of the research, precisely at the qualitative phase, certain constructs were found to be non-observable in the context which necessitated the rework of the conceptual frameworks.

While there are limitations to the research, these limitations, however, do not diminish the relevance of the findings in the present study. Successive sections suggest potential areas for research extension that would enrich the field of branding and marketing.

8.3.4 Future research avenues

The focus of this study is to establish the favourability of the brand positioning construct and its antecedents and moderators in relation to brand attachment and brand performance. This research attempt creates various potential avenues for further research. In this section, recommendations are detailed with regard to expanding the extant body of knowledge in the literature on brand positioning, its antecedents, moderators, and consequences.

In respect of the measurement and study validation, the present study proposed inclusive scales

of measurement for favourable brand positioning and utilised a mixed-method approach. Thus, in future research, the focus can tilt towards the future application of favourable brand positioning measurement.

As earlier mentioned, the present study was conducted in the hospitality industry, nevertheless, it was limited to hotels. The hospitality industry is composed of various key sectors which are globally widespread and functional. Therefore, future research can investigate the brand positioning construct in relation to attachment and performance as it exists in other sectors of the hospitality industry including the recreational and event sector, the travel and tourism sector, and the food and beverage sector (restaurants). The research may take another angle by conducting a comparative study of hotels and restaurants or another sector.

The research can also be expanded in the aspect of coverage. The present research was conducted within the Nigerian setting and the results may therefore not be generalisable or its generalisability may be assessed. Accordingly, it is recommended that the investigation of the relationship between the focal construct and its related constructs is replicated in other countries.

Additionally, other researchers can carry out a replicated study to gain greater validity and generalisability for the surveyed measurement as the present study utilised exploratory research. Furthermore, in future studies. The scales of the favourable brand positioning, as well as other related constructs, could be examined.

Another aspect of the research worthy of future investigation is the positioning construct of brand alliance fit. Despite previous literature confirming the potential that brand alliance fit (i.e., brand and product fit) has on brand performance and brand attachment, the qualitative findings of the present study revealed that the construct is not obtainable in hotels in the Nigerian setting. Therefore, future research may pursue the construct of brand alliance fit in other sectors of the hospitality industry or in hotels beyond the shores of Nigeria.

Given that the findings revealed some constructs (events, customer online engagement, and brand trust) to be insignificant and sector-conditioned, future research could replicate the study in a different sector of the hospitality industry or beyond, and test for the generalisability of findings on these constructs.

Given the omission of the ideas from leading consulting brands like Interbrands, future research could focus on reviewing the ideas on brand positioning constructs from these branding

consultancies.

8.4 SUMMARY

This study is the first empirical research in the Nigerian hospitality setting. It has contributed vast understanding to the body of knowledge on brand positioning and its relationship with brand attachment and brand performance. The complexity of the research phenomenon necessitated the application of a mixed-method approach in a bid to provide comprehensive and exact findings and conceptualisations. The qualitative research (interviews) permitted the development of a theoretical framework that was analysed in the quantitative research using a survey.

In the research, critical and specific questions were proposed and examined. One of such questions was the impact of methodological decisions by researchers on the strength of brand positioning, its antecedents, its consequences, and its moderators. Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) was employed in the analysis of the data collected which showed satisfactory psychometric properties. In addition, the satisfactory fit indices as well as the construct validity were illustrated in the SEM analysis and revealed that certain pathways were insignificant.

Based on the analysis, the findings specify that: certain factors (local iconness, authenticity, CSR, etc.) influence brand positioning; brand positioning positively impacts brand attachment and performance; and, brand attachment has a favourable relationship with brand performance. Some of the findings were justified based on findings from previous literature, while some were countered. Further studies in the study and in related contexts were suggested because of the limitations found during the course of the research. Recommendations were also provided, one of which is the need to investigate the constructs in other aspects of the hospitality setting (like restaurants).

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APPENDICES

APPENDIX I: Interview Guide

Introduction: Hello, my name is Modupe Olutimehin

Aim of the research: The purpose of this research is to extend the current knowledge of brand positioning within the discipline of marketing. This study examines the main effectiveness of a favourable brand positioning as one of the major components of strategy, branding and marketing of a company to build a sustainable competitive advantage and values; with the intention to give managers guidelines to measure and improve positioning strategies and tactics with emphasis on ethicality to achieve a favourable brand performance and suitability at consumer level.

Your perspective means much to help this research to understand the brand positioning strategy of your company. I give a guarantee that this discussion will be kept completely confidential and not for any commercial purpose. It would be extremely helpful if you would allow me to record our discussion. Whenever you do not feel comfortable about recording something, I can pause the recorder. If there are issues you may not feel comfortable talking about, then we can move on to other issues or topics.

About the interviewee

Title:

Interviewee:

Position:

Personal responsibilities:

How long have you been with the company?

Date:

Have you been involved with the development of the brand positioning strategy for your company? Yes/NO

BRAND POSITIONING: Definition Brand Positioning can be defined as an act of designing the co & Noor,2019) and image (Shahid,2019) to occupy a distinctive place in the mind of consumers rel 2020).		
	What does the terms 'brand positioning' mean to your company?	
	How is brand positioning applied in your company?	
	What are the benefits of brand positioning?	
Additional Question	<p>To what extent, do you think your company/brand is communicating what it is to your customers in order to establish a favourable brand positioning? (Brand Identity) Important?</p> <p>Do you think that the brand positioning of your company is a tool for the achievement of the advantages in competition to other company which is also influencing the perceptions of consumers about your company?</p>	
RQ1-What are the factors that influence brand positioning?		
STRATEGIC ALLIANCE FIT	Definition: Positioning fit can be defined as the extent to which two product categories as well-matched and the consistency of the partner brands (Sarmaniotis et al.,2014; Wason & Charlton 2015) to build a specific, identifiable and desirable image in the mind of the consumer.	
	What do the terms product fit and brand fit mean to you?	
	Brand fit	Definition: Brand fit can be defined as the degree of compatibility or similarity that are perceived by consumers to exist between a social cause and brand (Lafferty 2007; Bigné et al.,2012; Singh et al., 2014).
	Product fit	Definition: Product fit refers to the extent to which consumers perceive the compatibility of the product categories of two brands (Singh, et al., 2012; Moon, & Sprott,2016; Lee et al.,2018).
	To what extent, do you think product fit and brand fit can be applied in your company to achieve a favourable brand positioning? To what extent, do you think your brand, company or services can leverage on other brands or products to achieve a favourable brand positioning? Or any time you have used this strategy to influence brand positioning?	
	To the best of your knowledge, do you think the compatibility or similarity between products or services has influence on the positioning perception of the alliance?	

	To the best of your knowledge, do you think the perceptions of the partner brands have influence on the positioning of the alliance/co-branding?	
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	Brand Identity	Definition: Brand identity can be defined as a unique set of brand associations (Aaker,2012) and defining traits or central ideas (Foroudi et.al.,2017; Buil et.al.,2016) of what a brand is or what it aspires to create or maintain (Aaker,2012) and how it communicates these ideas to different stakeholders (Buil et.al.,2016).
	To what extent, do you think your company is communicating its brand to your customers in order to establish a favourable brand positioning? (Already asked).	
	What is the impact of brand identity on brand fit and product fit to create a favourable brand positioning?	
Additional Question	<p>What is the impact of your company/brand is communicating through the alliance or co-branding towards the positioning perception of consumers?</p> <p>To what extent the visual identity of your brand/company is distinguishable as compared to other brand/company?</p> <p>Do you think the visual identity of your brand/company is easily memorable?</p> <p>Do you think the consumer are able to differentiate between brand/company visual identity from other brand/company?</p>	
ONLINE BRANDING SUCCESS	Definition: Online branding success refers to the online interactive behaviors among consumer and brands which can be analysed to infer interests, understand competitors and perception of the market (Yang et al.,2018, Fantazzini & Toktamysova,2015; Jun & Park 2017; Won et al.,2018; Kulkami et al.,2012) to improve brand positioning.	
	To what extent, does your company engage in online contents to serve the purposes of influencing brand positioning?	
	Customer Online Behavior	Definition: Consumer online behavior is the totality of consumers decision with respect to the consumption and disposition of goods and services through the Internet (Nguyen et al., 2018; Ahuja et al., 2003; Javadi et al.,2012).
	How does your company manage your customer online behaviour to influence brand positioning?	

	To what extent, do you think brand identity could influence on customer online behaviour?	
	To what extent, do you think what your brand is communicating could influence on customer online behaviour?	
Brand Trust	Definition: Brand trust can be said as the consumer's confident beliefs to rely on a brand to deliver promised services or the ability to perform its stated functions (Lee et al., 2015; Molinillo et al.,2017; Sahin et al.,2011).	
	How does your company ensure brand trust?	

	How does your company/brand ensure consumer's confident beliefs to deliver promised services?	
	To what extent, do you think brand identity act as a central force to develop brand trust?	
	To what extent, do you think what your brand is communicating act as a central force to develop consumer's confident beliefs?	
	To what extent, do you think brand trust could influence on brand positioning?	
	To what extent, do you think consumer's confident beliefs influence could influence their perception about your brand?	
Online Review	Definition: Online review can be defined as any form of positive or negative statements made by an actual, former or potential consumer about a company, brand, product, which is available to a multitude of institutions and people through the Internet (Sotiriadis, & Van Zyl, 2013; Chu, & Kim, 2011; Park, & Kim, 2008).	
	How does your company carry out an online review survey?	
	To what extent, do you think online review could influence on brand positioning (perception about your brand)?	
	To the best of your knowledge, do you think brand identity could influence on online review?	
	To the best of your knowledge, do you think what your brand is communicating could influence on online review?	
Additional Question		

CSR	Definition: CSR describes how firms manage the business processes to produce an overall positive (Harjoto & Jo, 2011) to contribute to sustainable economic development, working with employees, their families, the local community, and society to improve their quality of life (Jamali & Mirshak,2007; Pomeroy & Dolnicar,2009).	
	To what extent, does your company or brand engage in CSR activities as an approach to brand positioning?	
	To what extent, do you think CSR activities is an approach to brand positioning?	
	To what extent, do your company make it known to influence the perception or mind of consumers in your favour?	
	To what extent, do you think brand identity act as a central force to engage in CSR activities?	

262

	To what extent, do you think what you/brand are/is trying to communicate is rooted in acting responsibly and making it known?	
Brand Relationship	Definition: Brand relationship can be defined as some sort of bond (physical, emotional or financial) between a brand and person (Veloutsou, & Moutinho, 2009; Smit, Bronner, & Tolboom, 2007; Xie, & Heung,2012) characterised by the unique history of interactions and anticipation of future occurrences (Xie, & Heung,2012).	
	How does your company develop brand relationship with consumers?	
	How does your company/brand develop an intense bond with consumers?	
	To what extent, do you think brand identity can act as a central force to build a strong brand relationship?	
	To what is extent, do you think what your branding is communicating act a central force to build brand relationship?	
	Based on your experience, do you think brand relationship could influence on brand positioning or the mind of the consumers?	

Additional Question		
BRAND LOCAL ICONNESS	Definition: Brand local iconness describes the extent to which a brand is perceived as local player and a symbol or icon connected with the local country (Sichtmann, et al.2019; Halkias et al.,2016) or the use of local resources (Mohan et al.,2018).	
	To what extent, do you think your brand is perceived as a symbol connected with the local country?	
	To what extent, do you think brand positioning can be created after local iconness?	
	To what extent, do you think brand local iconness can impact on attachment towards your brand?	
Additional Question	To what extent, do you think brand local iconness can impact the ‘bond connecting the customer with the brand’?	
BRAND AWARENESS	Definition: Brand awareness is the ability of a consumer to recognize or recall a brand (Kim et al.,2018; Wang et al,2016) that is, all descriptive and evaluative brand-related information, that relates to cognitive illustration of the brand (Foroudi,2019).	
	To what extent, do you think your consumers can recognize or recall your brand?	
	To what extent, do you think brand positioning could influence on brand awareness?	
	To what extent, do you think brand positioning could influence on consumer being able to recognize or recall your brand?	
	To the best of your knowledge, to what extent do you think brand awareness can be associated to build authenticity?	
	To what extent, do you think consumer being able to recognize or recall your brand can linked to ‘evaluation of realness’	
	To what extent, do you think brand awareness can help establish brand local iconness?	
	To what extent, do you think think consumer being able to recognize or recall your brand can help establish being seen as symbol connected with local country?	
Additional Question		
BRAND	Brand attachment is defined as "the strength of the bond connecting the brand	

ATTACHMENT	with the self" (Park et al.,2010, p.2).	
	To what extent, do you think brand attachment can influence brand performance?	

	To what extent, do you think "the strength of the bond connecting the brand to consumers can influence brand performance?		
	Please comment on these elements of brand attachment?		
	Affective	Definition: Affective can be defined as a state of psychological or emotional bond with a brand (Grisaffe, & Nguyen, 2011; Yuksel et al.,2010), creating a fervent commitment to repurchase (Grisaffe, & Nguyen, 2011).	
	Cognitive	Definition: Cognitive refers to ideas and thought evoked by persuasive messages and other forms of advertisements (Sicilia, & Ruiz,2010), forming evaluations and making decisions to purchase (Jamaluddin, Hanafiah, & Zulkifly,2013).	
	Conative	Definition: Conative refers to consumer's behavioral intention to continue repurchasing a brand or products within a certain period or in the future (Ahn, & Back,2018; Manhas, 2010).	
Additional Question			
BRAND WARMTH AND COMPETENCE	What do the terms brand warmth and brand competence mean to you?		
	Brand warmth	Definition: Brand warmth can be defined as the beliefs that brand is about intentions: good or bad (Fang, 2019a; Andrei, & Zait, 2014; Wu et al., 2017).	
	Brand competence	Definition: Brand competence refers to the ability of brand to induce its intentions (Andrei, & Zait, 2014; Wu et al., 2017).	
	To what extent, do you think brand warmth and brand competence can impact the positioning of brand in order to achieve performance?		
	To what extent, do you think brand warmth can be created after brand local iconness and brand authenticity?		
To what extent, do you think brand competence can be created after brand local iconness and brand authenticity?			

	To what extent, do you think brand warmth can impact on attachment towards brand, and ultimately brand performance?	
	To what extent, do you think brand competence can impact on attachment towards brand, and ultimately brand performance?	
Additional Question		
BRAND PERFORMANCE	Definition: Brand performance is the capability of an organization to achieve its organizational goal (Foroudi,2019) and the measure of the brand overall effectiveness perceived by stakeholders (Yang et al.,2015).	
	To what extent, do you think your company is achieving organizational goals?	
	Please comment on the following elements of brand performance and the influence brand positioning them?	
	Brand Loyalty	Definition: Brand loyalty can be defined as a deeply held commitment (Foroudi, 2019; Kim, Choe, & Petrick,2018) or

		biased behavior response expressed overtime (He, Li, & Harris,2012) to rebuy or re-patronized a preferred service or product consistently in the future (Foroudi, 2019).
	Brand Attitude	Definition: Brand attitude can be said as a consumer’s overall evaluation of a brand (Liu et al., 2012; Augusto, & Torres, 2018). This means the degree of like or dislike towards a brand by consumer, or the degree of positivity or negativity of consumer has about a brand (Kaya & Marangoz, 2014).
	Brand Equity	Definition: Brand equity refers to the differential effect (Keller,2016; Datta, et al.,2017) that brand knowledge has on consumer and the response to brand marketing efforts (Keller,2016; Datta, et al.,2017).
	Brand Satisfaction	Definition: Customer satisfaction refers to individual’s perception of how products and services by a company meet or surpass expectation (Lahap et al., 2016; Kaura et al.,2015; Saeidi et al., 2015).
	Brand Reputation	Definition: Brand reputation can be referred to as an immediate picture of a brand based on the aggregated images held over the years (Foroudi,2019) or the perception of quality associated with the name of the brand Bang et al., 2014).

Additional Question		

APPENDIX II: The domain and items of construct in extant literature

Construct	Item Measurement	Major reference
Brand positioning	My hotel brand...	
	The brand has tremendous promise	Foroudi et al. (2019)
	The brand has strong competitors	Foroudi et al. (2019)
	The brand has a unique product and service offering	Foroudi et al. (2019)
	The brand offers different services than other brands.	Vriens & Hofstede (2000)
	The feeling of using the brand's services is attractive to me	Vriens & Hofstede (2000)
	The brand creates a unique image in my mind	The qualitative study
	The brand communicates a sense of superiority	The qualitative study
Customer online engagement	My hotel brand...	
	I often participate in online customer-to-customer interactions for this brand	Christina et al. (2020); Kemp et al. (2020) and qualitative study

	I like actively participating in online customer-to-customer interactions for this brand	Christina et al. (2020); Kemp et al. (2020)
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Construct	Item Measurement	Major reference
	I thoroughly enjoy exchanging ideas with other people online for this brand	Christina et al. (2020); Kemp et al. (2020)
	I am most likely to post about the service experience	Kemp et al. (2020)
	I pay a lot of attention to anything about the brand	Wongkitrungrueng & Assarut (2018)
	I would become a follower of the brand on social media	The qualitative study
	I consider a brand that uses social media my top option when purchasing this type of service	The qualitative study
Brand Trust	My hotel brand...	
	The brand is reliable	Pagani et al. (2019); Song et al. (2019); Gretry et al. (2017); Nyadzayo et al. (2016)
	The brand meets my expectations	Pagani et al. (2019); Song et al. (2019); Gretry et al. (2017); Nyadzayo et al. (2016)
	I feel confident in the brand name	Pagani et al. (2019); Song et al. (2019); Gretry et al. (2017); Nyadzayo et al. (2016)

	The brand makes a conscious effort to maintain its promises to consumers	The qualitative study
	This brand never disappoints me	The qualitative study
	Overall, I trust this brand	Pagani et al. (2019); Song et al. (2019); Gretry et al. (2017); Nyadzayo et al. (2016) and qualitative

Construct	Item Measurement	Major reference
Online review	My hotel brand...	
	Information contained in the online review influences my decision toward a brand	The qualitative study
	When I experience excellent service from a brand, I leave a review online	Zhang et al. (2019); Filieri & McLeay (2014)
	The information I obtain from online reviews is sufficient to meet my needs	Zhang et al. (2019); Filieri & McLeay (2014)
	I put effort into evaluating the provided information	Zhang et al. (2019); Filieri & McLeay (2014)
	The information I get from online reviews enables me to evaluate both the positive and negative elements of the services	Zhang et al. (2019); Filieri & McLeay (2014)
	If I have a relevant suggestion for improving the service, I will communicate it to the company brand via online platforms	Zhang et al. (2019); Filieri & McLeay (2014)

Brand relationship	My hotel brand...	
	My relationship with this brand is very important to me	Veloutsou & Moutinho (2009); Pourazad et al (2019)
	This brand means more to me than other brands	Veloutsou & Moutinho (2009); Pourazad et al (2019)
	This brand has a great deal of personal meaning for me	Veloutsou & Moutinho (2009); Pourazad et al. (2019)

Construct	Item Measurement	Major reference
	This brand is like a person whom I am close to	Pourazad et al. (2019); Hudson et al. (2016); Pourazad et al. (2019)
	This brand and I complement each other	Hudson et al. (2016); Pourazad et al. (2019)
	This brand is a part of me	Hudson et al. (2016); Pourazad et al. (2019)
	This brand has grown in importance to me over time	The qualitative study
CSR	My hotel brand...	
	The brand is a good company	Sierra et al. (2017)
	The brand cares about its consumers and employees	The qualitative study

	This brand is very concerned with the local community	Lai et al. (2010); Diallo & Lambey-Checchin (2017)
	The brand is socially responsible	Diallo & Lambey-Checchin (2017)
	The brand seems to be environmentally responsible	Lai et al. (2010); Diallo & Lambey-Checchin (2017)
	The brand is concerned with environmental protection	Lai et al. (2010)
	The brand always adheres to the law	Diallo & Lambey-Checchin (2017)
	The brand respect moral norms	Lai et al. (2010); Diallo & Lambey-Checchin (2017)
	The brand strives to avoid unethical behaviour	The qualitative study
Event	My hotel brand...	
	I am in favour of events by the brand	Kemp et al. (2020) and qualitative; Shin et al. (2018)
	The brand event makes sense to me	The qualitative study

Construct	Item Measurement	Major reference
	I am pleased to live the experience	Kemp et al. (2020); Shin et al. (2018)
	I am satisfied with the event	Kemp et al. (2020); Shin et al. (2018)

	I like the event	Kemp et al. (2020); Shin et al (2018) and qualitative
	The event is good	Kemp et al. (2020); Shin et al. (2018)
	The event is attractive	Kemp et al. (2020); Shin et al. (2018)
Brand authenticity	My hotel brand...	
	My experiences with the brand have shown me that it keeps its promises	Eggers et al. (2013); Manthiou et al. (2018) and qualitative
	The brand always sticks to its principles	Heinberg (2019); Lude & Prügl. (2018)
	The brand makes a genuine impression	Eggers et al. (2013); Manthiou et al. (2018) and qualitative
	This brand is guided by sincere values	Eggers et al. (2013); Manthiou et al. (2018)
	The brand remains true to its values	Heinberg (2019); Lude & Prügl (2018)
	The brand obviously differentiates itself from the others	The qualitative study
	The brand wants to do its best at providing its service	Heinberg (2019); Lude & Prügl (2018)
Brand local iconness	My hotel brand...	
	To me, this brand represents what our culture is all about	Halkias et al. (2016); Heinberg et al. (2019)

Construct	Item Measurement	Major reference
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	<p>This brand does not represent what our culture is all about</p> <p>I associate this brand with things that are Nigerian</p> <p>I do not associate this brand with things that are Nigerian</p> <p>To me, this brand is a perfect symbol of Nigeria</p> <p>To me, this brand is not a very good symbol of Nigeria</p> <p>This brand means a lot to me, representing my culture</p> <p>This brand helps me to identify my true self</p> <p>To me, this brand represents my culture in the market</p>	<p>Mohan et al. (2018); Halkias et al. (2016)</p> <p>Heinberg et al. (2019); Sichtmann et al. (2019); Halkias et al. (2016)</p> <p>Heinberg et al. (2019); Sichtmann et al. (2019); Halkias et al. (2016)</p> <p>Sichtmann et al. (2019); Halkias et al. (2016)</p> <p>Sichtmann et al. (2019); Halkias et al. (2016)</p> <p>Qualitative</p> <p>Xie et al. (2015)</p> <p>Özsomer (2012)</p>
<p>Brand attachment</p> <p>Cognitive</p>	<p>My hotel brand...</p> <p>I am very attached to the brand</p> <p>I feel better when I use this brand</p> <p>I feel a strong sense of belonging to the brand</p> <p>This brand means a lot to me</p>	<p>Yuksel et al. (2010); Pedersen, & Nysveen (2001) and qualitative Song et al. (2019)</p> <p>Yuksel et al. (2010) Pedersen & Nysveen (2001)</p> <p>Yuksel et al. (2010) Pedersen & Nysveen (2001)</p>

	I will continue to use this brand as long as it provides the best value for me	The qualitative study
	I feel emotionally bonded to this brand	Veloutsou & Moutinho (2009)

Construct	Item Measurement	Major reference
Conative	I consider this brand to be my first choice	Yuksel et al. (2010) Pedersen & Nysveen (2001)
	I will speak about the brand to others	The qualitative study Pedersen & Nysveen (2001)
	I love using this brand	
	I intend to remain a customer of the brand	Yuksel et al. (2010) Pedersen & Nysveen (2001)
	I have found this brand better than others	Taghipourian & Bakhsh (2016)
	I will keep on using the brand for a long time	The qualitative study
Brand performance	My hotel brand...	
Loyalty	This brand will be my first option when choosing accommodation	González-Mansilla et al. (2019) and qualitative
	It makes sense to buy the products or use the services of this brand instead of any other brand	Foroudi (2019); He et al. (2012) and qualitative
	I believe that the features of the brand are well suited to what I like	He et al. (2012)

	My relationship with this brand is one I intend to maintain indefinitely	Nyadzayo et al. (2016)
	I would do almost anything to keep my relationship with this brand	Nyadzayo et al. (2016)
	My relationship with this brand is one I care a great deal about long-term	Nyadzayo et al. (2016)
	I would say good things about this brand to others.	The qualitative study

Construct	Item Measurement	Major reference
Attitude	Overall, I consider myself to be loyal to this brand	The qualitative study
	I am proud to stay in this hotel/or use this brand	Foroudi (2019)
	I can easily imagine the brand in my mind	Foroudi (2019)
	I believe the brand has good serviceability	Foroudi (2019)
	I evaluate the brand as positive	Wolfsteiner et al. (2019)
	I evaluate the brand as good	The qualitative study
	I have a favourable opinion of this brand	The qualitative study
Equity	This brand provides an authentic experience	Tasci & Guillet (2011)
	This brand offers high-quality services	Tasci & Guillet (2011)
	This brand offers good value for money	Tasci & Guillet (2011)

Satisfaction	If I had to choose among different brands offering the same type of service, I would definitely choose this brand	Iglesias et al. (2019)
	Even if another brand has the same qualities, I will choose this one	Iglesias et al. (2019)
	The likelihood that I would reconsider this brand is high	The qualitative study
	Overall, this brand has a significant positive image	The qualitative study
	My choice to use this brand has been a wise one	Japutra & Molinillo (2019)
	I am more satisfied with this brand than other brands	Japutra & Molinillo (2019)
	I am satisfied with the brand service	Song et al. (2019)

Construct	Item Measurement	Major reference
	The performance of this brand has fulfilled my expectations	Song et al. (2019)
	I feel happy using this brand	Song et al. (2019)
	I feel this has provided me with a pleasurable experience	The qualitative study
	Overall, I am pleased with this brand	The qualitative study

Reputation	The brand has a good reputation for providing appropriate services	Foroudi et al. (2019)
	This brand is concerned about consumers	Foroudi et al. (2019)
	This brand constantly tries to improve its services to satisfy its consumers better	Foroudi et al. (2019)
	I think the brand has reliable promises for future performance	Foroudi et al. (2019)
	The brand's reputation influences my choices	The qualitative study
	I believe this brand offers high-quality services	Nguyen et al. (2016); Foroudi et al. (2020)
Brand identity	My hotel brand...	
	This brand stands out from its competitors	He et al. (2012)
	This brand has a distinctive identity	He et al. (2012) and qualitative
	I am familiar with this brand	Sääksjärvi & Samiee (2011) and qualitative

Construct	Item Measurement	Major reference
	This brand is uniquely different from its competitors	Sääksjärvi & Samiee (2011)

	<p>This brand makes an effort to discover consumer needs</p> <p>This brand is consistent over time</p>	<p>The qualitative study</p> <p>The qualitative study</p>
Brand awareness	<p>My hotel brand...</p> <p>The hotel and the services are familiar to me</p> <p>The hotel and the services are well-known in detail</p> <p>Characteristics of the brand come to my mind quickly</p> <p>I can instantly differentiate the brand from other competing ones</p> <p>I can recognise the brand logo or symbol</p> <p>I can recognise this brand's name among other competitors</p> <p>When I think of a service/product category, the brand is always at the top of my mind.</p>	<p>Foroudi (2019) and qualitative</p> <p>Foroudi (2019)</p> <p>Godey et al. (2016); Marques et al. (2020)</p> <p>Godey et al. (2016); Marques et al (2020)</p> <p>González-Mansilla et al. (2019)</p> <p>González-Mansilla et al. (2019) and qualitative</p> <p>Qualitative</p>
Brand warmth	<p>My hotel brand...</p>	

Construct	Item Measurement	Major reference
	<p>I would describe the brand as warm</p> <p>I would describe the brand as friendly</p> <p>I would describe this brand as generous</p> <p>I would describe the brand as good-natured</p> <p>I find it easy to relate with the brand</p> <p>I would describe the brand as kind</p>	<p>Fang (2019); Bernritter et al. (2016); Kolbl (2020)</p> <p>Fang (2019); Bernritter et al. (2016); Kolbl (2020) and qualitative Bernritter et al. (2016)</p> <p>Fang (2019); Bernritter et al. (2016); Kolbl (2020)</p> <p>The qualitative study</p> <p>Kolbl et al. (2020) and qualitative</p>
<p>Brand Competence</p>	<p>My hotel brand...</p> <p>I would describe the brand as competent</p> <p>I would describe the brand as efficient</p> <p>I would describe the brand as capable</p> <p>I would describe the brand as effective</p>	<p>Fang (2019); Bernritter et al. (2016); Kolbl et al (2020)</p> <p>Fang (2019); Bernritter et al (2016); Kolbl et al. (2020)</p> <p>Fang (2019); Bernritter et al (2016); Kolbl et al. (2020)</p> <p>Bernritter et al. (2016)</p>

This brand is good with their work

The qualitative study

Kolbl et al. (2020)

I would describe this brand as intelligent

APPENDIX III: Questionnaire

Brand Positioning- Questionnaire

Aim of the research:

This research is conducted by Modupe Olutimehin, who is currently a Doctoral student at The University of the West of Scotland, London campus, UK. This research aims to examine the influence of brand positioning on brand attachment and brand performance.

Your perspectives about the brand positioning of this hotel or restaurant is what the survey intends to know. Your cooperation is critical to the successful completion of this project, as this success of this research depends on the information provided by consumers like you.

Responding to the questionnaire is entirely voluntary. Your participation and all data collected will remain anonymous, and responses will only be presented in an aggregated form without revealing individual identities. The questionnaire should take no more than 15-20 minutes to complete.

Many thanks in advance for your contribution!

Yours sincerely,

Modupe Olutimehin
UWS Business School
The University of the West of
Scotland UWS London campus, SE1
6NP

Brand Positioning- Questionnaire

1. Please indicate your general impressions about your hotel/restaurant brand positioning

Check all that apply.

S t r o n g l y D i s a g r e e	Disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neutral	Somewhat agree	Agree	Strongly agree
--	----------	----------------------	---------	-------------------	-------	-------------------

The brand has a tremendous promise

<input type="checkbox"/>						
--------------------------	--------------------------	--------------------------	--------------------------	--------------------------	--------------------------	--------------------------

The brand has strong competitors

<input type="checkbox"/>						
--------------------------	--------------------------	--------------------------	--------------------------	--------------------------	--------------------------	--------------------------

The brand has a unique product and service offering

<input type="checkbox"/>						
--------------------------	--------------------------	--------------------------	--------------------------	--------------------------	--------------------------	--------------------------

The brand offers different services than other brands.

<input type="checkbox"/>						
--------------------------	--------------------------	--------------------------	--------------------------	--------------------------	--------------------------	--------------------------

The feeling of using the brand's services is attractive to me

The brand creates a unique image in my mind

	<input type="checkbox"/>						
--	--------------------------	--------------------------	--------------------------	--------------------------	--------------------------	--------------------------	--------------------------

The brand communicates a sense of superiority

	<input type="checkbox"/>						
--	--------------------------	--------------------------	--------------------------	--------------------------	--------------------------	--------------------------	--------------------------

I have a favourable opinion of this brand

	<input type="checkbox"/>						
--	--------------------------	--------------------------	--------------------------	--------------------------	--------------------------	--------------------------	--------------------------

This brand stands out for me

	<input type="checkbox"/>						
--	--------------------------	--------------------------	--------------------------	--------------------------	--------------------------	--------------------------	--------------------------

2. Please indicate your general impressions about brand authenticity of your hotel/restaurant brand positioning

Check all that apply.

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neutral	Somewhat agree	Agree	Strongly agree
My experiences with the brand have shown me that it keeps promises	<input type="checkbox"/>						
The brand always sticks to its principles	<input type="checkbox"/>						
The brand makes a genuine impression	<input type="checkbox"/>						
This brand is guided by sincere values	<input type="checkbox"/>						
The brand remains true to its values	<input type="checkbox"/>						
The brand obviously differentiates itself from the others	<input type="checkbox"/>						
The brand wants to do its best at providing its service	<input type="checkbox"/>						

3. Please indicate your general impressions about brand local iconness of your hotel/restaurant brand positioning

Check all that apply.

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neutral	Somewhat agree	Agree	Strongly agree
To me, this brand represents what our culture is all about	<input type="checkbox"/>						
This brand does not represent what our culture is all about	<input type="checkbox"/>						
I associate this brand with things that are Nigerian	<input type="checkbox"/>						
I do not associate this brand with things that are Nigerian	<input type="checkbox"/>						
To me, this brand is a perfect symbol of Nigeria	<input type="checkbox"/>						
To me, this brand is not a very good symbol of Nigeria	<input type="checkbox"/>						

This brand means a lot to me, representing my culture

This brand helps me to identify my true self

4. Please indicate your general impressions about online engagement of your hotel/restaurant brand positioning

Check all that apply.

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neutral	Somewhat agree	Agree	Strongly agree
I often participate in online customer-to-customer interactions for this brand	<input type="checkbox"/>						
I thoroughly enjoy exchanging ideas with other people online for this brand	<input type="checkbox"/>						
I am most likely to post about the service experience	<input type="checkbox"/>						
I pay a lot of attention to anything about the brand	<input type="checkbox"/>						
I would become a follower of the brand on social media	<input type="checkbox"/>						

I consider a
brand that
uses social
media my
top option
when
purchasing
this type of
service

5. Please indicate your general impressions about brand trust of your hotel/restaurant brand positioning

Check all that apply.

	Strongly Disagree	Diasgree	Somewhat disagree	Neutral	Somewhat agree	Agree	Strongly agree
The brand is reliable	<input type="checkbox"/>						
The brand meets my expectations	<input type="checkbox"/>						
I feel confident in the brand name	<input type="checkbox"/>						
The brand makes a conscious effort to maintain its promises to consumers	<input type="checkbox"/>						
This brand never disappoints me	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Overall, I trust this brand	<input type="checkbox"/>						

6. 6. Please indicate your general impressions about online review of your hotel/restaurant brand positioning

Check all that apply.

	Strongly Disagree	Diasgree	Somewhat disagree	Neutral	Somewhat agree	Agree	Strongly agree
Information contained in the online review influence my decision toward a brand	<input type="checkbox"/>						
When I experience excellent service from a brand, I leave a review online	<input type="checkbox"/>						
The information I obtain from online reviews is sufficient to meet my needs	<input type="checkbox"/>						
I put effort to evaluate the provided information	<input type="checkbox"/>						
The information I get from online reviews enables me to evaluate both the positive and negative elements of the services	<input type="checkbox"/>						

if I have a

relevant
suggestion
for

improving

the service,

I will
communicate
it to the
company
brand via
online
platforms

7. Please indicate your general impressions about brand relationship of your hotel/restaurant brand positioning

Check all that apply.

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neutral	Somewhat agree	Agree	Strongly agree
My relationship with this brand is very important to me	<input type="checkbox"/>						
This brand means more to me than other brands	<input type="checkbox"/>						
This brand has a great deal of personal meaning for me	<input type="checkbox"/>						
This brand is like a person with whom I am close to	<input type="checkbox"/>						
This brand and I complement each other	<input type="checkbox"/>						
This brand is a part of me	<input type="checkbox"/>						
This brand has grown in importance to me over time	<input type="checkbox"/>						

8. Please indicate your general impressions about corporate social responsibility (CSR) of your hotel/restaurant brand positioning

Check all that apply.

	Strongly Disagree	Diasgree	Somewhat disagree	Neutral	Somewhat agree	Agree	Strongly agree
The brand is a good company	<input type="checkbox"/>						
The brand cares about its consumers and employees	<input type="checkbox"/>						
This brand is very concerned with the local community	<input type="checkbox"/>						
The brand is socially responsible	<input type="checkbox"/>						
The brand seems to be environmentally responsible	<input type="checkbox"/>						
The brand always adheres to the law	<input type="checkbox"/>						
The brand respect moral norms	<input type="checkbox"/>						
The brand strives to avoid unethical behaviour	<input type="checkbox"/>						

9. Please indicate your general impressions about events of your hotel/restaurant brand positioning

Check all that apply.

	Strongly Disagree	Diasgree	Somewhat disagree	Neutral	Somewhat agree	Agree	Strongly agree
I am in favour of events by the brand	<input type="checkbox"/>						
The event makes sense to me	<input type="checkbox"/>						
I am pleased to live the experience	<input type="checkbox"/>						
I am satisfied with the event	<input type="checkbox"/>						
I like the event	<input type="checkbox"/>						
The event is attractive	<input type="checkbox"/>						

10. The section below is to understand your impression of cognitive behaviours towards the brand positioning. Please indicate your degree of agreement or disagreement with the following statements.

Check all that apply.

	Strongly Disagree	Diasgree	Somewhat disagree	Neutral	Somewhat agree	Agree	Strongly agree
I am very attached to the brand	<input type="checkbox"/>						
I feel better when I use this brand	<input type="checkbox"/>						
I feel a strong sense of belonging to the brand	<input type="checkbox"/>						
This brand means a lot to me	<input type="checkbox"/>						
I will continue to use this brand as long as it provides the best value for me	<input type="checkbox"/>						
I feel emotionally bonded to this brand	<input type="checkbox"/>						

11. 11. The section below is to understand your impression of conative behaviours towards the brand positioning. Please indicate your degree of agreement or disagreement with the following statements.

Check all that apply.

	Strongly Disagree	Diasgree	Somewhat disagree	Neutral	Somewhat agree	Agree	Strongly agree
I consider this brand to be my first choice	<input type="checkbox"/>						
I will speak about the brand to others	<input type="checkbox"/>						
I love using this brand	<input type="checkbox"/>						
I intend to remain a customer of the brand	<input type="checkbox"/>						
I have found this brand better than others	<input type="checkbox"/>						
I will keep on using the brand for a long time	<input type="checkbox"/>						

12. The section below examines your loyalty. Please indicate your degree of agreement or disagreement with the following statements.

Check all that apply.

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neutral	Somewhat agree	Agree
This brand will be my first option when choosing accommodation/restaurant	<input type="checkbox"/>					
I believe that the features of the brand are well suited to what I like	<input type="checkbox"/>					
My relationship with this brand is one I intend to maintain indefinitely	<input type="checkbox"/>					
I would do almost anything to keep my relationship with this brand	<input type="checkbox"/>					
I would say good stuff about this brand to others.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
My relationship with this brand is one I care a great deal about long-term	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Overall, I consider myself to be loyal to this brand	<input type="checkbox"/>					

13. The section below examines the brand attitude. Please indicate your degree of agreement or disagreement with the following statements.

Check all that apply.

	Strongly Disagree	Diasgree	Somewhat disagree	Neutral	Somewhat agree	Agree	Strongly agree
I am proud to stay in this hotel/or use this brand	<input type="checkbox"/>						
I can easily imagine the brand in my mind	<input type="checkbox"/>						
I believe the brand has good serviceability	<input type="checkbox"/>						
I evaluate the brand as positive	<input type="checkbox"/>						
I evaluate the brand as good	<input type="checkbox"/>						
I have a favourable opinion of this brand	<input type="checkbox"/>						

14. 14. The section below examines the brand equity. Please indicate your degree of agreement or disagreement with the following statements.

Check all that apply.

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neutral	Somewhat agree	Agree	Strongly agree
This brand provides an authentic experience	<input type="checkbox"/>						
This brand offers high-quality services	<input type="checkbox"/>						
This brand offers good value for money	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Even if another brand has the same qualities, I will choose this one	<input type="checkbox"/>						
The likelihood that I would reconsider this brand is high	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Overall, this brand has a significant positive image	<input type="checkbox"/>						

15. 15. The section below examines the satisfaction. Please indicate your degree of agreement or disagreement with the following statements.

Check all that apply.

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neutral	Somewhat agree	Agree	Strongly agree
My choice to use this brand has been a wise one	<input type="checkbox"/>						
I am more satisfied with this brand than other brands	<input type="checkbox"/>						
I am satisfied with the brand service	<input type="checkbox"/>						
The performance of this brand has fulfilled my expectations	<input type="checkbox"/>						
I feel happy using this brand	<input type="checkbox"/>						
I feel this has provided me with a pleasurable experience	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Overall, I am pleased with this brand	<input type="checkbox"/>						

16. 16. The section below examines the brand reputation. Please indicate your degree of agreement or disagreement with the following statements.

Check all that apply.

	Strongly Disagree	Diasgree	Somewhat disagree	Neutral	Somewhat agree	Agree	Strongly agree
The brand has a good reputation for providing appropriate services	<input type="checkbox"/>						
This brand is concerned about consumers	<input type="checkbox"/>						
This brand constantly tries to improve its services to satisfy its consumers better	<input type="checkbox"/>						
I think the brand has reliable promises for future performance	<input type="checkbox"/>						
The brand's reputation influences my choices	<input type="checkbox"/>						
I believe this brand offers high-quality services	<input type="checkbox"/>						

17. The section below is prepared to understand your impression about brand identity.
 Please indicate your degree of agreement or disagreement with the following statements.

Check all that apply.

	Strongly Disagree	Diasgree	Somewhat disagree	Neutral	Somewhat agree	Agree	Strongly agree
This brand stands out from its competitors	<input type="checkbox"/>						
This brand has a distinctive identity	<input type="checkbox"/>						
I am familiar with this brand	<input type="checkbox"/>						
This brand is uniquely different from its competitors	<input type="checkbox"/>						
This brand makes an effort to discover consumer needs	<input type="checkbox"/>						
This brand is consistent over time	<input type="checkbox"/>						

18. The section below is prepared to understand your impression about brand awareness. Please indicate your degree of agreement or disagreement with the following statements.

Check all that apply.

	Strongly Disagree	Diasgree	Somewhat disagree	Neutral	Somewhat agree	Agree	Strongly agree
The hotel and the services are familiar to me	<input type="checkbox"/>						
The hotel and the services are well-known in detail	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Characteristics of the brand come to my mind quickly	<input type="checkbox"/>						
I can instantly differentiate the brand from other competing ones	<input type="checkbox"/>						
I can recognise the brand logo or symbol	<input type="checkbox"/>						
I can recognise this brand's name among other competitors	<input type="checkbox"/>						
When I think of a service/product category, the brand is always at the top of my mind.	<input type="checkbox"/>						

19. The section below is prepared to understand your impression about the brand warmth. Please indicate your degree of agreement or disagreement with the following statements.

Check all that apply.

	Strongly Disagree	Diasgree	Somewhat disagree	Neutral	Somewhat agree	Agree	Strongly agree
I would describe the brand as warm	<input type="checkbox"/>						
I would describe the brand as friendly	<input type="checkbox"/>						
I would describe this brand as generous	<input type="checkbox"/>						
I would describe the brand as good-natured	<input type="checkbox"/>						
I find it easy to relate with the brand	<input type="checkbox"/>						
I would describe the brand as kind	<input type="checkbox"/>						

20. The section below is prepared to understand your impression about the brand competence. Please indicate your degree of agreement or disagreement with the following statements.

Check all that apply.

	Strongly Disagree	Diasgree	Somewhat disagree	Neutral	Somewhat agree	Agree	Strongly agree
I would describe the brand as competent	<input type="checkbox"/>						
I would describe the brand as efficient	<input type="checkbox"/>						
I would describe the brand as capable	<input type="checkbox"/>						
I would describe the brand as effective	<input type="checkbox"/>						
I would describe this brand as intelligent	<input type="checkbox"/>						
This brand is good with their work	<input type="checkbox"/>						

A FEW THINGS ABOUT YOURSELF

21. 1. What is your gender?

Mark only one oval.

- Male
- Female
- Prefer not to say

22. 2. What is your age group?

Mark only one oval.

- Under 25 Years
- 25 - 30 years
- 30 - 40 years
- Above 40
- years Prefer
not to say

23. 3. What is the highest degree or level of education you have completed?

Mark only one oval.

- Below
- bachelor
- Bachelor

- Masters
- Ph.D./
- Doctorate
- Prefer not to
say

4. Please specify the most appropriate option below that indicates your employment status
(tick only one)

24. I am currently employed

Mark only one oval.

- Top executive or manager
- Owner of a company
- Lawyer, dentist or architect etc.
- Office/clerical staffs
- Worker
- Civil
- servant
- Craftsman
- Other

25. I am currently employed

Mark only one oval.

- Student
- Housewife
- Retired

I want to express my gratitude for your precious time and kind cooperation. The sequence of the questions was based on recommendations by Krueger (1994).

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APPENDIX III: Missing data examination at item level

<i>Items</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Missing</i>
<i>BPQ1</i>	<i>4.41</i>	<i>1.674</i>	<i>.0</i>
<i>BPQ2</i>	<i>4.21</i>	<i>1.544</i>	<i>.0</i>
<i>BPQ3</i>	<i>4.67</i>	<i>1.500</i>	<i>.0</i>
<i>BPQ4</i>	<i>4.95</i>	<i>.954</i>	<i>.0</i>
<i>BPQ5</i>	<i>4.41</i>	<i>1.452</i>	<i>.0</i>
<i>BPQ6</i>	<i>4.73</i>	<i>1.209</i>	<i>.0</i>
<i>BPQ7</i>	<i>4.43</i>	<i>1.465</i>	<i>.0</i>
<i>BPQ8</i>	<i>4.45</i>	<i>1.436</i>	<i>.0</i>
<i>BPQ9</i>	<i>4.29</i>	<i>1.422</i>	<i>.0</i>
<i>BAQ1</i>	<i>4.67</i>	<i>1.329</i>	<i>.0</i>
<i>BAQ2</i>	<i>4.31</i>	<i>1.596</i>	<i>.0</i>
<i>BAQ3</i>	<i>4.73</i>	<i>1.368</i>	<i>.0</i>
<i>BAQ4</i>	<i>4.55</i>	<i>1.466</i>	<i>.0</i>
<i>BAQ5</i>	<i>4.53</i>	<i>1.466</i>	<i>.0</i>
<i>BAQ6</i>	<i>4.47</i>	<i>1.500</i>	<i>.0</i>

<i>BAQ7</i>	<i>4.90</i>	<i>1.212</i>	<i>.0</i>
<i>BLIQ1</i>	<i>4.38</i>	<i>1.468</i>	<i>.0</i>
<i>BLIQ2</i>	<i>4.20</i>	<i>1.648</i>	<i>.0</i>
<i>BLIQ3</i>	<i>3.92</i>	<i>1.746</i>	<i>.0</i>
<i>BLIQ4</i>	<i>4.13</i>	<i>1.554</i>	<i>.0</i>
<i>BLIQ5</i>	<i>3.99</i>	<i>1.495</i>	<i>.0</i>
<i>BLIQ6</i>	<i>4.06</i>	<i>1.510</i>	<i>.0</i>
<i>BLIQ7</i>	<i>4.01</i>	<i>1.603</i>	<i>.0</i>
<i>BLIQ8</i>	<i>4.16</i>	<i>1.496</i>	<i>.0</i>
<i>OE1</i>	<i>4.15</i>	<i>1.549</i>	<i>.0</i>
<i>OE2</i>	<i>4.22</i>	<i>1.366</i>	<i>.0</i>
<i>OE3</i>	<i>4.02</i>	<i>1.599</i>	<i>.0</i>
<i>OE4</i>	<i>3.98</i>	<i>1.461</i>	<i>.0</i>
<i>OE5</i>	<i>4.07</i>	<i>1.526</i>	<i>.0</i>
<i>OE6</i>	<i>4.07</i>	<i>1.430</i>	<i>.0</i>

<i>BT1</i>	4.22	1.404	.0
<i>BT2</i>	4.22	1.418	.0
<i>BT3</i>	4.30	1.474	.0
<i>BT4</i>	4.68	1.435	.0
<i>BT5</i>	4.84	.842	.0
<i>BT6</i>	4.42	1.458	.0
<i>OR1</i>	4.67	1.095	.0
<i>OR2</i>	4.39	1.434	.0
<i>OR3</i>	4.41	1.420	.0
<i>OR4</i>	4.15	1.451	.0
<i>OR5</i>	4.57	1.209	.0
<i>OR6</i>	4.23	1.623	.0
<i>BR1</i>	4.64	1.379	.0
<i>BR2</i>	4.47	1.272	.0

<i>BR3</i>	<i>4.51</i>	<i>1.467</i>	<i>.0</i>
<i>BR4</i>	<i>4.43</i>	<i>1.400</i>	<i>.0</i>
<i>BR5</i>	<i>4.96</i>	<i>1.241</i>	<i>.0</i>
<i>BR6</i>	<i>4.60</i>	<i>1.441</i>	<i>.0</i>
<i>BR7</i>	<i>4.34</i>	<i>1.680</i>	<i>.0</i>
<i>CSRQ1</i>	<i>4.04</i>	<i>1.828</i>	<i>.0</i>
<i>CSRQ2</i>	<i>4.37</i>	<i>1.631</i>	<i>.0</i>
<i>CSRQ3</i>	<i>4.22</i>	<i>1.692</i>	<i>.0</i>
<i>CSRQ4</i>	<i>4.12</i>	<i>1.618</i>	<i>.0</i>
<i>CSRQ5</i>	<i>4.05</i>	<i>1.749</i>	<i>.0</i>
<i>CSRQ6</i>	<i>4.18</i>	<i>1.593</i>	<i>.0</i>
<i>CSRQ7</i>	<i>4.11</i>	<i>1.485</i>	<i>.0</i>
<i>CSRQ8</i>	<i>4.28</i>	<i>1.407</i>	<i>.0</i>
<i>EvQ1</i>	<i>4.00</i>	<i>1.630</i>	<i>.0</i>
<i>EvQ2</i>	<i>4.06</i>	<i>1.632</i>	<i>.0</i>

<i>EvQ3</i>	<i>4.09</i>	<i>1.622</i>	<i>.0</i>
<i>EvQ4</i>	<i>4.17</i>	<i>1.655</i>	<i>.0</i>
<i>EvQ5</i>	<i>4.33</i>	<i>1.488</i>	<i>.0</i>

<i>EvQ6</i>	<i>4.49</i>	<i>1.615</i>	<i>.0</i>
<i>CogQ1</i>	<i>4.19</i>	<i>1.500</i>	<i>.0</i>
<i>CogQ2</i>	<i>4.53</i>	<i>1.482</i>	<i>.0</i>
<i>CogQ3</i>	<i>4.91</i>	<i>1.181</i>	<i>.0</i>
<i>CogQ4</i>	<i>4.43</i>	<i>1.495</i>	<i>.0</i>
<i>CogQ5</i>	<i>4.57</i>	<i>1.245</i>	<i>.0</i>
<i>CogQ6</i>	<i>4.25</i>	<i>1.357</i>	<i>.0</i>

<i>ConQ1</i>	<i>4.43</i>	<i>1.392</i>	<i>.0</i>
<i>ConQ2</i>	<i>4.27</i>	<i>1.375</i>	<i>.0</i>
<i>ConQ3</i>	<i>4.61</i>	<i>1.154</i>	<i>.0</i>
<i>ConQ4</i>	<i>4.29</i>	<i>1.542</i>	<i>.0</i>
<i>ConQ5</i>	<i>4.69</i>	<i>1.313</i>	<i>.0</i>

<i>ConQ6</i>	<i>4.49</i>	<i>1.304</i>	<i>.0</i>
<i>LoyQ1</i>	<i>4.33</i>	<i>1.355</i>	<i>.0</i>
<i>LoyQ2</i>	<i>4.16</i>	<i>1.233</i>	<i>.0</i>

<i>LoyQ3</i>	<i>4.64</i>	<i>1.134</i>	<i>.0</i>
<i>LoyQ4</i>	<i>4.44</i>	<i>1.294</i>	<i>.0</i>
<i>LoyQ5</i>	<i>4.18</i>	<i>1.488</i>	<i>.0</i>
<i>LoyQ6</i>	<i>3.76</i>	<i>1.405</i>	<i>.0</i>
<i>LoyQ7</i>	<i>4.08</i>	<i>1.419</i>	<i>.0</i>
<i>BraQ1</i>	<i>4.22</i>	<i>1.797</i>	<i>.0</i>
<i>BraQ2</i>	<i>4.18</i>	<i>1.752</i>	<i>.0</i>
<i>BraQ3</i>	<i>4.13</i>	<i>1.802</i>	<i>.0</i>
<i>BraQ4</i>	<i>4.40</i>	<i>1.756</i>	<i>.0</i>
<i>BraQ5</i>	<i>4.30</i>	<i>1.687</i>	<i>.0</i>
<i>BraQ6</i>	<i>4.32</i>	<i>1.537</i>	<i>.0</i>

<i>BrqQ1</i>	4.08	1.702	.0
<i>BrqQ2</i>	4.08	1.625	.0
<i>BrqQ3</i>	4.11	1.665	.0
<i>BrqQ4</i>	4.29	1.662	.0
<i>BrqQ5</i>	4.22	1.473	.0

<i>BrqQ6</i>	4.39	1.519	.0
<i>SatQ1</i>	4.31	1.547	.0
<i>SatQ2</i>	4.69	1.413	.0
<i>SatQ3</i>	5.01	1.027	.0
<i>SatQ4</i>	4.48	1.496	.0
<i>SatQ5</i>	4.77	1.200	.0
<i>SatQ6</i>	4.45	1.480	.0
<i>SatQ7</i>	4.41	1.405	.0
<i>BrpQ1</i>	4.56	1.697	.0
<i>BrpQ2</i>	4.69	1.246	.0

<i>BrpQ3</i>	<i>4.43</i>	<i>1.681</i>	<i>.0</i>
<i>BrpQ4</i>	<i>4.73</i>	<i>1.427</i>	<i>.0</i>
<i>BrpQ5</i>	<i>4.51</i>	<i>1.467</i>	<i>.0</i>
<i>BrpQ6</i>	<i>4.43</i>	<i>1.394</i>	<i>.0</i>
<i>BidQ1</i>	<i>4.45</i>	<i>1.579</i>	<i>.0</i>

<i>BidQ2</i>	<i>4.92</i>	<i>1.255</i>	<i>.0</i>
<i>BidQ3</i>	<i>4.58</i>	<i>1.484</i>	<i>.0</i>
<i>BidQ4</i>	<i>4.38</i>	<i>1.743</i>	<i>.0</i>
<i>BidQ5</i>	<i>3.98</i>	<i>1.777</i>	<i>.0</i>
<i>BidQ6</i>	<i>4.27</i>	<i>1.568</i>	<i>.0</i>

<i>BawQ1</i>	<i>4.18</i>	<i>1.610</i>	<i>.0</i>
<i>BawQ2</i>	<i>4.16</i>	<i>1.664</i>	<i>.0</i>
<i>BawQ3</i>	<i>4.09</i>	<i>1.782</i>	<i>.0</i>
<i>BawQ4</i>	<i>4.18</i>	<i>1.554</i>	<i>.0</i>
<i>BawQ5</i>	<i>4.28</i>	<i>1.572</i>	<i>.0</i>

<i>BawQ6</i>	<i>4.22</i>	<i>1.439</i>	<i>.0</i>
<i>BawQ7</i>	<i>4.10</i>	<i>1.695</i>	<i>.0</i>
<i>BrwQ1</i>	<i>4.18</i>	<i>1.756</i>	<i>.0</i>
<i>BrwQ2</i>	<i>4.17</i>	<i>1.714</i>	<i>.0</i>
<i>BrwQ3</i>	<i>4.13</i>	<i>1.646</i>	<i>.0</i>
<i>BrwQ4</i>	<i>4.22</i>	<i>1.416</i>	<i>.0</i>

<i>BrwQ5</i>	<i>4.25</i>	<i>1.771</i>	<i>.0</i>
<i>BrwQ6</i>	<i>4.51</i>	<i>1.368</i>	<i>.0</i>
<i>BrcQ1</i>	<i>4.37</i>	<i>1.635</i>	<i>.0</i>
<i>BrcQ2</i>	<i>4.40</i>	<i>1.554</i>	<i>.0</i>
<i>BrcQ3</i>	<i>4.67</i>	<i>1.472</i>	<i>.0</i>
<i>BrcQ4</i>	<i>4.17</i>	<i>1.587</i>	<i>.0</i>
<i>BrcQ5</i>	<i>4.61</i>	<i>1.407</i>	<i>.0</i>
<i>BrcQ6</i>	<i>4.37</i>	<i>1.597</i>	<i>.0</i>

APPENDIX IV: Normal probability Q-Q plot

APPENDIX V: TOTAL VARIANCE EXPLAINED

Component	Initial eigenvalues			Extraction sums of squared loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	63.864	48.382	48.382	63.864	48.382	48.382
2	9.581	7.258	55.640	9.581	7.258	55.640
3	8.349	6.325	61.965	8.349	6.325	61.965
4	5.084	3.852	65.817	5.084	3.852	65.817
5	3.260	2.469	68.286	3.260	2.469	68.286
6	2.684	2.034	70.320	2.684	2.034	70.320
7	2.599	1.969	72.289	2.599	1.969	72.289
8	2.325	1.761	74.050	2.325	1.761	74.050
9	2.142	1.623	75.673	2.142	1.623	75.673
10	1.888	1.430	77.103	1.888	1.430	77.103
11	1.832	1.388	78.491	1.832	1.388	78.491
12	1.742	1.320	79.811	1.742	1.320	79.811
13	1.492	1.130	80.941	1.492	1.130	80.941
14	1.394	1.056	81.997	1.394	1.056	81.997
15	1.330	1.007	83.005	1.330	1.007	83.005
16	1.225	.928	83.932	1.225	.928	83.932
17	1.193	.904	84.836	1.193	.904	84.836
18	1.109	.840	85.676	1.109	.840	85.676
19	1.095	.830	86.506	1.095	.830	86.506
20	1.019	.772	87.278	1.019	.772	87.278
21	.899	.681	87.959			
22	.875	.663	88.623			
23	.818	.620	89.242			
24	.780	.591	89.833			
25	.741	.562	90.394			
26	.726	.550	90.945			
27	.671	.508	91.453			
28	.633	.480	91.933			

29	.570	.431	92.364
30	.555	.420	92.784
31	.523	.396	93.180
32	.502	.380	93.560
33	.483	.366	93.926
34	.449	.340	94.266
35	.437	.331	94.597
36	.421	.319	94.916
37	.398	.302	95.218
38	.389	.295	95.513
39	.373	.283	95.796
40	.369	.280	96.076
41	.343	.259	96.335
42	.319	.242	96.577
43	.307	.233	96.810
44	.281	.213	97.023
45	.258	.195	97.218
46	.255	.193	97.411
47	.239	.181	97.593
48	.230	.174	97.767
49	.220	.167	97.933
50	.204	.155	98.088
51	.194	.147	98.235
52	.176	.133	98.369
53	.167	.126	98.495

Component	Initial eigenvalues			Extraction sums of squared loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
54	.154	.117	98.612			
55	.148	.112	98.724			
56	.136	.103	98.827			

57	.118	.089	98.917
58	.116	.088	99.005
59	.113	.086	99.091
60	.107	.081	99.172
61	.097	.073	99.245
62	.082	.062	99.307
63	.075	.057	99.364
64	.074	.056	99.420
65	.072	.055	99.474
66	.069	.052	99.527
67	.059	.045	99.572
68	.057	.043	99.615
69	.052	.040	99.654
70	.051	.038	99.693
71	.044	.033	99.726
72	.040	.030	99.756
73	.035	.026	99.782
74	.033	.025	99.807
75	.032	.024	99.832
76	.028	.021	99.853
77	.025	.019	99.872
78	.023	.018	99.890
79	.022	.016	99.906
80	.017	.013	99.919
81	.016	.012	99.932
82	.014	.010	99.942
83	.012	.009	99.951
84	.011	.008	99.960
85	.009	.007	99.966
86	.008	.006	99.973
87	.007	.005	99.978
88	.005	.004	99.982

89	.004	.003	99.985
90	.004	.003	99.988
91	.003	.003	99.991
92	.003	.002	99.993
93	.002	.002	99.995
94	.002	.001	99.996
95	.002	.001	99.998
96	.001	.001	99.998
97	.001	.001	99.999
98	.001	.001	100.000
99	.000	.000	100.000
100	1.065E-14	8.069E-15	100.000
101	9.617E-15	7.285E-15	100.000
102	8.751E-15	6.629E-15	100.000
103	8.398E-15	6.362E-15	100.000
104	8.229E-15	6.234E-15	100.000
105	7.038E-15	5.332E-15	100.000
106	5.605E-15	4.246E-15	100.000
107	4.904E-15	3.715E-15	100.000

Component	Initial eigenvalues			Extraction sums of squared loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
108	4.647E-15	3.520E-15	100.000			
109	4.445E-15	3.367E-15	100.000			
110	3.764E-15	2.852E-15	100.000			
111	3.297E-15	2.498E-15	100.000			
112	2.827E-15	2.142E-15	100.000			
113	2.447E-15	1.854E-15	100.000			
114	1.858E-15	1.408E-15	100.000			
115	1.281E-15	9.702E-16	100.000			
116	7.821E-16	5.925E-16	100.000			

117	4.833E-17	3.661E-17	100.000
118	-5.767E-16	-4.369E-16	100.000
119	-9.051E-16	-6.857E-16	100.000
120	-1.404E-15	-1.064E-15	100.000
121	-1.769E-15	-1.340E-15	100.000
122	-2.798E-15	-2.120E-15	100.000
123	-3.232E-15	-2.449E-15	100.000
124	-3.621E-15	-2.743E-15	100.000
125	-3.866E-15	-2.929E-15	100.000
126	-4.878E-15	-3.696E-15	100.000
127	-5.569E-15	-4.219E-15	100.000
128	-6.552E-15	-4.963E-15	100.000
129	-6.709E-15	-5.083E-15	100.000
130	-8.275E-15	-6.269E-15	100.000
131	-9.496E-15	-7.194E-15	100.000
132	-1.104E-14	-8.360E-15	100.000
121	-1.769E-15	-1.340E-15	100.000
122	-2.798E-15	-2.120E-15	100.000
123	-3.232E-15	-2.449E-15	100.000
124	-3.621E-15	-2.743E-15	100.000
125	-3.866E-15	-2.929E-15	100.000
126	-4.878E-15	-3.696E-15	100.000
127	-5.569E-15	-4.219E-15	100.000
128	-6.552E-15	-4.963E-15	100.000
129	-6.709E-15	-5.083E-15	100.000
130	-8.275E-15	-6.269E-15	100.000
131	-9.496E-15	-7.194E-15	100.000
132	-1.104E-14	-8.360E-15	100.000

Extraction method: Principal component analysis

APPENDIX VI: Factor loadings

<i>Items</i>	<i>1</i>	<i>2</i>	<i>3</i>	<i>4</i>	<i>5</i>	<i>6</i>	<i>7</i>	<i>8</i>	<i>9</i>	<i>10</i>	<i>11</i>	<i>12</i>	<i>13</i>	<i>14</i>	<i>15</i>	<i>16</i>	<i>17</i>	<i>18</i>	<i>19</i>	<i>20</i>
<i>BPQ1</i>	.834																			
<i>BPQ2</i>	.868																			
<i>BPQ3</i>	.859																			
<i>BPQ4</i>	.874																			
<i>BPQ5</i>	.895																			
<i>BPQ6</i>	.890																			
<i>BPQ7</i>	.885																			
<i>BPQ8</i>	.916																			
<i>BPQ9</i>	.843																			
<i>BAQ1</i>		.873																		

<i>BAQ2</i>		<i>.891</i>																		
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<i>Items</i>	<i>1</i>	<i>2</i>	<i>3</i>	<i>4</i>	<i>5</i>	<i>6</i>	<i>7</i>	<i>8</i>	<i>9</i>	<i>10</i>	<i>11</i>	<i>12</i>	<i>13</i>	<i>14</i>	<i>15</i>	<i>16</i>	<i>17</i>	<i>18</i>	<i>19</i>	<i>20</i>
<i>BAQ3</i>		.876																		
<i>BAQ4</i>		.869																		
<i>BAQ5</i>		.865																		
<i>BAQ6</i>		.888																		
<i>BAQ7</i>		.832																		
<i>BLIQ1</i>			.823																	
<i>BLIQ2</i>			.885																	
<i>BLIQ3</i>			.929																	
<i>BLIQ4</i>			.880																	
<i>BLIQ5</i>			.847																	
<i>BLIQ6</i>			.893																	

<i>BLIQ7</i>			<i>.938</i>																	
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<i>Items</i>	<i>1</i>	<i>2</i>	<i>3</i>	<i>4</i>	<i>5</i>	<i>6</i>	<i>7</i>	<i>8</i>	<i>9</i>	<i>10</i>	<i>11</i>	<i>12</i>	<i>13</i>	<i>14</i>	<i>15</i>	<i>16</i>	<i>17</i>	<i>18</i>	<i>19</i>	<i>20</i>
<i>BLIQ8</i>			<i>.871</i>																	
<i>OE1</i>				<i>.882</i>																
<i>OE2</i>				<i>.762</i>																
<i>OE3</i>				<i>.916</i>																
<i>OE4</i>				<i>.869</i>																
<i>OE5</i>				<i>.883</i>																
<i>OE6</i>				<i>.862</i>																
<i>BT1</i>					<i>.878</i>															
<i>BT2</i>					<i>.867</i>															
<i>BT3</i>					<i>.905</i>															
<i>BT4</i>					<i>.879</i>															

<i>BT5</i>					<i>.864</i>															
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<i>Items</i>	<i>1</i>	<i>2</i>	<i>3</i>	<i>4</i>	<i>5</i>	<i>6</i>	<i>7</i>	<i>8</i>	<i>9</i>	<i>10</i>	<i>11</i>	<i>12</i>	<i>13</i>	<i>14</i>	<i>15</i>	<i>16</i>	<i>17</i>	<i>18</i>	<i>19</i>	<i>20</i>
<i>BT6</i>					.872															
<i>OR1</i>						.820														
<i>OR2</i>						.862														
<i>OR3</i>						.846														
<i>OR4</i>						.851														
<i>OR5</i>						.828														
<i>OR6</i>						.875														
<i>BR1</i>							.918													
<i>BR2</i>							.900													
<i>BR3</i>							.889													
<i>BR4</i>							.874													

<i>BR5</i>							<i>.843</i>													
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<i>Items</i>	<i>1</i>	<i>2</i>	<i>3</i>	<i>4</i>	<i>5</i>	<i>6</i>	<i>7</i>	<i>8</i>	<i>9</i>	<i>10</i>	<i>11</i>	<i>12</i>	<i>13</i>	<i>14</i>	<i>15</i>	<i>16</i>	<i>17</i>	<i>18</i>	<i>19</i>	<i>20</i>
<i>BR6</i>							<i>.898</i>													
<i>BR7</i>							<i>.896</i>													
<i>CSRQ</i> <i>1</i>								<i>.877</i>												
<i>CSRQ</i> <i>2</i>								<i>.900</i>												
<i>CSRQ</i> <i>3</i>								<i>.889</i>												
<i>CSRQ</i> <i>4</i>								<i>.918</i>												
<i>CSRQ</i> <i>5</i>								<i>.931</i>												

<i>Items</i>	<i>1</i>	<i>2</i>	<i>3</i>	<i>4</i>	<i>5</i>	<i>6</i>	<i>7</i>	<i>8</i>	<i>9</i>	<i>10</i>	<i>11</i>	<i>12</i>	<i>13</i>	<i>14</i>	<i>15</i>	<i>16</i>	<i>17</i>	<i>18</i>	<i>19</i>	<i>20</i>
<i>CSRQ</i> <i>6</i>								<i>.899</i>												
<i>CSRQ</i> <i>7</i>								<i>.832</i>												
<i>CSRQ</i> <i>8</i>								<i>.865</i>												
<i>EvQ1</i>									<i>.854</i>											
<i>EvQ2</i>									<i>.886</i>											
<i>EvQ3</i>									<i>.839</i>											
<i>EvQ4</i>									<i>.861</i>											
<i>EvQ5</i>									<i>.840</i>											
<i>EvQ6</i>									<i>.854</i>											

<i>CogQ1</i>										<i>.844</i>										
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<i>Items</i>	<i>1</i>	<i>2</i>	<i>3</i>	<i>4</i>	<i>5</i>	<i>6</i>	<i>7</i>	<i>8</i>	<i>9</i>	<i>10</i>	<i>11</i>	<i>12</i>	<i>13</i>	<i>14</i>	<i>15</i>	<i>16</i>	<i>17</i>	<i>18</i>	<i>19</i>	<i>20</i>
<i>CogQ2</i>										<i>.836</i>										
<i>CogQ3</i>										<i>.847</i>										
<i>CogQ4</i>										<i>.848</i>										
<i>CogQ5</i>										<i>.805</i>										
<i>CogQ6</i>										<i>.803</i>										
<i>ConQ1</i>											<i>.874</i>									
<i>ConQ2</i>											<i>.855</i>									
<i>ConQ3</i>											<i>.907</i>									
<i>ConQ4</i>											<i>.912</i>									
<i>ConQ5</i>											<i>.876</i>									
<i>ConQ6</i>											<i>.856</i>									

<i>LoyQ1</i>												<i>.895</i>								
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<i>Items</i>	<i>1</i>	<i>2</i>	<i>3</i>	<i>4</i>	<i>5</i>	<i>6</i>	<i>7</i>	<i>8</i>	<i>9</i>	<i>10</i>	<i>11</i>	<i>12</i>	<i>13</i>	<i>14</i>	<i>15</i>	<i>16</i>	<i>17</i>	<i>18</i>	<i>19</i>	<i>20</i>
<i>LoyQ2</i>												<i>.858</i>								
<i>LoyQ3</i>												<i>.864</i>								
<i>LoyQ4</i>												<i>.873</i>								
<i>LoyQ5</i>												<i>.873</i>								
<i>LoyQ6</i>												<i>.856</i>								
<i>LoyQ7</i>												<i>.846</i>								
<i>BraQ1</i>													<i>.857</i>							
<i>BraQ2</i>													<i>.907</i>							
<i>BraQ3</i>													<i>.905</i>							
<i>BraQ4</i>													<i>.835</i>							
<i>BraQ5</i>													<i>.889</i>							

<i>BraQ6</i>													<i>.899</i>							
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<i>Items</i>	<i>1</i>	<i>2</i>	<i>3</i>	<i>4</i>	<i>5</i>	<i>6</i>	<i>7</i>	<i>8</i>	<i>9</i>	<i>10</i>	<i>11</i>	<i>12</i>	<i>13</i>	<i>14</i>	<i>15</i>	<i>16</i>	<i>17</i>	<i>18</i>	<i>19</i>	<i>20</i>
<i>BreQ1</i>														<i>.824</i>						
<i>BreQ2</i>														<i>.880</i>						
<i>BreQ3</i>														<i>.892</i>						
<i>BreQ4</i>														<i>.907</i>						
<i>BreQ5</i>														<i>.903</i>						
<i>BreQ6</i>														<i>.885</i>						
<i>SatQ1</i>															<i>.821</i>					
<i>SatQ2</i>															<i>.843</i>					
<i>SatQ3</i>															<i>.793</i>					
<i>SatQ4</i>															<i>.901</i>					
<i>SatQ5</i>															<i>.867</i>					

<i>SatQ6</i>															<i>.912</i>					
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<i>Items</i>	<i>1</i>	<i>2</i>	<i>3</i>	<i>4</i>	<i>5</i>	<i>6</i>	<i>7</i>	<i>8</i>	<i>9</i>	<i>10</i>	<i>11</i>	<i>12</i>	<i>13</i>	<i>14</i>	<i>15</i>	<i>16</i>	<i>17</i>	<i>18</i>	<i>19</i>	<i>20</i>
<i>SatQ7</i>															.885					
<i>BrpQ1</i>																.930				
<i>BrpQ2</i>																.902				
<i>BrpQ3</i>																.883				
<i>BrpQ4</i>																.842				
<i>BrpQ5</i>																.905				
<i>BrpQ6</i>																.864				
<i>BidQ1</i>																	.880			
<i>BidQ2</i>																	.880			
<i>BidQ3</i>																	.861			
<i>BidQ4</i>																	.897			

<i>BidQ5</i>																	<i>.848</i>			
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<i>Items</i>	<i>1</i>	<i>2</i>	<i>3</i>	<i>4</i>	<i>5</i>	<i>6</i>	<i>7</i>	<i>8</i>	<i>9</i>	<i>10</i>	<i>11</i>	<i>12</i>	<i>13</i>	<i>14</i>	<i>15</i>	<i>16</i>	<i>17</i>	<i>18</i>	<i>19</i>	<i>20</i>
<i>BidQ6</i>																	<i>.916</i>			
<i>BawQ1</i>																		<i>.857</i>		
<i>BawQ2</i>																		<i>.856</i>		
<i>BawQ3</i>																		<i>.877</i>		
<i>BawQ4</i>																		<i>.892</i>		
<i>BawQ5</i>																		<i>.889</i>		
<i>BawQ6</i>																		<i>.886</i>		
<i>BawQ7</i>																		<i>.875</i>		
<i>BrwQ1</i>																			<i>.845</i>	
<i>BrwQ2</i>																			<i>.873</i>	
<i>BrwQ3</i>																			<i>.927</i>	

<i>BrwQ4</i>																				<i>.880</i>	
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<i>Items</i>	<i>1</i>	<i>2</i>	<i>3</i>	<i>4</i>	<i>5</i>	<i>6</i>	<i>7</i>	<i>8</i>	<i>9</i>	<i>10</i>	<i>11</i>	<i>12</i>	<i>13</i>	<i>14</i>	<i>15</i>	<i>16</i>	<i>17</i>	<i>18</i>	<i>19</i>	<i>20</i>	
<i>BrwQ5</i>																				<i>.850</i>	
<i>BrwQ6</i>																				<i>.890</i>	
<i>BrcQ1</i>																					<i>.904</i>
<i>BrcQ2</i>																					<i>.878</i>
<i>BrcQ3</i>																					<i>.862</i>
<i>BrcQ4</i>																					<i>.813</i>
<i>BrcQ5</i>																					<i>.884</i>
<i>BrcQ6</i>																					<i>.921</i>

Source: Analysis of survey data (SPSS file)

Extraction method: Principal component analysis.

Rotation method: Varimax with KMO normalisation.

Note: BP = Brand positioning, BA = Brand authenticity, BLI= Brand Local Iconness, OE = Online engagement, BT= Brand trust, OR= Online review, BR= Brand relationship, CSR= , EV= Event, COG= Cognitive, CON= Conative, LOY=Loyalty, BRA= Brand attitude, BRE= Brand equity, SAT =Satisfaction, BRP =, BRE= Brand reputation, BID= Brand Identity, Baw= Brand awareness, BRW= Brand warmth, BRC= Brand competence

APPENDIX VII: Univariate variables

Items	Mean		Std. Deviation	Skewness		Kurtosis	
	Statistic	Std. Error		Statistic	Std. Error	Statistic	Std. Error
BPQ1	4.06	.085	1.568	-.358	.132	-.351	.263
BPQ2	3.80	.086	1.599	-.282	.132	-.677	.263
BPQ3	4.24	.081	1.496	-.646	.132	.171	.263
BPQ4	4.41	.069	1.285	-.828	.132	.823	.263
BPQ5	3.80	.087	1.614	-.288	.132	-.706	.263
BPQ6	4.48	.066	1.218	-.744	.132	1.419	.263
BPQ7	4.43	.068	1.252	-.479	.132	.834	.263
BPQ8	3.94	.082	1.518	-.163	.132	-.645	.263
BPQ9	4.00	.077	1.422	-.221	.132	-.099	.263
BAQ1	4.18	.076	1.403	-.171	.132	.015	.263
BAQ2	4.08	.080	1.485	-.395	.132	-.419	.263
BAQ3	4.15	.079	1.467	-.326	.132	-.343	.263
BAQ4	4.25	.073	1.345	-.153	.132	.243	.263
BAQ5	4.07	.081	1.506	-.218	.132	-.366	.263
BAQ6	4.26	.076	1.416	-.536	.132	.286	.263
BAQ7	4.30	.078	1.449	-.692	.132	-.081	.263
BLIQ1	4.13	.077	1.422	-.778	.132	.080	.263
BLIQ2	3.94	.082	1.516	-.352	.132	-.418	.263

BLIQ3	3.94	.085	1.568	-.264	.132	-.603	.263
BLIQ4	4.06	.079	1.463	-.693	.132	-.134	.263
BLIQ5	3.75	.082	1.526	-.246	.132	-.932	.263
BLIQ6	3.69	.082	1.513	-.163	.132	-.973	.263
BLIQ7	3.75	.082	1.516	-.298	.132	-.979	.263
BLIQ8	3.61	.086	1.589	.024	.132	-1.043	.263
OE1	3.73	.086	1.598	-.166	.132	-.781	.263
OE2	3.83	.076	1.412	-.233	.132	-.497	.263
OE3	3.93	.080	1.488	-.249	.132	-.401	.263
OE4	3.57	.083	1.534	-.144	.132	-.845	.263
OE5	4.12	.074	1.364	-.795	.132	.206	.263
OE6	4.25	.066	1.220	-.807	.132	.519	.263
BT1	3.83	.079	1.458	-.211	.132	-.609	.263
BT2	3.96	.076	1.400	-.723	.132	-.259	.263
BT3	3.99	.076	1.410	-.336	.132	-.289	.263
BT4	4.30	.077	1.423	-.744	.132	.241	.263
BT5	4.21	.068	1.253	-.717	.132	.113	.263
BT6	4.18	.072	1.326	-.538	.132	.288	.263
OR1	4.14	.073	1.350	-.515	.132	.139	.263
OR2	4.21	.074	1.374	-.579	.132	.027	.263
OR3	4.03	.079	1.466	-.258	.132	-.366	.263
OR4	4.01	.076	1.401	-.482	.132	-.122	.263
OR5	4.16	.071	1.313	-.496	.132	-.135	.263
OR6	4.10	.081	1.497	-.475	.132	-.445	.263

BR1	4.36	.075	1.397	-.775	.132	.640	.263
BR2	4.02	.079	1.471	-.607	.132	-.605	.263
BR3	3.93	.085	1.572	-.075	.132	-.505	.263
BR4	3.97	.079	1.466	-.464	.132	-.662	.263
BR5	4.05	.090	1.675	-.299	.132	-.782	.263
BR6	3.97	.088	1.622	-.449	.132	-.827	.263
BR7	4.20	.082	1.516	-.654	.132	-.180	.263
CSRQ1	3.74	.091	1.679	-.033	.132	-.720	.263
CSRQ2	4.12	.082	1.514	-.478	.132	-.318	.263
CSRQ3	3.96	.083	1.534	-.039	.132	-.491	.263
CSRQ4	4.10	.079	1.464	-.459	.132	-.664	.263
CSRQ5	4.01	.086	1.590	-.528	.132	-.664	.263
CSRQ6	3.86	.086	1.596	-.134	.132	-1.013	.263
CSRQ7	3.71	.082	1.509	-.209	.132	-.802	.263
CSRQ8	3.92	.077	1.427	-.233	.132	-.321	.263
EvQ1	3.51	.089	1.640	.161	.132	-.810	.263
EvQ2	3.66	.088	1.632	.007	.132	-.837	.263
EvQ3	3.73	.084	1.557	-.122	.132	-.778	.263
EvQ4	3.84	.086	1.589	-.087	.132	-.681	.263
EvQ5	3.86	.081	1.497	.025	.132	-.450	.263
EvQ6	3.93	.088	1.629	-.218	.132	-.711	.263
CogQ1	3.72	.083	1.540	-.227	.132	-.683	.263
CogQ2	3.99	.082	1.521	-.462	.132	-.374	.263
CogQ3	4.17	.079	1.470	-.312	.132	-.271	.263

CogQ4	3.87	.084	1.550	-.178	.132	-.446	.263
CogQ5	4.02	.076	1.408	-.326	.132	-.138	.263
CogQ6	3.97	.073	1.354	-.383	.132	-.107	.263
ConQ1	3.93	.084	1.555	-.263	.132	-.654	.263
ConQ2	3.99	.074	1.370	-.312	.132	-.149	.263
ConQ3	4.21	.071	1.313	-.578	.132	.069	.263
ConQ4	3.73	.088	1.631	-.145	.132	-.969	.263
ConQ5	4.45	.070	1.290	-.884	.132	1.237	.263
ConQ6	4.48	.061	1.123	-.937	.132	1.398	.263
LoyQ1	3.87	.078	1.450	-.493	.132	-.629	.263
LoyQ2	3.91	.071	1.312	-.857	.132	-.206	.263
LoyQ3	4.17	.070	1.292	-.913	.132	.131	.263
LoyQ4	4.17	.071	1.320	-1.031	.132	.257	.263
LoyQ5	3.83	.078	1.440	-.482	.132	-.713	.263
LoyQ6	3.76	.069	1.284	-.686	.132	-.271	.263
LoyQ7	3.82	.076	1.416	-.629	.132	-.650	.263
BraQ1	4.14	.085	1.573	-.183	.132	-.450	.263
BraQ2	3.87	.088	1.633	-.088	.132	-.756	.263
BraQ3	3.97	.087	1.612	-.239	.132	-.616	.263
BraQ4	4.07	.086	1.589	.087	.132	-.673	.263
BraQ5	4.19	.082	1.520	-.344	.132	-.380	.263
BraQ6	4.17	.079	1.462	-.442	.132	-.033	.263
BreQ1	3.87	.083	1.544	-.048	.132	-.531	.263
BreQ2	3.71	.088	1.630	-.029	.132	-.703	.263

BreQ3	3.88	.083	1.545	-.210	.132	-.431	.263
BreQ4	4.00	.085	1.573	-.109	.132	-.456	.263
BreQ5	3.69	.085	1.580	-.026	.132	-.703	.263
BreQ6	4.27	.076	1.401	-.860	.132	.354	.263
SatQ1	4.38	.070	1.299	-.570	.132	.838	.263
SatQ2	4.10	.084	1.555	-.494	.132	-.346	.263
SatQ3	4.44	.072	1.327	-.630	.132	.657	.263
SatQ4	4.04	.080	1.486	-.371	.132	-.245	.263
SatQ5	4.36	.070	1.301	-.472	.132	.731	.263
SatQ6	3.99	.080	1.474	-.008	.132	-.319	.263
SatQ7	4.16	.070	1.301	-.202	.132	-.154	.263
BrpQ1	4.22	.086	1.600	-.020	.132	-.371	.263
BrpQ2	3.95	.086	1.584	-.242	.132	-.644	.263
BrpQ3	4.31	.080	1.475	-.456	.132	.006	.263
BrpQ4	4.60	.067	1.236	-.787	.132	1.371	.263
BrpQ5	3.99	.083	1.538	-.262	.132	-.443	.263
BrpQ6	4.07	.077	1.424	-.490	.132	-.238	.263
BidQ1	4.05	.081	1.505	-.255	.132	-.254	.263
BidQ2	4.41	.075	1.382	-.647	.132	.350	.263
BidQ3	4.08	.081	1.493	-.465	.132	-.482	.263
BidQ4	4.14	.082	1.513	-.280	.132	-.200	.263
BidQ5	3.76	.088	1.621	-.068	.132	-.616	.263
BidQ6	4.13	.078	1.447	-.586	.132	-.054	.263
BawQ1	3.91	.083	1.539	-.138	.132	-.575	.263

BawQ2	4.03	.082	1.524	-.363	.132	-.576	.263
BawQ3	3.90	.085	1.581	-.292	.132	-.737	.263
BawQ4	4.09	.078	1.444	-.294	.132	-.698	.263
BawQ5	4.18	.079	1.469	-.472	.132	-.115	.263
BawQ6	3.87	.082	1.528	-.302	.132	-.643	.263
BawQ7	3.72	.088	1.626	.118	.132	-.748	.263
BrwQ1	3.86	.088	1.631	.175	.132	-.477	.263
BrwQ2	3.62	.093	1.716	.085	.132	-.943	.263
BrwQ3	3.73	.089	1.644	-.023	.132	-.772	.263
BrwQ4	3.81	.083	1.540	-.259	.132	-.653	.263
BrwQ5	4.02	.086	1.601	-.223	.132	-.685	.263
BrwQ6	4.18	.076	1.401	-.594	.132	.073	.263
BrcQ1	3.78	.092	1.696	-.185	.132	-.812	.263
BrcQ2	4.31	.075	1.380	-.582	.132	.393	.263
BrcQ3	4.58	.067	1.244	-1.205	.132	2.099	.263
BrcQ4	3.80	.083	1.541	-.287	.132	-.961	.263
BrcQ5	4.03	.086	1.595	-.306	.132	-.564	.263
BrcQ6	4.05	.081	1.503	-.532	.132	-.353	.263

Valid N
(listwise)

APPENDIX VIII: Multivariate normality

Constructs	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
Brandpositioning	.250	340	.000	.659	340	.000
Brandauthenticity	.087	340	.000	.976	340	.000
BrandlocalIconnes s	.189	340	.000	.881	340	.000
Onlineengagement	.107	340	.000	.971	340	.000
Brandtrust	.105	340	.000	.954	340	.000
Onlinereview	.070	340	.000	.982	340	.000
Brandrelationship	.092	340	.000	.961	340	.000
CSR	.104	340	.000	.918	340	.000
Event	.065	340	.001	.988	340	.007
Cognitive	.125	340	.000	.952	340	.000
Conative	.101	340	.000	.771	340	.000
Loyalty	.102	340	.000	.968	340	.000
BrandAttitude	.108	340	.000	.955	340	.000
Brandequity	.105	340	.000	.972	340	.000
Satisfaction	.094	340	.000	.968	340	.000
BrandReputation	.087	340	.000	.979	340	.000
BrandIdentity	.094	340	.000	.967	340	.000
Brandawareness	.147	340	.000	.933	340	.000
Brandwarmth	.138	340	.000	.931	340	.000
Brandcompetence	.095	340	.000	.957	340	.000

Brandperformance	.043	340	.200*	.990	340	.024
Brandattachment	.066	340	.001	.921	340	.000

*. This is a lower bound of the true significance.

a. Lilliefors Significance Correction